

A COLLABORATIVE EXPLORATION OF
FAMILY-CENTRED REMINISCENCE
WITHIN VISITS OF CARE HOME
RESIDENTS WITH DEMENTIA

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Abstract

Background: For families of residents living in care homes, maintaining familial connections is paramount. This study focused on developing an understanding of family-centred reminiscence practices during care home visits, with the broader aim of supporting relationship-centred care and improving the overall experience of residents and their families.

Methods: This was a collaborative action research study which aimed to generate a shared understanding of the benefits and practical application of family-centred reminiscence, and to co-create a resource to support family members to use structured reminiscence during visits with their relatives living with dementia in nursing homes. Cycle One comprised of individual interviews and a group session where we discussed how families might introduce reminiscence into their visits. Cycle Two included three group workshops involving a Time-Machine activity, and two rounds of Emotional Touchpoints group interviews, interspersed with reminiscence-in-action with follow-up phone interviews. Cycle Three involved two focus group sessions to develop a co-produced practical guide, and a round of closing telephone interviews to assess the participants' experiences of the wider study. Data was analysed using reflexive thematic analysis. This study incorporated aspects of carer education relating to reminiscence and dementia friendly communication to allow families to adapt this into their visits, which was also included in our practical guide.

Findings: A family-centred approach to reminiscence was collaboratively developed and used by six family members, and founded on the experiences of participants, a practical guide was co-produced by the group. Relationship-centred care and the Six Senses Framework informed our approach which placed the family and familial relationships at the fore. An unexpected finding from this study was that families wanted more peer support to be available throughout their visiting journey.

Conclusions: The study has fulfilled the aim, whereby we have produced evidence on the benefits and practical application of a novel family-centred approach to reminiscence which facilitated connections between visiting family members and people living with dementia in care homes.

Contents

Abstract	2
List of Tables.....	6
List of Diagrams.....	6
List of Pictures	7
Acknowledgements	8
Author’s Declaration.....	10
Structure of the Thesis.....	11
Chapter One - Introduction and Context.....	12
1.0 Statement of study focus.....	12
1.1 What is dementia?	12
1.2 What are care homes, and what informs best practice?.....	14
1.3 Family Carers/ Carers Strategies and Rights	17
1.4 Current policies and the Impact of Covid-19.....	19
1.4 Reminiscence.....	21
1.4.1 <i>The Therapeutic Purposes of Reminiscence</i>	22
1.4.2 <i>The Reminiscence Bump</i>	27
1.5 Overview of the Wendy Baxter Scholarship	28
1.5.1 <i>Leaving behind a legacy</i>	29
1.6 Overview of my background and how this informed the study	30
1.7 Conclusion	32
Chapter Two – Literature Review	34
2.1 Familiarisation of the literature.....	34
2.3 Scoping Review.....	38
2.3.1 <i>Scoping Review rationale</i>	38
2.3.2 <i>Scoping Review Methods</i>	40
2.7 Scoping Review findings	47
2.7.1 <i>Search One: Experiences of family members following a Care Home admission</i>	47
2.7.2 <i>Search Two: Reminiscence</i>	56
2.7.3 <i>Search Three: Family Involvement in Care Homes</i>	63
2.8 <i>Key findings</i>	70
Chapter Three - Methodology.....	72
3.0 Introduction.....	72
3.1 Study aim and objectives.....	73
3.2 Research Paradigm	73
3.3 Alternative Epistemologies.....	75
3.4 What is Action Research?	77
3.4.1 <i>Alternative Research Design Considerations</i>	78
3.4.2 <i>Rationale for Action Research</i>	79
3.4.3 <i>Approach to Action Research</i>	80
3.5 Typologies of Action Research.....	81
3.5.1 <i>Holter and Schwartz-Barcott’s Action Research Typology</i>	82
3.6 The Continuum of Researcher Positionality within Action Research	84
3.7 Promoting rigour within this action research study	87

3.8 Theoretical Framework	90
3.8.1 <i>Relationship-Centred Care</i>	91
3.8.2 <i>The Six Senses Framework</i>	92
3.9 Ethical Considerations	97
3.9.1 <i>Ethical considerations of action research</i>	97
3.9.2 <i>Confidentiality</i>	101
3.9.3 <i>Anonymity</i>	101
3.9.4 <i>Negotiating permissions and access to the study sites</i>	102
3.9.5 <i>Accessing and gaining consent from visiting families</i>	102
3.10 Chapter summary.....	103
Chapter Four – Recruitment, Ethical Challenges, and Planned Methods	104
4.1 Overview of Study Design	104
4.1.1 <i>Cycle 1: Understanding Family Visits</i>	106
4.1.2 <i>Cycle 2: Exploring Reminiscence during Visits</i>	107
4.1.3 <i>Cycle 3: Co-creating a Family Centred Reminiscence Resource</i>	108
4.2 Study Site Recruitment.....	109
4.2.1 <i>Care Home selection criteria</i>	109
4.2.2 <i>Planned Study Site recruitment process</i>	111
4.2.3 <i>Study Site One</i>	112
4.2.4 <i>Study Site Two</i>	113
4.2.5 <i>Study Site Three</i>	114
4.3 Recruitment of Participants.....	116
4.3.1 <i>Participant inclusion criteria</i>	117
4.3.2 <i>Recruitment process</i>	117
4.4 Ethical Approval Process.....	119
4.4.1 <i>Amendments to ethics application</i>	121
4.4.2 <i>Additional Ethical Challenges</i>	123
4.5 Planned Research Methods.....	124
4.4.1 <i>Semi-Structured Interviews</i>	124
4.4.2 <i>Focus Groups</i>	125
4.6 Approach to analysis	127
4.6.1 <i>Alternative analytical approaches considered</i>	129
4.6.2 <i>Reflexive Thematic Analysis</i>	130
4.7 Rigour	133
4.7 Chapter summary	134
Chapter Five - Cycle One	135
5.1 Cycle One Overview	135
5.1.1 <i>Relationship between participants and residents</i>	136
5.2 Research methods used	137
5.4 Interview Findings	140
5.4.1 <i>Connection</i>	141
5.4.2 <i>Visit Experience</i>	146
5.4.3 <i>Prior experience of reminiscence</i>	152
5.4.4 <i>Peer Support</i>	153
5.5 Anticipated Methods for Objective Two.....	154
5.5.1 <i>Focus Group preparatory Work</i>	155
5.5.3 <i>Research methods used</i>	155
5.5.4 <i>Findings from first session</i>	158
5.6 Chapter summary and how this led into Cycle Two	164
Chapter Six – Cycle Two	165

6.1 Cycle Two Overview	165
6.1.2 Recruitment updates.....	167
6.2 First round of phone interviews and Time Machine group task.....	168
6.2.1 Findings from first round of telephone interviews	169
6.2.2 Methods used for the Time Machine Activity.....	172
6.2.3 Findings from group one	175
6.3 Second round of phone interviews and first Emotional Touchpoints session	182
6.3.1 Findings from second round of telephone interviews	183
6.3.2 Emotional Touchpoints Methods.....	186
6.3.3 Findings from group two.....	190
6.4 Third round of phone interviews and Second Emotional Touchpoints session.....	201
6.4.1 Findings from third round of phone interviews.....	202
6.4.2 Emotional Touchpoints Methods.....	207
6.4.3 Findings from group three	208
6.5 Chapter Summary and How this led into Cycle Three	219
Chapter Seven – Cycle Three	221
7.1 Recruitment updates.....	221
7.2 Cycle Three Overview	222
7.3 First group session.....	223
7.3.1 Research methods used	224
7.3.2 Findings from Group One.....	225
7.4 Closing telephone interviews	234
7.4.1 Findings from telephone interviews	235
7.5 Joint group session	242
7.5.1 Focus Group Methods	242
7.5.2 Research methods used	243
7.5.3 Findings from the joint group session	243
7.6 How this further informed our resource	253
7.7 Chapter Conclusion	253
Chapter Eight – Discussion	255
8.1 Merits and Limitations of the study	255
8.2 Critical Reflection of Action Research Methodology.....	260
8.2.1 Reflection on my role within the action research study	263
8.3 Discussion of key findings.....	267
8.3.1 Cycle One.....	269
8.3.2 Cycle Two	274
8.3.3 Cycle Three	278
8.4 Co-production process	281
8.5 Discussion of main themes raised	283
8.5.1 Contention between reminiscence and shared activities	284
8.5.2 Peer Support.....	286
8.6 Chapter conclusion.....	291
Chapter Nine –Thesis Conclusion and Recommendations	292
9.1 Thesis conclusion.....	292
9.2 Recommendations.....	295
9.1.1 Recommendations for care home practice.....	295
9.1.2 Recommendations for policy.....	296
9.1.3 Recommendations for future research.....	297
9.1.4 Recommendations for nursing education	297

References	299
Appendices	334
Appendix 1 – Notes used for ‘cold calls’ with study sites	334
Appendix 2 – Letter for study sites outlining study	336
Appendix 3 – Letter sent to study sites asking for managerial permission	338
Appendix 4 – Letter of managerial permission from Study Site One	340
Appendix 5 – Recruitment Leaflet	341
Appendix 6 – Participant Information Sheet	342
Appendix 7 – Consent Form	345
Appendix 8 – Semi-structured guide for individual interviews	347
Appendix 9 – Ethics Approval Letter.....	349
Appendix 10 – Staff Information Sheet	350
Appendix 11 – Ethics Amendment Approval Letter	353
Appendix 12 – Worked example of reflexive thematic analysis	353
Appendix 13 – Slides used for Reminiscence video.....	354
Appendix 14 – Guide for Cycle One group session.....	355
Appendix 15 – Reminiscence telephone interview guide	356
Appendix 16 – Guide for first group session of Cycle Two	357
Appendix 17 – List of words used for emotional touchpoints.....	358
Appendix 18 – Guide for second group session of Cycle Two	359
Appendix 19 – Guide for third group session of Cycle Two	360
Appendix 20 – Guide for first group session of Cycle Three.....	361
Appendix 21 – Closing interviews semi-structured guide	362
Appendix 22 – Guide for joint group session	362
Appendix 23 – Practical Guide on Family-Centred Reminiscence	363

List of Tables

Table 1 - Overview of preliminary searches.....	34
Table 2 – Summary of data collection activities and data analysis	106
Table 3 - Care Inspectorate Ratings.....	110
Table 4 - Participants' relationship to residents.....	137
Table 5 - Participants' relationship to residents (Cycle Two).....	168
Table 6 - Staff Members' role within the care home.....	222

List of Diagrams

Diagram 1: Steps of a Scoping Review	40
Diagram 2: PRISMA-ScR for Search One	43
Diagram 3: PRISMA-ScR for Search Two.....	44
Diagram 4: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources for Search Three	44
Diagram 5: Map of themes for Search One	48
Diagram 6: Map of themes for Search Two	56
Diagram 7: Map of themes for Search Three.....	64
Diagram 8: Overview of Action Research Cycles.....	105
Diagram 9: Overview of Cycle One Research Activities	136

Diagram 10: Overview of Cycle Two Research Activities 166
Diagram 11: Overview of Cycle Three Research Activities..... 223

List of Pictures

Picture 1: Emotions Before a Visit (prior to reminiscence) 194
Picture 2: Emotions During a Visit (prior to reminiscence)..... 197
Picture 3: Emotions After a Visit (prior to reminiscence) 199
Picture 4: Emotions Before a Visit (after reminiscence) 212
Picture 5: Emotions During a Visit (after reminiscence) 215
Picture 6: Emotions After a Visit (after reminiscence) 218

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Author's Declaration

I, Connor McDonald, hereby certify that this thesis has been written by me and has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "C. McDonald". The signature is written in a cursive, slightly slanted style.

Connor McDonald

Date 19th September 2025

Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is presented in nine chapters. Chapter One serves as an introductory chapter and provides the contextual background of the study. A preliminary literature search and a scoping review of the literature regarding the experiences of families following a care home admission, the current evidence base on reminiscence, and care home policies regarding family involvement are presented in Chapter Two. Chapter Three explores the methodology, theoretical underpinnings, and ethical considerations of this study before Chapter Four outlines the ethical approval, recruitment processes that were used, and planned research methods. Chapters Five, Six, and Seven explore the three action research cycles. Chapter Eight of this thesis critically outlines the merits and limitations of this study, my reflections on our action research approach, and discusses the key findings. Chapter Nine then presents recommendations for research, policy, practice, and nursing education before concluding the study.

The first-person is used throughout this thesis to illustrate my role within the action research process. Additionally, accessible language is adopted to align with the democratic nature of action research to allow the thesis to be readable by the action research team, and staff from the study site.

Chapter One- Introduction and Context

1.0 Statement of study focus

The focus of this study was to collaboratively explore how a family-centred approach to reminiscence could be used by visiting family members to enhance their connections to their loved ones living with dementia in a Scottish care home. This introductory chapter seeks to contextualise the thesis within the backdrop of the current policy issues regarding dementia in care homes. Concepts such as dementia, care homes, and reminiscence are introduced. A wider situational background for dementia and care homes is provided, including the current figures both at an international level and within a Scottish context. The concept of reminiscence is then explored in more detail including how it is currently used for reminiscence therapy, and how this relates to the reminiscence bump. Lastly, this chapter will then situate this thesis within the context of the Wendy Baxter Scholarship, and the concept of leaving behind a legacy.

1.1 What is dementia?

To fully understand the experiences of families of someone living with dementia, it is important that we first understand what dementia is and the implications of a diagnosis for both the individual and their family. This can be somewhat of a difficult task as dementia is an umbrella term for neurodegenerative conditions caused by illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease and can affect everyone differently. During the earlier stages of dementia, those living with dementia can often live relatively well and independently at home. However, as the condition progresses and symptoms become more complex, those with dementia may require

more support and no longer be able to remain living in their own home which can have differing effects on families as they adjust to their new role as a visitor.

Dementia can be simply defined as *“a set of symptoms that may include memory loss and difficulties with thinking, problem-solving or language”* (Alzheimer’s Society, 2017). The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2018) have given an expanded, biomedical definition of dementia as *“a syndrome in which there is a deterioration in memory, thinking, behaviour and the ability to perform everyday activities”* beyond what might be expected from normal ageing. Moreover, a dementia diagnosis is often accompanied by a degeneration in *“emotional control, social behaviour of motivation”* (WHO, 2018).

Advanced dementia can be complex to fully define as it can impact individuals and their families in unique ways depending on other factors such as underlying health issues or their personality. As dementia progresses, living well with the condition requires more support and level of care as advanced dementia often includes *“loss of autonomy, declining physical health, increasing vulnerability and frailty”* (Holmerova *et al.*, 2016, p4). In their definition of advanced dementia, the WHO state that the later stage of the condition is *“one of near total dependence and inactivity. Memory disturbances are serious, and the physical signs and symptoms become more obvious”* (WHO, 2021a). The WHO expand this by stating that some symptoms include a lack of awareness of the time and place, increased difficulty in recognising loved ones, an increasing reliance on assisted self-care, increasing mobility issues and behaviour changes which can sometimes escalate to aggression.

Advanced dementia involves complex healthcare needs that are deeply intertwined with psychosocial and spiritual dimensions. This highlights the importance of the care environment and the role of family carers. A key component of dementia care is that lived experiences are

unique to the individual and their family and as such, a flexible, compassionate, and evidence-based approach is required to allow the individual to live the best they can with dementia during the later stages. However, it is important to note that there are positive aspects of the caregiving experience. Lloyd, Patterson, and Muers (2016) outlined that positive aspects of caring arose from two key areas: those gained from the caring itself, and those that occurred from the relationship between the person with dementia and their carer. From the act of caring, carers reported that they gained satisfaction, emotional and personal growth, competence, and increased faith and spiritual growth. Similarly, carers shared that they felt that their relationship to the person living with dementia was strengthened through relationship gains, satisfaction in reciprocity, and fulfilling a sense of duty through caregiving. These positive aspects did not passively occur but were instead a result of the choices and strategies adopted by carers such as accepting their situation, which allowed them to view caring through a positive and empathic lens (Lloyd, Patterson, and Muers, 2016). Signifying that whilst caring for someone living with dementia can be challenging, it can also be a highly rewarding experience which can strengthen preexisting familial relationships.

1.2 What are care homes, and what informs best practice?

There are two main types of care homes that are prevalent in the UK: residential homes, and nursing homes. Residential homes offer accommodation, personal care and assistance with washing, dressing, medications and going to the toilet. Nursing homes, whilst offering similar assistance with personal care, differ as there is always at least one qualified nurse on duty to provide residents with nursing care and support residents that might need additional care for example those with severe learning difficulties or physical disabilities (NHS, 2019). Sanford *et al.* (2015) defined nursing homes as a facility with a domestic-styled environment that

provides long-term, 24-hour care for people with complex health needs and increased vulnerability who require assistance with activities of daily living. This study focusses on nursing homes, sometimes referred to as care homes with nursing, as those with advanced dementia generally require the additional support offered in nursing homes. Whilst this study centred on the family visiting experiences within nursing homes, the term “care home” was used throughout the thesis as this was the term used in the literature, and by the families themselves when they were talking about their experiences.

According to the WHO’s Global Health Observatory, as of 2017 there were 460,186 long-term residential care beds per 10,000 population in the UK with 303,682 dementia specific long-term residential beds per 10,000 (WHO, 2021b; WHO, 2021c). The 2024 Care Home Census for Adults in Scotland showed that of the estimated 30,170 care home residents in Scotland, approximately 19,000 were living with either medically diagnosed, or suspected dementia (Public Health Scotland, 2024). The number of residents with a formal dementia diagnosis increased by 3% between 2014 and 2024, whilst the number of those with suspected dementia fell by 32% (Public Health Scotland, 2024). However, the figures of people living with dementia are an under-representation due to issues with getting a diagnosis. Figures on the prevalence of dementia with care homes in Glasgow showed that whilst 58% of residents were living with dementia, an additional 31.8% of residents scored within the range of a possible dementia diagnosis, suggesting that approximately 30% of dementia cases can go undiagnosed in care homes (Lithgow, Jackson, and Browne, 2011).

To inform best practice, the Care Inspectorate published a quality framework focusing on care homes for older people in 2023 which outlines what they view as being best practice. The Care Inspectorate state that the purpose of the framework is to:

“... support services to evaluate their own performance. The same framework is then used by inspectors to provide independent assurance about the quality of care and support. By setting out what we expect to see in a high-quality service, we can also help support improvement. Using a framework in this way develops a shared understanding of what constitutes good care and support” (Care Inspectorate, 2023, p3).

The quality framework is founded on six key questions which are focussed on: how the home supports wellbeing, the leadership, staff team, setting, and care planning of the home, and the overall capacity for improvement. Each question is comprised of quality indicators which assess different aspects of care (Care Inspectorate, 2023). A key quality indicator for this study was indicator 5.2 which focusses on how carers, friends, and family members are encouraged to be involved within the care home (Care Inspectorate, 2023). A ‘very good’ care home undertakes a supportive and inclusive approach to keep carers and relatives involved in the delivery of care, with leaders engaging with them to ensure that they fully understand the views and expectations of families. Within this, there is a particular focus on maintaining familial relationships:

“The care home staff understand the complexities of family and other close relationships and can provide support to people to try to reconnect with friends or family where these relationships have broken down” (Care Inspectorate, 2023, p77).

This emphasises the important role that sustained family involvement can play within the care home environment, and the significance of maintaining familial relationships for as long as possible.

1.3 Family Carers/ Carers Strategies and Rights

In their “Global action plan on the public health response to dementia 2017-2025”, the WHO contend that carers should be seen as “*essential partners*” in the planning and provision of care in accordance with the wishes and needs of the individual with dementia regardless of the care setting (WHO, 2017). The WHO also raise the important issue of supporting carers to safeguard their physical and mental well-being which in turn will help them to provide the necessary care for their loved ones. Nevertheless, the Carers (Scotland) Act 2016 recognises that there is a contention between whether visiting family members are seen as “*visitors*” or as “*carers*”, and highlights that this can change from person to person (Scottish Government, 2021). Due to the ambiguity and lack of clear definition of “care” throughout the Carers Act and the possibility of low-level care provision, in many cases, the primary carer of the individual prior to a care home admission may continue to be viewed as a carer instead of a visitor.

Despite this, informal or family carers are a group that are oftentimes overlooked or dismissed as a small part of the population. However, recent figures paint a different picture and illustrate how important family carers are to society. The European Quality of Life Survey estimate that there are around 100 million caregivers in Europe which equates to approximately 20% of the EU population (Carers Worldwide, n.d.). This trend was mirrored when I examined the estimate of carers in the UK. The 2011 Census showed that there were around 6.5 million carers in the UK, however, Carers UK suggest that this is an underestimate with the actual figure being closer to 8.8 million as of 2019 (Carers UK, 2019). Additionally, the 2019 GP Patient Survey revealed that carers made up 17% of the English population over the age of 16 (Carers UK, 2019). These figures were repeated when I examined the Scottish

context. The Scottish Government estimate that there are 788,000 carers in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2021). Carers Scotland (n.d.) state that this equates to 17% of the adult population in Scotland and that 60% of Scottish residents will take on a caring role over their lifetimes. Current statistics showing the demographics of unpaid carers in Scotland give an indication of the population groups that are most likely to be frequent family visitors of a loved one in a care home. The 2020-2021 Carers Census showed that 62% of unpaid carers in Scotland were working age (18-64 years old) and those over the age of 64 accounted for approximately a quarter of carers (Scottish Government, 2021). Furthermore, 14% of unpaid carers were those under the age of 18. Additionally, 71% of unpaid carers were female with a more prominent gender split amongst working age adults with 76% females. These figures suggest that the most likely frequent care home visitor are adult children (with a higher likelihood of daughters) or spouses/intimate partners of the person living with dementia in the care home. This illustrates how family carers are a fundamental component of the care system not just in Scotland but worldwide.

The idea of family support and involvement is reflected in section five of the Dementia Palliare report which states that:

“...family and friends make an important and valued contribution to the lives and well-being of people with advanced dementia in and that the well-being of family and friends is important in its own rights” (Holmerová et al., 2016, p11).

This further illustrates that the role of family carers should be integral to policies focussed on advanced dementia to both fully support those living with dementia as well as their loved ones. Furthermore, this highlights how the definition of a carer as seen in the Carers (Scotland)

Act 2016 does not consider the crucial role that families play in the emotional and spiritual care of their loved one with dementia, which is explored further in this thesis.

1.4 Current policies and the Impact of Covid-19

Recent years have seen a renewed focus on both dementia research and policies for several factors. One such factor is the rising average life expectancy which has forced issues, like dementia, to the forefront of the policy agenda due to the mounting prevalence of the condition. Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI, 2021) have estimated that there are 50 million people living with dementia worldwide with 60% residing in low and middle-income countries. Nichols *et al.* (2022) estimate that by 2050, the number of people living with dementia globally will increase to 152.8 million with the cost of dementia increasing from US\$1 trillion in 2020 to US\$2 trillion by 2030 (ADI, 2021). This projection is corroborated by the Alzheimer's Society (2020) who state that the number of people living with dementia in the UK will rise to over 1,500,000 by 2040. It is estimated that there are currently 90,000 people living with dementia in Scotland with projected estimates showing a 50% increase over the next 20 years, and some estimates suggesting a third of people born today will develop dementia in their lifetime (Scottish Government, n.d.). From these figures, it is clear to see why dementia has been placed on the forefront of the policy making stage as if left unchecked, dementia is set to become a major health crisis in the near future.

The Fair Dementia Care Report conducted by Alzheimer Scotland in 2019 centred on the care and nursing costs for people living with advanced dementia in nursing homes. The report found that those living with advanced dementia in care homes are paying approximately £49 million a year in social care charges for the health care needs resulting from advanced dementia and that those in receipt of residential care are paying an additional £1.9 million in

non-residential social care charges (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019). The estimated total average costs for those living with advanced dementia in both care home and non-residential care settings is £50.9 million. However, this could be an underestimate due to the lack of exact records on the prevalence of dementia, both in care homes and the wider community, and lack of precise records of social care costs (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019). The report made several recommendations to help alleviate the issues raised. One major recommendation is that advanced dementia is recognised as a spectrum which includes palliative end of life care. Secondly, the report recommends that:

“[the] Scottish Government commits to recognising that the needs of people with advanced dementia are health care needs and ensure equality of access to appropriate health and nursing care, which is free at the point of delivery” (Alzheimer Scotland, 2019).

Thirdly, they recommended that there is an improved record of the prevalence of dementia, and advanced dementia, in both care settings and the wider community to get a better understanding of how resources are allocated.

The Covid-19 pandemic impacted all of us, but care home residents have been one of the most affected groups in society. Under the pandemic measures, care home visits were stopped to protect staff and residents from infection. Whilst lockdowns were not a new phenomenon to care homes, they were never used for a sustained period prior to the pandemic. As such, the measures, whilst necessary, had a substantial impact on the wellbeing of staff, residents and relatives over the course of the pandemic. The impact of visitation restrictions was investigated in a report published by Creative Covid Care (2021) titled “The Cost of Separation: The impact of visiting restrictions on families of care home residents during Covid-19”. For

many, the psychological cost of separation outweighed the risks of infection from Covid-19 and that the “*right to a family life had not been adequately balanced against the risks of infection*” (Creative Covid Care, 2021). Furthermore, for some the delay in reopening care homes to visits whilst the rest of society reopened signified that older people had been forgotten, deepening the existing invisibility of older people both in care homes and wider society. The report also stated that family carers expressed feelings of loss and grief at the separation and feared that their relative’s mental and physical health could decline as a result, even more so for those living with advanced dementia. There were fears that the needs of their loved ones could go unnoticed if family members were not there to notice or voice any concerns. When visits restarted with social distancing in place, some family members were distressed and upset when they could not hold their loved one’s hand or give them a hug which also caused confusion for those with dementia who could not understand why (Creative Covid Care, 2021).

1.4 Reminiscence

Central to this thesis is the concept of reminiscence and how families could be empowered to use this during their visits with their loved ones living in a care home. At its core, reminiscence is based on using tangible prompts or trigger items to stimulate conversation and recall of past experiences in a strengths-based manner by focussing on preserved abilities instead of dwelling on what has been lost (Subramaniam and Woods, 2016; Woods *et al.*, 2018; Ryan *et al.*, 2020). There are two main types of reminiscence: informal and formal, each with their own goal and process for conducting them (Tolson and Mitchell, 2019). Informal reminiscence is typically spontaneous and occurs naturally in conversations and storytelling with others. At the other end of the spectrum, formal reminiscence is intentional, planned activities and

usually delivered as part of an intervention or therapy. Reminiscence Therapy is a non-pharmacological, psychosocial treatment which supports people living with dementia to discuss events, people, and experiences from the past with the aim to induce memories, promote mental stimulation and improve well-being (Woods *et al.*, 2018; Redulla, 2020). Like informal reminiscence, reminiscence therapy makes use of prompts or trigger items such as videos, pictures, objects, music, or even smells (Redulla, 2020; Syed Elias *et al.*, 2020). Gibson (2011, p9) described reminiscence as an activity that “*builds bridges between people*”, illustrating how reminiscence could be used to enhance connections between family members.

1.4.1 The Therapeutic Purposes of Reminiscence

The therapeutic purposes of reminiscence devised by Bender, Bauckham, and Norris (1999) informed my approach to reminiscence. Bender, Bauckham, and Norris (1999) outlined 20 therapeutic purposes of reminiscence built on the needs of client, carer, and the unit itself. For this study, I focussed on four which would help family visitors remain connected to their loved one. The four ‘purposes’ used were:

- Reminiscence as fun
- Reminiscence to aid intergenerational communication
- Reminiscence to achieve cultural legacy
- Reminiscence and spirituality (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999)

1.4.1.1 Reminiscence as fun

Whilst reminiscence can be an effective therapy for people living with dementia, it can also be a fun and enjoyable activity. Any activity that is effective in assisting us to ‘switch off’ and forget our problems and pains for a short period of time is often welcome and can help us to

cope with our problems or improve our problem solving (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999). This approach to reminiscence is founded on the idea that having fun could be embraced by family visitors as it allows them to create new memories together and focus on the present moment with their loved one instead of reflecting on what they may have lost. Bender, Bauckham, and Norris. (1999) contend that a well-run reminiscence group can be a fun activity, if that is what the group leaders want to achieve, have the competent skills and have done the necessary work to identify effective prompts. Although the approach used in this study was not group based, it illustrates how families could tailor their approach to reminiscence to make it a pleasurable activity for them and their loved one. Furthermore, families often have pre-existing knowledge of their loved one's likes and dislikes, and life history which they could draw upon to identify effective prompts that are centred on enjoyable memories or hobbies. Reminiscence can be used by anyone regardless of age as we all have a past and life experiences that can be drawn upon through effective prompts such as films and music, meaning that it could be a useful tool for family visitors to connect with their loved one with dementia. Reminiscence to have fun can make participants feel part of a group through shared experiences and can often leave sessions feeling livelier than they did at the start (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999). This could be highly beneficial for families as it can allow their loved one with dementia to still feel a part of the family unit despite the move to a care home.

Reminiscence activities based on past hobbies such as crafts can be an effective means of eliciting both verbal and non-verbal responses from people living with advanced dementia, indicating that reminiscence centred on hobbies and fun activities are worthwhile endeavours (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Despite this, reminiscence purely for enjoyment can often be

dismissed or overlooked as it is perceived as not being goal driven. However, this approach aligns with the aims for this study as some families may visit a loved one with the seemingly simple aim of getting a smile or a look of recognition which could be facilitated by living in the moment and creating new memories.

Whilst Bender, Bauckham, and Norris (1999) discuss that reminiscence can be used by anyone, they note that reminiscence for the purpose of fun can be a valid approach for those that are physically or mentally frail or those that have sensory issues as it can be adapted to fit their abilities without dwelling on what they have lost. Additionally, the sense of wellbeing that can come from participating in reminiscence can be a 'springboard' to greater involvement meaning that those with dementia may engage more with their families if they enjoyed the sessions and feel valued as a result.

1.4.1.2 Reminiscence to encourage intergenerational communication

Bender, Bauckham, and Norris. (1999) also explored reminiscence to encourage and facilitate intergenerational communication. They observed that older people often have a strong desire to impart their legacy, especially to younger people or children, and examined intergenerational communication through the context of schemes such as partnerships between schools and care homes. While this is a different scenario to this study, the underlying principles of intergenerational communication can still be pertinent for family visitors such as adult children or grandchildren and how they communicate with their loved one. Intergenerational communication can and should be a reciprocal process with both parties learning from each other (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999). From these interactions, opportunities can arise for the young to address prejudices and stereotypes that they may hold about the older population and vice versa.

Whilst this may not seem relevant to the experiences of family visitors, the process of intergenerational communication can allow families the opportunity to focus on what their loved one can still do and dispel the notion that the person they knew has already gone. Studies have shown that intergenerational reminiscence can strengthen social connection between grandparents and grandchildren. Xu, Hagedorn, and Chi (2023) explored intergenerational reminiscence between Asian American grandparents and grandchildren and found that this allowed grandchildren to gain a richer understanding of their grandparents lives before and after immigration which strengthened their relationships and had the potential to improve their psychological and emotional wellbeing.

1.4.1.3 Reminiscence to achieve a cultural legacy

Another key benefit of reminiscence is the opportunity it can present for older people and those with dementia to explore and pass on their cultural legacy. Older people, including those with dementia, often have a wealth of experience and knowledge of the past that could be lost if it is not passed onto younger generations. Bender, Bauckham, and Norris (1999) discussed the idea of passing on a cultural legacy by giving the example of older people who emigrated when they were younger. They contend that as society has rapidly changed over the years, the experiences of older people could offer insights into how life used to be with this being sharper for those who have emigrated as their family may not know about their culture and history. This is relevant for those with dementia who may find comfort in passing on their knowledge of their culture and traditions to their family as it provides them with an opportunity to leave behind a cultural legacy that could live on after they have gone.

Cultural reminiscence has been previously used to explore Appalachian culture with those living with mild to moderate cognitive impairment (Hash, Kisinger, and Tennant, 2021). In

their study, Hash, Kisinger, and Tennant (2021) incorporated Appalachian music, folklore, and games into a six-week reminiscence program and concluded that cultural reminiscence has the potential to provide relevant experiences for those living with cognitive impairment. Therefore, indicating that cultural reminiscence could be beneficial for those living with dementia in care homes as it can provide them with opportunities to pass on their knowledge to their loved ones.

1.4.1.4 Reminiscence and Spirituality

Several values that are inherently advocated in reminiscence such as respect for the other person, valuing them, listening to them, and sharing experiences, also have a clear spiritual or religious component (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999). As these values are common across religions, it could be argued that spirituality may inform certain approaches to reminiscence and that a competency and familiarity of reminiscence could be useful in religious or spiritual work.

Although this may not sound like a priority for families, spiritual and emotional care can be an integral component of care provided by families that can often be overlooked. The critical role that emotional and spiritual care provided by families and friends play within the care of a person living with dementia in a care home disputes the notion that families relinquish their caring role once their loved one has moved to a care home and instead supports the continued role of families in care provision (Puurveen, Baumbusch, and Gandhi, 2018). Whilst reminiscence makes use of memory triggers, it is not about historical recall and instead is focussed on experiencing events, relationships, discussions and distilling the essence of events and the emotions behind them rather than the pure facts. This means that reminiscence will inevitably touch on the spiritual dimension of identity through exploration

of feelings which could be a powerful aspect to consider for families as whilst their loved one may not remember the details of past events, they may remember how they felt at the time and this in turn could be used to connect with them and maintain their emotional and spiritual well-being (Helgesen, Larsson, and Athlin, 2013). It could be argued that by failing to take the spiritual aspect of identity into account, we are not considering the whole person in our approach to care. A founding tenet and strength of reminiscence is that it considers all aspects of people and their identity, including spirituality, that other therapies or approaches may overlook. This could be a valuable avenue for families to explore as drawing on aspects of spirituality and religion may help them to bring comfort to their loved one with dementia and may provide opportunities to connect with them even when their loved one no longer recognises them.

1.4.2 The Reminiscence Bump

A key component of my approach to reminiscence was the exploration of the 'reminiscence bump'. The reminiscence bump is a term used to describe the disproportionate number of autobiographical memories stored dating from youth and early adulthood (Kopel and Rubin, 2016; Berntsen, Kirk, and Kopelman, 2022). As this tends to be a formative period for many, memories from this period are highly emotive and therefore can be effective for reminiscence. This is a widely recognised phenomena in autobiographical-memory research (Kopel and Rubin, 2016). Whilst this is typically described as being a single period from which more memories are retrievable, recent studies have demonstrated that different types of memory cues or triggers can produce distinct 'bumps' that differ in size and temporal location. For example, the reminiscence bump produced when cue words are used is typically smaller in range and covers earlier in the life span than the reminiscence bump which covers major life

events, and when scents are used, this bump is even earlier (Kopel and Rubin, 2016). This suggests that whilst trigger words or olfactory cues can produce reminiscence bumps, they would be more effective when used alongside physical trigger objects such as family photographs or personal items. A study by Rathbone, O'Connor, and Moulin (2017) explored the role of the self in the reminiscence bump in relation to using music as a trigger. Their study showed that personally significant songs were more likely to be related with episodic memories compared to songs with less personal meaning, and that a reminiscence bump was only produced when personally significant music was used. This suggested that personal significance plays a central role in the reminiscence bump, underlining how this is generally linked to formative memories and the development of identity. This could be an interesting avenue for families to explore as this could indicate that music from childhood, or key life events such as weddings, could be effective reminiscence triggers which could help to keep families feeling connected to each other.

1.5 Overview of the Wendy Baxter Scholarship

This doctoral study was supported by the Wendy Baxter Scholarship; a legacy gift made to the University of the West of Scotland by the family of Dr Wendy Baxter M.B.E. The donation was made in recognition of Dr Baxter's professional commitment to improving dementia care, and her own lived experience of dementia following her diagnosis in 2017. Her final months were spent in a care home, an experience that had a profound impact on her family and shaped their desire to fund research aimed at enhancing the lives of people with dementia and their families in similar settings.

Administered through the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP), the scholarship was established with the intention of supporting a PhD project that explored the

use of creative approaches within care homes. In line with this intention, the present study focused on developing an understanding of family-centred reminiscence practices during care home visits, with the broader aim of supporting relationship-centred care and improving the overall experience of residents and their families. This scholarship not only provides the foundation for the focus and values of the study focus but also reflects a meaningful legacy rooted in compassion, advocacy, and a commitment to practice-informed research.

It is well known that caring for a relative with dementia is both a rewarding and emotionally challenging experience. As dementia progresses it is common that family carers experience psychological and emotional strains including anxiety, depression and increased feelings of guilt and loss, which are often exacerbated by their loved one moving to a care home. Thus, the focus of the Wendy Baxter Scholarship supported the selection of family-centred, reminiscence as the creative anchor for a potentially helpful and enjoyable activity for families visiting care homes.

1.5.1 Leaving behind a legacy

A guiding principle of this study was providing family visitors and people living with dementia an opportunity to leave a legacy behind. This is particularly pertinent for this study as it was funded through a legacy scholarship. Johnston and Narayanasamy (2016) explored psychosocial interventions for people living with dementia that enhanced personhood and related to legacy. They defined leaving a legacy as situations where a person living with dementia can reveal or leave behind aspects of their personhood such as life story, identity, or insights into their past roles or achievements (Johnston and Narayanasamy, 2016). They argue that as dementia is a progressive condition that can erode personhood and aspects of identity, psychosocial interventions that seek to preserve personhood are welcome

developments in dementia care. Johnston and Narayanasamy (2016) postulate that the opportunity to leave a legacy can support the enhancement of personhood and therefore, interventions that review a person's past life such as life story work or reminiscence can demonstrate the personhood of the person with dementia and give a sense of the person and not the diagnosis by making links between their past and their present.

The legacy component of object-stimulated reminiscence, which enabled reminiscence of earlier life experiences, allowed a deeper understanding of the person with dementia's identity and previous life stages which may have been previously unknown to both care home staff and family members. This new knowledge of their life story could be utilised to provide guidance to further implement person-centred care and to get an insight into the reasons behind the person with dementia's behaviour and learn what holds meaning to them in the present (Johnston and Narayanasamy, 2016). The idea of leaving a legacy could particularly come to the forefront when involving adult children or grandchildren of people living with dementia in care homes as the use of reminiscence techniques could allow them to discover more about their loved ones which in turn would contribute to the concept of a "meaningful visit" resulting in both parties feeling better after the visit. Therefore, reminiscence could be a valuable tool for families to use during visits as it has the potential to enhance the personhood of the loved one with dementia and deepen their connections to each other.

1.6 Overview of my background and how this informed the study

As a carer of a parent living with dementia, I am acutely aware of the benefits of sustained connections and relationships throughout the dementia journey. My dad was diagnosed with early onset dementia in 2016 at the age of 52. Whilst this has undoubtedly been challenging for us as a family, my dad is still my dad and, overall, his personality is still as bright and at

times cheeky as it always has been. Although my dad is still living at home, this has been crucial for me to bear in mind for my own research as it is important to see beyond the diagnosis and see the person that remains and place them at the forefront.

My dad's diagnosis, and our family's dementia experience, has given me a passion and a drive for dementia research, which has shaped my academic career thus far. Listening to those with lived experience has informed my previous studies into the family experience of dementia. My Honours dissertation project evaluated the post-diagnosis support offered to carers of younger people living with dementia and my Masters thesis centred on the support offered to people living with dementia who were employed at the time of diagnosis. These studies, coupled with my own lived experience, instilled a drive in me to find novel ways of supporting families over the duration of their dementia journey. Therefore, the Wendy Baxter Scholarship presented an opportunity to continue with this. As previously outlined in section 1.5, the Wendy Baxter Scholarship inherently had a strong focus on supporting families to enhance their visits with loved ones living with dementia. This strongly aligned with my own passion for dementia research, and my ambition to support families living with dementia. Furthermore, by drawing on my own experience of how dementia can impact family dynamics, I was able to empathise and connect with study participants as they shared how they strived to maintain their connections with their loved ones living with dementia.

My background and lived experience of dementia helped to inform key decisions throughout this study. One such example was deciding on the epistemological positioning, which would shape the study. From my own experience of caring for my dad, I know that the dementia experience is a highly subjective one and therefore, this was something that I was mindful of. This was also true of care home visits, as each family or family member can have differing

views on what they want to achieve during a visit. However, whilst the visit experience is a subjective one, the concept of a 'visit' is socially constructed as there is a broad consensus on what the types of activities that a visit should entail.

Additionally, the decision to explore reminiscence as a tool for families to enhance their connections to their loved ones, was directly influenced by my own experience of using reminiscence with my dad. As previously stated in section 1.4, reminiscence is usually conducted by trained therapists or specialists through reminiscence therapy and typically delivered in group settings. Through caring for my dad, I recognised reminiscence as an effective method of achieving in the moment connections with him, which proved to be an enjoyable activity for us both. Moreover, I acknowledged that families are often best placed to know the topics or areas of interests which would be more likely to be effective to explore through reminiscence. For example, I knew music from the 1980s and Star Trek were effective triggers for my dad, which still sparks conversation to this day. Therefore, this inspired me to explore how families could be empowered to conduct family-centred, reminiscence as a creative anchor enjoyable activities during their care home visits, which strengthens and enhances their connections to their loved ones.

1.7 Conclusion

From an initial look at the current policies surrounding family carers of those living with advanced dementia in nursing homes, it is evident that more research is needed to better support family carers. The Covid-19 pandemic highlighted that some families feel that nursing homes are often forgotten about as seen in their frustration with the delay in resuming visitations compared to the rest of society. It is also clear that due to difficulties in accurately recording cases of dementia in the community and in care homes, it can be challenging to

determine the prevalence of advanced dementia in care homes as seen in the recommendations raised by the Fair Dementia Care report. As outlined in this chapter, reminiscence can be an enjoyable activity which could be utilised to enhance connections between family members during their visits.

Chapter Two – Literature Review

This chapter presents a scoping literature review, informed by an initial preliminary literature search conducted to explore the existing body of knowledge related to the research topic. The review was carried out in two stages: first, a preliminary literature search to map the breadth of current understanding; and second, a scoping review that more systematically examined relevant literature. The aim of the scoping review was to explore the experiences of families following the admission of a loved one with dementia into a care home, alongside the concepts of reminiscence and family involvement in care. This review provides context and justification for investigating family-centred reminiscence facilitated by visiting relatives in care homes.

2.1 Familiarisation of the literature

Prior to conducting the full scoping review, steps were taken to quickly familiarise myself with the breadth of literature across three domains of interest which were: the family experience following a care home admission of a person living with dementia, the current care home practice relating to dementia, and the current care home policies and practice relating to end of life care for people living with dementia. As I was coming from a social policy background, this was an important step in my learning to sensitise myself to the current literature relating to care homes and residents living with dementia. To do this, I conducted an informal preliminary search of the literature centred on three domains of interest and selected a small sample of papers from each one. Mak and Thomas (2022) contend that a preliminary search of the literature is an important step in determining the breadth of the research question, whether a scoping review on the research topic has already been conducted, and if there is

sufficient literature to warrant a scoping review. Furthermore, a preliminary search of the literature can be an instrumental step in the development of the search strategy, such as the search terms used and the identification of databases for the full literature review, which can be further refined based on the papers found during the preliminary search (Mak and Thomas, 2022). Additionally, the search terms used in this preliminary stage may return too many papers that are irrelevant or outside the scope of the search, indicating that the search strategy and the inclusion and exclusion criteria will need to be defined and further refined.

This process was conducted between November and December 2021. Three searches were undertaken as part of a preliminary literature search and the search terms and inclusion criteria are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 – Overview of preliminary literature searches

Search topic	Database(s) Searched	Time frame	Total Results	Initial No. based on title and abstract	Final number of results
The experiences of family caregivers of someone with dementia following care home admission	EBSCO: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CINAHL Complete, • Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition, • MEDLINE • APA PsycArticles 	Papers published after 2010	22,471	6	6
The current care home practice relating to dementia care and those living with dementia	Web of Science	Papers published after 2010	68,524	10	6
Current policy and practice in place in care homes relating to palliative and end of life care for those with dementia	EBSCO: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CINAHL Complete • Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition • MEDLINE • APA PsycArticles, • SocINDEX with Full Text 	Papers published after 2011	6,104	4	4

Due to the number of results returned by each search, the selection and refinement process involved making an initial judgement based on the relevance of the titles. After this, the papers were further refined by reading the abstracts to determine the relevance. The selected papers were then read in full to ensure that they were relevant to the search terms. The insights gained, particularly around terminology and thematic gaps, directly informed the

design of the scoping review, including the development of search terms and inclusion criteria, which are explored in section 2.3.2.1.

Two papers were selected from each search based on their relevance to the search terms and critical Appraisal tools were used on the selected papers to determine which framework would be the most appropriate for the full scoping review. The Frameworks used were the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Framework, the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Framework, and the Centre for Evidence Based Medicine (CEBM) Framework (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme, 2023; Lockwood, Munn, and Porritt, 2015; Greenhalgh and Taylor, 1997). Whilst the three frameworks were broadly similar, it was determined that the CASP Framework would be the most appropriate for the scoping review as it offered a varied but concise analysis that prompted further examination of papers in more detail.

The examination of papers relating to the experiences of families following care home admission was highly beneficial for the scoping review as it started the identification of the main themes that ran through the current literature, for example the feelings of grief experienced by families, and the potential gaps in the literature that this thesis could address. Although the search identified a large volume of sources, scrutiny of a sample of titles and abstracts permitted sensitisation to key concepts and terminology to inform and focus future searches. It also identified search terms that yielded items beyond the scope of my study such as palliative care, and appreciation of how to meaningfully combine search terms within different databases. Whilst this exercise centred on trialling search terms and critical appraisal frameworks, it importantly allowed identification of three domains of interest around which to frame the searches for the main scoping review. These were: the experience of families

following a care home admission, the current evidence on reminiscence, and contemporary care home policy regarding family involvement.

2.3 Scoping Review

This scoping review was framed using the PRISMA-ScR checklist devised by Tricco *et al.* (2018).

2.3.1 Scoping Review rationale

Grant and Booth (2009) define a scoping review as an initial assessment of the scope and range of current knowledge and research evidence. Colquhoun *et al.* (2014, p5) expand this, stating that a scoping review is a “*form of knowledge synthesis that addresses an exploratory research question aimed at mapping key concepts, types of evidence, and gaps in research related to a defined area or field by systematically searching, selecting and synthesizing existing knowledge*”. A scoping review also permitted breadth in the review question and permitted a range of evidence sources to be included such as grey literature and policy documents (Munn *et al.*, 2018). Consideration was given to undertaking a systematic scoping review which Peters *et al.* (2015) argue standardises the process and reporting of a scoping review and although this was not undertaken, some elements such as PRISMA-ScR diagrams were embraced to promote rigour and transparency. An integrated review was also considered but as this is typically used to generate new theories or test existing ones by assessing the current state of the science and evidence presented in the literature this was rejected (da Silva, Brandão and Ferreira, 2020). Furthermore, as the literature review was centred on examining three domains of interest, a scoping review was appropriate as it permitted exploratory searches on the three concepts before synthesising the findings to situate this study within the gap in the literature.

Arksey and O'Malley (2005) list four common reasons why a scoping review approach may be used:

- to examine the scope of research activity,
- to determine the value of conducting a full systematic review,
- to summarise and disseminate research findings, and
- to identify gaps in the knowledge base (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005, p21).

A scoping review was selected as the preliminary literature search highlighted three domains of interest to frame the search terms. Therefore, a scoping review allowed me to draw upon a wide range of literature to explore these concepts, and to identify gaps and areas of interest to situate this study.

2.3.1.1 Scoping Review process

The original framework devised by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) comprised of five main steps, outlined in Diagram 1 below.

Diagram 1: Steps of a Scoping Review

2.3.2 Scoping Review Methods

This section outlines the methods used throughout the three searches of the scoping review.

2.3.2.1 Eligibility criteria

Several parameters were applied to the searches. Firstly, papers had to be published in English to avoid the need for a translator. Secondly, only papers published within the last 10 years of the search (between 2012 and 2022) were included to ensure that the evidence presented was still relevant in the ever-evolving field of dementia research. This scoping review also included grey literature, which is defined as literature that is not formally published in sources such as books or journal articles and can include material such as government reports, conference proceedings, and unpublished clinical trials (Cornell University Library, n.d.). Borenstein *et al.* (2009) contend that literature reviews that only consider published studies

can result in an inflated impression of the evidence base which could result in inappropriate conclusions being drawn. Grey literature was gathered by searching through the publications from relevant groups, such as the Creative Covid Care project.

2.3.2.2 Search Strategy

The main scoping review comprised of three searches exploring: the experiences of families following a care home admission, the concept of reminiscence, and the current care home practice in place concerning family involvement. The following databases were searched EBSCO: CINAHL Complete, Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition, MEDLINE, APA PsycArticles, and SocINDEX with Full Text, as well as searching Web of Science. These databases were selected as the preliminary literature search demonstrated that they were likely to be of relevance due to the volume of papers related to dementia that searches returned. Multiple databases were searched to ensure that key or prominent papers were not overlooked. The reference lists of papers were also searched to see if any additional papers were within the search parameters and as a result could also be included in this literature review.

2.3.2.2.1 Search terms used

The first search used the following terms: “dementia or Alzheimer’s” AND “nursing homes or care homes” AND “family caregiver experience” and searched through the following databases on EBSCO: CINAHL Complete, Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition, MEDLINE, APA PsycArticles, and SocINDEX with Full Text. This aimed to evaluate the strength of the current evidence base surrounding the experiences of family carers following a care home admission of a loved one with dementia. This was an important area to examine as it

signposted the issues that current family visitors face during visits with their loved ones which helped to guide the initial interviews during the first cycle.

The second search used the search terms “Reminiscence therapy” AND “dementia or Alzheimer’s” and searched through the following databases on EBSCO: CINAHL Complete, Health Source: Nursing/Academic Edition] and APA PsycArticles. This aimed to uncover the current use of reminiscence with people with dementia and the potential ways that previous studies have involved family members. This was crucial as this study focussed on the acceptability of family-centred reminiscence and was underpinned by the originality of involving families in a novel way.

Finally, the third search used the following search terms: “nursing homes or care homes” AND “family involvement” AND “guidelines or policy” and searched through Web of Science. Web of Science was selected as the preliminary literature search returned a large volume of papers regarding care home policies on family involvement. This search critically examined the current care home practice regarding the involvement of families and was a valuable step as it gave me a better understanding of how families are involved in care homes and how my study will be situated in differing care home cultures and management styles.

2.3.2.3 Selection of sources for evidence

To screen the search results, titles were reviewed for relevance to the topic, and the abstracts or summaries of those remaining were examined and refined to a final selection. Final review papers were selected based on their significance for the topic. The refinement process is displayed by the PRISMA-ScR diagrams below in Diagrams 2, 3, and 4 to concisely show how I narrowed down and focused my search to generate a manageable number of results without compromising the integrity and rigour of my search.

Diagram 2: PRISMA-ScR for Search One

Diagram 3: PRISMA-ScR for Search Two

Diagram 4: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases, registers and other sources for Search Three

2.3.2.2.1 Critical Appraisal Tools

Critical appraisal tools were used as part of the screening process for selecting papers. Whilst not a part of Arksey and O'Malley's original framework, Daudt, Van Mossel, and Scott (2013) strongly suggest that quality assessment of studies should be an essential element of a scoping review if they are to be useful in practice, policymaking or to inform future research. The main critical appraisal framework used in this review was developed by the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) as it offered a varied but concise analysis that prompted me to examine the papers in more detail. Whilst this was not an essential component of a scoping review, it was deemed a necessary step to form an analysis which considered the strength of the evidence presented in the papers in line with the recommendations from the Joanna Briggs Institute (Peters *et al.*, 2015). The CASP Framework also helped to build the foundation for further analysis focussing on the rigour and trustworthiness of studies which was instrumental for the literature review. The CASP Framework predominantly applied in this review was comprised of three checklists used for: Qualitative Studies, Systematic Reviews, and Randomised Control Trials (RCT). When a CASP tool was not appropriate, it was substituted for either the Joanna Briggs Checklist for Quasi-Experimental Studies or the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool version 2018 by Hong *et al.* (2018).

The Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Qualitative Framework consisted of ten questions grouped into three sections: are the results of the study valid, what are the results, and will the results help locally. The first two questions were designed to act as a screening process before deciding to continue assessing the paper. The ten questions required a "yes", "no" or "can't tell" with a comment box following each question which was designed to assist with recording the reasons for the answers. This was a highly beneficial feature as several of the questions required more than a ticked box to answer, which assisted with forming my

analysis. The CASP Systematic Review Framework also comprised of the same sections with broadly similar questions designed to question if the authors included relevant papers and if they assessed the trustworthiness of them before including them in their study.

2.3.2.4 Thematic synthesis of results

A thematic analysis (TA) was performed on the papers included in this review informed by the six-stage process outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022):

1. Familiarising yourself with the data
2. Coding
3. Generating initial codes
4. Developing and reviewing themes
5. Refining, defining and naming themes
6. Writing up the report

This aligned with the aim of this scoping review which sought to explore and synthesise the three search concepts, instead of summarising the results of relevant papers. Furthermore, a thematic analysis based on the work of Braun and Clarke (2006) has been used in previous scoping reviews as a means of identifying the key concepts and themes in the literature (Stenberg *et al.*, 2018; Haugstvedt, 2020; Finkelstein, Sharma, and Furlonger 2019; and Hamel *et al.*, 2021).

The emergent themes from each search are presented as a “map” and measured by how prevalent these were in the selected papers, these are presented in Diagrams 3, 4, and 5. Evidence maps are often a common feature of a scoping review as it can help to identify and analyse the gaps in the evidence base and highlight the results in a user-friendly format, like a figure or graph (McGowan *et al.*, 2020). Peters *et al.* (2015, p145) state that evidence maps

can be presented in a “*logical, diagrammatic, tabular, or a descriptive form*” that is aligned with the scope and objective of the review. Evidence maps can present the results of the search in numerous ways such as the distribution by year or research methods used, based on what would clearly illustrate the results in line with the objective and question of the review (Peters *et al.*, 2015). For this study, the results were mapped based on the prevalence of the themes from the evidence base. This aligned with the aim of this review which was to explore the key concepts of the family experience following a care home admission, reminiscence, and family involvement in the care home.

2.7 Scoping Review findings

This section will outline the findings from the three searches of this scoping review.

2.7.1 Search One: Experiences of family members following a Care Home admission

A thematic analysis was performed guided by Braun and Clarke (2022). There were four themes that emerged from the analysis: feelings of guilt and loss, adjusting to new roles, communicating with staff, and maintaining relationships. The map of these themes is illustrated by Diagram 5 below which is measured by the prevalence of the themes across the selected literature.

Diagram 5: Map of themes for Search One

2.7.1.1 Theme one: Feelings of guilt and loss

For many families, a care home admission of a loved one is often accompanied by feelings of guilt or loss which can have a profound impact on their mental health as well as the visit experience.

Feelings of guilt are often rooted in the misconceived idea that a family member has failed in their duty to care for their loved one at home (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Midtbust *et al.*, 2018; Statz *et al.*, 2021). The decision to move a loved one into a care home is often accompanied by a heavy emotional burden with families experiencing loss, a lack of control over the care of their loved one, as well as grief, particularly when focusing on the progression of the disease and the potential changes in the personality their loved one (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). This can often exacerbate an already difficult period in the trajectory of the disease and illustrates how the care home experience can be an emotionally taxing one with family members feeling that they had failed as a carer or

betrayed the trust of their loved one in moving them. This emotional toll can sometimes result in families second guessing their decision and feel that they need to justify their decision, both to themselves and to others (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). However, some family caregivers found the transition easier, with lower levels of guilt, once they recognised and accepted that their loved one needed round the clock care that was better suited for a care home environment than remaining at home.

It has been shown that the source of guilt can differ depending on the relationship with the person with dementia. Statz *et al.* (2021) showed that adult children commonly reported feelings of guilt as a result of balancing their working life as well as their pre-existing roles as a parent or spouse whilst trying to also fulfil their responsibilities as a caregiver to their loved one with dementia in a care home. These competing responsibilities may be a contributing factor in the visiting behaviours of adult children as they visited less on average compared to spousal carers with 11 visits per month compared to 19.6 visits per month during the study (Statz *et al.*, 2021). Conversely, whilst they visited less on average, adult children were concerned with not visiting enough and often compared their level of involvement with siblings. Approximately 30% of participants in the study reported that they felt guilt from members of the family. Family members noted that they experienced feelings of guilt if a visit did not go as well as they expected as they felt that they were unable to make a meaningful connection with their loved one (Statz *et al.*, 2021). This highlights the importance of 'meaningful visits' for families in encouraging them to preserve their relationship with their loved one with dementia. A component of this is challenging the perception that a visit is about making memories and instead focus on merely being present, whether that means reminiscing with the person with dementia by looking at photos or listening to music, or even something as simple as holding hands (Statz *et al.*, 2021). This further reinforces the

importance of empowering family visitors, for example with resources that support family-centred reminiscence, to help them to have more meaningful connections that leave them feeling happier and alleviate the persisting feelings of guilt.

Families also reported that a care home admission was accompanied by feelings of loss. Crawford *et al.* (2015) noted that for some family caregivers, whilst their loved one was still alive in a care home, they felt as though they were no longer with them. This was particularly pertinent for spousal caregivers who were more likely to have lived with their loved one for the majority of their life and therefore struggled with the physical loss following the care home admission. This is echoed by a more recent study by Cottrell *et al.* (2020, p229) who stated that the physical loss of the family member from the home was associated with the “*loss of family and home*”. This demonstrated the emotional and mental impact that a care home admission can have on families and could be a contributing factor in families struggling to adjust to care home visits. Therefore, this supports the exploration of family-centred reminiscence as a way to strengthen connections between family members and alleviate feelings of loss by continuing to bond with their loved one living with dementia.

2.7.1.2 Theme two: Adjusting to a new role

Following a care home admission, many families must adapt to their changing role and responsibilities regarding the care of their loved one with dementia. For the majority, this means adopting their new role as a ‘visitor’ instead of being the primary caregiver for the person with dementia (Helgesen, Larsson, and Athlin, 2013; Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Lee *et al.*, 2022). For some family caregivers, this came as a relief as they welcomed the changed responsibilities and felt relieved that the stresses and challenges of caring for their loved one at home were over (Hennings and Froggatt, 2019). However, for

others the move to a care home did not offer respite from their caregiver responsibilities with some feeling that they had to assume the role a spokesperson for their loved one in order to communicate any requirements, such as dietary needs or assistance with sight or hearing, and to monitor the levels of care within the care home (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). This encapsulates the idea that a move to a care home does not necessarily mark the end of the 'carer' role but instead changes the context of the role and the associated responsibilities. In most cases, this is evident in the role that family visitors play in the emotional and spiritual care of those living in a care home and the importance of supporting families to remain involved in the care of their loved one. Families can often adopt different 'roles' within the care home depending on their loved one's needs in order to preserve their well-being, comfort and dignity. Helgesen, Larsson, and Athlin (2013) defined these as a spokesperson, a guardian and "*being a link to the outside world*" with the role of a visitor being the constant overarching role that encompassed these. The idea of being the link to the outside world is an important one to consider as it highlights the essential role that visits can play in keeping the person with dementia connected to the rest of their family and friends, even when they may no longer be able to communicate or recognise them, which in turn can help to maintain their emotional and spiritual well-being.

Furthermore, this can be heightened for the families of immigrants with dementia in a care home who may have additional, more complex issues, such as the loss of a second language with family members having to act as a translator for both the care home staff and their loved one with dementia. As part of a study looking at the experiences of families of immigrants living in Swedish care homes with dementia, Rosendahl, Söderman, and Mazaheri (2016) examined the additional roles that families adopt to support their loved one who had lost their ability to speak Swedish. The results of their study showed that the families of

immigrants who had lost their second language, took on the additional roles of acting as an interpreter for both staff and the person with dementia, as well as being the expert on their loved one, with a particular focus on the cultural aspects of care which may have been overlooked otherwise (Rosendahl, Söderman, and Mazaheri, 2016). Whilst this is not a common experience for families in general, it illustrates the important role that visits play in the care of people with dementia and the consequent roles that families adopt to help facilitate this.

2.7.1.3 Theme three: Communication with staff

A major component of the literature on family experiences following a care home admission was the impact that the relationship between the families and staff had during the transition phase and beyond.

Clear lines of communication alongside a positive working relationship with care home staff was seen as a key facilitator in helping family members to adjust to their new role within the care home and allow them to handover the care of their loved one to staff, knowing that they are in safe hands (Johansson *et al.*, 2014; Lethin *et al.*, 2016; Rosendahl, Söderman, and Mazaheri, 2016; Pritty, De Boos, and Moghaddam, 2020; and Tasseron-Dries *et al.*, 2021). A healthy relationship with staff can make all the difference in making families feel welcomed during visits and in turn could encourage them to visit more frequently as they feel included in the care of their loved one and supported by staff (Johansson *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, families felt more comfortable visiting if staff were able to notice and help when the person with dementia was becoming distressed, for example when their family member was leaving and needed staff to distract them or calm them down (Johansson *et al.*, 2014). In the same study, Johansson *et al.* (2014) found that a welcoming environment within care homes during

the transition period helped to lower the levels of doubt and feelings of losing control experienced by family members as they felt that they were able to voice their views or worries concerning the care of their loved one. In a more recent study, Tasseron-Dries *et al.* (2021) highlighted that communication between families and staff played in a major role facilitating family involvement within Namaste care sessions in care homes with both groups noting that a good working relationship was crucial for active participation. This illustrates the importance of staff and family relations in not only helping the families adjust during the transition phase but also in encouraging active participation in the care of the person with dementia and facilitating frequent visits.

Conversely, communication breakdown between staff and families can have a detrimental impact on the visit experience and the levels of trust that families had towards the staff caring for their loved ones (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Pritty, De Boos, and Moghaddam, 2020, and Tasseron-Dries *et al.*, 2021). Role confusion can be a major factor in the breakdown of communication between staff and families with both parties struggling to understand the roles and expectations relating to the care of the person with dementia. Consequently, families felt that they did not have a voice if they were not consulted by staff and felt that they were unwelcomed and concerned about the lack of communication (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). Furthermore, a communication breakdown often led to feelings of uncertainty with some families concerned that any complaints made against staff could have an adverse impact on the care of their loved one (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). This clearly illustrates how a more antagonistic relationship between staff and families without clear communication can have an impact on the well-being of families and foster anxiety and concern surrounding the care of the person with dementia.

2.7.1.4 Theme four: Maintaining Relationships

Frequent family visits are an essential part of maintaining the relationships with the person with dementia which had positive impacts on the well-being of both the family visitors (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Johansson *et al.*, 2014; Lee *et al.*, 2022) and the person with dementia in the care home (Helgesen, Larsson, and Athlin, 2013; Cronfalk, Norberg, and Ternestedt, 2018; Hennings and Froggatt, 2019; Pritty, De Boos, and Moghaddam, 2020; Tasserion-Dries, 2021; and Van Corven *et al.*, 2022).

A care home admission did not mark the end of pre-existing relationships but was merely the next chapter with emotional bonds remaining that connected families together. Families often maintained relationships through remaining involved in the care of their loved one by bringing in their loved one's favourite foods, decorating their room to make it more homely, or helping to keep the room in the care home tidy (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). Maintaining relationships by remaining involved in the care of their loved one helped to alleviate the feelings of guilt experienced by some families during the transition phase. Furthermore, for some families, their relationship with their loved one had become closer as the dementia advanced with a son stating that:

“Actually, the contact with my father was never very intimate, but towards the end he surrendered completely to me. I arranged everything for him. I just noticed that he was glad when I was there, and that he also kind of put the responsibility entirely with me”
(Van Corven *et al.*, 2022, p5).

This encapsulates the importance of maintaining, or even improving, relationships following a move to a care home for both the family and the person with dementia. However, it is not

without difficulties. As the disease progresses, issues with verbal communication can arise, meaning that families must find new ways of communicating with their loved one.

When people with dementia are no longer able to communicate verbally, their families often rely on non-verbal means of communication to try and remain connected for as long as they can (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; McCormack, Tillock, and Walmsley, 2017; and Cronfalk, Norberg, and Ternestedt, 2018). For many, this means relying on sensation, stimulation, or rhythmic activities such as humming or something as simple as a hand massage as a means of non-verbal connection. A key part of this was for families to be present in the moment and aware that seemingly small actions have a larger impact for their loved one in maintaining a sense of purpose and belonging (McCormack, Tillock, and Walmsley, 2017). This further illustrates how some families adapted to remain connected during the trajectory of the disease to continue to be there for their loved one.

However, visits often became difficult during the later stages of the disease when the person with dementia no longer recognised their loved one (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Rosendahl, Söderman, and Mazaheri, 2016; Hennings and Froggatt, 2019; and Van Corven *et al.*, 2022). Some families eventually stopped visiting as the pain of watching a loved one deteriorate sometimes became too much to bear (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014). In addition to this, some spouses felt that they became invisible due to their partner no longer recognising them and as such it was too painful to visit frequently as it served as a reminder of the cognitive deterioration (Hennings and Froggatt, 2019). This serves as a reminder that for some family members, it was too painful to remain involved in the care of their loved one and consequently they stopped visiting the care home.

2.7.2 Search Two: Reminiscence

There were four themes that emerged from the thematic analysis: reminiscence as communication, benefits of reminiscence, family involvement in reminiscence, and importance of setting. The prevalence of these themes in the literature is illustrated by Diagram 6.

Diagram 6: Map of themes for Search Two

2.7.2.1 Theme one: Reminiscence as communication

Previous studies have suggested that reminiscence can be used to aid with communication for people with dementia, even when verbal communication is no longer possible (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Evans, Garabedian, and Bray, 2019).

In a study exploring the benefits of crafts as reminiscence triggers in women living in care homes with advanced dementia, Pollanen and Hirsimäki (2014) examined the verbal and non-verbal reactions to crafts as memory triggers during reminiscence therapy sessions. The

recordings of their sessions uncovered four non-verbal reactions to the memory triggers: looking at the object, kinaesthetic reactions (body movements in reaction to the trigger), haptic reactions (touching the object to sense it, such as scratching or pinching) and finally smelling the triggers (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014). This illustrates how reminiscence could be used by families to connect with non-verbal people with dementia, which could prove to be invaluable for those who may be struggling to connect with their loved one during visits. Moreover, the study also showed how reminiscence can help people with dementia communicate with others, even when they either forget words or are non-verbal altogether. Participants used their body language or movements during the sessions when they were interested in taking part in the discussions or to examine a particular trigger. They also used their movements as substitutes for words when they were trying to describe objects which enhanced reciprocal communication when they were non-verbal. This supports the idea that reminiscence could be used to facilitate communication when a person with dementia is struggling to communicate verbally and as such could be a useful tool for families to draw on during care home visits.

In a separate study, Evans, Garabedian, and Bray (2019) examined the impact of a music-based reminiscence programme on people with dementia and their families. Participants were gifted personalised CDs and booklets based on the observations from volunteers and the session leader from the reminiscence groups. Families reported that these materials helped them to connect with their loved and foster discussions based around music with one carer stating that her husband often looks at the booklet and shows it off whenever they have a visitor to the house (Evans, Garabedian, and Bray, 2019). Whilst this study was carried out in the community instead of within a care home, it highlights the impact that a personalised approach to reminiscence can have on the person with dementia and their families, and how

it can allow them to connect with each other. This greater connection could arguably help families of people with dementia in care homes not only to communicate during visits but also to help to assuage the feelings of guilt described by previous studies. Furthermore, Evans, Garabedian, and Bray (2019) suggest that their study showed that a music-based reminiscence can help facilitate non-verbal communication between those with advanced dementia and their families. Music based reminiscence interventions have been found to support non-verbal communication in those with advanced dementia and can facilitate recall of memories, for example from childhood or early adulthood (Evans, Garabedian, and Bray, 2019). Consequently, this supports the idea that reminiscence interventions can help boost communication and engagement and can help to keep families connected with their loved one with dementia.

2.7.2.2 Theme two: Benefits of reminiscence

Reminiscence has been shown to have several benefits for people with dementia such as improvements in cognition and quality of life, decreasing symptoms of depression and improving some aspects of memory. Various studies have suggested that reminiscence can have a positive impact on cognition, symptoms of depression for those with dementia (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013; Siverová and Bužgová, 2014; Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2016; Bohlken *et al.*, 2017;) and auto-biographical memory (Kirk *et al.*; 2019).

Reminiscence has been shown to reduce depressive symptoms for those living with dementia. As part of a study assessing the impact of individualised, thematic reminiscence sessions based on the SolCos model on older adults with Alzheimer's, Van Bogaert *et al.* (2013) examined the impact on cognition and depressive symptoms over six to eight reminiscence sessions. Their results showed that those in the intervention group had better Mini-Mental

State Examination (MMSE) and Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS-30) scores that measured cognition and depression than the control group (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013). Those with moderate levels of disease were found to have a greater change in MMSE score however, the intervention was shown to have a positive change in the GDS scores for both mild and moderate levels of disease. This demonstrates that reminiscence can be an effective intervention for those with dementia and could support the use of family-centred reminiscence during care home visits.

These results are supported by a similar study by Siverová and Bužgová (2014) which showed that prior to the intervention, 70% of participants presented depressive symptoms, however, this declined to 37% post intervention. They suggest that reminiscence can be an effective, nonpharmaceutical intervention as it is built on the idea that people long for recognition and connection, particularly those with dementia who are often isolated and find it difficult to connect with others and as such lose their feelings of self-worth and value (Siverová and Bužgová, 2014). This reinforces the idea that family-centred reminiscence could be an effective intervention during visits as it allows those with dementia to connect with their loved one which in turn could have an improvement on their quality of life.

Conversely, a systematic review by Woods *et al.* (2018) is more critical of the current evidence surrounding reminiscence as an effective intervention for those with dementia. They note that whilst reminiscence can cause a slight improvement in cognition scores immediately after the course of the intervention, this does not continue weeks or months after the sessions, suggesting that the benefits are only short term. Whilst this could discourage the use of reminiscence as a standalone treatment, it still supports the use of family-centred reminiscence for this study, which is not seen as a therapy or treatment but instead as a way

to keep families connected following a move to a care home. Furthermore, Woods *et al.* (2018) found that group sessions and those carried out in the community may have small benefits on communication and levels of interaction for people with dementia both immediately after sessions but also potentially for weeks or month later (Woods *et al.*, 2018). Whilst this supports group sessions, this benefit may carry over for family centred sessions as it helps to foster greater connection between them and their families.

2.7.2.3 Theme three: Family Involvement in reminiscence

Whilst this may be the first study to explore family-centred reminiscence delivered during care home visits, there have been several papers that have examined family involvement in reminiscence sessions which highlight how receptive families can be to the sessions as well as the issues that they may face (Subramaniam, Woods, and Whitaker 2014; Evans, Garabedian, and Bray, 2019; O’Philbin, Woods, and Holmes, 2020; and Ryan *et al.*, 2020).

One paper looking at family involvement was a study by Ryan *et al.* (2020) which examined the impact of individualised reminiscence delivered through an app for family carers and those living with mild to moderate levels of dementia. A key point raised in this study was that for some families, not all memories were positive and as such revisiting them during the reminiscence could be challenging and distressing. However, by discussing these memories and addressing the feelings that lay behind them, families were able to reconnect with their loved one with dementia (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, families liked the app design as it made them feel like they were not alone on the journey of caring for their loved one and helped them to feel that they were supporting their loved one to boost their self-esteem and find comfort. Families also reported that reminiscence brought them closer to their loved one through the sessions acting as a communication aid, as well as a way to prompt memory

sharing (Subramaniam, Woods, and Whitaker 2014; Ryan *et al.*, 2020). This was also shared by some people with dementia who stated that they felt more open with their carer, conversely some reported that their carer had become more protective of them after the sessions (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). This reminiscence approach provided family carers with the opportunity to not only revisit memories but also create new ones and more importantly, celebrate the life that they had and continue to have with their loved one (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). This illustrates how family-centred reminiscence could be a crucial resource for families who may struggle with what to do in visits as it can create an opportunity for them to connect with their loved ones as well as create new memories to cherish.

Whilst family involvement can often be a positive experience, it can also be distressing for some families and sourcing pictures or similar triggers can create an unnecessary burden for carers (Fletcher and Eckberg, 2014). This could be distressing as some carers found it difficult to find photos and when they did, it highlighted parts of the past that their loved one no longer remembered. Despite this some carers noted that whilst looking at photos was often a sad experience, it also reminded them of happier moments in the past of shared experiences with their loved one. One carer also stated that whilst her husband may not have remembered the people or moment from a photo he reacted to the “*essence of the photographs*” which comforted her in some way as it still allowed her to connect with him (Fletcher and Eckberg, 2014, p78). Reminiscence also changed the families’ perception of their loved one’s quality of life which suggested that whilst the long-term benefit of the intervention is uncertain, it can provide comfort and help to lessen feelings of guilt (Fletcher and Eckberg 2014; Ryan *et al.*, 2020). This suggests that family-centred reminiscence delivered during visits could not only help keep families connected to their loved ones but also help their own mental wellbeing by assuaging the feelings of guilt and loss following a care home admission.

2.7.2.4 Theme four: Importance of setting

The mode and setting for the delivery of reminiscence can have an impact on how receptive participants are and the effectiveness of the intervention (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013; Subramaniam, Woods, and Whitaker, 2014; Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2016; Bohlken *et al.*, 2017; Woods *et al.*, 2018; O'Philbin, Woods, and Holmes 2020; and Ryan *et al.*, 2020). Reminiscence is typically delivered either in groups sessions or individually by a trained facilitator and usually held either in the community or within a care home setting. The outcomes of a reminiscence intervention can be linked to the setting with different modes of delivery offering different benefits.

Whilst group reminiscence sessions can be beneficial in boosting communication skills, for some family carers and their loved ones, a one-to-one session is preferable as it can allow them to reconnect with each other (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). Family carers conveyed that the home-based aspect of the reminiscence app meant that the person with dementia was more relaxed and as such shared more intimate or personal memories than they possibly would have done in group sessions which was considered to be integral to their continued involvement in the reminiscence (Ryan *et al.*, 2020). This supports a family-centred approach to reminiscence for families to use during their visits as their loved one would be in a familiar environment in which they feel relaxed.

Interestingly, this preference for an individual setting for reminiscence is reflected in some families' openness to paying for an individual session compared to a group in the community. Some carers were willing to pay £40 more to have a one-to-one reminiscence session in their homes instead of a group session (O'Philbin, Woods, and Holmes, 2020). Additionally, carers were twice as likely to pick an individual reminiscence service over a group session in the

community. This was also reflected in the preferences of those with dementia, who were more inclined to choose an individual setting over a community group. This would suggest that family visitors may be receptive to a family centred reminiscence approach for use during care home visits as it maintains the one-to-one setting which could foster a deeper connection with their loved one through revisiting memories. Furthermore, studies have suggested that a care home setting for a reminiscence intervention can lead to a slight improvement in self-reported quality of life for those with dementia (Woods *et al.*, 2018). This supports the idea that reminiscence can be more effective if it is delivered in a setting that the person with dementia feels safe and comfortable in such as a common room in a care home or in their bedroom.

An individual setting for reminiscence can also be an effective way to connect with older adults with dementia who do not respond to more group-oriented sessions (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013). A personalised individual approach to reminiscence can have potential therapeutic advantages for people with dementia when sessions are more structured with appropriate memory triggers. Typically, sourcing the right trigger items for each person involves collaboration with their friends and families however, a family-centred approach could remove this and empower family visitors to plan appropriate reminiscence sessions based around available items which hold meaning to them and their loved one.

2.7.3 Search Three: Family Involvement in Care Homes

There were three themes that emerged from the analysis: importance of family involvement, Staff related factors/staff perception, and the impact of the Covid-19 restrictions on family involvement. The prevalence of these themes in the literature is illustrated by Diagram 7.

Diagram 7: Map of themes for Search Three

2.7.3.1 Theme one: Importance of family involvement

Family involvement within care homes can take many forms from visits with loved ones to a more formal approach through advanced care planning. The continued involvement of families after a care home admission can be vital source of support both for the person with dementia and staff.

A key point is that families and friends play a critical role within the care of a person with dementia living in a care home by offering emotional, spiritual or at times, personal care following a care home admission (Puurveen, Baumbusch, and Gandhi, 2018). This disputes the notion that families relinquish their caring role once their loved one has moved to a care home and supports the idea that a care home admission is not the end of the story but a new chapter with new responsibilities. Another important aspect of continued family involvement is that family members can sometimes notice the early signs of a loved one's changing health before staff as they have more experience of the individual to draw upon. There are three ways that families can contribute to the timely detection of changes in health (Powell *et al.*,

2018). The first is that family members noticed the early signs through past experiences of caring for the individual which granted them more knowledge of their usual health through spending time with them during nonpersonal care visits. Secondly, family members often informed care home staff about the signs that could indicate changing health, even if there was sometimes confusion about who they had informed, or information had not been passed on to other staff. Lastly, staff members were educated by family members about their loved one's health history, the related indicators of declining health and how this may cause a change in behaviour (Powell *et al.*, 2018). This demonstrates the key role that continued family involvement can play in bolstering the care of their loved one and support staff to fully care for them.

Family involvement can often involve taking on an advocacy role during the care planning process with them acting as their loved one's advocate during decision making (McCreedy *et al.*, 2018; Gonella *et al.*, 2022). This further illustrates how the role of the family in the care of their loved one does not necessarily end following a care home admission but instead it signifies a new phase that may involve different challenges than their past role. In a study by McCreedy *et al.* (2018), just over half of care home residents involved in the study with severe cognitive impairment had no one advocating for them or conveying their wishes during care home assessments. Furthermore, they noted that the level of family involvement during care planning assessments is low however, it increases as their loved one's cognitive abilities decline. This can also fluctuate from care home to care home, suggesting that care home culture can play a role in encouraging continued family involvement. Additionally, continued family involvement within the care home adds to the sense of 'home' for residents. Conversely, infrequent family visits were seen as an indicator of behavioural and psychological disturbances among people with dementia (Gaugler and Mitchell, 2022). This further

highlights the important role that family involvement and visits can play in maintaining the mental well-being of people with dementia living with dementia in care homes.

2.7.3.2 Theme two: Staff related factors and staff perceptions of family involvement

There are several factors that can both hinder and facilitate family involvement within a care home. Several studies have examined these and the consequent impact on the levels of family involvement in the care of their loved one in the care home.

Trust in staff from family members is arguably an important factor that can influence levels of family involvement in care (Boogaard *et al.*, 2017; Law, Patterson, and Muers, 2017). Families stated that they felt it was important that they were able to trust staff to meet, or exceed, the level of care that they would be able to provide their loved one themselves (Law, Patterson, and Muers, 2017). Additionally, families' trust in the ability of staff to deliver care was directly linked to the growth of a trusting relationship, with a lack of trust causing families to feel that they had to supervise staff during visits to ensure that their loved one was receiving a satisfactory level of care within the care home (Law, Patterson, and Muers, 2017). This demonstrates how levels of trust in staff can impact family involvement within the home as a lack of trust could take some families' attention away from being present during visits with their loved one with dementia if they feel that they need to monitor staff. In turn, this could potentially have an adverse effect on the families' ability to maintain their relationship with their loved one.

In their monitoring of staff, families not only focussed on how staff interacted with their loved one, but also how their loved one responded to staff and how staff acted towards other residents as they expected staff to be attentive to their loved one during visits and believed that they would not receive satisfactory care without family monitoring (Law, Patterson, and

Muers, 2017). This reinforces the idea that if there is not a trusting relationship between families and staff, then families no longer feel that staff would deliver an appropriate level of care for their loved one and therefore believe that they need to monitor staff to ensure satisfactory care is delivered.

Information sharing and family involvement in decision making can be instrumental in improving the levels of trust that families have in care home staff, and health care professionals in general. For families to fully trust staff, staff had to show that they trusted families and therefore include them in any decisions relating to the healthcare of their loved one (Boogaard *et al.*, 2017). This highlights how a trusting relationship between staff and families is reciprocal and how trust can help to facilitate family involvement in the decision-making aspect of the care of their loved one in the care home.

The importance of a welcoming atmosphere within the care home in encouraging family involvement cannot be overlooked, with families expecting staff to make them feel welcome by greeting visitors and being willing to talk and listen to any concerns (Kiljunen *et al.*, 2018). Families felt that staff's ability to work with visitors was a basic standard and expected staff to facilitate family involvement through accurate answers to questions and information sharing on their loved one's health, care, and daily activities without needing to be asked (Kiljunen *et al.*, 2018). This encapsulates how staff can help to encourage family involvement by building trust by being welcoming to visitors and sharing information with families.

Similarly, staff encouragement can increase the frequency or duration of family visits, in addition to encouraging a wider circle of family members or friends to visit. Increased visits along with a home-like environment can help to comfort residents and improve their psychological and emotional wellbeing, which can be particularly important for those with

dementia (Miller, 2019). This highlights how staff can help to facilitate family involvement as well as encourage a wider circle of visitors which can have benefits for residents, especially those living with dementia.

In situations where families were not involved in the care of their loved one, they typically felt comfortable to delegate control and care duties to staff which then made it more difficult to include family members in discussions on care planning or to share the care needs and preferences of their loved one (Mariani *et al.*, 2017). Another barrier hindering family involvement was the feelings of guilt that many families felt after admission which adversely affected their ability to confide in the care home staff about the care of their loved one (Mariani *et al.*, 2017). This further demonstrates the domino effect of the initial feelings of guilt accompanying a care home admission which can have negative knock-on effects on family involvement in care of their loved one down the line.

2.7.3.3 Theme three: Impact of Covid-19 restrictions

The past few years have seen care homes being disproportionately impacted by restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Whilst these measures have been widely debated, they served as barriers to family involvement in the care of their loved one as well as demonstrating the crucial role that families played in the care provision within the care home (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021; and Gaugler and Mitchell, 2022).

The Covid-19 pandemic has undeniably had an adverse effect on the mental health for many; however, it could be argued that carers felt this more sharply than most (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021). The visiting restrictions put in place during the pandemic impacted family carers with 76% of respondents scoring 12 or more in a General Health Questionnaire, with 12 points or more indicating “*clinical mental distress*” (Creative Covid Care, 2021, p5).

Furthermore, family carers had an average score of 18.16, compared to an average of 12.7 for the wider public. Visit frequency was also a contributing factor towards the severity of the impact from restrictions with those who visited more than once a week scoring higher than those who visited less frequently (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021). This illustrates the importance of family involvement in care for the emotional and mental wellbeing for families and the adverse impact if this is suddenly removed.

The pandemic restrictions also highlighted the problematic connotations of referring to families as 'visitors' compared to 'carers' as it was felt that it minimised the continued role that families played in the delivery of care of their loved one within the care home environment (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Gaugler and Mitchell, 2022). This misconception about the role of the family within the care home was reflected in the visit restrictions which highlighted that policy makers only had a shallow understanding of the role that families played as partners in care and how instrumental the continued relationship was for both carers and their loved one with dementia.

The pandemic also emphasised the role of information sharing and communication with staff in facilitating family involvement and maintaining some level of involvement despite restrictions. When communication over restrictions broke down, families felt uninformed about their loved one's wellbeing and experienced feelings of anxiety and fear over the uncertainty (Gaugler and Mitchell, 2022). This demonstrates how timely communication can facilitate family involvement in care, and how a breakdown in communication can heighten anxiety for carers and exclude them from the care of their loved one.

Separation because of visit restrictions also removed a key support network for some families who had incorporated care home visits into their daily routine and viewed staff as friends and

a community (Creative Covid Care, 2021). A lack of visits caused families to worry about their loved one's health and feared that separation could cause a decline, particularly for those with dementia. Some families also believed that the standard of care within the care home would potentially decline if they were not there to monitor it or voice the needs of their loved one (Creative Covid Care, 2021). Further illustrating how involvement in care can be important for families in reassuring them that their loved one is receiving a high standard of care and the additional stress caused if they cannot visit to monitor care.

Furthermore, a lack of visits meant that some families feared that they were losing valuable time to connect with their loved one. Whilst care homes utilised other means of contact such as video calls or phone calls, residents still felt isolated from their loved ones which could have had a detrimental impact on their wellbeing (Prins *et al.*, 2021)., Once in-person visits were reinstated, families were not allowed to have physical contact with their loved one which was a distressing and upsetting experience for families and those with dementia who may not have understood why the measures were in place (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021). This further illustrates how the pandemic restrictions hindered family involvement within the care home to the detriment of both families and their loved one. However, this could be viewed as highlighting the important role that families play when they are able to participate in care and how this benefits the emotional and mental wellbeing for both parties.

2.8 Key findings

It is evident from these searches that there is a breadth of literature surrounding the family experience of a care home admission, the current evidence and use of reminiscence, and family involvement within care homes. The literature clearly demonstrates the issues that families face following moving a loved one with dementia to a care home, such as persisting

feelings of guilt or loss as well as the struggle to adjust to their new role within the home. Likewise, there is encouraging evidence surrounding the use of reminiscence as a non-pharmaceutical intervention for those with dementia. Whilst there is some debate on the long-term benefits of the intervention, the contemporary literature suggests that reminiscence can be an effective means to encourage both verbal and non-verbal communication for those with dementia. Furthermore, the use of reminiscence-based apps for families in the community highlight the potential benefits of developing a family-led approach for during care home visits.

Additionally, there is evidence supporting the continued involvement of families in the care of their loved one in a care home whether this is through adopting a role of an advocate for their loved one in care planning or offering emotional support for their loved one during visits. Recent studies have highlighted the detrimental impact of visit restrictions during the covid-19 pandemic, illustrating the vital role that family visits play in maintaining the mental and emotional wellbeing of those with dementia, as well as the benefits for the families (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021; and Gaugler and Mitchell, 2022).

However, this review has identified a gap in the contemporary literature as there is a lack of research on the visit experience for family visitors in the period in between the transition phase and end of life care. Moreover, whilst there has been a recent increase in studies examining the use of app-based reminiscence for families, I did not find an example of a completely family-led reminiscence intervention, both in care homes and within the wider community. Therefore, this thesis seeks to address this gap by developing a family-centred reminiscence-based intervention for use during care home visits of people with dementia.

Chapter Three - Methodology

3.0 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodological approach adopted for this study. Grounded in this context, the research sought to generate a collaborative understanding of the benefit and practical application of family-centred reminiscence and to co-create a resource to support family members to use structured reminiscence, through an approach that prioritises collaboration, reflection, and practical impact. The chapter begins by presenting the aims and objectives of the study, providing a foundation for the methodological decisions that follow. Action research was selected as the primary methodology due to its participatory nature and alignment with the values of co-production and real-world change. The chapter then considers alternative research approaches that were explored and ultimately set aside, explaining how action research offered the most suitable framework for addressing the study's goals. Following this, the philosophical foundations of action research are discussed, with particular attention to the epistemological and ontological assumptions that shaped the study. The chapter then details key features of the action research process, including relevant typologies and continuums, and explains how these were applied in practice to guide the study. The theoretical underpinnings are also examined, especially in relation to the family experience of care home visits, and how these informed the research design. Finally, the chapter concludes with a discussion of the ethical considerations and measures taken to ensure rigour and trustworthiness throughout the research process.

3.1 Study aim and objectives

This study had two key aims. Firstly, to generate a collaborative understanding of the benefits and practical application of family-centred reminiscence and then, to co-create a resource to support family members to use structured reminiscence during visits with their relatives living with dementia in care homes.

There were five main objectives of my research. Cycle one aimed to create a shared understanding with family visitors of the experience of visiting the care home and understand the ways that they might already use informal reminiscence during their visits. Cycle two explored with family visitors the benefits and practical application of using reminiscence techniques during visits and develop a participatory approach to family-centred reminiscence which the families used during their visits. Cycle Three sought to co-create a resource to support the delivery of family-centred, individualised reminiscence informed by the study findings. The third cycle included staff from the study site to discuss how they could support families to use the co-produced resource and the delivery of family-centred reminiscence.

3.2 Research Paradigm

According to Lather (1986), a research paradigm reflects the worldview and beliefs of the researcher where it is believed to be the conceptual foundation for methodological decisions regarding research methods (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017; Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Methodology experts suggest that a research paradigm comprises of epistemology, ontology, and methodology (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

For this study, a social constructionist position was adopted which viewed reality as socially constructed within the bounds of a particular context, for example, the family experience of

care home visits. Although care homes are governed by regulatory bodies and best practice guidelines, the experience of family visitors within the care home is a socially constructed phenomenon that is not static. Bryman's (2012) definition of social constructionism recognises flux within social phenomena with no absolute, determinable truth. As visiting is a social phenomenon it follows that to be useful, my reminiscence approach needed to be responsive to 'in the moment' changes in addition to the progressive nature of dementia and variations in the personal outcomes that mattered to family members to be helpful. As such, any reminiscence approach used, could not be considered absolute as it was influenced by how receptive each person with dementia was during the visit, which in turn, determined the delivery and outcome of the reminiscence approach. Furthermore, the term "visit" in relation to care homes is a social construction with each family having their own meaning of what a visit should entail and their consequent role within the home and delivery of care. Therefore, for this study, it was not about challenging pre-held perceptions surrounding visits but instead understanding what it meant for each family and how they viewed their continued role in their relative's life.

Ontological positions reflect the assumptions and beliefs about the nature of the social world held by the researcher (Scotland, 2012; Blaikie and Priest, 2017). These philosophical assumptions regarding the nature of reality are critical in forming meaning from collected data and are crucial in positioning the approach to the research problem, its significance and how to solve it (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Moreover, ontology questions if the social world is a real, tangible thing or if it is a social construction unique to each individual (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

Epistemology goes further than ontology and questions the nature and forms of acceptable knowledge in a discipline or research area and questions if the social world can, or should, be studied by adhering to the same ethos and procedures as the natural sciences (Bryman, 2012). Guba and Lincoln (1994, p108) contend that that epistemology queries the nature of the relationship between the *“would-be knower and what can be known”*. However, the answer to this is constrained by the ontological position as epistemology guides how data and knowledge can be gathered based on the assumptions held by the researcher on the nature of the social world.

Every research paradigm is based on ontological and epistemological assumptions, and it is crucial that these are explicit when attempting to produce new knowledge about the social world (Blaikie and Priest, 2017). Blaikie and Priest (2017) also contend that whilst paradigms are an unavoidable aspect of research, loyalty to any one approach is unnecessary and undesirable and the challenge for researchers is to select a paradigm that provides the best approach to answering the research question given the associated assumptions. The ontological and epistemological assumptions of reality and what constitutes knowledge underpins the consequent approach to both methodology and axiology. The methodology utilised is heavily guided by the selected paradigm as it is crucial that the methods used works congruently within the parameters of their ontological and epistemological approach.

3.3 Alternative Epistemologies

Social constructionism formed the epistemological foundation for this study as it holds the belief that meaning, and truth are not external things to discover but are constructed through the subject and object working in partnership to generate knowledge (Crotty, 1998). Furthermore, within the constructionist view of reality, there is no absolute truth as it is

produced through social interaction and is in a constant state of revision (Bryman, 2012). Bryman (2012) contends that it is also reflected in the notion that the accounts of the social world by researchers are themselves social constructs and as such, a researcher offers a specific version of social reality, rather than a definitive truth. Alternative approaches, such as objectivism and subjectivism, were also explored before selecting social constructionism.

Contrasting social constructionism, objectivism asserts that meaning and social phenomena exist independently from consciousness or social actors (Bryman, 2012). Consciousness in this context refers to the awareness of an external factor. Crotty (1998) contends that understandings and values can be objectified in participants and as such, if research is conducted correctly, objective truth can be uncovered. This means that for the objectivist approach, reality is external to those living in it and can become an almost tangible phenomenon. Therefore, a researcher within objectivism, views knowledge as a concrete, discoverable thing to be uncovered, regardless of how it is viewed. However, this was not appropriate for this study as the visit experience is a highly individualised one driven by the families' expectations and perceptions of what a visit should entail.

Opposing this is subjectivism which is built on the assumption that all knowledge is subjective and that there is no objective or tangible truth that exists externally. Crotty (1998) asserts that for subjectivists, meaning does not result from an interplay between subject and object but is imposed on the object by subject. However, subjects still create and attach meaning to objects based on a collective unconsciousness, such as dreams or religious beliefs. For Crotty (1998), meaning in a subjectivist view of reality can come from almost anywhere, apart from an interaction between the subject and the object to which it is attributed to. Whilst the families' experience of visiting their loved one is a subjective one, the concept of a 'visit' is a socially

constructed one and as such, a social constructionist approach was deemed to be appropriate for this study. Furthermore, the desire to take collaborative action with family carers aligned with action research approaches.

3.4 What is Action Research?

Reason and Bradbury (2008) assert that action research is a participatory process that seeks to bring together action, reflection, theory, and practice in the pursuit of practical solutions to issues of concern. Action research is a strategy that engages social researchers and stakeholders in an ongoing cycle of co-generative knowledge creation, action design and evaluation of outcomes (Greenwood, 2007). A unique aspect of action research is that it is an empirical and logical problem-solving process involving cycles of action and reflection, rooted in collaborating with participants (McNiff and Whitehead, 2006; Reason and Bradbury, 2008; Kemmis, McTaggart, and Nixon, 2014; McNiff, 2017). Kemmis, McTaggart, and Nixon (2014) contend that at its core, action research is a self-reflective spiral of research cycles of planning, acting and observing, reflecting, and then re-planning in consecutive cycles of improvement. Each step in the cycle flows into the next subsequently leading to the generation of new knowledge as each cycle develops. Whilst the literature presents this as a linear process, in practice it is more fluid and responsive with steps often overlapping or repeating within each cycle. As such, action research is an emergent research process where the findings of each step act as the starting point for the next, with each cycle building on the findings of the previous one.

For Reason and Bradbury (2008), the primary objective of an action research study is to produce practical knowledge that is useful to people in the everyday conduct of their lives with the goal that this is continued and repeated once the research has concluded. This is

consonant with an aim of this thesis which aims to develop a family-centred, structured reminiscence resource and consequent resource which could be used by other family carers to inform implementation of reminiscence during their visits with their loved ones with dementia. Additionally, Reason and Bradbury (2008) contend that participation lies at the heart of action research as the overall goal is to work towards practical outcomes as well as creating new forms of understanding through the collaboration between the various groups involved in the study.

3.4.1 Alternative Research Design Considerations

Other research designs were considered that could be used to investigate a reminiscence-based intervention before action research was selected as the methodology for this study. One alternative design considered was a case study approach, which is briefly explored below. Whilst this approach was ultimately rejected, it would be remiss to say that some aspects were not incorporated into my design.

A case study approach was briefly considered for this study as it allows a researcher to closely examine a data set within a specific context, typically based on a small geographical area or a small number of subjects (Zainal, 2007). Case studies also offer researchers an opportunity to examine an activity within the bounds of its own circumstances (Stake, 2005). Moreover, case studies can also be used to investigate the meanings of situations and to report on the personal experiences to offer readers the opportunity to make their own judgment about how things work (Stake, 2010). Furthermore, Gerring (2004) contends that a case study is an intensive examination of a single unit for the purpose of understanding a larger class of related units, in this instance a unit is a spatially bounded phenomenon such as a group of people or a political party, observed at a single time or over a set timeframe. Yin (2014) adds that case

studies can be suited to answer the 'how' and 'why' questions in a study which can be beneficial in understanding a particular phenomenon. Nevertheless, whilst case studies can be used to investigate a particular phenomenon in rich detail, this approach was ultimately rejected. For this study, whilst case studies would have enabled me to examine the impact of reminiscence during family visits to care homes, it would have required assumptions to be made about the family experience of visits.

3.4.2 Rationale for Action Research

Action research was therefore selected for this study due to its explicit emphasis on collaboration, shared ownership of the research process, and its capacity to facilitate practice change. These features were especially important given the study's aim to work alongside family carers to co-develop meaningful reminiscence practices within care home settings. Action research was selected as it is a participatory process that involves multiple stakeholders engaging in a systematic inquiry into an issue where they might otherwise be research subjects or recipients of interventions in a conventional study design (Stringer, 2007; Reason and Bradbury, 2008). Furthermore, where traditional research seeks to uncover generalisable solutions to issues regardless of the context, action research centres on localised solutions that work in the specific situation of the study (Stringer, 2007). Participation is a key tenet of a successful action research study as the inherent complexities of the problem addressed requires the knowledge and experience of a broad and diverse group of stakeholders who will all bring their own intellectual or experiential expertise to the table (Greenwood, 2007). This collaboration was an important aspect for this study as I wanted to work alongside families to develop a novel approach to reminiscence based on their experiences of visiting their loved ones, rather than making assumptions about possible issues that they were facing. However,

action research is not a homogenous design, and alternative action research approaches are explored in next section.

3.4.3 Approach to Action Research

Various forms of action research exist. This study adopted a Collaborative Action Research (CAR) approach, although Participatory Action Research (PAR) was also considered during the design phase. Participatory Action Research was considered as it is an approach to action research that seeks to readdress the traditional power dynamic between the researcher and participants. As with conventional action research, PAR is comprised of iterative, reflective action cycles whereby participants collect and analyse data before determining an appropriate course of action based on the results. Baum (2006, p854) asserts that PAR blurs the line between the usual roles of researcher and participant until the *“researched become the researchers”*. During this process the *‘researched’* become research partners and are involved throughout the whole research process including selecting the research topic and design, data collection and analysis, and determining how the study results are disseminated thus shifting the power dynamic between researcher and participants. Whilst this would be an interesting approach and foster a deeper sense of ownership over our family-centred approach to reminiscence for families, it was deemed that it was not appropriate for this study as the study needed to have a clearly defined research topic and design to achieve ethical approval before approaching potential participants.

Collaborative Action Research (CAR) was explored and ultimately selected as an appropriate approach for this study. Townsend (2014) asserts that collaborative action research builds on the general theme of collaboration and refers to specific applications of action research which places more of an emphasis on what in other approaches would be less specific and more

general collaborative aspects. This aligns with the definition proposed by Greenwood and Levin (2007) that collaborative action research incorporates collaboration, action, and research to co-produce knowledge in the shared pursuit of social change. Furthermore, a key feature of collaborative action research is that it is based on the idea of bringing together a group with different roles and responsibilities to come together and work towards a shared goal and purpose. By establishing a collaborative relationship between people with different roles and experiences, collaborative action research places an emphasis on the different roles that they inhabit with the intention that everyone can bring their own unique knowledge and experience to the table in a shared process through which the group can learn and act together. For Townsend (2014), this focus on bringing together differing viewpoints, requires collaborative action researchers to place an emphasis on how the attitudes and beliefs of each individual construct their perspectives. Consequently, knowledge is therefore viewed as socially constructed by participants through their individual interpretive framework built from their pre-existing knowledge, beliefs, and previous experiences and as such aligns with the social constructionist theoretical perspective that underpins this study. The challenge for collaborative action research is to overcome this by co-creating knowledge and understanding through shared activities that acknowledges and benefits from the varying perspectives of collaborators. This challenge was offset using both individual interviews and group sessions to ensure that every participant had an opportunity to share their perspective.

3.5 Typologies of Action Research

Numerous typologies of action research have been proposed by methodologists to offer clarity and guidance to those considering undertaking an action research study. For this study, action research typologies were used to frame my study aims and approach to action research

to determine if this was an appropriate approach for this study. Grundy (1982) contends that typologies are not different research methods but instead refer to the differences in the underpinning assumptions and worldview held by the researcher and how this can lead to variations to the design and the power dynamic between the researcher and participants. The action research typology proposed by Holter and Schwartz-Barcott (1993) was utilised for this study as it offers an accessible foundation to determine an appropriate approach to action research.

3.5.1 Holter and Schwartz-Barcott's Action Research Typology

In their typology, Holter and Schwartz-Barcott propose three broad approaches to action research: technical collaborative, mutual collaborative, and enhancement.

In the technical collaborative approach, the overarching aim for the researcher is to test a specific intervention based on a pre-specified theoretical framework with the question of if the intervention is applicable within a practical setting. In this approach, the collaborative aspect of action research between researcher and participant is more facilitatory as participants are only required to introduce and explore the intervention in question during their own practice. As a result, the researcher alone has the responsibility to identify the problem and create the intervention before participants become involved and agree to implement the intervention. Typically, this approach results in an effective and sudden change in practice however, enthusiasm can often wane as previous practices begin to remerge thus limiting the long-term effectiveness of the intervention (Holter and Schwartz-Barcott, 1993). The knowledge generated from a technical collaborative approach is typically predictive centred on validating and refining a pre-existing theory and intervention.

Within the mutual collaboration approach to action research, the researcher and participants collaborate to identify potential problems and to ascertain their root causes and potential interventions that could be introduced to address this. The problem is identified after a series of discussions with the researcher and participants resulting in a shared understanding of the problem in question and underlying causes. Participants involved in the study gain a new understanding of their practice and as such the implementation of the intervention has the potential to have a more long-term impact once the initial enthusiasm has worn off. However, due to the direct involvement in the implementation, the success of the intervention is closely linked to participants, and any changes tend to be short-lived when these individuals leave the system. This was partly addressed by this study through the co-creation of a resource that assists those out with the study to implement the intervention based on the findings of this study. The type of knowledge produced by this study is typically descriptive in nature and focusses on the development of new theories and interventions (Holter and Schwartz-Barcott, 1993).

In the enhancement approach to action research, there are two key aims for the researcher. The first aim is to increase the closeness between the current issues facing practitioners within a specific setting and the theories adopted to explain and address those issues. The second aim, which goes further than the other two approaches, is to aid and empower practitioners to identify the underlying problems within their practice by raising the shared awareness and consciousness (Holter and Schwartz-Barcott, 1993). This process is emancipatory in nature as it gives the participants more choice and freedom within the scope of the study whilst also empowering them to continue to critique and improve their practice once the study has reached its conclusion.

After taking the three proposed typologies into consideration, it was determined that the mutual collaboration approach was most appropriate for this study. The technical collaborative approach was rejected as although there is some degree of collaboration, the participants are not involved in creation of the intervention and as such the implementation may not be successful or sustainable in practice (Holter and Schwartz-Barcott, 1993). Furthermore, for this study, the technical collaborative approach does not take into consideration that due to the uniqueness or subjective nature of the care home visit it cannot be addressed by a uniform intervention and instead requires a personalised approach. Likewise, the enhancement approach was not deemed to be appropriate as it was out with the scope of this study which adhered to a strict timeframe. Moreover, the theoretical aspects of this approach were deemed to be too onerous to place on families. However, the mutual collaborative approach was selected as it promotes equality between the researcher and participants, which ensures that the intervention is more likely to be retained for longer as participants will feel a sense of ownership over it as a result of being involved in the development process.

3.6 The Continuum of Researcher Positionality within Action Research

For McNiff (2013; 2017), the pursuit of a successful, collaborative partnership within an action research study requires researchers to have an awareness of their own ideas and beliefs but also have an aptitude to incorporate the ideas of others. Whilst this may seem idealistic or over simplified, it is widely accepted that the traditional boundaries between researcher and participant are blurred in an action research study. Unlike other methodological approaches that include clearly defined researcher and participant roles with set boundaries, action research is founded on collaboration and practical, shared problem solving. Meyer (2000)

argues that the democratic nature of action research that strives for equality between researcher and participant is a fundamental strength and distinctive factor of action research. However, action research forces the researcher to examine their own role in the context of the study and is typically viewed through the lens of 'insider' or 'outsider' roles, each with their own challenges and advantages (Herr and Anderson, 2005). Within this study I, as the researcher, adopt multiple roles. For most of the study, I am an outsider researcher collecting data. However, it would also be remiss of me to dismiss my own experience as a carer of someone with dementia and as such, could be viewed as an insider at times, which assists with creating a more collaborative relationship with participants through our shared experiences. Therefore, I needed to be conscious that I did not become over involved and conflate my experience with those of the participants.

As part of their examination of the role of the researcher within action research, Kerstetter (2012) explored the 'insider' and 'outsider' position that researchers can adopt. An 'insider' researcher becomes closely engaged with participants over the duration of the research process and almost becomes part of the team. Dwyer and Buckle (2009) contend that this close connection to participants allows researchers to engage participants more easily and to draw upon their shared experiences to gather a richer data set. However, this runs the risk that researchers will face difficulties in separating their personal experiences from those of participants and end up conflating the two. Furthermore, the researcher needs to be prepared to address questions surrounding potential bias in their research that may arise due to their closeness to participants and the research area (Serrant-Green, 2002). This is something that I had to be mindful of throughout this study due to my own experience as a carer. Conversely, an 'outsider' researcher adopts a more objective approach to the research

area and participants ensuring that there is sufficient emotional distance between them and participants (Chawla-Duggan, 2007). As such, there are clearly defined boundaries in place between the researcher and participant. However, this distanced and objective approach can cause difficulties in gaining access to potential participants due to a lack of relationship with gatekeepers (Gasman and Payton-Stewart, 2006). Additionally, this distanced approach could mean that participants will not 'buy into' the intervention if they have not built a relationship with the researcher.

Herr and Anderson (2005) have explored the role of 'insider'/'outsider' researchers in more detail with their continuum of positionality, which is comprised of six categories: Insider (researcher studies own practice), insider in collaboration with other insiders, insider(s) in collaboration with outsider(s), reciprocal collaboration (insider-outsider teams), outsider(s) in collaboration with insider(s), and outsider studies insider. This study was situated within the fifth category of this continuum: outsider(s) in collaboration with insider(s). Herr and Anderson (2005) contend that this is the most common form of collaborative research as it is often more common for outsiders to initiate research projects than insiders, except for instances when insiders invite outsiders for a collaborative evaluation. This approach is not without potential pitfalls as there is the justifiable concern that collaborations between university researchers and communities can be co-opted by the researcher as they typically have a greater incentive in publishing the study (Cochran-Smith and Lytle, 1993). Additionally, within this approach, researchers must examine how they approach participants. For McLaughlin (1996), if researchers enter a collaborative study with the mindset that they know more than the participants, they frame themselves as '*outsider experts*' instead of

collaborative researchers. This in turn, reinforces a tendency by insiders to mirror this belief and undervalue their own knowledge of the topic.

3.7 Promoting rigour within this action research study

Rigour is defined by the Merriam-Webster dictionary as the “*quality or state of being exact, careful, or with strict precision, or the quality of being thorough and accurate*” (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). For Cypress (2017), the term qualitative rigour presents an oxymoron as qualitative research is a journey of explanation and discovery that is often founded on subjective experiences and as such does not lend to stiff boundaries. However, rigour can be a useful tool in maintaining consistency in the methods used in data collection, research processes and analytical approaches to present an accurate representation of the population in question (Crescentini and Mainardi, 2009).

The seminal work by Lincoln and Guba (1985) has been a guiding influence on how to maintain rigour in a qualitative study. Lincoln and Guba (1985) argued that the underlying question of rigour in a qualitative study is how can the researcher persuade the target audience that their findings are worth taking notice of? In answer to this, Lincoln and Guba (1985) devised a ‘trustworthiness criteria’ that could be used to evaluate the integrity and rigour of a qualitative study. Their criteria comprised of four key components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

For Lincoln and Guba (1985), the credibility of a study allows the audience to recognise and relate to the findings. Stahl and King (2020) state that credibility poses the question of the congruence of the findings with reality however, this is subjective and relies on individual judgements. This entails seeking to understand how the ideas and findings presented in a

study relate to each other. Unlike quantitative research, there is no expectation that all reactions relating to credibility would result in the same conclusion as credibility is a construction built on the experiences of both the reporter and subsequent readers. Furthermore, a qualitative study could be considered credible if it presents an accurate portrayal or interpretation of human experience that is recognisable by people and makes sense to those who have a similar experience, for example other family visitors to care homes. To maintain credibility in this study, analytical approaches that presented original wording were used and direct quotations were utilised when appropriate to represent the data and to minimise the risk of misrepresentation. Additionally, a range of perspectives and experiences were captured and presented to ensure that one opinion was not held in higher regard than others.

Transferability is the ability to transfer research findings or methods from one group to another, or how the findings could be applied within different contexts, or with other participants (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). As Stahl and King (2020) note, this can be rather difficult as by design qualitative research does not and cannot aim for replicability. Despite this, qualitative researchers maintain that the results and patterns from one study or context may be applicable to other contexts. Furthermore, it could be argued that if you cannot learn from applying a study to a different set of circumstances, the impact of the original study is limited (Stahl and King, 2020). A frequent criticism of action research is that there is an inherent lack of generalisability due to the context specific and iterative nature of the design meaning that what works in one context may not be applicable to another (Reason and Bradbury, 2008). To address this issue, whilst study participants were brought together during group sessions, we worked collaboratively to tailor the intervention to meet the needs and

specific context of their individual visits. This aligns with the social constructionist approach as it shows how the intervention can be adapted to meet what each participant considers to be a 'good visit' thus strengthening confidence in the transferability of the study findings.

Dependability refers to the auditability of a study or how well another researcher can follow the decision trail made by the initial researcher. The decision trail is achieved by accurately conveying: the specific purpose and aim of the study, the reasoning behind the participant recruitment strategy, methods used for data collection and the timeframe for this, the approach used for data analysis, how the findings were interpreted and presented, and the techniques used to determine the credibility of the data (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). For Stahl and King (2020) a key component of dependability is the clear communication and understanding of the role that a researcher's values and passions played in their decisions, or what they call reflexive auditing. They contend that reflexive auditing is characteristic of post positivist research and for them, it is a basic requirement for an acceptable research manuscript. For an action research study, Heikkinen, Huttunen, and Syrjälä (2007) argue that the principle of historical continuity is a key component in strengthening validity and rigour. Historical continuity is focussed on how a study is reported regarding the chronological and logical sequence of events that establishes causalities in addition to the objectives of the actors involved. By adhering to this process, any action research study will have a clear beginning, middle and end which demonstrates how each cycle is built on the previous one and how it flows into the next (Heikkinen, Huttunen, and Syrjälä, 2007). As such, I have taken a narrative approach to reporting this study following the chronological order of events where the data collection, analysis and findings of each cycle are reported before moving on to report the next cycle. This clarifies the action research methodology and highlights how the

objectives for each cycle influenced and linked to the next in addition to how the collaborative actions emerged across the cycles.

Confirmability is the final component of Lincoln and Guba's (1985) trustworthiness criteria set. Confirmability refers to the extent to which the results could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers external to the original study. Confirmability can only be achieved when credibility, transferability and dependability have already been established (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). According to McKay and Marshall (2000), confirmability is the partner of dependability however, where dependability is built on transparent reporting of processes, confirmability is determined by data being traceable to the source and that subsequent judgements and assertions are logical and coherent and strives to illustrate how the findings of the study emerged from the data and not from within the beliefs of the researcher. To achieve this, I acknowledged and addressed the potential risk of bias from being a family carer of someone with dementia by building the intervention collaboratively with participants informed by their needs and wants regarding visiting their loved one in the care home.

3.8 Theoretical Framework

Throughout the design and conduct of this study, particular attention was given to the theoretical foundations that align with the aim of the study. Two key frameworks, namely, relationship-centred care (Sheard, 2004; Woods, Keady, and Seddon, 2008) and the Six Senses Framework (Nolan *et al.*, 2006), were embedded across all stages of the research process. These frameworks provided a conceptual lens through which I remained mindful of the emotional, relational, and ethical dimensions of care, guiding both the engagement with participants and the interpretation of emerging insights

3.8.1 Relationship-Centred Care

Relationship-centred care has been a key component of this study as it seeks to preserve familial relationships through the entire dementia journey, including within care homes and at the advanced levels of dementia.

Whilst person-centredness (Kitwood, 1997) is rightly considered to be an important aspect of care, it could be argued that a relationship-centred approach to care could provide a more appropriate way of understanding important aspects of successful services and how to facilitate family involvement. Traditionally, care services considered the needs of people living with dementia and their families as separate entities however, Sheard (2004) called for the development of a new approach that saw the person living with dementia within the context of important and significant relationships which builds the case for adopting a relationship-centred approach. Woods, Keady, and Seddon (2008) contend that the concept of person-centred care devised by Kitwood, is rooted in the interactions and relationships between caregivers and people with dementia, and as such could be consistent with more of a focus on relationships. Therefore, a relationship-centred approach is not a rejection of person-centred care but instead builds on it. Relationship-centred care views the interpersonal relationships between the person with dementia, care home staff, and families as integral components of good dementia care (Woods, Keady, and Seddon, 2008). Similarly, Soklaridis *et al.* (2016) examined the role of relationship-centred care within healthcare more broadly and concluded that relationship-centred care provides a means to move away from the patient-centred model of healthcare by focusing on the key role of all relationships in the delivery and outcomes of care. Although relationship-centred dementia care considers the interpersonal relationships between the person with dementia, staff, and families, this study

primarily focuses on the relationship between the person with dementia and their family members as the sustained involvement of families within care homes is fundamental for those living with dementia.

Whilst advocating for a relationship-centred approach to dementia care, Woods, Keady, and Seddon (2008) note that some families can be profoundly affected by the progression of dementia as they understandably struggle with their loved one changing due to the disease, especially when recognition and communication become impaired. Therefore, continued involvement without increased support or guidance can be a distressing or upsetting experience for some. This was instrumental for this study as relationship-centred care is not only key to facilitating family involvement within the care home environment but also a fundamental aspect of a family-centred approach to reminiscence. A relationship-centred approach was a guiding principle for this study as it was used to frame the family-centred structured reminiscence intervention to work with participants to preserve their familial relationship with their loved one with dementia living in the care home and to overcome potential communication barriers resulting from advanced stages of dementia.

3.8.2 The Six Senses Framework

This study was also underpinned by the Six Senses Framework developed by Nolan *et al.* (2006) which was founded on a relationship-centred approach to care. Ryan *et al.* (2008) view the Six Senses Framework as prerequisites for good relationships within the context of care provision. The underlying premise for the Six Senses Framework is that good quality, relationship-centred care can only be achieved and delivered when the six 'senses' are experienced by all the groups involved i.e. the resident, care home staff, and families (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Woods, Keady, and Seddon, 2008). Watson (2016) further placed the Six Senses

Framework within the context of relationship-centred care. As dementia progresses, it can become difficult to maintain relationships and those with advancing dementia can often be isolated and experience 'social death' (Watson, 2016). Social death occurs when an individual is no longer seen as a social actor or actively involved in the lives of other people (Brannelly, 2011; Froggatt, 2001). Assumptions surrounding the impact of dementia on personhood can directly affect the way that people living with dementia are perceived by others and the quality of their relationships, care, and their life (Lyman, 1993). A common misconception is that advanced dementia removes an individual's personhood by the "*very splintering of the sedimented layers of being until ultimately there is nothing left*" (Davis, 2004, p.375). Adopting this view will mean social death is more likely to happen for people with advanced dementia. However, the Senses Framework seeks to overcome this by placing dementia care within the context of continued relationships with the aim of preserving the personhood of those living with dementia.

The Six Senses Framework, with a focus on relating this to dementia and the experiences of family visitors, was used to underpin this study as it emerged from the concept of relationship-centred care based on the importance of interactions among people as the foundation of any therapeutic activity. The Six Senses Framework is comprised of six 'senses': security, continuity, belonging, purpose, fulfilment, and significance (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). Although Nolan *et al.* (2006) contend that achieving all six senses is a prerequisite for relationship-centred care, for this study, I focussed on the two 'senses' of Belonging and Continuity with an emphasis on how they relate to the relationship between family visitors and their loved one with dementia and maintaining familial relationships. The senses of Belonging and Continuity were selected as they aligned with the goal of this study which was to explore the use of family-centred reminiscence as a means of sustaining family

relationships within care homes. Therefore, achieving a sense of belonging was integral to this approach. Similarly, achieving a sense of continuity was crucial as the study sought to preserve pre-existing relationships by using reminiscence to explore hobbies or interests as a way of remaining connected.

3.8.2.1 Sense of Belonging

The sense of belonging was a key component behind this study as it was integral that the person living with dementia in the care home still felt included within the family unit. Nolan *et al.* (2006) explained how the sense of belonging can differ for older people compared to carers. For older people it represents opportunities to “*maintain and/or form meaningful and reciprocal relationships, to feel part of a community or group as desired*” (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). This was important to bear in mind during this study as I felt it was critical that the person with dementia felt included and loved by their family even when they may no longer be able to express themselves verbally or even when they are unable to recognise their loved ones. For family carers, this focussed on being able to maintain or improve valued relationships and to be able to confide in trusted individuals to feel that they are not ‘in this alone’ (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). Once more, the idea of maintaining relationships was critical for this study as previous literature has showed that families can often struggle with care home visits and feeling like they are losing their loved one. However, it is important to keep in mind that a care home admission is not the end of their life story but merely the next chapter and as such the continuation of family relationships should be at the foreground. As such this idea runs through this study, and I worked with families to reframe their visits to focus on maintaining the familial bonds that connect them to their loved one for as long as possible instead of dwelling on what was lost.

3.8.2.2 Sense of Continuity

The sense of continuity as outlined by Nolan *et al.* (2006) was a critical component of the theoretical underpinnings of this study. For family carers this was built around maintaining shared pleasures or pursuits with their loved one (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). This was arguably one of the main driving forces behind this study as it aimed to work alongside family visitors to empower them to use the co-created intervention built on the principles of formal reminiscence during visits with the loved one. This was heavily focused on the families' taking ownership of the intervention and using it to connect with their loved one during visits through shared activities that they used to enjoy together. This could include things like reminiscing about the past using photobooks or meaningful objects, or a hobby that they used to enjoy such as gardening, focusing on what their loved one with dementia is still able to do as the disease progresses. These seemingly simple tasks can make all the difference in working towards maintaining relationships through shared pleasures or hobbies.

Whilst Nolan *et al.* (2006) previously explored the idea of continuing shared hobbies or activities, Walters, Oyebode and Riley (2010) examined the concept of continuity through the lens of continued relationships for spousal caregivers of people living with dementia. Although they studied this within the context of living in the community, the importance of continued relationships is transferable and highly relevant for those visiting a loved one in a care home. Walters, Oyebode and Riley (2010) interviewed spousal caregivers of someone with dementia and their results indicated that a sense of continuity increased the likelihood for caregivers to empathise with the experience of their loved one. For some spouses, following a diagnosis of dementia, they no longer perceived their loved one as being the same person and as such they felt that they were already in the grieving process for the person they

felt they had lost. Consequently, they tended to use depersonalised, objectifying, or negative language which could be viewed to create an 'emotional buffer' by distancing or disconnecting themselves from distress caused by their changing role (Walters, Oyeboode and Riley, 2010).

Conversely, carers who still viewed their spouse as the 'same person' also experienced distress from their changing role. However, rather than distancing themselves from the past, they instead sought to gain solace from focussing on continuity with the past and dispel notions of change by concentrating on the enduring identity of their spouse. For Walters, Oyeboode and Riley (2010), a person-centred and empathic view of dementia care was more readily displayed by those who perceived a sense of continuity in their spouses and relationships whereas, those who felt a sense of discontinuity were more likely to feel more negative emotions in response to behaviours. Furthermore, they appeared more likely to experience feelings of guilt in contrast to those that experienced a sense of continuity, who were less likely to experience feelings of guilt due to their person-centred and empathic approach which was more likely to facilitate practical solutions (Walters, Oyeboode and Riley, 2010). This further reinforces the importance of supporting families to have continued relationships for as long as they can as it can help to alleviate some feelings of guilt as well as allow them to see their loved one and not just the diagnosis. However, Walters, Oyeboode and Riley (2010) noted that for some spouses, continuity was rooted in their commitment to the institution of marriage regardless of their spouse's ability to participate in the marriage which goes some way to explain the sense of comfort gained through continuity and the importance of maintaining relationships.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Research ethics refers to a set of moral or legal principles that aim to safeguard or assure the rights of participants (Locke, Alcorn, and O’Neill, 2013). Cochran-Smith and Lytle (2007, p24) ascertain that “*Everything’s ethics*” and as such our ethical frames underpin multiple decisions throughout the research process. Fundamentally, research ethics concern recognising what is acceptable or unacceptable research practice as well as acknowledging what is right or wrong. For this study, I have opted to separate the discussions surrounding ethics into two sections. The first section discussed in this chapter refers to the ethical considerations regarding the research methodology and how this is reflected in practice. The procedural aspect of ethics that focuses on the approach taken to obtain ethical approval is discussed in the next chapter.

3.9.1 Ethical considerations of action research

Undertaking an action research approach can be challenging when discussing ethical concerns as the emergent aspect of the methodology can make it difficult to identify all potential ethical issues from the start as the initial plan may evolve over the duration of the study (Walker and Haslett, 2002). Locke, Alcorn, and O’Neill (2013) identified eight ethical principles that action researchers should adhere to that are congruent with the ethically accepted means implicit in the methodology. These principles are:

- Principle of inclusivity
- Principle of maximum participation
- Principle of negotiation and consensus
- Principle of communicative freedom
- Principle of plain speaking

- Principle of right action
- Principle of self-reflexivity
- The affective principle (Locke, Alcorn, and O'Neill, 2013, p113-114).

To meet the principle of inclusivity, the onus is on the action research group to consider all those who have an interest in the focus of the research as stakeholders and as such try to include them when appropriate. This is consonant with the principle of maximum participation. For Locke, Alcorn, and O'Neill (2013), anyone who actively involved in the study through their practice or sharing their knowledge, are entitled to be recognised as full members of the action research group, even though their role within the study may change over time. This aligns with the democratic nature of collaborative action research and departs from power dynamics between the researcher and the researched typically found in traditional research. The principle of negotiation and consensus means that when feasible, discussions surrounding research aims and design, ownership of data, and the dissemination process should include consultation with stakeholders. Additionally, the research process should also include negotiation and consensus building among participants when appropriate. This increases the sense of ownership that participants have over the study since they have an active role within the study and aligns with the democratic nature of action research. However, due to the nature of a doctoral study, decisions regarding the study aims and design for this study had to be made prior to applying for ethical approval and before participants could be approached.

The principle of communicative freedom refers to the right held by action research participants to withdraw from the study or renegotiate the grounds for their participation at any point throughout the study. This is imperative for a study that includes family visitors as

participants may need to withdraw for several different reasons such as bereavement, illness or they may no longer want to be involved. Furthermore, it could be viewed as unethical to ask family visitors to participate in a study that would take several months without clearly acknowledging that they have the right to withdraw at any time without an explanation and as such I designed the three cycles of the study to allow for participants to leave and for new participants join at the start of each cycle. Another key principle for Locke, Alcorn, and O'Neill (2013) is the principle of plain speaking which means that the participants and those in the wider interest group have the right to be communicated with in language that maximises their understanding without the use of unnecessary jargon or overly academic language. This especially applies to the language adopted in documents such as participant information sheets and consent forms as it is imperative that potential participants fully understand what the study would entail and what would be required of them prior to data collection. In line with this, documents such as participant information sheets were available in other formats if required and were informed by the relevant guidelines, for example, the Royal National Institute of Blind People guidelines on accessible documents to ensure that those that may have sight issues could still make a fully informed decision before consenting to participate. Moreover, this also applied to the third cycle of this study which aimed to create a resource based on the findings of this study that could be used to by others to facilitate or support family led reminiscence. As such, it was important that this was accessible to those outside of academia for it to be more user friendly.

The sixth principle for Locke, Alcorn, and O'Neill (2013) is the principle of right action. This means that the research group participants and researchers must collaboratively decide if the research aims, and consequent understandings are morally right in the context of the setting.

For this study, this meant that the co-created intervention was designed to minimise the risk of causing distress to participants and their loved one, for example by working together on an appropriate approach for when the person living with dementia did not engage with the reminiscence. In line with this, the principle of self-reflexivity refers to the idea that all members of the research group must be transparent regarding the discursive assumptions that they bring to the study. This is important to bear in mind as pre-conceived assumptions or opinions could influence their approach to the intervention and the wider study. Furthermore, any assumptions held could influence what members view as morally right within care home visits in context of the study setting. For example, what they view as a 'good visit' could determine what they think is an appropriate approach to facilitate reminiscence during visits with their loved one. Finally, the affective principle refers to the right of participants to have their feelings and opinions respected in addition to the recognition that feelings can be regarded as appropriate research information. This was particularly pertinent to this study as since it was based on the participant's visit experience and their desired personalised outcomes, it is important that they felt that their views were respected and considered.

As Locke, Alcorn, and O'Neill (2013) note, these eight principles represent the best ethical practice for a collaborative group that seeks to work together to address a particular issue that also strives to be transparent, built on equality of esteem and equity of involvement, and works towards generating shared meanings and understandings. However, these represent ideal situations and cannot guarantee against dilemmas or issues in practice. Furthermore, McNiff (2013) and McNiff and Whitehead (2011) identified four key points that should be

considered as best ethical practice for action research. These are: confidentiality, anonymity, accessing and withdrawing from the study, and securing permissions from all involved parties.

3.9.2 Confidentiality

Any data collected throughout the research process must be kept in the strictest of confidence. To meet data protection legislation and to address the issue of confidentiality, all paper-based raw collected data and non-anonymised transcripts were stored in a secured locker within the centre at the university. Additionally, no information was shared outside of my supervision team and all personal data was kept secure. All digital data including interview recordings were stored in a password protected file on my university OneDrive account and all data files were encrypted. This aligns with all relevant data protection legislation and the ethical approval permissions granted by the ethics committee.

3.9.3 Anonymity

Within research, anonymity refers to concealing the identities of participants along with any identifying characteristics to ensure that their participation in the study is not discovered. This is particularly important when involving families with loved ones in care homes as it is crucial that the care of their loved one is not jeopardised by their involvement in the study. Therefore, within this study the names of participants and care homes were not disclosed and removed during the transcription of interviews and group sessions. However, McNiff (2017) states that the idea of anonymity may not always be applicable within an action research study as some participants may rightly wish to be recognised for their involvement in the research process and have their contributions acknowledged.

3.9.4 Negotiating permissions and access to the study sites

The process of gaining access to the study site was somewhat of an arduous one. The first port of call was to make an initial phone call to prospective study sites to introduce myself and provide a brief overview of my study ideas to gauge their interest. If homes were interested then a letter was emailed to the care home manager, that outlined the study in more detail and indicated how the study might impact the day-to-day activities within the home. The main purpose of this was to ensure that the homes were comfortable with being involved in a research study and were open to providing a quiet area for data collection however, this was open to negotiation. This was a valuable process as it has allowed me to begin to form relationships with the necessary gatekeepers which was instrumental in gaining access to prospective participants. Furthermore, it offered the opportunity to discuss my ideas with managers and gain their insight into the practicalities involved. The next stage involved phoning the care homes back to ensure that they were still interested before emailing or posting a letter formally asking for managerial permission for them to become a study site for this study which allowed accessing the care homes for data collection.

3.9.5 Accessing and gaining consent from visiting families

A careful approach was used during when recruiting participants through the care homes as I was mindful that this was their loved one's home. This also raised the ethical issue of ensuring that family visitors did not feel coerced or pressured into participating due the care home manager granting access and they did not want to risk jeopardising the care of their loved one. This was addressed by making it clear on the recruitment flyers and participant information sheet that participation was completely voluntary with no obligation to join up.

Furthermore, mechanisms were in place to avoid coercion for example, prospective participants were approached in the first instance by the gatekeeper to avoid feeling pressurised to join if approach by the researcher. It was also made clear that participants were free to withdraw from the study at any time and that this would not impact their loved one's care which was vital in order to build trust and maintain with participants and demonstrate good faith (McNiff, 2017).

3.10 Chapter summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive assessment of the methodological choice of action research. Reasons for this approach were given and was justified by examining alternative approaches that were considered. This chapter also explored the role of the researcher in action research and how this can change over the course of the study. The theoretical underpinnings of relationship-centred care and the Six Senses Framework which have been embedded throughout this study were examined. Ethical issues raised in action research were also explored by examining the issues faced and how they were overcome in this study.

Chapter Four – Recruitment, Ethical Challenges, and Planned Methods

This chapter explores the recruitment and ethical challenges that were faced within this doctoral study. The chapter begins by providing an overview of the study design that was adopted to address the overall aim of the study, before outlining the study site, and participant recruitment requirements. A detailed narrative is then provided on the recruitment process within prospective study sites that offers an insight into the challenges faced during the recruitment process. The participant recruitment process is also explored and outlines how relationship building was integrated into this. An overview of the process involved in gaining ethical approval for the study and any additional ethical challenges that arose during recruitment is provided. Lastly, this chapter will outline the planned methods and analytical approach for this action research study.

4.1 Overview of Study Design

As discussed in Chapter Three, collaborative action research (CAR) is a participatory and democratic research methodology that is underpinned by the fundamental principles of collaboration, participation, and shared decision making (Townsend, 2014). A unique and distinctive feature of any action research is that it follows a cyclical process that involves planning, action, observation, and reflection.

As collaborative action research focuses on bringing together different viewpoints, and understanding how individuals construct their perspectives, appropriate methods were selected that aligned with this approach and allowed for the exploration of participants'

experiences of visiting their relatives in the care home. It was anticipated that we would require three action cycles to complete this. Whilst these cycles are presented as three distinct activities, there was some element of overlap as one cycle concluded, and the next cycle began, repeating as needed to refine understanding and improve practice. An overview of the three action research cycles, and research activities, is provided in Diagram 8 below.

Diagram 8: Overview of Action Research Cycles

Table 2 below also summarises the data collection activities, levels of participant involvement, and approach to data analysis across the three cycles.

Table 1 – Summary of data collection activities and data analysis

Cycle of Study	Data Collection Methods	No. of participants involved	Data Analysis
Cycle 1	Individual semi-Structured Interviews	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Focus group session	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
Cycle 2	3 rounds of Semi-structured telephone interviews	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Focus group and Time machine activity	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Focus group and emotional touchpoints	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Focus group and emotional touchpoints	5	Reflexive thematic analysis
Cycle 3	Focus group	4	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Semi-structured telephone interviews	5	Reflexive thematic analysis
	Focus group with family visitors and staff members	7	Reflexive thematic analysis

4.1.1 Cycle 1: Understanding Family Visits

Cycle One was a preparatory cycle that had two overarching aims. The first aim was to create a shared understanding with family visitors that captured their current experience of visiting their loved one in a care home. The second aim was to gain an understanding of the ways that family visitors might already use informal reminiscence during their visits. Although these are seen as two independent aims, they were captured during the one process. This involved conducting individual semi-structured qualitative interviews that focussed on understanding

how participants currently view their visits. This included understanding how they prepared for visits, if they did any visit activities and how they feel after a visit. As the interview progressed, the concept of 'reminiscence' was introduced whereby we explored if the participants had any prior formal experience of it. I used reflexive thematic analysis following informed by Braun and Clarke (2022) to determine the main themes from the interviews. The themes were collated and formed the basis of a focus group which sought to explore these themes in more detail and to form a group identity, a crucial component of action research. During the session, the group were shown an introductory video on reminiscence which opened the conversation on ways that they used it informally during their visits and how they think they could use a more structured approach to reminiscence during future visits. After reflecting with family visitors on how they already used reminiscence informally, they were provided with instructions for a short reminiscence task that they could do with their relative which then moved the study into the second research cycle.

4.1.2 Cycle 2: Exploring Reminiscence during Visits

Cycle Two's focus was to explore with family visitors the benefits and practical application of using aspects of family-centred reminiscence during visits. This involved a series of three collaborative workshops interspersed with reminiscence-in-action with follow-up phone interviews. After each group, participants were invited to try reminiscence activities with their loved ones during their visits after which I followed-up with a short telephone interview to discuss what they did and how they found it. Each group session involved different activities to orientate our conversations on reminiscence. During the first group session we completed a 'Time Machine' activity to demonstrate the types of memories that could be effective to explore through our approach to reminiscence. Prior to this session, I met with an Alzheimer

Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant to discuss my approach and how to reduce the risk of distressing participants. Furthermore, I followed the “Time-machine Guidance Sheet” published by NHS Education for Scotland (n.d.). An adapted Emotional Touchpoints guided by MacBride, Miller, and Dewar(2017) was used over the second and third groups to explore how families felt at key points during the visit experience and to assess if the use of reminiscence had any impact by asking participants to summarise how they felt before, during, and after a visit by selecting an emotion card. During the second group, participants were asked to do this based on how they felt before they had tried reminiscence. This was then repeated during the third group based on after they started using reminiscence to assess it had changed how they felt about visiting their relatives.

4.1.3 Cycle 3: Co-creating a Family Centred Reminiscence Resource

Cycle Three aimed to co-create with family visitors a resource to support the delivery of family-centred, individualised reminiscence informed by the study findings. This included a co-production workshop, where as a group we developed the design brief for the content and format of our resource. Following this, the design brief was used to produce a physical copy of the resource which was then shown to a focus group consisting of the study participants, and three staff members from the study site. During the focus group, staff members were invited to share their thoughts on the resource and how, and when they could distribute it to families of future residents moving into the home. This was also used to ‘sense check’ and ensure that the content was clear to someone who wasn’t involved in the study or development of the resource.

4.2 Study Site Recruitment

Whilst I was aiming to recruit up to three study sites, data collection was only carried out in one home due to the recruitment challenges outlined in this chapter. Due to the cyclical, and often longitudinal, nature of action research studies, engagement in action research requires more of a commitment from participants than other forms of research and therefore participation can seem daunting resulting in participant attrition throughout the study (Jiang, 2019). As I was conducting research within a care home setting, I was aware that families may withdraw from the study at any point due to factors such as illness or bereavement. Therefore, I aimed to recruit multiple study sites to reduce the impact of attrition on my study.

4.2.1 Care Home selection criteria

To be eligible as a participating study site, care homes had to meet the following criteria. Firstly, the homes had to have a rating of four or above from the Care Inspectorate, indicating a “good” level of care. Secondly, the homes needed to be within 15 miles from my research base. The first stage of the screening process involved compiling a shortlist of care homes providing 24-hour nursing facilities (typically called care homes with nursing or nursing homes) that were registered to provide dementia care. In terms of logistics and due to resource constraints, I prioritised potential sites that could be reached within a travel time of one hour from my university base.

As there is known variability across the care home sector in terms of care quality (Spilsbury, 2024), it was important to identify care homes considered to provide at least a good standard of care using externally verifiable criteria. A good quality of care was desirable as this meant that family carers, my target participants, were more likely to be confident in the care their relative was receiving, arguably making them more likely to be receptive to an invitation to

consider taking part in the study, than those who might be concerned about the quality of care. As a positive and trusting relationship is essential between an action researcher and study sites, it was important to know how the quality of care at the facility was rated prior to commencing access negotiations. Furthermore, ethical challenges would be likely to arise if the standard of care at a study site was known to be unsatisfactory and the challenges faced by the care team would be a deterrent to their potential for long term participation or support for the study. Accordingly, I initially screened potential care homes using the published quality ratings of the Care Inspectorate. To be invited to become a study site the care homes needed to have a Care Inspectorate rating of four or above. The full rating scale is outlined in Table 3 below.

Table 3 - Care Inspectorate Ratings

Rating	Explanation
6 Excellent	Outstanding or sector leading
5 Very good	Major strengths
4 Good	Important strengths, with some areas for improvement
3 Adequate	Strengths just outweigh weaknesses
2 Weak	Important weaknesses, priority action required
1 Unsatisfactory	Major weaknesses, urgent remedial action required

Potential study sites were excluded if they had a Care Inspectorate grade under four or if they were in the process of changing management as the potential for introducing new and

innovative interventions would likely to have been unsupported in that environment. Care homes in this position were also excluded as it would have been difficult to arrange access for data collection with changing management. Likewise, care homes operated by the local authority were also excluded as they have a range of supports not available to private care homes.

4.2.2 Planned Study Site recruitment process

Prior to contacting prospective study sites, I identified five potential study sites that met the selection criteria outlined above. Before contacting homes, I worked with one of my supervisors to develop my communication strategy to ensure that I gave managers a succinct overview of my ideas for the study and how the home could help, without overwhelming them with overly academic language and information. This aligns with best practice in the literature as gatekeepers have the right to know what the proposed research process involves, the potential benefits and operational impact of the study, which is more likely to attract a positive dialogue with gatekeepers (Singh and Wassenaar, 2016). This involved preparing short bullet points to be used when phoning managers that outlined who I was and what the Wendy Baxter Scholarship was, why I wanted to do my study in their care home, a brief description of action research with a focus on the collaborative nature, and what the timeframe would be and how the home could help (see Appendix 1).

The planned first stage of recruiting study sites involved 'cold calling' the care homes to introduce myself and to either speak to the manager or to arrange a suitable time to phone back. For homes that were interested in becoming a study site, a short letter would be sent by email, outlining the study in more detail and what the impact, if any, would be on the staff (see Appendix 2). Following this, the next step was to arrange a face-to-face meeting with the

managers in the care home to discuss my study and to answer any questions they might have had. I planned to be accompanied by one of my supervisors when visiting for support and to demonstrate to the homes that I had a strong supervision team supporting me. If the managers indicated that they were interested in becoming a study site, I sent a formal letter asking them to send a letter of managerial permission outlining that I had permission to conduct my study within the care home.

With organisational management permission in place, I planned to discuss the details of participant recruitment seeking support from the manager or a delegated member of their team. Due to ethical concerns, such as families feeling coerced by an external researcher if I approached them myself, the initial steps in recruiting families were planned to be conducted by the study sites. During this meeting, the care homes were provided with a one-page document outlining the inclusion and exclusion criteria for recruiting participants and an overview of the recruitment process. This was to ensure that they were only approaching those who met the criteria. Whilst I was aiming to recruit up to three care homes, I only had one study site recruited for the start of data collection.

4.2.3 Study Site One

I made initial contact with Study Site One in June 2022 and spoke to the manager of the home over the phone to introduce myself and to discuss the study following the process outlined above. From our conversation, the home was receptive to becoming a study site and a short letter was emailed to the manager on the same day to provide an overview of the study in more detail. I then contacted the home the following week (July 2022) to answer any additional questions they might have had and to ask if they were still interested in becoming a study site. Following this conversation, a formal letter was sent (August 2022) to the home

requesting formal managerial permission for the home to become a study site (see Appendix 3). After a few delays, I received a letter indicating managerial permission in November 2022 (see Appendix 4). I was mindful that the approaching Christmas period is always a busy time for care homes, so it was mutually agreed to resume the recruitment process in the new year. An in-person meeting was arranged for February 2023 to meet with the deputy manager of the home, alongside one of my supervisors. This meeting allowed me to discuss the study in person and outline the planned process to recruit participants once I had received ethical approval. Once I was ready to begin recruiting participants, I met with the deputy manager in June 2023 to discuss the recruitment strategy in more detail.

4.2.4 Study Site Two

Whilst I was having my initial conversations with Study Site One, I contacted two other homes about becoming study sites with varying levels of success. I phoned one home in June 2022 and following the same process, sent a letter outlining the study. However, the manager contacted me in August 2022 to say that the home would not become a study site as families were not interested in participating.

Following this I contacted another home, Study Site Two, in March 2023, by phoning the home to introduce myself and the study. Following the initial call, I emailed the manager to send more information regarding the study, and a meeting was arranged for April 2023 to meet in person along with one of my supervisors. Due to previous arrangements, the Deputy Manager of the home attended the meeting and consequently, I received a letter of managerial permission from the home in early June 2023. Participant recruitment materials were emailed to the home in August 2023, and a meeting was arranged to discuss recruitment in more detail. At this meeting, I met with the Regional Senior Nurse for the care provider, and I was

informed that the home was going through a “blip” and would be unable to continue as a study site, however I was advised that I could go through the care provider’s ethics board to recruit another home from within the company. This was approved by the care provider’s ethics board in September 2023, and the Senior Regional Nurse began contacting homes about becoming a study site. By October 2023, I was informed that she was unable to find a home that was receptive to becoming a study site as homes were still in “a state of flux from the pandemic” and that managers were too busy preparing Winter Resilience Plans. Current literature shows that the Covid-19 pandemic had a devastating impact on care homes and long-term care. Burton *et al.* (2024) examined the impact of the pandemic on Scottish care homes and found that between March 2020 and October 2021, 27.1% of care homes had one outbreak, 20.1% had two, 8.3% had three, and 6.2% had four or more. Furthermore, it is well documented that care homes were disproportionately impacted by the pandemic with 47% of all covid deaths in Scotland occurring in care homes (Creative Covid Care, 2021). These statistics clearly show why care home managers were still apprehensive during the later stages of the pandemic and the potential infection risk of an external researcher entering the home.

4.2.5 Study Site Three

After Study Site Two withdrew from the study, I approached a third home, Study Site Three, about participating in the study. Study Site Three was chosen as it met the selection criteria outlined above. The care home was first contacted in November 2023 following the same process as Study Sites One and Two however, the initial meeting in December 2023 was conducted over Microsoft Teams due to Christmas events taking place within the home. An in-person meeting was later arranged for February 2024 during which I received a letter of managerial permission for the home to formally become a study site. We also discussed the

process that was going to be used to recruit participants. During this meeting, the manager mentioned that she had six family visitors who had indicated to her that they were interested in participating in the study after she had emailed out the information sheet with the home newsletter. Additionally, she asked if she could invite families whose relative living in the home did not have a formal diagnosis of dementia as she had two families in mind who she thought could benefit from the study. Due to the difficulties surrounding getting a formal diagnosis within care homes, my participant inclusion criteria were updated to include families of residents with mild cognitive impairment or dementia-like symptoms/probable dementia without the need for a confirmed dementia diagnosis. This involved submitting an amendment to my application to the School's Ethics Committee. The process to submit this amendment and the reasoning behind it is outlined in section 4.4.2 towards the end of this chapter.

The conversations with Study Site Three continued to go well and in a slight change to the agreed recruitment process, I arranged to meet with participants through the manager instead of contacting them directly, to introduce myself and the study. The day before the meeting, I contacted the home to check that the meeting was still going ahead, and I was informed that I would only be meeting one family visitor alongside two activity coordinators. This meeting went well, with both staff members and family visitor showing interest in joining the study. As the agreed process was not completely followed by the manager, I did not have the contact details for the other families interested in the study.

When I contacted the manager to arrange another meeting with interested families, communication broke down completely despite phoning and emailing weekly. A letter was sent to the home to inform them that if I did not receive any communication from them by a

specific date, I would not be able to continue with the study within the home as it would not be feasible to conduct collaborative action research with one participant.

Whilst the process to recruit study sites can seem a bit drawn out, it was a crucial step in building rapport with the gatekeepers and staff in the study sites which is an essential component of an action research study. This process also me to ensure that any potential study sites were aware of their rights regarding participation and principles of research ethics. These principles included confidentiality, anonymity, participating voluntarily, and the right to withdraw from the study (Dahlke and Stahlke, 2019). Dahlke and Stahlke (2019) contend that as with research participants, gatekeepers and study sites need to voluntarily decide to participate in a study with an informed understanding of their rights and what participation would entail. After the completion of my recruitment process, I had one care home formally on board for my study, Study Site One.

4.3 Recruitment of Participants

A purposive sampling approach was used to recruit family visitors of residents living with dementia as participants. Stringer (2007, p43) contends that as action research typically centres on a particular issue or population group, a purposive sampling technique is required in order to consciously recruit based on a particular set of attributes, including the extent to which they are affected or have an effect on the issue of interest. Battaglia (2008) defines purposive sampling as a non-random sample with the main objective of producing a sample that can used as a logical representation of a particular population or phenomenon. Furthermore, purposive sampling aims to increase the depth of understanding on a research topic, as opposed to seeking a breadth of knowledge (Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, Campbell *et al.* (2020) argue that as a purposive sample can better align with the aims and

objectives of research, it improves the rigour and trustworthiness of the study and results. Therefore, for this study I recruited based on set criteria outlined below.

4.3.1 Participant inclusion criteria

To be included as a study participant, individuals had to be a family visitor of a resident living with dementia at one of the approved study sites. For this study, a family visitor was defined as a spouse/partner, adult child/grandchild, or a close friend of a resident with dementia. Additionally, they had to visit at least twice a month.

Participants were excluded from the study if their loved one with dementia had recently been admitted to the care home within the past three months as they both would need time to adjust to their new roles and surroundings during the transition phase. Family visitors were also excluded if their loved one with dementia was receiving end of life or palliative care as that is understandably a difficult time that is accompanied by additional issues compared to the normal visiting experience.

4.3.2 Recruitment process

The first stage of the recruitment process involved conducting preparatory work with gatekeepers to explore the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study to ensure that only families that meet the criteria were approached about participating. Following this, the assigned gatekeeper was provided with recruitment posters and leaflets to begin the initial conversations with families who they thought would be receptive to participating in the study [See Appendix 5]. If families were interested, then the staff member provided them with a participant information sheet, which outlined the aim of the study, the estimated length of participation and an indication of what each cycle would entail [See Appendix 6]. To optimise

accessibility, the participant information sheet was also available in other formats if required and informed by relevant guidelines, for example, the Royal National Institute of Blind People's guidelines on accessible documents (Available: [Creating accessible information and communication resources for health and social care | RNIB](#)). If families were interested in participating in the study after this initial conversation with the staff member, their contact details were provided to me by the gatekeeper for me to introduce myself, arrange a meeting to discuss the study, and to answer any initial questions they may have had.

During this in-person discussion, participants were provided with an additional copy of the information sheet, if required, for them to refer to and we discussed it in more detail to avoid any confusion over any sections or to answer any additional questions. At this point, participants were provided with the informed consent form, which was also explained. A common concern from participants surrounded the section which asked if they consent to their "*likeness being digitally recorded*". Once I explained that it meant that I would use a voice recorder during the interviews and possibly video record the group sessions to record what was discussed to aid with my transcripts but that the recordings would not be published or shared anywhere, the participants were reassured and were happy to sign the form. This conversation was done to ensure that prospective participants were fully informed about the study and what participating could mean for them prior to being invited to sign the consent form. In addition to this, participants were given a "*cooling off*" period of at least a week to ensure that they did not feel pressurised to sign the consent form and had adequate time to think about if they wanted to participate in the study, which aligns with recognised best practice (Olivier and Olivier, 2001; Bosk, 2002; Golec *et al.*, 2004; Wilfond and Porter, 2019; Ajemba and Arene, 2022). Once the week had elapsed, participants were contacted to arrange a time and date for their first interview and participants returned their signed consent form

when I conducted their interview. Whilst this process may seem protracted, it was an important in building a relationship and rapport with the participants prior to the interviews, which helped to enhance the conversational flow and to put the participants at ease. During the first group session, the group were asked how they wanted to be communicated with for future data collection activities for example, if they were happy with me initiating contact or if they would prefer if I went through a staff member from the study site. All participants stated that they were happy for me to contact them via a phone call or text message.

4.4 Ethical Approval Process

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee in February 2023. This followed applying for ethical approval through the University's online Ethical Review Manager. This was an online system which was used to submit and process applications for ethical approval. The submitted application was sent to the Chair of the Ethics Review Committee for the School of Health and Life Sciences, alongside School Reviewers.

To apply for ethical approval, I had to ensure that I had recruitment leaflets, participant information sheets, consent forms, and a draft interview guide (see Appendixes 5,6,7, and 8). This was highly beneficial as it meant that I had to consider the practical aspects of my study and how I was planning on conducting my interviews and group sessions within the care homes.

My ethics application was underpinned by four key guiding principles: autonomy, justice, beneficence, and nonmaleficence (Artal and Rubenfeld, 2017). The principle of autonomy drove the process of informed consent as participants were asked to sign a consent form prior to data collection. The principles of justice and beneficence were key drivers behind the decision to do an action research study as it sought to empower family visitors of people with

dementia in care homes to draw upon reminiscence to create a meaningful visit experience for both them and their loved ones. The principle of nonmaleficence underpinned any decisions made regarding the participants of this study. It was imperative that participants were not placed under any undue distress as a consequence of participating.

Furthermore, I had to demonstrate how my study met my responsibilities under GDPR legislation. Under GDPR, there are six principles that must be adhered to regarding processing personal data. These are:

- 1) Be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently
- 2) Be kept to the original purpose
- 3) Be minimised (i.e. only collect necessary personal data)
- 4) Have the accuracy upheld
- 5) Be removed if they are not necessary
- 6) Be kept confidential and their integrity maintained (UK Data Service, n.d.)

Moreover, there were several ethical issues surrounding my study site that had to be taken into consideration. The names of the care home as well as the local authority were redacted from the transcripts to prevent the study site from being identifiable. These measures helped to safeguard the reputation of the care home as well as the residents and staff. Procedures were put in place in case signs of malpractice were observed during data collection or reported by family members. In this situation, I would have report them immediately to my supervisors before passing it onto the relevant authorities.

My initial application was sent back for amendments and clarification, particularly surrounding how I was defining “*family-centred reminiscence*” and clarifying what personal data was going to be collected and stored over the course of the study. This was a helpful step

for the development of my study as it was crucial that the terms used throughout, like family-centred reminiscence, were clearly defined to avoid confusing participants or gatekeepers in my study sites when negotiating access. The letter outlining ethical approval is included in Appendix 9.

4.4.1 Amendments to ethics application

An amendment to my initial application was submitted in January 2024. The amendment requested to make two changes. Firstly, following the conversations with Study Site Three (outlined above), I sought to broaden my inclusion criteria for participants to include family visitors of residents with mild cognitive impairment or dementia-like symptoms/probable dementia without the need for a confirmed dementia diagnosis. Current literature shows that the figures of people living with dementia in care homes are an under-representation due to issues with getting a diagnosis. Figures on the levels of dementia within care homes in Glasgow showed that whilst 58% of residents were living with dementia, they found an additional 31.8% of residents who scored within the range of a possible dementia diagnosis (Lithgow, Jackson, and Browne, 2011). This suggests that around 30% of dementia cases can go undiagnosed in care homes and therefore supported widening my inclusion criteria as there could have been families of residents within this group who would have benefited from participation. Therefore, due to the difficulties surrounding getting a formal diagnosis after a move to a care home, my participant inclusion criteria were updated to reflect this following submitting an amendment to my application to the School's Ethics Committee. Changing my inclusion criteria did not impact the quality of the study as the main purpose was to explore the acceptability of family-centred reminiscence during visits, and not necessarily on the potential benefits of reminiscence for residents with a formal diagnosis of dementia. However,

whilst widening my inclusion criteria would have benefitted my study, I was also mindful of additional ethical considerations. I amended my participant information sheet and recruitment flyers to include the terms *“families of residents with dementia or cognitive difficulties”* when discussing my inclusion criteria. This was to avoid causing families undue distress by suggesting that their relative had a dementia diagnosis that either the family did not know about, or that the resident did not have. Secondly, I requested an amendment to broaden my participant recruitment strategy to include care home staff as I experienced some recruitment challenges that became known during the action research process when recruiting only family visitors.

The main objective of my third action research cycle was to collaboratively work with my participants to create a resource on family-centred reminiscence that could be used by other families outside of the study. As care home staff would be distributing our co-produced resource to families coming into the home, it was prudent to involve them at this stage as had valuable insight into how this could be used within the care home. As part of this, I conducted a short group session with care home staff that were involved in the provision of care and included individuals such as care assistants and activity coordinators. During this group, staff members were provided with a copy of the co-produced resource, and we discussed how they envisioned using it with families coming into the home.

The inclusion of staff was a highly beneficial step for my study as since staff would be distributing the resource to families coming into the home, it was important that they were included in the action research group. By including staff in the study, there were additional ethical issues that needed to be addressed. Firstly, it was crucial that staff members had given informed consent prior to joining the study. Information sheets were distributed to interested

staff members that outlined why they were invited, and what taking participating would include (Appendix 10). A key ethical consideration was that staff members knew that participation was voluntary and that they did not feel coerced to join by management or senior staff members. This was highlighted in the information sheet and upon discussion when recruiting care staff. Staff were also required to sign a consent form; this was the same form used for all participants in the study. The letter from the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Board approving the amendment is included in Appendix 11.

4.4.2 Additional Ethical Challenges

There were several additional ethical challenges that needed to be addressed over the course of my study. Firstly, due to the nature of research within care homes, I had to have a planned process in place with the deputy manager of the home, in the event of a participant withdrawing from the study due to bereavement. This was a crucial as I wanted to avoid causing distress or upsetting participants whilst also acknowledging if a participant withdrew from the group. If a participant told me that their relative in the home was seriously unwell, or had died, I would meet with the deputy manager of the home to discuss what the participant had told me, and how to move forward with their data that had been previously collected over the course of the study. During this meeting, we would also discuss the best way to inform the rest of the group to be transparent without causing distress due to the emotionally charged nature of the participant withdrawing.

Furthermore, due to the emotional nature of visiting a loved one with dementia, I met with those with expertise in the field to develop my approaches. When developing my interview schedule for the first action research cycle, I met with the Associate Executive Lead for Localities from Alzheimer Scotland to discuss the topics that I wanted to cover during the

interviews. Additionally, I met with an Alzheimer Scotland Dementia Nurse Consultant to discuss how to approach the “Time Machine” activity with families which illustrated the trajectory of dementia and the types of memories that could be more effective for reminiscence.

4.5 Planned Research Methods

Throughout my three action research cycles, I planned on conducting rounds of semi-structured, individual, qualitative interviews with my participants, and rounds of focus groups with participants, each centred on a different activity.

4.4.1 Semi-Structured Interviews

A semi-structured interview is an exploratory interview technique that follows a protocol or guide, which is devised beforehand, and is focused on a core topic which provides a general structure to the interview, whilst allowing for discovery and space to follow topics which emerge as the conversation goes on (Magaldi and Berler, 2020). This approach was selected as it aligned with the exploratory nature of Cycle One and allowed me to uncover the participants’ perceptions and insights of their visits whilst allowing scope to discuss issues that were pertinent to their unique visit experiences. Whilst the aims of Cycle One could have been met by a single group session, the use of individual interviews was a fundamental step in building a relationship with participants, which was an integral part of action research (Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman, 2011). Furthermore, due to the flexible and versatile nature of semi-structured interviews, I was able to develop a conversational flow to the interviews through open-ended questions alongside improvised responses to emergent topics (Kallio *et al.*, 2016; Galletta, 2013; Polit and Beck, 2010). Due to the flexibility of semi-structured interviews, an interview guide is meant to provide some structure and focus to the natural conversation

using open-ended questions and follow-up probe questions which can be referred to throughout the interview depending on the responses from participants (Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik, 2021). For this study, the interview guide was developed and refined before data collection and explored two key themes: the participants' current visit experience, and their pre-existing knowledge of reminiscence, using descriptive questions accompanied by prompts to elicit further information. The interview guide is included in Appendix 8.

Whilst in-person was the optimum interview environment for this study, plans were in place to conduct the interviews virtually through TEAMS in the event that in-person interviews were not feasible. Virtual qualitative research methods have been extensively examined in recent years as the Covid-19 pandemic demonstrated their effectiveness (Sah, Singh, and Sah. 2020; Lobe, Morgan, and Hoffman, 2020; Chia and Razak, 2021; de Villiers, Farooq, and Molinari, 2022). Whilst virtual interviews are seen as acceptable alternatives to face-to-face methods, there are additional ethical concerns that need to be addressed. It is imperative that platforms used for virtual interviews are secure and keeps participant's data safe. Furthermore, participants need to be computer literate and have access to an internet connected device with a microphone and camera in addition to a space that is private and free from distractions for the interview (Lobe, Morgan, and Hoffman, 2020; Chia and Razak, 2021).

4.4.2 Focus Groups

A focus group is a research method involving more than one participant per data collection and can sometimes be referred to as a group depth interview, a group interview, or a focus group interview (Wilkinson, 2004; Liamputtong, 2011). Broadly speaking, focus groups can be seen as 'collective conversations' with small or large groups and discussions are centred to examine a particular set of topics using a collective activity (Kamberelis and Dimitriadis, 2008;

Kitzinger, 2005). The main aim of a focus group is to explore and understand meanings and interpretation from a specific group to gain an understanding of the issue at hand from their perspectives (Liamputtong 2009).

Gomm (2009) contends that that focus group participants are selected as they are a purposive sample, and the research provides questions or topics for a group discussion. Focus groups typically involve up to eight participants from a similar social background, or who have similar experiences or concerns who are brought together to discuss a specific issue guided by a moderator (Liamputtong, 2011). Wong (2008) argues that a smaller group of between four and six participants are preferable when participants are discussing intensive experiences. Since my focus group centred on discussing the families' visit experiences and how they have used reminiscence informally, both subjective and emotionally charged topics, a smaller focus group was preferable for this study. This decision was also influenced by the limited number of participants recruited from the study site.

A key point of focus groups is that rather than aiming to reach a consensus on the discussed topics, focus groups should encourage a wide range of responses to better understand the attitudes, opinions, and experiences of participants on the research issues (Hennink, 2007). This aligned with the aims of Cycle One, as I was interested in further understanding how families felt about their visits, and the various ways that they may have used reminiscence during their visits prior to joining the study. A focus group format was chosen for this study as they can be flexible in allowing the researcher to explore a variety of topics with a range of participants, and it allows participants to react and build on the responses from other participants within the group (Krueger and Casey, 2014; Stewart and Shamdasani, 2014; Gomm, 2009). This was compliant with the principles of collaborative action research as a

focus group is inherently collaborative and creates a dialogue between the researcher and participants (Bergold, 2012). This also aligned with the peer support aspect that participants mentioned during their interviews as a focus group approach allowed them to learn from each other as they shared their experiences.

4.6 Approach to analysis

Prior to analysis, each recording was listened to twice through to ensure I was sensitised to the data. These recordings were then transcribed with field notes to supplement the transcriptions. Due to the semi-structured nature of the interviews, a more selective transcription process was taken. Davidson (2009) contends that any transcription process is inherently selective whereby certain aspects, such as conversational tangents, are not transcribed and that instead of viewing this as a problem, selectivity needs to be recognised as a practical and theoretical requirement of research. Furthermore, selectivity needs to be understood in relation to the overall goals and objectives of the study as unnecessary information can limit the readability of the transcript and have a detrimental impact on the research purpose (Duranti, 2007; Davidson, 2009). A naturalised or intelligent verbatim transcript can be a common way to produce a more “readable” transcript that does not include excessive repetitions, verbal fillers, or irrelevant tangents in conversation whilst keeping the context and meaning of quotes intact by including indications of laughter and non-verbal cues are included if they add context to what was being said (McMullin, 2021). This was consonant with the purpose of the interviews as it allowed me to focus on understanding the participant’s visit experiences, by removing any conversational tangents that were not relevant to the interview questions or topics.

Additionally, when transcribing, it was imperative that the document produced was easily analysable and readable. McMullin (2021) suggested including timestamps for sections that were unclear or inaudible, or at regular intervals to aid with checking the transcript against the original audio. Member checking was also offered in this study, whereby the participants were offered a transcript or a synopsis of their interview to read over. This was important as it alleviated the risk that I had inadvertently taken something out of context or misconstrued what they were meaning to convey (Birt *et al.*, 2016). This provided participants with an opportunity to add anything that they may have overlooked during the initial interview or if anything new of relevance occurred since the interview, however, this offer was not accepted by any of the study participants. To enhance the readability of the transcripts, a new line was used for different speakers in addition to a hanging indent and pseudonyms to indicate when a new speaker started.

The initial transcripts were securely stored and encrypted on OneDrive in a password secured folder. This was to ensure that all data collected was secure and only accessible to myself and my supervisors. Prior to analysis, the original transcripts were edited to remove any identifying attributes such as the name of their loved one and the name and location of the care homes to preserve the participants' anonymity. A 'master sheet' was also prepared which contained the name, pseudonym, and important relevant demographic characteristics for each participant to assure that each transcript could be linked by myself to the correct participant which was essential when reviewing the transcript after the removal of names and identifying characteristics. The master sheet was then encrypted, and password protected and stored on OneDrive to ensure that all data relating to participants was secure.

4.6.1 Alternative analytical approaches considered

A framework analysis was briefly considered for this study. A key feature of a framework analysis approach is that it creates a series of thematic frameworks which allows the researcher to move between multiple layers of abstraction without losing sight of the raw data, or the overarching themes (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013; Kiernan and Hill, 2018). Whilst I have incorporated some elements of this approach into my analysis process, primarily the use of a spreadsheet as a means of data management, a full framework analysis was deemed to be too time consuming and resource intensive for the purpose of the research within the timeframe available (Gale *et al.*, 2013). A spreadsheet was used to manage data as it allowed me to view all the responses related to a particular question at the same time. This was beneficial for my category formation as I could see how the differences and commonalities across the responses. Additionally, for a full framework analysis, the thematic matrices would be rooted in my theoretical framework and embedded throughout the study. This would not be necessary for this stage of my study as instead of focusing on theoretical concepts, the interviews explored the families' current visit experience and their thoughts on the use of using aspects of reminiscence during their visits with their loved ones.

Reflexive thematic analysis aligned with my chosen methodology of collaborative action research. Johnson (2008) contends that action research should involve an ongoing process of data analysis whereby data is analysed as it is collected. This is accomplished by looking for emergent themes or categories that can then be used to influence further data collection, which is consonant with the iterative and reflexive nature of thematic analysis. Additionally, data analysis within action research contains interrelating processes of analysis and coding (Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman, 2011; McNiff, 2017). Ahmed *et al.* (2025) contend that

throughout the thematic analysis process, emphasis is placed on the iterative and reflexive nature of the approach whereby researchers are actively engaged with the data and have an awareness of their theoretical positioning and biases. Similarly, Mertler (2007) states that within qualitative action research, an appropriate approach to data analysis should involve an inductive process where the action researcher analyses the data for patterns and similarities, which aligns with the overarching research question therefore this aligned with the reflexive and iterative nature of collaborative action research and therefore reflexive thematic analysis was the best fit for this study.

4.6.2 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is an accessible and increasingly popular method of qualitative data analysis that has been regularly cited (Braun and Clarke, 2012). At its core, thematic analysis is a method for developing, analysing, and interpreting patterns across a qualitative dataset, resulting in the development of themes reflective of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; 2022, Guest, MacQueen, and Namey, 2011; Gerritse *et al.*, 2018; Clarke *et al.*, 2019; Roberts, Dowell, and Nie, 2019). By placing an emphasis on meanings across a data set, thematic analysis allows researchers to recognise and make sense of collective or shared meanings and experiences (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas, 2013). This was particularly appropriate for Cycle One of this study which sought to understand the current experiences of families visiting the care home to determine if there were commonalities across their experiences. Reflexive thematic analysis builds on this by involving the practice of critically reflecting on the role of the researcher and the research practice and process (Braun and Clarke, 2022). This is consonant with action research, as reflexivity and reflection are fundamental components of an action research study whereby each cycle is built on the previous one (Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman, 2011; Heikkinen, Huttunen, and Syrjälä, 2012;

Townsend, 2013; McNiff, 2017). Furthermore, Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman (2011) contend that when reporting on qualitative findings, reflexivity needs to be taken into account as the researcher's own social identity and background will impact on the research process. This was pertinent for this study as my own role as a carer of a parent living with dementia perhaps heightened my sensitivity to the participant's experiences which assisted with identifying the common themes across the dataset.

Rowley (2014) state that due to the cyclical nature of action research and the inherent reflexivity, data analysis is ongoing throughout the action research process. Similarly, they contend that as action research is heavily embedded within organisational and social settings, it is difficult to separate data collection from data analysis. Therefore, action researchers often utilise qualitative data analysis, such as thematic analysis, to make sense and generate understanding and insights from the evidence and reflections that have emerged, with a view to contribute new knowledge or theories (Rowley, 2014). This therefore justifies the use of reflexive thematic analysis as it aligns with the cyclical and reflexive nature of collaborative action research.

4.6.3 Outline of Approach

For this study, my reflexive thematic analysis was informed by Braun and Clarke's (2022) six phase process. This process involved:

1. *familiarisation with data*
2. *coding*
3. *generating initial themes*
4. *developing and reviewing themes*

5. *refining, defining and naming themes*

6. *writing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2022, pgs. 35-36)*

The first phase of the analysis centred on familiarising myself with the dataset, through a process of immersion. This involved reading and re-reading the transcripts to begin to sensitise myself to the data. Whilst I was re-reading the transcripts, I made notes to capture my initial thoughts on the data and highlight select quotes that I felt captured key points of the participants' experiences. Although this was not the identification of codes or themes, it was a beneficial step in immersing myself in the data which was instrumental for the analysis.

The second phase of the analytical process was focussed on systematically coding the transcripts. Coding included identifying the segments from the transcripts that were pertinent to the research question or captured an interesting aspect of the participants' experiences and applying succinct and analytically-meaningfully labels to each code. This process was focussed and specific as each code aimed to capture a single concept or meaning. I then re-read the transcripts and annotated each code to capture my thoughts and how they might fit into the initial overarching themes. This aligned with Braun and Clarke (2022) who contend that reflexive thematic analysis is not purely centred on summarising or reducing a data set but also focusses on capturing the researcher's 'analytical take'. Following coding, the next phase centred on generating the initial themes that emerged from the transcripts. This involved identifying patterns of shared meanings from across the dataset and compiling groups of codes that relate to the same concept or idea. This is an active process whereby themes are constructed based on the data, the research question, and the researcher's insights and knowledge. A worked example of this is included in Appendix 12.

4.7 Rigour

Adhering to a pre-established systematic process promoted rigour throughout my data analysis, and study, by clearly outlining how my data will be analysed. Elo *et al.* (2014) state that to promote rigour, the concept of trustworthiness as established by Lincoln and Guba (1985) must run through all three key stages of qualitative analysis: preparation, organisation, and reporting of results. This aligns with the reflexive thematic analysis approach outlined above, as adhering to a set process enhanced the trustworthiness, and by extension the rigour of this study. Trustworthiness and rigour in qualitative analysis is directly linked to decisions made during data collection (Elo *et al.*, 2014). An example of this is being transparent about sampling. Purposive sampling is commonly used in action research however, it can be difficult to assess the trustworthiness of the sampling technique if full details are not provided such as the sampling approach and a short description of the method and justification for recruiting based on selected characteristics (Kynğäs *et al.*, 2011; Creswell, 2013). Therefore, it was critical that I clearly stated that that I used purposive sampling, and the criteria used to recruit participants as previously outlined in section 4.3.

It has been recommended that the risk of misrepresentation could be alleviated by having two or more coders to develop the codes and categories for analysis (Elo *et al.*, 2014). Conversely, it could be argued that having more than one coder could lead to conflicting interpretations of the data and as such undermine efforts to enhance the rigour of the coding process (Odinot *et al.*, 2013). Whilst I can see the merit of both stances, I opted to be the only coder and have the codes verified by a member of my supervision team. This approach was taken not only as a pragmatic decision since I have a limited timeframe, but also to ensure that the codes being applied were representative and consistent across the transcripts whilst still aligning with the question-driven approach to the main categories.

4.7 Chapter summary

The chapter explored the recruitment and ethical challenges that were faced during this action research study. It opened with an overview of the study design and objectives for the three action research cycles. After this, it outlined the process of recruiting the study site and participants and a detailed narrative was provided on the challenges faced during the study site recruitment process. The process involved in gaining ethical approval for the study and any additional ethical challenges that arose during recruitment was outlined. Lastly, this chapter provided an overview of the planned methods and analytical approach for the three action research cycles. The next three chapters explore the three cycles of this study and begin by outlining any variations from the planned methods and explore any preparatory work undertaken.

Chapter Five- Cycle One

This chapter will explore the findings from Cycle One of this action research study. Firstly, it will give a brief overview of the aims and objectives of the cycle of this study, any amendments made to the planned methods (see section 4.4) are outlined along with the reasoning behind any changes. Next, the chapter outlines the exploratory interviews that were conducted at the start of Cycle One and how these led into the second part of this cycle. The second half of Cycle One centred on a focus group session which brought the participants together for the first time. This chapter will end by focussing on the reminiscence task that participants were invited to try, and how this led into the second cycle.

5.1 Cycle One Overview

Cycle One was a preparatory cycle for my study which had two overarching aims. The first being to create a shared understanding with family visitors that captured their current experience of visiting their loved one in a care home. The second aim was to gain an understanding of the ways that family visitors might already use informal reminiscence during their visits. Although these are seen as two independent aims, they were captured during the one process. The first data collection activity of the cycle was to conduct a round of semi-structured, individual qualitative interviews with participants to understand how they viewed their visits. This included understanding how they prepared for visits, their visit activities, and how they felt after a visit. As the interview progressed, the concept of 'reminiscence' was introduced to explore if the participants had any prior experience of reminiscence, and to get their initial thoughts on using this during their visits. The findings from the interviews underpinned a focus group to further explore these topics and to begin to form a group

identity, which is a crucial component of collaborative action research (Townsend, 2014). Due to the emergent nature of action research, plans can change and evolve as the study goes on to respond to the needs and wants of the group. As Cycle One progressed, the plan for the focus group changed to also include showing participants an introductory video on reminiscence. This was used to open a conversation on ways that they used reminiscence informally during their visits and to discuss their thoughts on using a more structured approach to reminiscence during future visits. After this discussion, the participants were provided with instructions for a short reminiscence task that they could do with their relative which then moved the study into the second research cycle. This emergent nature of action research allowed for each research activity to be informed by previous activities within the action cycle. Diagram 9 below outlines the research activities for Cycle One.

Diagram 9: Overview of Cycle One Research Activities

5.1.1 Relationship between participants and residents

Participants were recruited following the process outlined in Chapter Four, Section 4.3.2. The initial phone call and face-to-face meetings with each participant was a key component of the recruitment process as it was integral in forming a relationship that was built on mutual trust and respect, which was crucial for successful collaborative working within an action research study (Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman, 2011). Incorporating relationship-building into the recruitment process helped to enhance the conversational flow of the interviews and to put

participants at ease. A total of four participants were recruited from my study site during the first action research cycle and Table 4 outlines the participants' relationship to the care home residents.

Table 4 - Participants' relationship to residents

Participant pseudonym	Relation to resident
Participant One	Ex-partner/close friend
Participant Two	Daughter
Participant Three	Daughter
Participant Four	Husband

Whilst Participants Two and Three were from the same family, they were both included in the study as our introductory conversations had demonstrated that they had different perspectives on the visit experience and were interviewed individually to capture this. As detailed in Chapter Four, Section 4.4, all participant data was anonymised, and participants were assigned a pseudonym in line with data protection and research ethics. All four participants were involved in both data collection activities in Cycle One (see Table 2).

5.2 Research methods used

There was no variation from the anticipated methods outlined in Chapter Four, Section 4.4.1. The interviews were conducted in a quiet room in the study site that was to the best of my abilities, free from distractions. Gagnon, Jacob, and McCabe (2015) contend that the location of an interview should be viewed as a fundamental component of the research process with particular focus on how the participants' visibility, privacy, and confidentiality are related to the interview location and location-specific phenomena. For three interviews, the library in the care home was used. However, for one of the interviews, the dining room was used which

meant that there were a few interruptions from staff as the kitchen for teas and coffees was connected to the room. This particularly was the case after one interruption as the staff member stopped for a short conversation with the participant. Furthermore, whilst I was not asking about any issues with staff, the participant may have felt unable to raise any staff related factors that had an adverse effect on their visits due to an infrequent staff presence throughout the interview. The recording was paused during each interruption. This could have had an impact on the interview as after a few of the interruptions, one or both of us had momentarily lost our concentration. This is consonant with Bjørvik *et al.* (2023) who state that different interview locations can elicit different research questions and responses.

The interviews were designed to have a 'softer' start to act as an icebreaker to allow the participant to settle into the interview (see Appendix 8). Following this I summarised and briefly explained what the interview would entail and reiterated that they were free to withdraw from the interview at any point. Due to the emotional nature of the topic, I was responsive to any signs of stress or distress and worked with my supervisors to have a procedure in place if it was needed. At the end of interviews, participants were given the opportunity to ask any questions and to discuss any issues raised. This debrief also included signposting families to additional support such as the Alzheimer Scotland 24-hour helpline, liaison nurses or local carer groups. This helped to ensure that families were aware of the support networks available to them by giving them up to ten minutes, this could have been extended if required, at the end of the session for discussion and the opportunity to contact them at a later suitable time for one-to-one support.

The interviews were digitally recorded with consent using a digital voice recorder. A secondary recording device was also used as redundancy or backup in case of any unforeseen issues with

the primary recording. During the interviews, field notes were also collected to record any non-verbal data such as body language and paralinguistics in addition to my initial thoughts of anything that stood out during the interviews. Whilst having the backup recorder was beneficial, I learned after the first interview that having the two recorders too close to each other resulted in feedback in the recording. This did not have an adverse effect on the interview, but it meant that some sections of the first minute or two were a bit more difficult to hear when transcribing. Moreover, some of the participants needed an additional few minutes to settle into the interviews as the act of turning the voice recorder on caused them to become a bit stilted in their responses, however, this faded after a few minutes. This was addressed in later sessions by having the recorder ready prior to participants arriving for the group sessions.

There were several steps to the interview process that needed to be considered in tandem with building rapport (Magaldi and Berler, 2020). The first stage centred on introductions, the presentation of the research topic, and securing informed consent (Baumbusch, 2010). For this study, this was achieved during the first in-person meeting with each participant prior to the interviews during which I introduced myself and the study. We also discussed the participant information sheet and informed consent form before participants were formally invited to join the study. At the start of the interview, participants provided me with their signed informed consent form, and I outlined the purpose of the interview and what we would discuss. During this stage, participants had the opportunity to ask any questions they might have had regarding the research or the interviews, which helped to create a safe and open environment (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Magaldi and Berler, 2020). As the interview progressed, more in-depth questions were introduced and moved towards more challenging topics which elicited more emotional responses as such, the interview used language comfortable and

familiar to participants (Magaldi and Berler, 2020). This was essential in building rapport with participants and creating a relationship with participants which was built on mutual trust and respect. As the interview develops, a more free and open dialogue can emerge between the interviewer and the interviewee (Whiting, 2008). At this stage, the interview guide can be an essential tool in preventing the interview from becoming a casual conversation that moves away from the research topic. This was pertinent for my interviews as a few participants felt comfortable enough to bring up topics that whilst they were important to their experience, were not relevant to the research topic and therefore the interview guide was needed to gently guide the interview back to the topic at hand.

5.3 Interview Findings

The purpose of the individual interviews was two-fold. The first was to explore the current visit experiences of families visiting loved ones living in care homes with dementia. The second purpose of the interviews was to explore the families' current knowledge and prior experience of reminiscence, and if they would be receptive to trying it during their visits. Following the process outlined in Chapter Four, Section 4.5.3, a reflexive thematic analysis informed by Braun and Clarke (2022) was conducted on the four interview transcripts. The questions from the interview guide were used to form the basis of the codes and the initial themes. The first section on the interview centred on the participants' current visit experience. After refinement of the initial themes, there were two overarching themes. The first of which was the concept of having a connection, and the second overarching theme was the visit experience as a whole. The second part of the interview focussed on participants' prior experience of reminiscence and looking ahead to the second cycle of the study. This had three

themes: no formal experience of reminiscence, receptive to trying reminiscence, and peer support through the study.

5.3.1 Connection

The first section of the interview was centred on understanding the current visit experience for families and how they feel about visiting their loved one with dementia. The first overarching theme was the concept of connecting with others, which proved to be an important topic for families. There were three sub-themes which were important in understanding the ways that families remained connected during their visits. These were: connection with their loved one with dementia, connection with staff, and connection through a shared activity.

5.3.1.1 Connection with their loved one with dementia

All four participants discussed the importance of remaining connected with their loved one with dementia for as long as possible and this was their primary motivation for visiting regularly. This sentiment was echoed in their responses when they were asked what they look forward to when visiting. Participant One poignantly notes that simply having that positive interaction makes the visit worthwhile:

“He goes “I'm glad you're here” and holds onto my arm “I'm glad you're here, it's good to see you”. So, I like that wee bit as well”.

Conversely, Participant One also mentions that visits can sometimes be difficult, especially when her partner has a “wee tear” in his eye, however she notes that they were not sure if this was from cold air or if it was an emotional reaction.

The importance of maintaining connections was also echoed by Participants Two and Three, who are sisters and often visit their mum together. When asked what she looked forward to when she visited her mum, Participant Two answered:

“...most of all, just seeing Mum...If I don't see her, I miss her so much and that's the most I look forward to...I always find when I come and visit mum, I go home feeling a lot happier. It's incredible. It really is.”

Again, Participant Two clearly states that her primary motivation for regularly visiting her mum is that she misses her if she does not visit often and as such, she tries to visit at least three times a week. From other responses throughout the interview, it became apparent that Participant Two used to care for her mum before the move to the care home and her mum was always surrounded by family as *“she was just life and soul and so we just doted on mum”*. This captures the importance of sustained family involvement for Participant Two and the use of *“doted on”* further suggests that Participant Two actively enjoys her visits and helping her mother instead of viewing visits as a chore or part of her duty as a daughter. Likewise, Participant Three answered that she looks forward to visiting her mum as she enjoys *“just talking to her and seeing her smile”*. This encapsulates how important maintaining familial connections can be, and how crucial it can be to ensure that the person with dementia still feels a sense of belonging within the family. It also demonstrated how a seemingly simple act like receiving a smile can be a meaningful interaction that enhances the important familial connection between visiting family members and their loved one living in the care home. A response from Participant Four captures the importance of maintaining a connection with a loved one living in a care home. When asked what he looks forward to when visiting the home, he replied:

“Eh, what do I look forward to? Obviously seeing [Wife], that’s it in a nutshell...if you get a smile, you’re in business and if her eyes are open, that kind of stuff”.

Furthermore, whilst this was not a quantitative study, from the reflexive thematic analysis, I discovered that over the course of his interview, Participant Four’s wife was mentioned sixty times. This clearly illustrates that although his wife is now living in the care home, she is still a significant and fundamental part of his life.

5.3.1.2 Connection with Staff

As outlined in Chapter Two section 2.6.1.3, it was apparent that establishing a connection and relationship with staff was an important aspect of adjusting to visiting a loved one in a care home. Whilst all four participants mentioned that they have a relationship with staff, the nature of this relationship differed. Participants Two and Four stated that staff are often involved in their visits and that they have a good rapport with them. On the other hand, whilst Participants One and Three welcome interaction with staff, they maintain more of a working relationship with staff as they are not involved in their visits with their loved ones.

When asked if they speak to staff before visiting her mum, Participant Two stated that *“you couldn’t not interact with them”* and explained she often needs staff assistance in helping her mum get from her bed to her wheelchair. Participant Two also expands on this with:

“So, we do, we interact and have a laugh with them...they’ll tell us things that we don’t know about my mum”

Participant Two also stated that some of the staff interact with her mum in Irish Gaelic, as this was her mother tongue, and that her mum was teaching some of the staff some phrases. As part of this she stated that:

“They’re my mum’s life now and they’re what’s keeping her so fantastic, you know, and she’s so fantastically well, it’s incredible, it really is”

This suggested that Participant Two embraced staff involvement during her visits as she acknowledges the role that the staff play in her mum’s life and the benefits for her mum in encouraging this interaction. Similarly, Participant Four welcomed staff involvement in his visits with his wife stating that for him, chatting to the staff and other residents is *“part and parcel”* of the visit experience. Conversely, for Participants One and Three, whilst they get on well with staff, they have more of a working relationship with them and staff typically were not involved in their visits apart from assisting with moving the resident to and from wheelchairs.

Participant One stated that when she arrives at the home, she greets the staff and *“if there’s something wrong, they’ll come and they’ll tell me”*. This is consonant with the findings from the literature review (Chapter Two, Section 2.6.1) as having a clear line of communication alongside a positive working relationship can help families to adjust to their role within the home and allow them to relinquish care of their loved one as families are reassured that their loved ones in the care home are in safe hands (Johansson *et al.*, 2014; Lethin *et al.*, 2016; Rosendahl, Söderman, and Mazaheri, 2016; Pritty, De Boos, and Moghaddam, 2020; and Tasseron-Dries *et al.*, 2021). As shown in Chapter Two, Section 2.6.1 information sharing can be a fundamental component of a family’s relationship with the home as it can allow staff to become more responsive to when the person with dementia was becoming distressed or if families noticed signs of illness such as a chest or urine infection which they were able to pass onto staff (Powell *et al.*, 2018).

5.3.1.3 Connection through a shared activity

For every participant, doing a shared activity with their loved one with dementia was a critical part of remaining connected to them. For example, during her interview Participant One mentioned that she keeps two easy jigsaw puzzles in her partner's room in the care home which she often does with him. Whilst on the surface this can seem like a simple task, it allowed her to connect with him by doing the jigsaw together.

Participants Two and Three both discussed a Life Story style of book that another one of their sisters made and how they used this during their visits with their mother. Life Story work is a term used to explain how reminiscence can be used to encourage people to reflect on their lives, both thematically and chronologically, using a book which includes written recollections, photographs, and other relevant memorabilia and is at the heart of relationship-centred care (Gibson, 2011). Having this as a tool for visits was highly beneficial for Participant Two as her mother is *“always animated and she never gets bored of it, and she's always animated when we do that. So, it's a great thing to have”*. Participant Three expands on this by stating that their Life Story book contains family pictures from over the years and includes all her mother's grandchildren and great-grandchildren. This was an ideal way for them to not only have an enjoyable visit with their mother looking through the book, but it also allowed them to keep their mother somewhat connected to the wider family.

During the interview, Participant Three also talked about how she often brings her dog to the home when she visits her mother, which helps her to see the care home as her mother's home. She also mentioned that the other residents often enjoy seeing the dog run about as it is a bit more unusual compared to the normal day to day activities:

“All the old people like him, he cheers them up as I suppose it’s something different, a wee dog running about, isn’t it”

This also became apparent during our interview as she had brought her dog with her and let him explore the library as we were talking. On the other hand, Participant Four stated that he does not plan any activities or take anything with him when he visits his wife. However, during the interview he talked about how he assists her with her breakfast, allowing him to feel connected to her during a visit which can be very meaningful for him as his wife is non-verbal due to the progression of her dementia:

“it’s nice to connect with [Wife] as best I can, and I give her breakfast then”.

However, he mentioned that when his wife was in her previous care home, and before her dementia advanced, he would bring in a ball and would see if she would hold it and pass it back to him as she used to be a professional netball player. Unfortunately, during the interview he stated that his wife has lost her motor skills, meaning that activities such as this are no longer possible. These conversations highlighted how families use various activities during their visits to keep connected to their loved ones living with dementia, and how their visits can be adapted to maintain this connection despite the challenges that can arise as the condition progresses.

5.3.2 Visit Experience

Whilst all participants were visiting residents from the same care home, they all had differing visit experiences. Within the overarching theme of Visit Experience, there were three sub-themes that were raised during our interviews which were pertinent to understand how each

participant viewed their visits. These were: “Does it feel different to before”, Visit Environment, and Feelings after a visit.

5.3.2.1 Does it feel different before?

For any family, a loved one moving into a care home is a major change and can have ramifications for maintaining their familial connection. During the interviews, participants were asked if their visits felt any different compared to before the care home admission. Most participants stated that it felt different to before. Participant One stated that visiting the care home is “*definitely different*” compared to when she used to visit him at his own home. However, she also notes that caring for her partner was difficult before he moved into the care home:

“I'd rather be in his own house, but I know it's hard when he was like that [living in the community]”.

This encapsulates the contradictory feelings that families can often experience, as they recognise that the required level of care would not be feasibly achieved in the community by families or home care, whilst also feeling guilt and grief at the move to the care home. Similarly, Participant Three noted how moving her mother from the family home into a different environment had an impact on their visits. This was particularly as issue as due to her mother’s hearing loss, they had to talk loudly for her to hear them:

“We’re all loud people, I don't know why, maybe because my mum got a bit deaf and we all have to shout, and she wouldn’t hear if you didn’t shout like that”.

Participant Three shared that this was intensified in the care home with other conversations going on in the background. She also noted that it was more relaxing to visit her mother when

she was at home as she was able to go out for walks with her to local parks whereas whilst the care home has large grounds, she is unable to go for walks with mother in her wheelchair beyond the care home grounds due to the steep hills and busy roads that lead up to and surround the home:

“The home would have been in her own home. It would have been more kind of relaxing, it would. We could take her out at any time even if it's just a walk”

Conversely, whilst Participant Two often visited with her sister (Participant Three), she had a completely different perspective on if the visit felt different compared to before. Participant Two views the care home as her mother's home now and as such did not see it as being different to when she lived at home: *“It's, it's wonderful. We still just, we're visiting mum today. It's, we don't feel any different”*. However, Participant Two spent a part of the interview going over her experience of being her mother's sole named visitor during the Covid-19 Pandemic, and the additional emotional strain that this placed on her.

“It broke my heart...Obviously. When I was the designated visitor, it was so different. I didn't feel so cheery when I was on my own, ever and that obviously got through to my mum as well. So, it was, the visits were so different from what they are now”.

From this excerpt, it is clear to see that being the sole visitor during the pandemic had a detrimental impact not only on her, but also on her mother as she moved into the home just before the pandemic and therefore had not adjusted before the restrictions were put in place.

5.3.2.2 Visit Environment

For any visit, the visit environment can have influence the activities available to families, and how they feel during the visit. In this study, the three common visit locations were: the resident's room, the care home grounds, and the lounge.

Participant One always started her visits in her partner's room and then, weather permitting, sometimes took her partner outside in his wheelchair if he was receptive to that. For Participant One, having the visit in the room, allowed her use different activities to keep her partner mentally stimulated and involved in the visit. For example, she would often turn on the TV in the background as soon as she got up to the room:

"I put the TV on anyway because sometimes he likes the TV... I know used to like that film, so he sat for a wee while, and he watched it".

Additionally, Participant One would bring in holiday pictures to talk about the shared experiences they had prior to life in the care home as a way to *"to get his memory going"*.

Similarly, Participants Two and Three tried to get their mother outside as much as possible during their visits as their mother grew up on farms in Ireland as such, being outside was an effective way to keep her calm and settled during visits. They incorporated being outside into their visits by having afternoon teas outside together with their mother in the grounds. One memorable visit involved having an Ireland themed afternoon tea as another family member had brought back Irish snacks and food from a holiday. Through this activity, it allowed them to connect with their mother through the visit location:

“We sat round and she ate, and we talked about Ireland, and it made her think back and she would tell us a bit about the farm then, which she’s not mentioned in a long time”.

However, Participant Four found that his wife was more stimulated if he visited in the communal lounge in the care home as she would give non-verbal responses to what was going on around her:

“You know, you know some stimulation, whether it’s some folk beside her. Obviously, staff are coming and going, so there’s more liable to get some form of dialogue, whereas there you’re stuck in a room and forgotten”

Whilst having visits in the lounge was preferable, he mentioned that he would move them to his wife’s room if other family members were visiting to give them more privacy.

From these responses, it was clear that the families often had their visits in various locations which in turn would determine the activities that they were able to do with their loved ones. This was important to bear in mind for the later stages of the study when we would be discussing ways to incorporate reminiscence into their visits, as reminiscence would work best if it was conducted in a comfortable and familiar environment.

5.3.2.3 How families felt after visits

For any family, visiting a loved one in a care home is an emotionally charged experience which can either make their day, or leave them feeling worse than they did before the visit. Whilst a visit can be an enjoyable experience, some families can struggle with leaving their loved one in the home after a visit. For two participants, they struggled to leave their loved ones due to constantly worrying about them after a visit. This is not to say that they disclosed any major

issues with the care provided in the home, but they stated that they were always thinking about them when they were not visiting. For example, Participant One stated that she usually feels sad after a visit as she worries if her partner has a cup of tea as that typically helped to settle him after she left. Likewise, Participant Three noted that if the visit does not go to plan, then that would cause her to leave feeling worse than she did when she arrived:

“you're a bit sad, a bit melancholy because you think that wasn't nice to see her not so happy”.

She also noted that she often *“hates”* leaving her mother as she used to stay with her at weekends before she moved into the home and that her mother never lived alone. These responses highlight that a care home admission does not mean that families stop worrying about their loved one's wellbeing and that even if a 'good' visit does not completely alleviate this.

Conversely, Participants Two and Four talked about how they generally feel happy after a visit. Participant Two mentioned that when her mum is animated and happy during a visit then she leaves feeling that it was a wonderful visit. She also talked about how her mother has always been a big part of her life and that she could not imagine life without, so simply seeing her made her feel *“blessed”*. For Participant Four, he discussed how he has no issues leaving his wife after a visit as he knows that she is safe and well looked after in the home, which was the most important aspect for him. He also stated that after a visit he *“goes away and lives [his] own life...play pickleball or go for walks”*. It was interesting to hear that whilst he visits six days a week and views his visits as an integral part of his day, he also maintains his separate hobbies and *“lives his own life”*. This could imply that his hobbies and interests were an important aspect of maintaining his mental wellbeing which in turn assisted with visiting regularly

without experiencing burnout. He also discussed how he simultaneously feels “*very sad*” that his wife was diagnosed at a younger age, which prevented her living an active life like she used to.

These responses show that even for one individual, leaving a visit can contain a multitude of emotions. Furthermore, they highlight that if a visit goes well, some families can leave feeling uplifted and more positive. This was important for later cycles of this study as I hoped that the use of reminiscence could help families have more positive visits which would help them to view visits as a positive part of their day or week. It was hoped that this positive interaction would be a source of comfort for some families and enhance their connections to their loved one.

5.3.3 Prior experience of reminiscence

Before introducing a family-centred approach to reminiscence into visits, it was important to determine if any participants had prior experience of formal reminiscence so that the following sessions could be tailored to either build on their pre-existing knowledge or introduce reminiscence more broadly.

From the interviews, it became apparent that no participant had formal experience of reminiscence, and whilst most knew what it was, they did not know what Reminiscence Therapy was. However, they all used reminiscence informally in various ways whether this was looking through family albums together or bringing in food that they used to enjoy. Participant Four summarised how the families felt during visits as he said:

“I mean I do reminisce, that’s all I’ve got really in many respects, you know”

This demonstrated that for him, reminiscence is a natural activity that can be enjoyed with someone living with dementia and at times, it can transcend the communication barriers that can occur during the later stages of dementia. Reminiscence can also present an opportunity for families to see beyond the dementia diagnosis, and see the person that is still there, which is essential in maintaining the connection that the families raised earlier in the interviews.

Despite not having any prior experience of formal reminiscence, every participant was receptive to introducing this into their visits. When asked if she thinks her loved one would find reminiscence helpful, Participant One talked about using photobooks or albums that the family have made that they go through together and suggested that she was interested in using aspects of reminiscence during visits as a means to remain connected. Also, both Participants Two and Four were interested in exploring reminiscence as a focal point for a visit and to use it in different ways to elicit a response from their loved ones. This was an encouraging start to the study as participants were open to trying new activities during their visits and discovering new ways of staying connected to their loved ones living in the care home. Additionally, it was interesting to hear how they had already incorporated elements of reminiscence into their visits, even if they might not have realised that was what they were doing, as a natural component to their visits.

5.3.4 Peer Support

When asked their thoughts on the idea of using group sessions throughout the study, every participant was interested in the peer support aspect of groupwork. Participant One stated that she had not met any other families within the home apart from saying hello at the door:

“I don't meet any of the families here”

She felt that this was an aspect that was missing from her experience of visiting the home after the pandemic-related visit restrictions were lifted. Additionally, Participant Three noted that she was interested in hearing about the experiences of other visitors and the ways that they could learn from each other. This was something that I felt could be beneficial for later stages of the study whereby participants could share the different reminiscence activities that they have tried and the types of responses that they received from their loved ones.

On a similar note, Participant Four almost adopted an activist-type mentality when asked about his thoughts on group sessions as he wanted to try anything that could help his wife, or other families going through similar experiences as he stated that visiting a loved one in a care home is not an *“easy ride”*. This aligned with one of the aims of the study which sought to develop a resource that could be used by other families after the study had concluded. It was also encouraging to hear that this was something that resonated with how some participants felt and the ways in which they wanted to help others, when this aim was raised with them.

5.4 Anticipated Methods for Objective Two

The second objective of Cycle One sought to introduce the concept of reminiscence, explore how families already used some aspects of reminiscence informally, and begin to discuss how families could incorporate reminiscence into their visits. Following the initial round of interviews that started the cycle, a focus group was planned to bring the participants together to begin to form a group identity, to further explore the topics raised in the interviews, and to introduce reminiscence in more detail.

5.4.1 Focus Group preparatory Work

Prior to the first group session, I worked with my lead supervisor to develop a short, ten-minute video which served as an introduction to reminiscence. This aimed to build on what participants already knew about reminiscence by providing an overview of what reminiscence and best practice for using it. The purpose of the video was not to make families feel like they were previously 'visiting wrong', but to start the conversation around how aspects of reminiscence could be incorporated into their visits, and how reminiscence can often require a slower approach than other visit activities. The slides used in the video are include in Appendix 13.

As the group involved an element of carer education, I worked alongside my supervisors to develop my guide to ensure that it was clear and concise enough without being patronising or talking down to families. This was crucial for the study as action research is built on mutual respect and as such, I wanted to demonstrate from the start that I respected every participant and that they had a voice throughout the study.

5.4.3 Research methods used

There was no variation from the anticipated methods outlined in Chapter Four, Section 4.4.2. The group session was conducted in the dining room of the care home as the library was unavailable. However, as the group finished at 12pm, the ending coincided with the staff beginning to set up the dining room for lunch. This meant that participants were leaving whilst staff were trying to bring residents in for their lunch which somewhat disrupted the group and distracted participants. Future groups were held in the library, when possible, to avoid clashing with mealtimes.

The group was designed to have a softer start whereby the participants settle into the session and introduced themselves over a tea or coffee. Following this I summarised and briefly explained what the group would entail and reiterated that they were free to withdraw from the group at any point. The group session was digitally recorded with full consent using a digital recorder, with a secondary device used as a redundancy. During the group, I also collected field notes to capture my initial thoughts and anything that stood out from the session.

A brief group guide was used to help steer the group conversation and to stay on topic (see Appendix 14). The group started with a brief icebreaker task before having a discussion on the group expectations and how we were going to work as a team. This served as a softer start to the group and allowed time for the participants to get to know each other. The group expectations were written down on a piece of flipchart paper as we were discussing them and included: respecting when other people speak, maintaining confidentiality, and feeling safe to share within the group space. These were not meant to be group rules per se but allowed us as a group to lay out our expectations from each other, and how we would work as a group going forward. Following this, we briefly revisited the topics of connection, and how families had used informal reminiscence during their visits, which were raised during the individual interviews

To begin the conversation on reminiscence, families were shown a short introductory video on reminiscence. This summarised what reminiscence is and why it is a common activity within care homes by exploring some of the key benefits such as focussing on preserved abilities and improving communication and connection. This was particularly relevant for this study as families highlighted in the interviews that this was something that they hoped to get

out of the study. Participants were then introduced to key principles of reminiscence such as the concept of person-centredness, taking a strengths-based approach, and focusing on memory sharing instead of factual accuracy. For families, this was important to bear in mind, as reminiscence is not meant to be quiz on memories or events, but instead should focus on sharing activities together, and connecting with loved ones by exploring the past.

Participants were also provided with a brief overview of dementia-positive communication. This was an important section as reminiscence is more effective with a gentle approach that gives people with dementia time to process what they are being asked. However, I was also mindful of presenting this in a way that did not make participants feel that they were previously visiting incorrectly. The video also briefly covered some common difficulties of reminiscence, particularly around not answering for the person with dementia, or trying to force reminiscence if they are not receptive. This was a crucial point as reminiscence is meant to be an enjoyable activity for everyone and only works when all parties involved participant willingly. The video ended by inviting participants to try a short reminiscence task during a visit by bringing in an object that held meaning to both them and their relative with dementia. The discussion after the video centred on the families' initial thoughts on reminiscence with a particular focus on the dementia-friendly communication tips that were presented. This led onto a discussion which centred on the ways in which we thought reminiscence could be used to maintain their connection with their loved ones before talking about the short reminiscence task and if the families had any initial thoughts on how they would do this.

The group ended with a brief reflection on how we found the first group and if anything could be done differently next time before arranging the next session. We also discussed a

communication strategy, to ensure that all participants were comfortable with me contacting them directly instead of through the care home.

5.4.4 Findings from first session

Following the same process as the interviews for transcription, a reflexive thematic analysis was conducted. The purpose of the groups was to further expand on the key themes raised in the individual interviews, and to introduce reminiscence in more detail. The first overarching theme was the idea of Connection with two sub themes: Informal reminiscence, and Importance of family involvement. The second theme was introducing reminiscence in more detail, and this had two sub-themes: countering the idea of “*visiting wrong*”, and the ways families envisioned using reminiscence in their visits. The last theme was the idea of Peer Support within the context of the group sessions and how families thought this could help them.

5.4.4.1 Connection

As the theme of Connection was prevalent throughout the interviews, I was interested in exploring this further with the group, within the context of reminiscence and family involvement.

5.4.4.1.1 Informal Reminiscence

Whilst it was clear from the interviews that participants did not have any prior experience of formal reminiscence, they all used it in various ways informally during their visits, even if they were not aware of it.

This idea was summarised by Participant Two who said that she did not realise how much she reminisced with her mother until we discussed it during her interview:

“I didn't even realise how much we reminisce until we spoke about it”

This was an important point for me to explore as I wanted families to see family-centred reminiscence as building on what they already do during visits and not something that was completely new or daunting. The conversation then moved onto the ways that the participants used aspects of reminiscence, or reminiscence-like activities with their relatives to connect with them during visits. Participant Two talked how she used a Life Story book to guide the conversation with her mother. This was done by bringing out the book, and she would tell her mother a *“little bit of a story about them”* which would lead onto further conversations. Responding to this, Participant One discussed how she used two different photo albums with her partner during her visits. The first album contained photographs from when her partner used to go hill walking around Scotland with a hillwalking group. This facilitated conversations around a hobby which he used to enjoy in addition to talking about the people he used to walk with. Participant One noted that whilst both did not always know who everyone was in the pictures, they both enjoyed discussing them. The second album contained family photographs, particularly ones of his sons growing up, and was named *“Family Man”*. However, whilst they both enjoy looking through this, he sometimes mistakes pictures of his son's mother with his partner which can be difficult for her at times. This was something to be mindful of when using reminiscence later in the study to minimise the risk of causing further confusion.

Continuing this conversation, Participants Two and Three discussed how they had an Irish themed afternoon tea with their mother with Irish food like seaweed, cheese, and sweets. They both commented on how this presented their mother with an opportunity to talk about growing up in Ireland and both were amazed at how much she was recalling and how

animated she was during this. Whilst Participant Two mentioned this during her interview, it was encouraging for the other group members to hear from a fellow participant that using aspects of reminiscence could easily be incorporated into a visit and have a positive impact on both them and their relative with dementia.

5.4.4.1.2 Importance of family involvement

The participants also discussed how crucial sustained family involvement was for both them and their loved one living in the home. Participant Three talked about how her mother was always very “*family orientated*” and liked having the family constantly around her. Therefore, they always try to mark family events within the care home to keep their mother involved in family life. Participant Two gave the example of how in the summer, they have birthday parties for their mother, and another family member would often bring his guitar to play Scottish and Irish folk music. This was something that their mother thoroughly enjoyed as music was a big part of their family life as their father was a piper. This showed how as a family, they try to keep their mother involved in family life as much as they can and aligned with the Senses of Belonging and Continuity raised in the Methodology chapter (Chapter Three, Section 3.8.2). When talking about family involvement, the conversation moved onto how this tied into visit frequency. Participant One mentioned how whilst her partner still recognises her, he does not always recognise his sons, as they cannot visit as often due to work commitments:

“[He] recognises me, but I don’t know if he recognises his son. I don’t know if that’s because I visit more and he’s working a lot.”

The group then discussed how families could be encouraged to visit more frequently, which could consequently strengthen their connection to their loved one living with dementia in the care home. This conversation presented a natural point in the wider discussion to introduce

remembrance and now this could be a potential means of encouraging frequent visits and enhanced connections with relatives.

5.4.4.2 *Introducing Remembrance*

As previously mentioned, a short ten-minute video was shown to introduce remembrance in more detail and to start the conversation on how this could be incorporated into their visits. As part of this, participants provided their feedback to the video once it was shown and remarked on how effective they found it. However, following the section on dementia-friendly communication, some participants believed that they had previously been visiting incorrectly, and I had to counter this to reassure them that they had not. The conversation then moved onto how the families think they could use remembrance themselves.

5.4.4.2.1 *“Visiting Wrong”*

After watching the practical tips and dementia-friendly communication sections of the video, some families then felt that they had been visiting “*wrong*” previously by not giving their relative enough time to process what was being said. For example, Participant Two commented on how she realised that they often talked “*at*” their mother instead of talking “*to*” her. This was something that I was acutely mindful of as I did not want participants leaving the group feeling like they were visiting incorrectly. Instead, this allowed for a discussion on how remembrance is a focused activity based on memory retrieval and requires a slower approach that provides the person with dementia time to think about what is in front of them. Furthermore, I was able to empathise with the group by sharing that as a carer of a parent with dementia myself, I knew and understood how difficult this can be at times. This also allowed me to demonstrate to the group that I was not coming in as a complete “*outsider*” but that I was also coming to the group as a carer myself, which aligned with the idea that we

could share as a group our thoughts and experiences without any judgement, a fundamental part of an action research study. The topic of insider/outsider researcher positionality was previously explored in Chapter Three, section 3.6, and will be further reflected on in Chapter Eight.

5.4.4.2.2 Ways to use reminiscence

The group also provided an opportunity for participants to share their initial thoughts on reminiscence and how they would use it during their visits. For example, Participant Four shared how him and his wife used to enjoy cooking together using a collection of cookery books:

“We could certainly enjoy doing that, it’s something we used to do a lot was cook together”

Therefore, he planned on bringing in a few books during a future visit for them to look through together, as whilst his wife was non-verbal, Participant Four believed that the act of looking at the pictures together could stimulate her and get a smile from her. During his interview, he emphasised how getting a smile from her improves his mood and helps to keep him connected to her.

Following an example of reminiscence in the video which centred on darning socks, Participants Two and Three mentioned how their mum used to enjoy knitting Icelandic style jumpers for them throughout their lives and as such thought that bringing in some wool and knitting needles could be an effective trigger for a reminiscence session as it would focus on a past hobby and also touch on the family aspect of it as well. During the conversation on the types of topics that could be effective, such as family events like birthdays and weddings,

Participant Two talked about how their mother does not remember their father and therefore talking about their wedding day would be unlikely to be an effective topic for them:

“For example, my mother’s wedding day, she doesn’t know my father so there’s not much point in bringing them in.”

This illustrates the potential benefits of a family-centred approach to reminiscence through empowering families to use it themselves, as they know their loved one better than anyone. When selecting effective trigger topics or objects, this insight can be invaluable and a key aspect of this approach to reminiscence as it allows participants to maintain and strengthen their connection to their loved one living in the care home.

5.4.4.3 Peer Support

When reflecting on how the group sessions could work for everyone going forward, participants raised how they felt the peer support aspect of the group could help them over the duration of the study. Participants One and Two shared how it was good to meet people in a similar position to themselves and how previously they did not have an opportunity to meet with other family visitors. Participant One stated that whilst she recognised participants Two and Three from “*coming in and out*” of the home, she “*didn’t know [them] to speak to*”. Building on this, Participant Two felt that “*It’s good to know other people in the same position*” and noted that the first session was “*nice and casual*”. This was something that could help throughout the study as participants were more likely to share their experiences if they felt relaxed in the groups. Furthermore, this could allow for peer-to-peer learning whereby participants share reminiscence tips with each other, allowing us to work together towards a shared goal as an action research group.

5.5 Chapter summary and how this led into Cycle Two

Cycle One was an exploratory cycle which sought to understand how families currently viewed their visits and to introduce the concept of reminiscence. Both the interviews and the group session highlighted the importance of maintaining familial connections and facilitating meaningful interactions between family visitors and their loved ones in the care home. Cycle One also demonstrated that although participants had no formal experience of reminiscence, they all used it informally, such as looking at family photographs, during their visits to connect with their loved ones. The cycle ended with participants being invited to try a short reminiscence task during an upcoming visit. This led into Cycle Two which centred on co-developing a family-centred approach to reminiscence which was rooted in reminiscence in action activities and the participants' experiences of using this during their visits.

Chapter Six – Cycle Two

This chapter will explore the research activities from Cycle Two and the findings from the group sessions and reminiscence-in-action activities. It will give an overview of the aims and objectives of the second action research cycle of this study, demonstrating how this was founded on the findings from Cycle One. Cycle Two was centred on three group sessions each with a different aim, which were interspersed with reminiscence-in action-activities with phone interviews. The revised methods and interview techniques are outlined for each session before exploring the findings and how this led into the following session. This chapter will end by focussing on the key findings of the cycle, and how this led into the third and final cycle.

6.1 Cycle Two Overview

Cycle Two was the largest of the three cycles of this study and had two overarching aims:

- to explore with family visitors, the benefits and practical application of using reminiscence techniques during their care home visits.
- to develop a collaborative approach to family-centred reminiscence which the families will trial during their visits.

As with Cycle One, whilst these are presented as two separate aims, they were achieved during the one process and were closely intertwined with each other. The first data activity of the cycle was a round of short semi-structured, qualitative, telephone interviews, which lasted for approximately 30 minutes. During the interviews, the same participants from Cycle One shared their experiences of doing a short reminiscence activity with their loved one during a

recent care home visit. In this short interview, participants were asked to discuss how they used reminiscence, how they selected a topic or item and why, where they had the session, how long it was, and how they finished it. This was repeated before each group session. The first group session of the cycle centred on a “time machine” activity, which allowed us to explore the reminiscence bump and the types of memories that are typically more effective for reminiscence activities. The second group session used an emotional touchpoints approach to discuss how participants felt before, during, and after a visit before using reminiscence. The emotional touchpoints approach was repeated for the last group session to determine if participants felt differently during visits after trying reminiscence. Diagram 10 below outlines the research activities for Cycle Two.

Diagram 10: Overview of Cycle Two Research Activities

6.1.2 Recruitment updates

Before Cycle Two commenced, Participant One withdrew from the study due to her loved one in the care home passing away. Whilst this was unexpected, procedures were in place for this situation. I met with my gatekeeper within the care home to discuss whether the other participants knew, and if not, how to approach this during the next group session. From this discussion, it was decided that participants would be told at the start of the first group session of the cycle as I wanted to be transparent about why the participant left whilst approaching it in a sensitive manner. When participants were notified, they shared that they suspected that this had happened as they noticed that they had not seen either Participant One or her relative in the home for a few weeks, and that they knew this was part of the reality of visiting in a care home.

Following Participant One withdrawing, two additional participants joined the study. Prior to them joining the sessions, I met with them individually to discuss the information sheets and the consent forms following the same procedure as Cycle One (see Section 4.3.2). During this meeting, the two participants were shown the short reminiscence video from the end of the first cycle to summarise what the group had discussed before they joined the study. Participant Five joined for the start of Cycle Two, and due to prior engagements, Participant Six joined from the second group session of the cycle. Table 5 provides an updated summary of the relationships between participants and residents living in the care home.

Table 5 - Participants' relationship to residents (Cycle Two)

Participant pseudonym	Relation to resident
Participant Two	Daughter
Participant Three	Daughter
Participant Four	Husband
Participant Five	Daughter
Participant Six	Brother

This added a different dynamic to the group as the sibling relationship might have meant that Participant Six had a different perspective on the visit experience which could have influenced how he used reminiscence during his visits. As outlined in Table 2 (see section 4.1), participant involvement fluctuated across the data activities conducted in Cycle Two. The first and second groups both involved four participants, and group three involved all five participants. Additionally, four participants engaged with the telephone interviews across Cycle Two.

6.2 First round of phone interviews and Time Machine group task

The first data collection activity of Cycle Two was a round of short, semi-structured individual telephone interviews with participants which centred on a recent visit during which they tried a short reminiscence activity with their loved one. A key advantage of telephone interviews is that they can be more time efficient than face-to-face interviews and can be seen as an efficient method to gather contextual information for studies (Block and Erskine, 2012; Sobo *et al.*, 2003). At the end of Cycle One, we made the pragmatic decision as a group to use telephone interviews as they were more convenient for the participants as it meant that we

could easily schedule an interview at a time that was convenient for them instead of scheduling an in-person interview to align with when they were visiting the care home. A disadvantage of telephone interviews is that non-verbal expressions such as facial expressions and body language cannot be observed, however, additional information can be gleaned from the voice and intonation used during the interview (Saarijärvi and Bratt, 2021).

Two weeks after the end of Cycle One, I sent out a short text message to participants asking if they had an opportunity to try reminiscence during a recent visit. We then arranged a suitable date and time for a short telephone interview to discuss their experience of using reminiscence and their thoughts on what worked well for them and their loved one. Three participants replied and interviews were arranged between December 2023 and February 2024 as participants had noted during the previous group session that late December and January was usually a busy time in the care home and suggested leaving any data collection activities until February. One interview was conducted mid-December, and the other two interviews were conducted mid-February and were approximately 15 minutes long. The phone interviews were recorded with permission by having my phone on loudspeaker with a digital voice recorder sitting alongside it. To reduce the risk of a breach of confidentiality, I ensured that I was in a private room with the door closed prior to phoning participants. The semi-structured interview guide was developed using the prompts for the reminiscence task provided at the end of Cycle One and is included in Appendix 15.

6.2.1 Findings from first round of telephone interviews

As with Cycle One, connections was a prevalent theme throughout the first round of telephone interviews for participants. During our conversations, participants shared how they

incorporated short reminiscence activities during their visits to enhance their connection with their loved ones living in the care home.

Participant Two shared how she used an Irish newspaper for the basis of her first reminiscence activity. This proved to be an effective trigger for her mother as she used to read an Irish newspaper every Sunday and by showing the newspaper to her mother, a conversation occurred which centred on her mother's childhood experiences of living on a farm. This was prompted by a page in the newspaper which contained a story about a farmer and had a picture of a farmer with sheep behind him, which led to a discussion on Participant Two's grandfather who had a farm:

"...it just got from better and better because we started then talking about all the animals that used to be on the farm.... So, we had a great talk about that and then some of it was in Gaelic and my mum was reading it in Gaelic ...but ehm, it was really lovely, and we read that paper from top to bottom, every bit we could you know what I mean..."

This demonstrated how a seemingly small activity, like looking at a newspaper, was able to spark a full conversation using aspects of reminiscence, which allowed families to connect with their loved one. Participant Two stated that she felt that this marked a "*wee kinda breakthrough*" as her mother was understanding what they were discussing and was animated and engaged throughout the half an hour activity.

Participant Three discussed how she used knitting for her reminiscence activity, which was partly inspired by the example of darning socks in the reminiscence video at the end of Cycle One as this highlighted how hobbies and interests can be preserved throughout a dementia diagnosis. Participant Three mentioned how her mother was always a great knitter, but she

had not tried it since she moved into the care home four years ago. For her short reminiscence task, Participant Three brought in a piece of knitting which was already started with a few rows, for their mother to continue with.

Despite having not knitted for several years, her mother managed to successfully knit for around ten minutes:

“...my mum still was a good knitter cause she only had dropped one stitch, so that was a big thing], you know”

Whilst the success of the activity was not gauged by the quality of the knitting, Participant Three felt encouraged by seeing her mother complete an activity which she used to thoroughly enjoy before the care home. Furthermore, this demonstrated how reminiscence could be used in various ways with the one resident, as Participants Two and Three both took different approaches in their activities with their mother, yet still both managed to keep her engaged throughout.

Participant Four discussed how he used reminiscence with his wife during a visit on the lead up to Christmas by bringing in a few cookery books and going through the motions of planning a Christmas meal together. He mentioned that he chose this as an anchor topic as it was an activity that they used to do together every year:

“[Wife] and I used to kind of sit down and decide what we were going to have for Christmas, you know starters, main courses, that kind of stuff, so that’s what I did.”

He felt that it would be something that would be familiar to her that both would enjoy. As he previously mentioned, his wife is non-verbal and relies on facial responses as a means of communication. Despite this communication barrier, he used the short activity as a way of

reminiscing about the meals that they used to make together. As there was a limited response from his wife, the activity was brief and lasted around ten minutes after coming to “*some form of conclusion*”, however, Participant Four still felt that it was a “*worthwhile session*” as it presented an opportunity to connect with his wife through reminiscence and had “*a lot of fun out of that*”. Whilst this was not a traditional form of reminiscence, it illustrated how families could use the principles of reminiscence as a means of enhancing their connection to their loved one by incorporating a short reminiscence activity into their visits.

This initial round of short phone interviews suggested that reminiscence was an activity which was easily incorporated into family visits and had a positive impact on family’s experience of visiting their loved ones. However, this also raised the question on if participants were completing a “shared activity” with their loved one, instead of a “pure” reminiscence activity, and if this mattered for families. At this stage of the study, I felt that families were adopting the principles of reminiscence to develop their own approach which worked for them and their loved one in the care home. This was the priority for me as I did not want families to become overwhelmed in trying to use reminiscence during their visits, instead I wanted this to be an enjoyable activity which they could share and help to maintain their connection to their loved one.

6.2.2 Methods used for the Time Machine Activity.

Following the initial round of phone interviews, the first group session of the cycle focussed on a “Time Machine” activity to gently prompt us a group to think about the types of memories that are generally more effective for reminiscence. There were three objectives for this group session:

- To summarise what we did during the Cycle One.
- To reflect on the first reminiscence task.
- To discuss the reminiscence bump and how this could inform our approach.

6.2.2.1 Focus Group Methods

Cycle Two used the same focus group process as the previous cycle (see Chapter Four, Section 4.4.2) with the aim of meeting the three objectives outlined above. The group session was centred on a “time machine” style activity as a way of gently prompting the group to think about the type of memories that might be most effective for their loved one. Additionally, the purpose of the group was to bring participants together to share the ways that they used reminiscence during their visits and how they could learn from each other to try using reminiscence in different ways.

6.2.2.2 What is the Time Machine?

The time machine can be an effective analogy to demonstrate how memory deteriorates with dementia and has been previously used to help care staff understand what is happening and to find ways to support people with dementia (Mackenzie, Smith, and James, 2015). For most people, their earliest memories begin at around three to five years of age, and the events that are easiest to recall tend to be associated with heightened emotions such their first day of school, meeting their partner, and their first job.

People who do not have memory problems, generally display a “recall gradient”, meaning that recent events are typically recalled better than older ones, except for significant emotional memories (Mackenzie, Smith, and James, 2015). However, the recall gradient is often disrupted by dementia as recent events becoming increasingly difficult to recall, despite this,

emotional or significant memories from the past are more easily recalled. As dementia progresses, the inability to make new memories can often cause a “*time-shift*” as people living with dementia gradually lose the ability to recall recent events, their current reality will start to blend with earlier memories eventually leading to their perception of reality to shift back in time (Mackenzie, Smith, and James, 2015). This time-shift is typically referred to as “last in first out”, whereby, they might first forget that they have moved into a care home, then that their spouse has died or that they have retired and so on. Whilst this is not a uniform experience, the time machine is an effective analogy to illustrate how dementia can typically impact memory recall. The time machine utilises a timeline to illustrate this and asks people to look back on their lives and start listing milestone events from their earliest memories to the present. The completed timeline represents the common phases of a person’s life from relationships, employment, significant life events, up to the move into a care home (Mackenzie, Smith, and James, 2015). During the activity, it is highlighted that these memories or significant events are associated with heightened emotions and that highly emotive memories are the most readily recalled, even with a dementia diagnosis. As the activity goes on, events on the timeline are crossed off starting with the most recent, demonstrating that recent memories are the first to be affected by dementia. As this occurs over a time gradient, earlier memories are often well preserved and form the main source of information for individuals who are “*time-shifted*” (Mackenzie, Smith, and James, 2015). This activity can be a useful way for families to understand why their loved ones are exhibiting behaviours and to understand how dementia affects the storage and retrieval of memories.

6.2.2.3 Research methods used

There was no variation from the planned methods outlined above. The group session was conducted in the library in the study site as I knew from Cycle One that this was a quiet room

free from distractions. Like in Cycle One, the group had a softer start whereby we talked as a group over tea and coffee which provided an opportunity for Participant Five to be introduced to the group and get settled before we got started. A semi-structured guide used for this session (see Appendix 16) to help steer the group conversation and to support the delivery of the time machine activity.

The group session opened with a recap of Cycle One and was highly beneficial for all of us as it allowed us to remind ourselves of what we did, and how this led into Cycle Two. This was helpful for Participant Five, as it provided her with an overview of the previous group activities and the plan for going forward. The second objective of the group asked participants to reflect on the reminiscence activity, whilst this was partly accomplished by the phone interviews, I felt that it was also important that this was shared in the group setting as it would provide participants with an opportunity to learn from each other and build on the peer support aspect of the group which was highlighted in Cycle One. A “Time Machine” activity was used to facilitate a discussion into the ‘reminiscence bump’ and how this could inform our approach to reminiscence going forwards.

6.2.3 Findings from group one

Following the same process as Cycle One, the group session was transcribed, and a reflexive thematic analysis was conducted. The purpose of the group was to reflect on the short reminiscence activity, and to complete the time machine activity as a group. The first overarching theme centred on the practical application and benefits of using reminiscence during a visit, this had two sub-themes: how families used reminiscence, and the impact this had on them and their loved one. The second theme was the Time Machine activity, which was the focus of the group. This facilitated a conversation on the participants’ own memories

which then allowed them to utilise the same approach for their loved ones, and how this could inform future reminiscence activities. The theme of Peer Support, and how the groups could provide an opportunity for shared learning and mutual support ran through the session and. This was continuing theme from Cycle One, highlighting how important it was for families.

6.2.3.1 Reflection on Reminiscence Task

Whilst the initial round of phone interviews asked participants to individually reflect on the first reminiscence task, I wanted to incorporate a discussion on reminiscence into the group session to provide an opportunity for shared learning. I hoped that by sharing how they each used reminiscence, they could share tips about what worked for them and pool their ideas together. This also aligned with the peer support aspect of the groups which participants highlighted in Cycle One.

Participant Four started the conversation by sharing how he had used cookery books during a visit prior to Christmas for a short reminiscence task based on planning a Christmas meal with his wife. Whilst this was the same activity that he reflected on during the phone interview, it was beneficial for the group to hear how reminiscence could be adapted for use with a loved one who was unable to communicate verbally. Additionally, the group encouraged him by saying that the activity was still successful if he felt that he got something from it:

Participant Two: *“Well, you know, even if you’re getting something good from it [Participant Four]”.*

Additionally, the conversation then moved onto how Participant Four assists the staff with his wife’s breakfast and medication six days a week, and how this helps him to communicate with her:

Participant Four: Oh totally, you're communicating, you're communicating in some way.

Participant Two: You're talking away whilst you're doing it.

Participant Four: Like "this porridge is shite today, [wife].

[laughs]

This short exchange demonstrated how families can adapt their visits to meet the needs of their loved one and try to remain connected for as long as possible. Following this, Participant Three shared how she had brought in some knitting for her mother to do during a recent visit as it was something that she used to do before she moved into the home. During this conversation, it was mentioned that her mother had not knitted for at least ten years despite this, she only dropped one stitch, which surprised the group:

Participant Four: That's marvellous. That's a skill, the coordination in that is amazing. That's brilliant.

Participant Five: That's really good.

Again, this highlights the peer support participants received from the group and how they encouraged each other when they shared their experiences of using reminiscence. This was a beneficial conversation for Participant Five as it demonstrated how past hobbies can be effective triggers for reminiscence and serve as a means of connecting with loved ones. All three participants shared that they enjoyed using reminiscence during their visits, with Participant Two stating that she was "*dead happy because it was more of an engaging time that we'd normally have*". This captured the aim of the study as I wanted families to have a

range of activities based on the principles of reminiscence that they could do with their loved one that kept them engaged and connected after the move to a care home.

The main purpose of this reflection was for participants to hear how the rest of the group incorporated aspects of reminiscence into their visits and provide an opportunity for peer learning. The reflections from participants demonstrated how aspects of reminiscence could be incorporated into enjoyable visit activities to facilitate meaningful connections. Whilst she did not have the opportunity to try using reminiscence prior to the group session, Participant Five shared how she was planning on using reminiscence when she visited her mother. As her mother was a devout Catholic before she moved into the care home, her religion was an influencing factor for selecting trigger objects for a future reminiscence session:

Participant Five: Well, I've been looking at old Catholic books that my mum had and there was one of the Pope that was one of her favourites so.

This was encouraging to hear as despite only joining the study a few days before the group, she was already engaged and enthusiastic about how she could use reminiscence to have a more meaningful connection with her mother. This was something that she was struggling with during her visits as she mentioned to the group that her mother would sometimes try to bite her if she tried to touch her:

Participant Five: And she bites, because if you go near her, she doesn't like getting touched or anything like that. So, this is how it's hard for us.

However, Participant Five hoped to overcome this and aimed to give her mother a hand massage which gave her a goal to work towards over the duration of the study.

6.2.3.2 Time Machine Activity

After reflecting on the first reminiscence task, we moved onto the time machine activity and discussed the types of memories that could be effective for reminiscence. This activity had two parts. First, we completed the time machine activity, using the participants' own timeline which led into a conversation on their own childhood and life events to illustrate how emotionally charged memories are often the strongest. Following this, we then used the completed timeline and discussed how this could inform future reminiscence activities.

The Time Machine Activity was started by asking the group what their earliest memory was, and this led onto a conversation about games that the participants used to play in school:

Participant Four: *I remember playing marbles against a wall all the way walking from my house to primary school*

We then discussed moving into the family home, and what participants remember. Participants Two and Three shared their memories of moving from a tenement to what would become their family home:

Participant Two: *[Participant 3], do you remember when we left the tenements, and we moved, and the new house had a bath and, in the tenements, we never had a bath, and I thought it was-*

Participant Three: *Luxury*

[...]

Participant Five: *That was a luxury back then.*

Completing the timeline together as a group allowed me to demonstrate the longevity of emotional memories before we moved to the "time machine" section of the activity.

Additionally, this activity helped to further bond the group together through reminiscing and sharing memories from their childhood. We then completed the time machine activity as a group to illustrate how memory retrieval is impacted by dementia and how this could explain some behaviours exhibited by people living with dementia. We discussed how people living with dementia might forget that they have moved into the care home or that they retired from their job, which could explain some patterns of behaviour. The conversation then moved onto how this could impact how participants' loved ones viewed themselves. This was an interesting conversation as participants shared how their loved ones were sometimes unable to recognise themselves in family photographs and how this influenced the pictures that they could use for reminiscence activities:

Participant Five: I showed my mum a picture of her from when she was a wee girl, and she didn't want to see it. She was like "take that away, I don't want to see that".

Participant Three: Mum probably wouldn't recognise herself if we showed her a picture of when she was younger. We could tell her, and she'd just laugh probably, don't you think?

This further demonstrated how dementia can act like a "time machine" with people living with dementia thinking that they are in a different period in their lives and cannot always recognise pictures of themselves or loved ones as that does not match up with their reality. As part of this, I shared with the group my own experiences of this whilst caring for a parent with dementia, which worked as an example of how this can impact not only the person living with dementia but also their family. This had the additional benefit of building on the mutual trust which was integral for action research as I was not asking the group to share anything that I would not be comfortable sharing myself. Lastly, we discussed how emotion-based memories,

and the time machine analogy could inform future reminiscence activities. Participants Three and Five talked about using their respective parents' wedding day pictures during a future reminiscence activity:

Participant Three: *Yeah, yeah. We could show her a picture of her wedding day; we've never really showed her anything like that.*

Participant Five: *We done that with mum. Dad brought a picture up and they're outside the church...He brought that up to show her and she's just looking at it, you know, didn't know what to say.*

This was particularly beneficial for Participant Three as during Cycle One she shared that her mother does not recognise pictures of her father anymore, which was something that she hoped reminiscence could change. As part of this, Participants Two and Three talked about using a picture of the Singers sewing machine factory as that was where their parents met with Participant Three sharing how their mother still reacts to images of the factory clock tower:

Participant Three: *We've got a big picture of the Singer's clock that my dad bought her. It's in her room and she still looks up at it and says "Singers". Singer's is a reminiscence [trigger] for my mum I would say.*

This further illustrated how the Time Machine activity could inform the group's approach to family centred reminiscence by focussing on emotions-based memories or key events in the person living with dementia's timeline. The discussion was potentially helpful for Participant Five in particular as the group were sharing ideas on how they could use reminiscence activities during visits. The time-machine activity was a successful educational element of the

study which empowered family caregivers to use reminiscence. A fundamental part of this was exploring the types of memories that participants could explore using reminiscence and the trigger objects or topics that could facilitate this. Additionally, whilst Mackenzie, Smith, and James (2015) explored how the time machine activity helped staff in care settings to understand dementia, this study demonstrated how this could also be used with families to explore how reminiscence can be a tool to meaningfully connect to their loved ones with dementia.

The group session ended by planning a date for the next meeting and asking the group if the phone interviews on reminiscence were still convenient for them. Participants were also asked to try another short reminiscence activity with their loved one based on what we discussed during the group.

6.3 Second round of phone interviews and first Emotional Touchpoints session

Prior to the second group session of the cycle, I conducted another round of short, semi-structured interviews, using the same process and interview guide as the initial round of interviews. Three interviews were carried out between February and March 2024, one with Participant Two, and two with Participant Five, and lasted for an average of 25 minutes. Only two participants had used reminiscence since the previous group session, which resulted in a shorter round of interviews. As with the first round of phone interviews, the second round asked participants about a recent visit in which they had used reminiscence and their experiences of using it with their loved one.

6.3.1 Findings from second round of telephone interviews

During the second round of telephone interviews, participants shared how they had further incorporated reminiscence into their visits to enhance and strengthen their connection to their loved ones in the care home.

Over the course of two telephone interviews, Participant Five discussed her attempts at using reminiscence to connect with her mother and how her approach to reminiscence changed. Participant Five's first attempt at using reminiscence was inspired by the timeline and time machine activities from the first group and centred on her childhood with her mother. However, the approach that she used was arguably not reminiscence based as it involved asking her mother a series of questions without the use of trigger object. She reported that her mother was able to answer a few questions but found the activity upsetting:

“So, she was able to answer some but not able to answer some other ones so. I think she was finding that part hard and she was just saying that she couldn't talk and then she burst out crying”

Although Participant Five was enthusiastic about using reminiscence, the use of questions without accompanying trigger objects had the opposite effect than she was aiming for. She mentioned that she felt that there is a “*disconnection*” between them which was making visiting her mother a difficult experience and thought that reminiscence could be a way to bridge this gap. Whilst simply asking questions is not reminiscence, it could be seen as an integral part of developing Participant Five's understanding of reminiscence, and more importantly what works well for her mother. By the end of our conversation on how trigger objects could elicit more of a reaction from her mother, Participant Five's understanding of reminiscence shifted, and she said that she would bring in family photographs to gauge her

mother's reaction in a future visit. Interestingly, despite the initial teething problems with using reminiscence, Participant Five noted that she was beginning to feel more confident about visiting her mother as she had *"something that [she] can base things on"*.

Participant Five shared that after changing her approach to reminiscence, she was able to better connect with her mother during visits. In one visit, Participant Five used her mobile phone to show her mother family photographs as she thought that this would be easier for her eyesight than a printed photograph. This was an improvement from the previous interview as not only did Participant Five use photographs as a trigger object, but she also adapted to meet her mother's abilities, drawing on the strengths-based approaches from the introductory video on reminiscence (see Chapter Five). As the visit went on, Participant Five continued to get a positive reaction from her mother:

"I was really getting some quite good responses to some of the pictures...She was listening, and she was being attentive."

By using a trigger object as the basis for her reminiscence activities Participant Five elicited a more positive reaction from her mother and in turn had a more enjoyable visit. During a Mother's Day visit, Participant Five was able to give her mother a hand massage and put a new scarf around her neck, a stark difference to how she described her mother's reactions during the previous group session. This was also an aimed outcome that she wanted to achieve over the course of the study as she hoped that reminiscence could be a way to make her mother more comfortable around her. Participant Five explained how she feels that there is *"a little bit of a connection"* and that during a recent visit her mother mentioned that she was *"really glad [she] was here"* indicating that she was beginning to bridge the disconnect that she indicated in her first interview.

Participant Two shared how music-based reminiscence was an effective way for her to connect with her mother. During a recent visit, she supported her mother to go to a St Patricks Day music event in the care home. Whilst this was a group reminiscence session, I thought it would be beneficial to hear about her experience and how her mother engaged with music-based reminiscence. Participant Two stated that music effectively improved her mother's mood which prompted further exploration of music-based reminiscence:

"She cheered up like nothing on Earth, so now I just think music is the best thing on this Earth for you know, cheering people up."

Participant Two also shared that prior to her mother's dementia diagnosis, they would have nights in the family home listening to tapes of old Irish and Scottish music. This further adds credence to this use of music for future reminiscence sessions as it was something they used to enjoy together as a family. The effectiveness of music-based reminiscence suggested to Participant Two that music could be a way for her to *"bring [her] mother back to remember [her] dad"* as both Participants Two and Three have stated that their mother cannot recognise photographs of their father. Therefore, Participant Two was interested in possibly trying Scottish bagpipe music during a future visit to gauge her mother's reaction before showing her a photograph of her father. This further supports a family-centred approach to reminiscence as families can effectively select topics, such as folk music in this instance, and use this to meaningfully engage and connect with their loved one.

The second round of phone interviews further demonstrated how reminiscence could be incorporated in differing ways during family visits which both the participant and their loved one enjoyed. The first interview with Participant Five also illustrated the issues that can arise by overwhelming the person living with dementia with too many questions. However, it was

encouraging to hear how she had learned from this and had some positive visits using reminiscence which helped to increase her belief in herself and her abilities. It was also interesting to hear how effective music was as a trigger for Participant Two and her mother through the emotional links to her mother's childhood in Ireland and later life in the family home. This further highlights the benefits of a family-centred approach as families may have an insight into their loved one's history which is instrumental in selecting effective triggers for reminiscence.

6.3.2 Emotional Touchpoints Methods

Following the second round of phone interviews, the next group session of the cycle focussed on an Emotional Touchpoints Activity to assess how participants felt at key points of the visit experience. There were three objectives for this group session:

- To summarise what we did during the last group
- To reflect on the how participants have continued to use reminiscence.
- To complete the first Emotional Touchpoints activity.

Emotional Touchpoints is an interviewing technique which seeks to explore an individual's experience in a structured way by centring on emotions. This is achieved by focussing on key neutral events, or "touchpoints", in an experience whereby participants are asked to reflect on their experiences and select from a range of emotion words or phrases which summarise how they felt at each point and explain why they selected it (Macbride, Miller, and Dewar, 2017). Additionally, blank cards are available if participants want to select a word that is not in the pre-prepared collection (Dewar *et al.*, 2009). By applying emotional touchpoints to assess the patient experience of hospitals, Dewar *et al.* (2009) argued that this presented

patients with the opportunity to discuss what they saw as potential solutions to issues that they previously raised, helping patients to co-design improvements to services, rather than passively providing information. Furthermore, hospital staff highlighted the following benefits of adopting emotional touchpoints to learn about patient and family experiences:

- Helps patients and families to get in touch with their own experience.
- Challenges assumptions about what staff feel is important to patients and their families.
- Enables development of relationships with patients, families and staff.
- Helps people to see in a balanced way both positive and negative aspects of experiences.
- Helps patients and families to be involved in shaping and improving the service.
- Helps to redress the power imbalance between interviewer and service user (Dewar *et al.*, 2009).

Several of these benefits align with the key tenets of collaborative action research, and wider action research. For example, addressing the power imbalance between the interviewer and service user is consistent with the democratic nature of action research outlined previously in this thesis (Chapter Three, section 3.6) which supported the use of emotional touchpoints for this study. Furthermore, challenging assumptions about how families feel about visits was instrumental in understanding their feelings towards the use of reminiscence during their visits. Building on this, it was important to get a balanced view of their experiences to understand the positive and negative aspects of their visit experience to determine if reminiscence affected this in any way.

6.3.2.1 Emotional Touchpoints process

For the emotional touchpoints activity, I followed an amended version process set out by Dewar *et al* (2009). This involved two stages: developing the materials and carrying out the discussion.

The first stage of this process centred on developing the materials that would be used during the emotional touchpoints sessions. The three touchpoints identified for this study were “before a visit”, “during a visit”, and “after a visit” and were selected as they are key emotional moments in the visit experience. The literature explored in Chapter Two, Section 2.7.1, and conversations with my participants highlighted that visiting a care home can include a range of emotions with some families dreading visiting, and others looking forward to them. Furthermore, Chapter Two illustrated that families can experience heightened feelings of guilt if a visit did not go as well as they expected due to being unable to make a “*meaningful connection*” with their loved one (Statz *et al.*, 2021, p10). Therefore, these touchpoints were selected to explore how families felt about their visits before they started to use reminiscence and determine if reminiscence had helped them to have more positive experiences of visiting their loved ones.

The words and phrases used for the emotion cards were primarily gathered from the transcripts from previous data collection activities in the study supplemented by the findings of the literature review (Chapter Two). The full list of words used is included in Appendix 17. Previous transcripts were used to generate the words and phrases as I wanted to be led the participants’ own experiences and not by any assumptions that I might have had about how families feel about their visits. After refinement, three phrases were removed which are

highlighted on the list. The final list of words was then written on flashcards to be used during the group session.

The second stage of this process centred on conducting the discussion with participants. Whilst emotional touchpoints are typically used in one-to-one settings, such as individual interviews (Dewar *et al*, 2009; MacBride, Miller, and Dewar, 2020), this approach was adapted to be used within group settings for this study. Emotional touchpoints were used during two group sessions as a way of facilitating a wider group discussion on how participants felt at key points of the visit experience and how reminiscence could be used to improve this.

During the sessions, participants were invited to discuss their visit experience with the group and share how they felt throughout their visits. For each touchpoint, the flashcards containing words or phrases linked to emotions were laid out on a table. Participants were asked if they wanted to add any additional words or phrases that were not on the table and blank flashcards were available to add these. Participants were then asked to spend 60 seconds selecting one or two flashcards which they felt resonated with how they felt during a typical visit with their loved one. The group were then invited to share why they selected their cards, and how this related to their visit experience. This was repeated for the second emotional touchpoints session to examine if participants had more positive visits with their loved ones and enhanced their connections after using reminiscence.

6.3.2.2 Research methods used

There was no variation from the planned methods previously outlined and I followed the same process as the last session to allow Participant Six to be introduced to the group. After this, I outlined what we would cover during the session and reminded participants that they were free to withdraw at any time. The group session was recorded using a digital voice recorder

supplemented by field notes. The primary and redundancy recorders were set up and turned on prior to participants arriving, however the chat with participants was not included in the transcript. A semi-structured guide (see Appendix 18) was used to guide the discussion and to support the delivery of the emotional touchpoints portion of the session. As with the previous group, I followed the same process as Cycle One for transcription and conducted a reflexive thematic analysis.

6.3.3 Findings from group two

The purpose of the group was to further reflect on how the study participants had used reminiscence since the last group session, and to complete the first emotional touchpoints activity. The first overarching theme built on the findings from the previous group session and centred on the practical application and benefits of reminiscence. The second theme centred on the first emotional touchpoints activity. Participants were asked to reflect on their visits before they started using reminiscence and select the emotion card that resonated with how they felt before, during, and after a typical visit. This activity was then repeated during the next group to determine if participants felt differently towards visits after using reminiscence. Additionally, this allowed Participants Five and Six to share their experiences of visiting their loved one prior to joining the study as they joined after the individual interviews were completed. The theme of Peer Support was also prevalent with shared learning and participants supporting each other, further demonstrating how important this was for families.

6.3.3.1 Reflections on Reminiscence Task

As with the previous group session, the group opened with a short reflection on how the participants had used reminiscence within their visits. Whilst this was partly covered in the

phone interviews, it was beneficial for us to discuss this as a group and to provide participants with an opportunity to learn from each other and further explore how reminiscence could be used in various ways. Additionally, this allowed Participant Six to hear more about reminiscence and begin to think about how he could incorporate this into his visits with his sister.

Participant Five opened the discussion by sharing how she had adapted her approach to reminiscence to meet her mother's abilities by using her mobile phone to show her family photographs from her 21st birthday. Whilst this was the same reminiscence activity that we discussed during her second phone interview, it has helpful for the rest of the group to hear about how reminiscence can be used in a strengths-based way. Furthermore, the group were supportive and shared her enthusiasm when she talked about how she got a positive reaction from the task:

Participant Two: That's fabulous, do you feel like this is something that hadn't happened before, [Participant Five]?

Participant Five: Well, aye, this has been a big change in her.

This exchange further illustrates the inherent peer support from the group sessions, and highlights how a supportive environment also allowed participants to share the aspects of visiting that they struggle with:

Participant Five: But that was the day she was completely lost and was trying to get out of the bed. It was really distressing.

It was encouraging to see how the group rallied round each other and empathised with each other's experiences. This also provided an opportunity for the group to share advice and tips with each other.

Following this, Participant Three shared how she tried speaking to her mother in Irish Gaelic during a few visits, as this was her mother's only language for the first 20 years of her life. This was an effective reminiscence trigger as it built on previous reminiscence activities which were centred on her mother's childhood in Ireland. However, this was not without difficulties as Participants Two and Three mentioned that for a few weeks, their mother was only communicating in Irish:

Participant Two: *She had a few weeks when she was only speaking [Irish] Gaelic.*

[crosstalk]

Participant Three: *But now she started to talk more [Irish] Gaelic than she ever did, she, she might end up losing her English.*

The conversation between Participants Two and Three highlights that whilst the use of Irish Gaelic was an effective trigger for reminiscence sessions, it had an unforeseen impact on the rest of their visits for a few weeks. This could be partly explained by the fact that as this was their mother's first language, the ability to communicate Irish Gaelic may be better preserved as dementia progresses than her ability to use English. This recalls the Time Machine analogy from the previous group session as Irish Gaelic was their mother's sole language for much of her formative years. Despite this, both participants were able to communicate with their mother, and Participant Two later discussed how their mother thoroughly enjoyed a Saint Patrick's Day event that was held in the care home. Whilst this was the same visit that we

discussed earlier during her phone interview; it was interesting to hear about it again within the context of the difficulties that they had with communicating with their mother in English. This reiterated the effectiveness of music, not only as a reminiscence trigger, but also a means of lifting her mother's mood. This also resonated with the experience of Participant Six, as whilst he did not have an opportunity to try reminiscence prior to the session, he talked about how music is effective for his sister:

Participant Six: *Well, I've never heard my sister sing in her life, never in her life. See that wee group I mentioned, she sings along with them. Old Scottish songs they sing.*

Despite never hearing her sing prior her moving to the care home, he would regularly hear his sister singing Scottish folk songs with a small group of residents. This was particularly powerful for the group to hear as he had previously mentioned that his sister's dementia was quite advanced which limited the activities that he could do with her and shows how music and reminiscence can be used to forge connections by focussing on what people with dementia can still do, instead of focussing on the abilities that they have lost.

6.3.3.2 Emotional Touchpoints Activity

Following this, the group moved onto the emotional touchpoints activity which asked participants to reflect on their visits before they started using reminiscence and discuss how they felt at key points of the visit. For this session, I asked participants to think about how they felt before, during, and after a visit.

6.3.3.2.1 Before a visit

For the first touchpoint, I had eight flashcards with various emotions on them for participants to select with blank cards available if they wanted to add additional ones. These emotions were: apprehensive, looking forward to it, feeling down, duty-bound, excited, relaxed, upset,

and reluctant. Participants were asked to spend 30 seconds looking at the cards and select the card that most resonated with their experience or add another emotion to the table. After this time had elapsed, Participant Five asked for “accepting whatever happens” to be added to the table as she felt that:

“Even if it’s a bad day, we should accept it and accept that person has dementia and whatever that visit is going to be, it’s going to be”.

This was added to the list as I wanted the emotional touchpoints to be led by the participants’ own words and experiences. Picture 1 illustrates the emotions that were selected by participants which best reflected how they typically felt before a visit before they tried reminiscence.

Picture 1: Emotions Before a Visit (prior to reminiscence)

When asked what card he selected, Participant Six stated that:

“I don’t have any feelings in the sense of worrying about my sister, or anything else. I don’t think about her all week, I come up here, come in, and I accept whatever I get when I come in. Doesn’t bother or worry me, it’s part of life”.

Whilst he was worried about coming across as “cold”, the other participants in the group reassured him that this was a “brilliant attitude” to have as it showed that he was confident in the care that his sister was receiving and that he was not worried or apprehensive about what reaction he might get during a visit.

Participant Two shared that she often actively looks forward to visit, acknowledging that they might not always go to plan:

“I would say that I look forward to it sometimes... I always love to see my mum, I'm not always going to say it's going to be a great visit, but I always want to see her”.

This echoed the theme of Connection from Cycle One as simply the act of seeing her mother was motivation for Participant Two to regularly visit the home. It was reassuring to hear Participant Two acknowledge that whilst visits might not always go well, she always feels connected to her mother and actively looks forward to visiting her. Participant Two also noted that she had experienced every emotion that was on the table at some point before a visit since her mother had moved to the care home but that anticipating visits was an overarching feeling.

Conversely, both Participants Three and Five discussed their struggles with aspects of their visits. Participant Three stated that she had experienced all the emotions on the table at various points however, she ultimately selected “feeling down” as whilst she enjoys visiting her mother, she noted that watching her mother’s dementia advance was understandably

difficult. Participant Five stated that she often felt upset about visiting her mother whilst simultaneously feeling duty-bound to maintain regular visits.

“You know, feeling upset about having to go...You’re also duty bound, you feel duty bound to do it, you know.”

The idea of feeling “duty-bound” fuelled her struggles with visiting as she felt that she had to visit her mother instead of wanting to visit her. Furthermore, this also made her feel that she had complete activities during her visits, like giving her mother a hand massage, as she felt that needed to pay back her for looking after her throughout childhood and being unable to complete activities further added to her stress.

6.3.3.2.2 During a visit

I had 18 flashcards for the second touchpoint, which asked participants to reflect on how they felt during a typical visit. As with the first touchpoint, participants were asked to spend 30 seconds looking at the cards before selecting the one that captured how they felt, and Picture 2 below shows the range of emotions which participants selected.

Picture 2: Emotions During a Visit (prior to reminiscence)

Participant Three discussed how she always felt loved during her visits whilst recognising that her mother might not always remember that the visit:

"I'll take "feel loved by mum", she's happy to see us ...Even if she'll forget we were there 10 minutes later, but she is happy to see us."

It was heartening to hear she acknowledged that the love and connection is still preserved despite the dementia. This also aligned with the goal of using family-centred reminiscence as Participant Three focussed on the in-the-moment connections and spending meaningful time with her mother, instead of dwelling on the trajectory of the disease. Continuing with the theme of connections, Participant Two stated that she felt that both "happy" and "feeling connected" resonated with her experience:

“Feeling connected or happy. Well, I’m always happy to see mum it makes me happy to see her, it really does.”

As with her response to the first emotional touchpoint, Participant Two explains that even if a visit does not go to plan, or is a bit difficult, she is still happy to see her mother and feel connected to her. This encourages her to visit regularly as she worries about her mother if she does not have that frequent interaction that often lifts her spirits. Participant Five captured the often-contradictory nature of visiting her mother at the home as she selected both “sad and “joyful”:

“Because of how the day's actually going during the visit, you know, so you could be sad during the visit, or you could be really joyful during the visit”.

This was an interesting response as it demonstrated how Participant Five’s mood was influenced by the visit. This encouraged her to strive for more “joyful” visits as it helped her to remain connected to her mother and feel more involved in her care. Additionally, Participant Five wanted to select “Being Positive” as an overarching emotion for her as she endeavoured to keep looking on the positive side of visits which helped her to feel more confident in her abilities to visit and help care for her mother.

Participant Six shared how he felt at home during visits. Whilst this theme was raised in Cycle One as viewing the care home as their loved one’s home, Participant Six perspective differed slightly:

“Because I do feel at home. My sister is here, and my daughter [works] here, you know.”

He explained that he felt at home whenever he visited as visits were deeply intertwined with his family life. This also meant that he frequently visited his sister most days as he would spend

time with her whilst he was waiting for his daughter to finish her shift. This was an interesting angle to consider as it suggested that his visits were often unplanned and revolved around his daughter's shift pattern. This could also further explain why he mentioned in the previous emotional touchpoint that he never worried about his sister as his daughter was directly involved in her care.

6.3.3.2.3 After a visit

The last emotional touchpoint centred on how participants felt after a normal visit and participants were asked to spend 30 seconds looking at the cards before either selecting the one that resonated with their experience. Picture 3 below shows the range of emotions which participants selected which captured how they felt after a typical visit.

Picture 3: Emotions After a Visit (prior to reminiscence)

Participant Five started the conversation by asking if “mixed feelings” could be added table and ultimately, this was the card that she selected. This built on her responses to the previous

emotional touchpoint and further highlights how a visit can involve several contradictory feelings as seen in the previous responses. Continuing with this idea, Participant Two selected two cards which captured how she typically felt after a visit. Firstly, she mentioned that she was grateful that she can still spend quality time with her mother and have a form of connection with her:

Participant Two: *"...Well, I would say grateful because Mum's still alive."*

Participant Three: *"Aye, I was thinking that."*

Participant Two: *"She'll be 98 in July, so I'm very grateful that she's still here".*

This reiterated the importance of family for both Participants Two and Three and demonstrated that they are appreciative for the time that they can spend with their mother in the home. Conversely, Participant Two also noted that she can often feel worried about her mother after a visit however, she has never felt disappointed if a visit did not go to plan This continued what she said during the second emotional touchpoint when she discussed that whilst she is always happy to see her mother and spend time with her, she worries about her in the days following a visit until she next visits. This captures a common experience, and one which was explored in the literature review in Chapter Two, as many families often worry about their loved ones even if they have no issues with the care they receive.

Participant Six also stated that he was grateful as he explained he does not have any concerns about his sister's care or worry about how a visit is going to pan out and instead accepts whatever happens when he is in the home. For him, this allowed him to almost compartmentalise a visit as he spends time with his sister and then continues with the rest of the day knowing that she is safe and happy in the home.

Lastly, Participant Three said that she “*always feel[s] uplifted*” after visiting her mother which was heartening to hear as it showed how much of an impact a visit can have on her mood. This was an interesting contrast to her response to the first emotional touchpoint and suggested that spending time connecting and being in her mother’s company reassured Participant Three that although the dementia is progressing, her mother is still there. This covered a key point for the study, as I wanted to help families to remain connected to their loved ones living in the home and to continue to see the person behind the dementia and taking a strengths-based approach to visits.

The responses to this session illustrated that visits are subjective experiences and can involve a wide range of emotions, such as feeling connected or worried about their loved one. This activity also highlighted a few of the difficulties that families faced during their visits, such as the emotional toll of seeing their loved one’s dementia progress, or visits that do not go to plan. It also demonstrated how visits lifted the participant’s moods and how positive interactions can help to keep families connected. The next session repeated this activity to explore if the use of reminiscence had changed how participant’s felt about their visits and their connections to their loved ones.

6.4 Third round of phone interviews and Second Emotional Touchpoints session

Prior to the last group session of the cycle, I conducted a final round of short, semi -structured interviews, using the same process and interview guide as the previous round of interviews. Three interviews were carried out between April and May 2024, a joint in-person interview was conducted with Participants Two and Three after the previous group session as this was

a convenient time for both participants and allowed them to both discuss a reminiscence activity that they jointly did with their mother. Whilst this was an in-person interview, I followed the same interview guide and procedure as the phone interviews. One phone interview was conducted with Participant Four, and two with Participant Five, and lasted for an average of 25 minutes.

6.4.1 Findings from third round of phone interviews

As with the previous rounds of phone interviews, participants were asked about a recent visit in which they had used reminiscence and to discuss how they felt when they were using it with their loved one. The concept of maintaining connections continued to be prevalent throughout the interviews and was a primary motivator for regular visits.

Participants Two and Three discussed how they had continued to use knitting as part of their reminiscence activities with their mother. As previously mentioned, knitting was an effective reminiscence trigger for their mother. After using knitting a few times during visits, they started to keep the needles and wool in their mother's room so that it was at hand for when they wanted to use it. During this visit, the knitting activity lasted for approximately 15 minutes, with a short break part of the way through as their mother stopped engaging with it. However, they were able to reengage their mother with the activity after a few minutes as they took over the knitting themselves to see if this would gently prompt her to continue with the activity:

Participant Three: *"Yeah, we gave it to her first, and then I said, we'll do a couple of rows each. So, I sat and done one and she was staring at me and going "what are you knitting". So, I told her I was knitting a wee scarf for the dog."*

Participant Two: *"She was quite happy with that".*

Participant Three: *“But then you did a couple of rows. I’m sure we then gave it back to her again.”*

Both Participants Two and Three discussed how much they loved knitting with their mother as they both stated that they are not knitters, and they all had a laugh at their attempts to knit a few rows each. This exemplifies how reminiscence could be incorporated into visits in such a way that is enjoyable for everyone and leaves families with fond memories of time spent together. It also illustrates that reminiscence cannot be forced if the person with dementia does not engage with the activity, and that by giving their mother a short break, they were able to successfully try again.

They also shared how they had used their mother’s catholic faith for reminiscence activities, and first tried to use reminiscence informally to gauge their mother’s reaction:

Participant Three: *“. So, we said that we’d do a decade of the rosary, 10 Hail Marys... My mum looked round and burst out laughing saying that we were awfully holy.”*

Whilst this was an informal reminiscence activity, they talked about how they had a laugh and that they were particularly heartened to see that their mother’s sense of humour had not changed. It also prompted both participants the idea to continue with using religion as the basis of a future reminiscence activity. During another visit they used a prayer shawl and prayer cards which were effective trigger items for a short reminiscence activity. Both participants shared how reminiscence had a positive impact on their visit experiences:

Participant Two: *“Oh it is. You know, we’re having more good days aren’t we than bad days?”*

Participant Three: *“Oh yeah, definitely”*

Participant Two: *“100%. We go down the road laughing most days now. It's great.”*

This captured the heart of the study, as I wanted to work with families to develop ways to incorporate reminiscence into visits to help them have more positive visiting experiences. It was reassuring to hear that they were having more positive days than negative, as this encouraged them to see visiting as an enjoyable activity and to continue to look forward to spending time with their mother.

Participant Five also shared how she had used her mother’s Catholic faith for the basis of a reminiscence activity and continued building on what she had learnt from previous reminiscence activities. During one visit, Participant Five used her mother’s rosary book as a trigger object for a reminiscence session, which proved to be effective and got positive reactions from her mother:

“So, I just thought the book would be a good idea, she took the book, and I actually sat and read the book to her, and she let me. I thought this was brilliant, you know. So, I was really enjoying that day with her, I really enjoyed that day.”

Participant Five selected this as an avenue to explore through reminiscence as her mother was a devout Catholic, and she knew that she had books in the house that held meaning for her mother. However, whilst her mother engaged with the book, participant Five reported that she did not recognise that it was her book:

“She didn’t seem to remember anything, but I mean, I’m delighted that she even took off me and that she was, you know, letting me read to her.”

Despite this, she noted that she was feeling more positive about visiting, and enjoying seeing her mother, instead of viewing it as her duty as she had previously mentioned. Following the religious theme, Participant Five used family photographs from her First Communion during a visit, which elicited a positive reaction:

“I showed her a communion picture of me when I made my first Holy Communion, and there’s a big, big picture that my mum and dad got made and I showed her that and she remembered that, which was really good.”

Participant Five also shared how she had started to have joint visits with her father where they would look through old family photographs with her mother which allowed her to connect with both of them. This was something which meant a lot to Participant Five as she had previously talked about how she was struggling to balance her home life, visiting her mother, and assisting her father. She also mentioned that her brother was *“bringing up pictures of his holidays, different things and showing her some different pictures on the phone”* illustrating that the family started to embrace reminiscence as an effective and meaningful visit activity. This also marks a change from the previous group session during which Participant Five shared her frustrations that she felt that most of the visits were left to her and that she felt that other family members could do more to help. Therefore, it was positive to hear how other family members were beginning to visit a bit more, which helped Participant Five to view visits as an enjoyable activity, instead of her duty. Additionally, Participant Five shared that she was beginning to feel more confident in her abilities which allowed her to assist her mother in

ways that she would have been unable to do before. Participant Five also talked about how her mindset surrounding visits has shifted significantly over the course of the study:

“So, with all those things, I’m just so positive about everything, I’m like a changed person.”

Even when talking about days that did not go as well, she always added the caveat that she knew that there would be good days and bad days. This was a stark contrast to when she joined the study as she sounded tearful when she talked about her visits and stated that she was not coping with them. It was heartening to hear over the interview how Participant Five had used reminiscence to further connect with her mother, but also to give herself reassurance that she can help her mother and feel comfortable in her role within her mother’s life in the care home.

Participant Four discussed his second time using reminiscence during a visit with his wife which centred on looking at photographs from their years spent together such as of holidays or of family members. However, as his wife is non-verbal due to advanced dementia, he had a limited response to the photographs. He reported that there whilst there was a “wee flicker” from his wife, he still thoroughly enjoyed looking at the pictures with her as it allowed him to reminisce about their first date together. Furthermore, whilst he got a limited response, he still felt connected to her during the visit, and was not deterred from using reminiscence again:

“For myself, looking back at these photographs, it brought back some fond memories of times we’ve had together, you know, and obviously, that first memory when she invited me to her college ball, I took a photograph of us at it [...] That was the first time we had went out together”.

Participant Four shared that reminiscence was something that helped him and whilst the communication barrier presented by his wife's dementia limited what he was able to do, he still felt that using reminiscence was beneficial for him:

“Oh, you know, life is about reminiscence. My main purpose is to feed [Wife] and chat about other things. I mean, I do reminisce, you know talking about people that were asking after her that kind of stuff. I think it's certainly beneficial, and it would be beneficial for somebody who gets more correspondence. I mean, that's the real kind of sad thing with [Wife], there's no communication, no verbal communication at all”.

The idea that *“life is about reminiscence”* helps to demystify reminiscence and shows that it is something that is widely accessible. This also built on the findings from the individual interviews from Cycle One which showed that participants had already incorporated some aspects of informal reminiscence into their visits prior to the study. It also demonstrates that for some families, advanced dementia means that reminiscence offers an opportunity to somewhat overcome the additional communication issues and maintain the connection and familial bonds between loved ones.

6.4.2 Emotional Touchpoints Methods

Following the third round of phone interviews, the last group session of the cycle focused on a second Emotional Touchpoints Activity to assess how participants felt at key points of the visit experience after using reminiscence. As with the previous group, there were three objectives for this group session:

- To summarise what we did during the last group
- To reflect on the how participants have continued to use reminiscence.

- To complete the first Emotional Touchpoints activity

6.4.2.1 Emotional Touchpoints preparatory work

The second emotional touchpoints activity used the same touchpoints as the previous group (“before a visit”, “during a visit”, and “after a visit”). Moreover, the same words and phrases were used for the emotion cards, with the addition of the cards added by the participants during the first activity. This was done so that I could compare the responses from the two sessions to assess if there was a change in how participants felt over the course of the visit after incorporating short reminiscence activities into their visits.

6.4.3 Findings from group three

The purpose of the group was to further reflect on how the participants had incorporated reminiscence into their visits, and to complete the second emotional touchpoints activity. Following the same transcription and analytical processes as previous groups, two main themes were identified. The first overarching theme further built on the findings of the cycle and focussed on the practical application and benefits of reminiscence. The second theme centred on the second emotional touchpoints activity which asked participants to reflect on a recent visit in which they used reminiscence with their loved one.

6.4.3.1 Reflections on Reminiscence Task

The first ten minutes of the group session centred on reflecting on the ways that participants had incorporated reminiscence into their visits since the last group. As with the previous sessions, this provided an opportunity for peer learning and group reflection on how reminiscence could be used during visits.

Participant Five shared how she had used her mother's religious books and read a few passages to her during a recent visit. She reported that whilst her mother did not recognise the book, she picked it up to look at it herself and even turned a few pages, which Participant Five felt was "*really fantastic*". This demonstrated how even a seemingly small interaction, like looking through a book, can have a positive impact in making a visit an enjoyable and meaningful activity. Participant Five also discussed her experiences of reading to her mother, and how she was engaged throughout:

Participant Five: "*I was sitting reading like bits from it, and she was letting me read it, which was absolutely fantastic. I knew she was listening to me, you know. It was fun, I was delighted*".

Participant Two: "*It does, it lifts your spirits, it really does. That's amazing.*"

This short exchange further illustrates the impact that a positive interaction can have for families. Furthermore, it was great for the group to hear how enthusiastically Participant Five talked about her visits compared to a few months prior to this. It was also fascinating for Participant Five to share with the group how she had used reminiscence to explore her mother's Catholic faith, building on what we had previously discussed during the Time Machine session. The idea that a visit "*lifts your spirits*" was great to hear and summarises what I hoped families would achieve from reminiscence as I wanted families to find ways of leaving visits feeling uplifted and that they had formed a meaningful connection to their loved one.

Participants Two and Three also shared how they had continued to use knitting as the basis for their reminiscence sessions with their mother. They recounted to the group how during a recent visit, they had brought out the knitting from a previous visit for their mother to

continue. However, they shared that after completing two or three rows, she *“folded it up and tossed it on the bed”* and that both participants each continued doing a few rows each as a means of reengaging their mother with the activity:

Participant Three: *“She laughed at the sight of me knitting. She’d never seen me knitting before, it amused her. She was giggling, wasn’t she, and then [Participant 2] did a wee bit of knitting and then we gave it back to her again and she stuck with it. I took photos of her cause she looked really engrossed.”*

Participant Five: *“That’s lovely, isn’t it.”*

Participant Two: *“It was lovely to see her knitting.”*

This was something that we discussed during the interview that I thought would be beneficial to share with the group as it was an effective way of gently trying to reengage their mother with the reminiscence activity whilst also ensuring that they did not force it. Additionally, it was heartening for the group to hear how they attempted the knitting together, and whilst it might not have been the neatest, both participants and their mother laughed together about it.

Participant Six shared how he tried using reminiscence with his sister. Inspired by how other participants had used family photographs for their reminiscence activities, Participant Six decided to bring in photographs of family dogs to see how his sister would react:

“I brought photographs in; of a couple of dogs I had years ago. Actually, photographs that my sister took. I brought them in, about half a dozen or so and she hadn’t a clue. She knew they were dogs, but that was it. I named them, and she recognised their names, but she had no inclination that she took the photographs.”

Prior to joining the study, Participant Six shared with me that he felt that his sister's dementia was too advanced for reminiscence to work, but that he was willing to try it to see if it would be beneficial to her. As such, this was the first time that he had tried to use reminiscence during a visit and after trying he still felt that he did not get anything from it or that his sister engaged with the photographs. That being said, he went on to talk about how his sister has a great quality of life within the home, and that he regularly hears his sister singing with other residents:

Participant Six: *"The fact that [Sister] is in here now has improved her quality of life. I came in here, I can't remember if I mentioned this already, and she was sitting up the corridor at the back. She's sitting amongst about 4 or 5 women, and they've all, except of one, they've all got varying degrees of no memory and they're singing old Scottish songs. I've never heard her sing in my life."*

Participant Two: *"Oh, really?"*

Participant Six: *"Never, and they were singing at the back. Every now and then I'll come in, usually on a Friday night and ask if they've all been drinking [laughs]"*

This suggested that whilst individual reminiscence did not work Participant Six, a music based, group reminiscence session may be an effective means to keep his sister engaged. Despite not finding reminiscence entirely beneficial himself, Participant Six still engaged with the group activities and encouraged the rest of the group to continue trying it.

6.4.3.2 Emotional Touchpoints Activity

After our reflection on reminiscence, we moved onto the second emotional touchpoints activity. Following the same process as the previous session, a semi-structured guide was used

to guide our discussion and to support the facilitation of the emotional touchpoints activity (see Appendix 19). As with the previous group, participants were asked to reflect on their experiences of using reminiscence and discuss how they felt at key points of their visits. These touchpoints were: before, during, and after a visit.

6.4.3.2.1 Before a visit

For the first touchpoint of the session, I had nine flashcards with various emotions on them. These were the same eight from the first session, with the addition from Participant Five and participants were asked to spend 30 seconds looking at the cards before selecting the one the best aligned with their experiences, or to add another card if that was required. Picture 4 illustrates the range of emotions that participants selected.

Picture 4: Emotions Before a Visit (after reminiscence)

Participants were invited to share why they selected their chosen card and Participant Two opened the conversation by explaining why she picked both “looking forward to it” and “accepting whatever happens”. Participant Two stated that:

“I always look forward to seeing Mum but I always think it’s never going to be the same visit twice [...] So I’m accepting whatever happens in that visit cause you never get the same visit twice.”

Whilst Participant Two also stated that she looked forward to visits during the first session, it was interesting to hear that this time she paired it with “accepting whatever happens” as she recognises that the responses she gets from her mother can, and do, vary from visit to visit. This could be seen in her experiences of using knitting as a basis for her reminiscence sessions with her mother as she was a bit more disengaged with it the second time before they were able to gently prompt her to try it again.

Participant Three shared that she *“always feel[s] excited”* to see her mother which was a stark contrast to her response during the last group where she selected that she often *“felt down”* before visiting her mother as she found it difficult to watch her mother’s dementia progress. This suggests that by using reminiscence during visits, Participant Three was able to see past her mother’s dementia and take more of a strengths-based approach to visits. This could be seen in her disbelief that her mother was still able to knit despite having not done so for several years. Whilst this was a short activity, it demonstrates the potential impact that reminiscence can have during a visit in connecting families together. Participant Five explained that whilst she would agree with all the cards that were selected, she still feels a sense of duty and responsibility in ensuring that she visits her mother regularly:

“You know, it is your duty, it is your mother, or it is whoever it is that’s in the home and you’ve got responsibility. You feel you’ve got responsibility. So, I guess that is duty bound.”

This was something that Participant Five had previously touched on as she felt that it was her duty as the daughter to both visit her mother in the care home, and care for her father. As a result of this, she was struggling to view visits as an enjoyable activity due to the stress of juggling her own home life whilst caring for her parents. However, this time round, she took a softer view as she felt that this was her opportunity to repay her parents for supporting her through her life. By shifting her point of view, Participant Five began to feel less stressed or burdened by visits and instead saw them as a way to remain connected to her mother, and to her father through joint visits.

Participant Six explained he also agreed with feeling a sense of duty to visit his sister, but that he also does not worry about a visit beforehand as he knows that she is happy in the home and well cared for:

Participant Six: "Well, I'd probably agree with that but what I find is that I find [sister] exactly the same every time I come in except she's breathing bad or she's breathing good. Exactly the same."

Participant Three: "She's got a nice temperament. She's jolly."

He explained that he never worries about how his sister will be prior to a visit and that by having this mindset, he is able to communicate with his sister in the moment. This exchange also further highlighted the peer support aspect of the group as participants had started to recognise each other's loved ones in the home and engaged with them as well.

Participant Four selected "relaxed" for his card however, he did not share his thoughts when invited to during the first touchpoint of the session.

6.4.3.2.2 During a visit

For the second touchpoint participants were asked to reflect on how they felt during a visit after using reminiscence and we had 20 flashcards for this. Following the same procedure as the first touchpoint, participants were given 30 seconds to look at the cards before being asked to select the one that summarised how they felt during a visit and Picture 5 shows the responses from participants.

Picture 5: Emotions During a Visit (after reminiscence)

Participant Two selected both “feel at home” and “fortunate” and shared her thoughts on how she feels during a visit:

“I would say that one because we have just now started because we've said that we always visited Mammy in a group you know when she was at home and I said this mum's home now and I don't mean a home-home, this is her wee house.”

This echoed a similar sentiment she made during the initial interviews at the start of Cycle One as she discussed how she now views the care home as being her mother’s home and that

the visits are not overly different from when she would visit her in the community. By reframing the visits this way, Participant Two almost removed the pressure that can sometimes be placed on families as they feel that they need to visit a certain way and instead she is simply visiting her mother in her home. This was a nice way of looking at visits as it could allow families to focus more on connecting to their loved ones in the moment instead of focussing on acting a certain way or thinking about have a 'right' visit.

Similarly, Participant Four selected both "relaxed" and "feel loved". Throughout the study, Participant Four made it clear that he still feels loved by his wife, even if verbal communication may no longer be possible and that he loves spending time with her each morning at breakfast time. Additionally, he stated that he is "*always relaxed*" when he visits the home as he loves just spending time with his wife. This was apparent throughout the study as his face lit up whenever he talked about her and shared with the group fond memories that they shared together.

Participant Three stated that "feeling connected" captured how she felt during a visit with her mother. However, for Participant Three, this also meant that she constantly thinks about her on days that she cannot visit:

"I think about her constantly, from morning to night, but to be actually here"

Whilst it was great that Participant Three felt connected to her mother during visits, this exchange also captures the inverse of this as she shared that she is thinking of her mother "*morning to night*" when she is unable to visit her. This echoes the findings from the literature review in Chapter Two which highlighted that some families constantly worry about their loved one and experience feelings of guilt or loss even when they know they are well looked after in care homes Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Midtbust *et al.*, 2018; Statz

et al., 2021). This was particularly heightened for Participant Three as she shared that she used to live with her mother to care for her and therefore still struggled at times to adjust to her role as a visitor. Towards the end of the discussion on the second touchpoint, Participant Two shared that:

“But you could almost be feeling of those in the one day. You could go in and start off and its brilliant and then within half an hour you’re like ‘get me out of here’.”

This captured the reality for many families in that a visit can be a very emotional experience and can be determined by how their loved one reacts to them or engages with activities. This further supports the use of family-centred reminiscence as it provides families with a range of activities that they could do with the loved ones and as shown by Participants Two and Three, can also be used to gently re-engage their loved ones by doing the activity together and enjoying spending time together.

6.4.3.2.3 After a visit

The last emotional touchpoint of the session focussed on how participants felt after a visit of using reminiscence and had twelve flashcards. Picture 6 below shows the range of emotions which participants selected which captured how they felt after a visit.

Picture 6: Emotions After a Visit (after reminiscence)

Participant Four selected “grateful” and “mixed feelings” as he stated that he is “*always grateful for the staff*”. This was something that he had previously discussed as he expressed this thanks to the staff for always providing him with breakfast alongside his wife. This meant that they could still share a meal together, allowing him to overcome the communication barrier and connect with his wife during visits. Participant Two echoed this sentiment and stated that:

“[the staff] lift us up sometimes and can say things that make you laugh, they’re brilliant. I don’t feel down now, I used to. I mean, if that was me when I was going myself, I would be, 100%.”

This recalls the idea of Connecting with Staff from Cycle One and illustrates how staff involvement in visits, even if it is a passing comment or having a laugh, can help lift their spirits and break the ice during the lulls in visits. This also continues what Participant Two shared

during Cycle One as she viewed the staff as being extended members of her mother's family and therefore wanted to have a strong relationship with them.

Participant Five felt that "uplifted" and "satisfied" summarised how she felt about visits since joining the study. She explained that this was rooted in her newfound belief in herself and knowing that she is able to cope with visits that do not go as well as she would have liked:

"I think it's accepting it, you know, it's accepting that, you know, for me that was really hard, but I think I've been more positive now and you know, I'm able to sort of cope with it better, you know, and I'm getting my head round it a bit, you know. So, when something happens now, I'm not so bad and I'm just remaining positive."

This illustrated that Participant Five feels calmer about visiting her mother and is reassured by having coping mechanisms in place for when visits do not go well. This further demonstrates her growth over the course of the study, partly through the use of reminiscence, but also through hearing from fellow participants who have been in her position. The peer support aspect of the group has been fundamental in developing our approach to reminiscence but also in coming together and sharing experiences of visiting and caring for loved ones with dementia.

6.5 Chapter Summary and How this led into Cycle Three

Cycle Two centred on working alongside participants to determine how reminiscence could be incorporated into their visits and if this was something that they found beneficial in remaining connected to their loved ones. We used activities such as the time machine analogy to explore reminiscence in more detail and to think about the types of memories that could be effective for sessions. The three rounds of telephone interviews demonstrated that family-

centred reminiscence could be an enjoyable activity that enhanced participants' connections to their loved ones living in the care home. An adapted emotional touchpoints approach was used to assess if the use of reminiscence had changed how families felt before, during, and after visits. An additional round of phone interviews was planned for Cycle Three to gauge how participants felt about their experiences of reminiscence and the wider study. Moreover, our work as a group in exploring how reminiscence could be used during visits was continued in Cycle Three as we aimed to develop a resource that was rooted in the experiences of participants, that could be used by other families to assist them to use reminiscence themselves during their visits.

Chapter Seven – Cycle Three

This chapter will explore the methods used in Cycle Three and the subsequent findings from the group sessions and phone interviews. Firstly, it will provide a summary of the aims and objectives of the third action research cycle, and the proposed methods that I planned to use to meet these. Cycle Three built on the findings from Cycle Two and centred on the development and refinement of a family-centred reminiscence resource. Additionally, Cycle Three asked participants to reflect on and evaluate their experiences of using aspects of reminiscence during their visits, and of their experience of the study. The methods and interview techniques used, and the approach to transcription and analysis are outlined for each data collection activity within the cycle, before exploring the findings and how this led into the following activity. This chapter will end by focusing on the key findings of the cycle, and the development of the resource.

7.1 Recruitment updates

At the start of Cycle Three, I met with my gatekeeper within the care home to discuss how to include staff in the last group of the cycle. During this meeting, it was agreed that the gatekeeper would approach staff based on their availability for the group, and their interest in the study, and provide them with an amended version of the Participant Information Sheet which outlined how they would be involved in the study [see Appendix 10]. As outlined in Chapter Four, section 4.4.2, this was approved by the School's Ethics Board. Interested staff members were also provided with a consent form to sign to indicate that they fully and freely consented to joining the study. It was crucial that staff were not pressured or coerced to join the study by management or other staff members, and both the information sheet and the

consent form clearly stated that they were free to withdraw at any time. Table 6 provides a summary of the staff members that joined the study, and their role within the care home.

Table 6 - Staff Members' role within the care home

Participant pseudonym	Role within the study site
Staff Member One	Senior Carer
Staff Member Two	Activities Co-Ordinator
Staff Member Three	Activities Co-Ordinator

All three staff members joined the study for the last group session of the cycle to discuss the resource alongside the other participants.

7.2 Cycle Three Overview

Cycle Three was the last cycle of this action research study and had one overarching aim:

- To co-create with family carers a resource to support delivery of family-centred reminiscence informed by the study findings.

The first data activity of the cycle was to conduct a group session with the participants from Cycle Two which focussed on the development of our resource on family-centred reminiscence. As part of this, participants were asked to reflect on their recent reminiscence activities, before the conversation moved onto the resource development, whereby participants were asked for their opinions on the format, content, and timing of the resource. The second activity was a round of telephone interviews to capture how participants felt about using reminiscence, and the study in general. Over the course of the interviews, participants were asked to reflect on their experiences of the study and highlight aspects

which worked well for them, and if there were areas that could have been done differently. Additionally, they were asked if they would recommend reminiscence to other families visiting the care home. The last activity of the cycle was a group session which brought participants and three members of staff from the care home together to discuss the resource and how we envision that it could be used within the care home. Diagram 11 outlines the research activities for Cycle Three.

Diagram 11: Overview of Cycle Three Research Activities

As summarised in Table 2 (see section 4.1), participant involvement was varied across the Cycle Three. Four participants were involved in the first group session, and all five participants engaged with the closing round of telephone interviews. Seven participants attended the final group session of the study, which brought families and care home staff together to refine our co-produced resource on family-centred reminiscence.

7.3 First group session

The first activity of the cycle was a group session during which we discussed our ideas for the resource and started the process of co-producing this. There were three objectives for this group session:

- To summarise what we did during Cycle Two
- To reflect on how participants have further incorporated aspects of reminiscence since the end of Cycle Two
- To have a discussion and plan the development of the resource

Cycle Three utilised the same focus group process as the previous two cycles (see Chapter Four section 4.4.2) with the aim of meeting the three objectives outlined above. The group session centred on the co-development of the resource on our family-centred approach to reminiscence. Additionally, the purpose of the group was to bring participants together to further share how they had incorporated aspects of reminiscence into their visits since the end of Cycle Two. This provided an opportunity for peer-to-peer learning and to discuss if the use of reminiscence had changed their visits with their loved ones.

7.3.1 Research methods used

There was no variation from the planned methods outlined above. Originally, the session was planned on being conducted in the library within the study, however, it was moved to the dining room as the library was being repainted. Whilst this was a quiet room, Cycle One highlighted that it was not completely free from distractions as staff frequently needed access to get the room ready for mealtimes. Therefore, I was mindful of the fact that the dining room was going to be used for lunch after the group and therefore had to ensure that we did not overrun our time to reduce the risk of interruptions. To start the session, I briefly outlined what I planned to cover during the group, and to remind participants that they were free to withdraw from the group at any time. As with previous groups, the session was digitally recorded with full consent using a digital recorder supplemented by field notes. A semi-

structured guide was used to steer the group and to ensure that we stayed on topic, whilst allowing a certain degree of flexibility for participants to raise issues that they wanted to discuss (see Appendix 20).

7.3.2 Findings from Group One

Following the same transcription process as Cycles One and Two a reflexive thematic analysis was conducted. The first overarching theme focussed on the practical application and benefits of incorporating aspects of reminiscence into family visits. The second overarching theme centred on the development of the resource and had three subtopics: the chosen format of the resource, the content that families felt would be most beneficial, and the timing of when other families should receive this. The concept of peer support was prevalent as shared learning, and mutual support ran through the session. As this was a continuing theme from both Cycles One and Two, it was clear that this was important for families as part of their support network.

7.3.2.1 Reflection on Reminiscence Task

Before we had a discussion on developing our resource on family-centred reminiscence, I asked participants to reflect on the ways that they incorporated aspects of reminiscence into their visits and the impact this had on their visits. This had two purposes, firstly, it presented another opportunity for peer-to-peer learning and discovering novel ways for families to use reminiscence during their visits. Secondly, it helped to contextualise the later conversation on our resource as families were already thinking about how they had used reminiscence, and how their visits, and their mindset, had potentially changed over the duration of the study.

Participants Two and Three talked about how they continued using knitting as an effective trigger for short reminiscence sessions with their mother and the impact this had on their

visits. Whilst they had previously only used reminiscence in their mother's room, they tried knitting with their mother outside in the grounds of the care home. Right from the offset, their mother was laughing as they reported that she always finds it "*dead funny*" when she is handed the knitting as it was something that she had done for years. Even this seemingly small interaction shows that reminiscence through knitting was a joyous activity for both participants and their mother and allowed for a positive visit experience. Both participants went on to say that their mother managed to complete two rows of the knitting before they had to move her inside for dinner, However, during the process of moving their mother back inside, the wool became tangled:

Participant Two: "*See by the time we got in, the wool was round my mum, right round the wheels, round sunglasses and we couldn't untangle it. We had to get scissors and cut the wool off.*"

Participant Three: "*How could that possibly happen. We couldn't stop laughing.*"

Although the end of the visit did not quite go to plan, this was something that all three of them laughed at, and both participants noted that it was a memory that they would cherish, even if it "*ended like Laurel and Hardy*". This exemplifies that for both participants, the focus was not so much on the knitting itself, but more on the experience that they could share together and to have a laugh with their mother. However, later in the group, Participant Two noted that they can often get a mixed response from their mother regarding reminiscence, particularly when talking about her childhood in Ireland. This demonstrated that whilst reminiscence can be an effective tool for families, it does not work all the time and is dependent on factors such as the trigger object used and how receptive the person with dementia is to the activity.

During the session, Participant Five showed the group some Catholic books and pictures that she had used with her mother for her reminiscence sessions and shared how this had helped to shift her mindset and resulted in her enjoying her visits more. She noted that a particularly effective picture was one of Pope John Paul II as her mother recognised him and sparked further conversations relating to her Catholic faith. For example, she showed her mother pictures of a Rosa Mystica statue that she had in the family home prior to moving to the care home, and pictures of Jesus on the Cross as she knew that her mother liked regularly going to mass. Whilst these seem like small things in isolation, they can have a meaningful impact for visiting families as Participant Five went on to say that:

“Obviously, there’s healing, you know, in these things, you know. She did remember the book; I got a good response with that today.”

The idea of reminiscence as a tool for *“healing”* is an interesting one to consider, as for families, exploring their loved one’s faith through reminiscence may have somewhat of a healing effect regarding their religion and strengthening their connections to one another. This further highlights the potential benefits of incorporating aspects of reminiscence into visits. Participant Five also shared how reminiscence has impacted her and her mindset regarding visiting her mother. She mentioned that after using reminiscence over the course of three months, she was beginning to feel more positive and felt that she was in her stride with using reminiscence and adapting her visits to react to how her mother is in the moment. She also mentioned that she was *“more relaxed”* about visiting her mother. This illustrates the impact that reminiscence has had on Participant Five over the course of the study, as at the start of the study she was visibly tearful when she was talking about her visits and was open with how she was not coping with them. Participant Five also explained that she can see a difference in

her mother since incorporating reminiscence into her visits. By feeling like she was helping her mother, Participant Five was encouraged to visit more regularly and strengthened their connection.

Conversely, Participant Six reported that he did not find reminiscence a helpful tool as he felt that his sister's dementia was too advanced for it to have any benefit, and he talked about a recent visit to illustrate this. He shared that his sister's best friend had recently moved into the home, and his sister had no recollection of her. Moreover, her friend had a birthday party in the home, and his sister was supported to go to the other unit to attend, and whilst she enjoyed it at the time, when Participant Six visited that evening, she had no memory of it. This could indicate that reminiscence-based activities could have in-the-moment benefits for her, like the group singing that he talked about in Chapter Six section 6.3.3.1, however as he did not want to try reminiscence again due to his fixed mindset, we were not able to explore this further.

Despite this, he stated throughout the group, and the study, that he felt that this approach to reminiscence could be beneficial for other families if they used it before their relative's dementia was too advanced:

“So, maybe if you get them 2 or 3 years beforehand, you would maybe make their life a wee bit better and they would remember part of it.”

This further demonstrates that whilst reminiscence can be an effective tool for families, it will not work for everyone and indicates that it requires families to be open to trying new visit activities for it to have any potential impact or benefits for them.

7.3.2.2 Development of resource

The main purpose of this group session was to develop our resource, and the discussion centred on three components of this: the content of the resource, the format of the resource, and when should families be provided with the resource and who within the home would be based place to introduce the resource to families.

7.3.2.2.1 Content

The discussion on the content of our resource focussed on two key aspects: practical guidance, and emotional support for families as participants knew through their own experiences that adjusting to visiting a care home can often be a challenging and lonely period.

Participants noted that the practical components of the study, such as dementia friendly communication and best practice for reminiscence should be at the fore of our resource. This was rooted in the effectiveness of the video introduction to reminiscence which was shown to participants at the start of the study and guided participants to think about communication strategies which would be more effective for reminiscence sessions. Participant Five stated that for her, it was important that our resource would help families *“to do these things the right way”*. Furthermore, she also noted that:

“Everything takes a bit of time as well, you know, so it's just remembering to, you know, leave it, sit it down and see if there's a response or you know and not overwhelming them too much if you think they're getting tired.”

Dementia friendly communication was something that participants felt was important to include as reminiscence can only work if both parties engage in the activity. Additionally, it was crucial for families to be aware for signs of fatigue or disengagement from their loved one, as reminiscence cannot be forced and runs the risk of causing unnecessary distress for

both the family and the person with dementia. In line with this, the group also stated that examples of how reminiscence could be used would be highly beneficial to include in the resource as it would help to inspire families to think about how they could incorporate aspects of reminiscence into their own visits. Participant Two also felt that examples would be helpful as:

“...at the beginning you don’t have a clue of what to do really”

It was important to use examples from the participants to illustrate how reminiscence was used in various ways to meet the interests and abilities of the person with dementia, whether this was looking at family photographs, or past hobbies such as knitting. Participant Five also raised the point that examples of how they used reminiscence could demonstrate that this can be something that can be easily accessible such as using a mobile phone to show pictures as not only does this mean that a wide range of photos are available, but it also allows the pictures to be enlarged, potentially making it easier to make out faces and details. This highlights how participants had embraced reminiscence and found ways of adapting it to meet the abilities and needs of their loved ones, and how other families could do the same.

A key point raised during this discussion was that every resident and visit is unique and what works can vary from visit to visit. For example, Participant Two shared that she felt that her mother reacted differently to each visit as she *“never [gets her] mum the same”*. This was an important point to include as it could encourage families to try the same reminiscence activity again if it does not go to plan, but also that they can repeat the same activity and potentially get a different reaction each time. This was one of the main messages of the study, as I did not want families to overly focus on planning reminiscence, or trying to make it go ‘perfectly’, instead I wanted this to be a tool or range of activities that they could use to have a joyous visit which would strengthen their connection with their loved one. It was encouraging to hear

to participants had not only taken this message on board but wanted to pass it on through our resource as well.

Participants also wanted the resource to offer a type of emotional support for other families going through what is understandably a difficult and emotionally charged experience. Participant Two summarised this with:

“Put at the top of it ‘don’t panic’ cause I panicked a lot when my mum first came in here”.

Following this theme, there was a conversation about the importance of trying to keep the bad visits in perspective and not being discouraged if visits do not go as well as they hoped. This was a point that was raised by Participants Two and Five, as the study and reminiscence helped them to see that whilst ‘bad’ visits will still happen, the next day could be better and that there was still hope. The idea of hope through reminiscence was prevalent throughout the study, and one that participants wanted to come through the resource as well. Participant Five stated that reminiscence can:

“...give people a bit of hope that things can change and they might not think it's gonna could change because I didn't think that, so you know, the reminiscence has worked for me...”

The idea of giving families hope for the future was one that proved to be a fundamental part of our approach to family-centred reminiscence as it helped families to see past the dementia and the move to the care home to see that their loved one was still there by focussing on their preserved abilities and crucially, that it was still possible to have meaningful, positive interactions with them.

7.3.2.2.2 Format

A key discussion point during this session centred on what the ideal format for our resource would be. Originally, I had envisioned this being a short video, as the introductory video on reminiscence was well received by participants towards the start of the study and whilst participants noted that this was effective, not everyone would have the facilities to be able to play a DVD or access an online video. Therefore, the conversation was led by participants on the type of resource that they would find helpful if they were trying to use reminiscence for the first time. After a discussion, it was decided that a printed practical guide would be more accessible than a video clip, and would also be easier to use from the family perspective:

Participant Five: *"I think if you're reading something then I think that's a whole lot easier."*

Participant Two: *"Yeah"*

Participant Three: *"You keep it in better"*

Participant Two: *"And you've got it to hand, you know what I mean, you've got it there if you need to go back"*

Previously in the study, I had printed copies of the slides used in the introductory video for participants to refer to and this proved to be effective over the course of the study, particularly when participants wanted to go back over some of the technical aspects such as dementia friendly communication. Participants also mentioned that a printed handout is something that could be kept in their loved one's room so that it would always be at hand if they needed to refer to it. The group also raised an interesting point that for some people, information that they have read is more easily retained compared to information that they have listened to from a recording. This was not something that I had previously considered but it took on board

as I wanted our resource to be something that would be easily accessible but also effective in introducing families to our approach to family-centred reminiscence and how to incorporate this into visits.

7.3.2.2.3 Timing

The last discussion point that we covered in the development of our resource was when should families be provided with the resource, by whom. When asked when they think families should be given this, Participant Three felt that it should be given “*right away*” with Participant Two expanding on this by stating that at the beginning families “*feel very, very, alone and you don’t know what’s happening*” so having activities such as reminiscence could aid families in adjusting to their role as a visitor within the care home. This was something that I was interested in following up in a later group which would bring three members of staff into the study to get their perspective on how our resource could be used within the care home.

Participants also felt that families would be more receptive to the resource and open to trying reminiscence if it was provided by the care home management as they are the first point of contact for new families coming into the home. Participant Two captured this idea as she felt that in time “*you get to know the carers but at the start [managers] are the kinda authority*”, suggesting that the endorsement of reminiscence would hold more weight coming from senior members of staff in the initial settling in period. However, Participant Six raised that staffing issues within the care home sector could mean that staff might not have time to talk over or assist families with something such as using reminiscence into their visits. This was another interesting point of conversation that I wanted to continue during the next group session as keen to find ways of supporting the delivery of family-centred reminiscence,

without adding to the workload of staff within the home. Furthermore, the staff members involved in the study may have differing answers on who would be best placed to discuss the resource with families coming into the home and how they can be supported throughout their visits.

7.3.2.3 How this informed the resource

After this group session concluded, I worked to draft an initial resource on family-centred reminiscence based on the findings of the study and guided by the group session. I was mindful to root the content in the experiences of the participants as I wanted their voices to come through and demonstrate that the practical guide was the result of the group's work instead of just my own. The slides used in the introductory video on reminiscence, particularly on dementia friendly communication and best practice for reminiscence were adapted for our practical guide to ensure that our resource had sound practical advice to help families to learn about reminiscence and start to incorporate it into their own visits.

I then worked with the UWS Marketing team on the design side of the practical guide to showcase our work and improve the readability. This involved creating graphics to illustrate the findings from the emotional touchpoints sessions which highlighted how reminiscence had helped participants to feel more positive about their visits. The initial batch of the first draft were then distributed to participants so that we could discuss this during the last group session and ensure that it had the approval from the group before a final draft was completed.

7.4 Closing telephone interviews

The second data collection activity of Cycle Three was a round of short, semi-structured individual telephone interviews with participants. These interviews asked participants to reflect on their experiences of using reminiscence and of the study.

I followed the same process as Cycle Two (see Chapter Six, section 6.2) and arranged a suitable date and time with participants for the interviews. All five participants responded, and interviews were conducted in July 2024, and were approximately 30 minutes long. The interviews were recorded with full permission. A semi-structured interview guide was developed which asked participants to reflect on their experiences during the study and is included in Appendix 21.

7.4.1 Findings from telephone interviews

The first section asked participants what worked well in the study, if anything surprised them, could anything have been done differently, and was there anything that they found difficult.

7.4.1.1 *What worked well*

Participants reported that the group sessions were an effective part of the study and provided an opportunity for much needed peer support. This idea was nicely captured by Participant Four who stated that:

“You end up just becoming to me, one big family.”

This was lovely to hear, and this also clearly came across in the groups as participants got to know each other’s loved ones and would interact with them during their visits. For example, Participant Four shared that he would often chat to Participant Five’s mother whilst he was giving his wife her breakfast and would then reassure Participant Five that her mother was looking well that morning or share what they were chatting about. This mutual support was ideal for families and allowed participants to share reminiscence ideas with each other. Participant Five felt that everyone *“got something out”* of the groups and that it was great to

hear the feedback from other families on how they used reminiscence. This was echoed by Participant Four as he said:

“You know, I think the more people kind of get together and meet and discuss various ways of actually, I use the word treating, but helping or dealing with their loved ones is a great idea.”

However, the peer support aspect of the groups did not work for everyone as Participant Six felt that some participants were *“more concerned about [their] problems in life”* and that he was *“sitting listening to stuff that [he] didn’t want to listen to”*. Despite this, he went on to say that he liked trying to get them to work around their problems and talk about solutions. This perhaps suggests that whilst some of conversations might have been dominated by one or two participants, it still allowed for a degree of shared learning and mutual support which was beneficial for families within the home.

7.4.1.2 Did anything surprise you?

When asked if anything surprised them about the study, most participants responded that they had not previously considered using reminiscence during their visits with their loved ones. Participant Two shared that before participating in this study, she felt that *“nobody else has really bothered to do something”* like this to help family visitors. She also shared that the study had made her more aware of reminiscence and how it could be adapted by families to connect with their loved ones. Similarly, Participant Three stated that after visiting her mother for four years, *“every visit becomes similar”* so she enjoyed have a range of activities to incorporate to help break up visits throughout the week. Furthermore, she was surprised at how much her mother has enjoyed knitting again and how effective it has been for them to see and even do together. Additionally, Participant Five noted that for her, the study *“brought*

to light” that reminiscence was something that families could use and felt that she would not have thought about using it unless someone told her about it. This encapsulates the purpose of developing our practical guide as I wanted to empower families to use reminiscence during their visits if they felt that this could be something that can help them to get a meaningful connection or interaction with their loved one living with dementia.

7.4.1.3 Could anything have been done differently?

Whilst participants had enjoyed taking part in the study, I was keen to find out if there was anything that they felt could have been done differently. Participant Two felt that the groups:

“[covered] enough that whatever kinda state of dementia they’re in, we can still get through to them”.

Despite this, Participant Six felt that his sister’s dementia was too advanced for reminiscence to have any benefit and believed that *“there’s not much that can be done”* to help her. Furthermore, he felt that a larger group would have improved the study as there would have been *“a wider range of people”* and that even if *“they might not be contributing all the time, but it [would] give people food for thought”*. This possibly would have helped him to contribute more during the groups as he felt that it was hard for him to contribute as he did not find reminiscence helpful and therefore did not have examples of how other families could use it. Additionally, a larger group could have been more beneficial for Participant Six as he felt that during our sessions, we *“only had one person doing most of the talking”* and he believed this might have been balanced if there were a wider range of opinions round the table. This was something that I was originally aiming for, however the recruitment issues outlined throughout Chapter Four meant that I was only able to recruit one study site to the study which limited the number of participants I was able to recruit.

7.4.1.4 Was there anything you found difficult?

The last question of this section centred on if there was anything that we covered during the sessions that participants found difficult. This was something that I was mindful of as I was aware that we covered some potentially emotional or distressing topics during the study, such as the progression of memory loss through the Time Machine activities. Participant Two shared that whilst she did not find the topics themselves difficult, she initially found it difficult to get her mother to open up during the reminiscence sessions. However, she went to say that:

“...the fact we have done this study and the fact that we have tried things and find that you can make a difference and she does open up, you know what I mean, and make her smile, make her laugh, which she hadn’t been doing much of.”

Illustrating that whilst reminiscence may initially appear daunting to families, it is something that can be adapted to fit their needs and can have benefits for both them and their loved one. Similarly, Participant Four discussed how he enjoyed the “open talking” and “frank exchanges” during the groups and that whilst the groups touched on some difficult topics, they reflected the reality of life. Furthermore, he explained that he found these parts of the groups easier as he knew that I could relate to the reality of caring for someone with dementia as I was “experiencing what [they’re] all experiencing”. This was reassuring to hear and highlighted how coming to the groups as both an insider and outsider allowed me to approach topics sensitively by drawing on my own experiences as a carer and the emotional challenges that families can go through. By sharing my own experiences, I was able to create a safe space where participants could share their own thoughts without fear of judgement. This could be seen with Participant Six who felt able to share how the study did not help him. He shared that whilst he did not find the topics being discussed difficult, he had difficulty with some

aspects of the groups at times as he felt that he could not contribute “*any great amount*” to the conversations on reminiscence.

The second section asked participants to reflect on their experiences of reminiscence and if they would continue using it, and if they would recommend it to other families coming into the home.

7.4.1.5 Will you continue using reminiscence?

Participants were asked to reflect on their experiences of reminiscence and if they believed that they would continue using it during their visits once the study was completed. It was encouraging to hear that four out of the five participants reported that they would continue with reminiscence as they felt that it was beneficial to them and their loved one. Participant Three noted that she was keen in bringing in more Irish newspapers and continuing with the knitting as both proved to be not only effective reminiscence triggers, but also enjoyable activities that allowed her to connect with her mother in a meaningful way and resulted in more joyous visits. Similarly, Participant Four stated that he would “*continue doing anything that [he] thinks will help [his wife]*”. Thus, capturing the idea that many families are looking for ways to help their loved ones during their visits, and that reminiscence could be an effective tool for some of these families to strengthen their connection with their loved ones and provide the emotional care that families offer which was highlighted in Chapter Two. Participant Five shared that she was going to continue with reminiscence as it was something that she could do with her dad when they visited her mother together, and helped to give comfort and confidence to both of them:

“Oh, definitely. I'm gonna keep continuing it, aye. Without a doubt, aye, and you know, come up with dad too, you know, and just keep it going the way we're doing things now because it's much better and I feel so much confident about my mum and coming in. Aye, I've enjoyed it, I really have enjoyed it.”

The idea of reminiscence bringing her family together was lovely to hear and illustrated the importance of enjoyable visit activities for families, and how a positive visit experience is highly beneficial for everybody and encourages families to visit more regularly.

7.4.1.6 Would you recommend reminiscence to other families?

As we were co-producing our practical guide informed by the study, I felt it was prudent to ask participants if they would recommend reminiscence to other families as a worthwhile visit activity. Participant Two gave reminiscence a ringing endorsement as she felt that:

“...if you just go up for a normal visit, and you don't reminiscence, you're not getting the same goodness out the visit”

This summarises what I hoped families would get out of reminiscence as I wanted them to have an enjoyable visit that helped them to leave feeling uplifted and more positive. Similarly, Participant Five said that she would recommend it to others as she found it was an effective means of connecting to her mother and was a source of hope for her:

“I think it really does help, really definitely does help, without a doubt. I feel a strong view about that, that the reminiscence is something that I didn't think of, and yes, it does give you hope, and yes it does work.”

Whilst reminiscence was beneficial for Participant Four, he noted that *“there's no magic cure and what will work for some, won't work for others”*. However, he felt that nothing would be

lost by trying it and would “*without a doubt*” recommend it to others. Interestingly, whilst Participant Six did not find reminiscence helpful at all, he did feel that this might be something that could help others, with the caveat that he believed that it had to be started early enough. This highlighted that even though he personally did not find it helpful, he still recognised how it could help others and allow them to connect with their loved ones.

7.4.1.6 Participant Reflections on the study

Participants also shared their reflections on the study as a whole and how they found participating in research for the first time. In her response, Participant Two stated that she would “*do it all again*” and that she was glad that I had the printed handout of the slides used during the introductory video as she found them useful to go back over and refresh herself on what we covered during the study. As with a previous response, Participant Four highlighted that he appreciated that I shared my own experiences as a carer with the group and that for him, this enhanced the study:

“It wasn’t just theory based, or book based, you know, you’re living it, and I think that’s a big, big plus, you know, for your study.”

Participant Five noted that the peer support from the group sessions has been a great source of support for her as it introduced her to fellow visitors who she can confide in and talk to about their shared experiences. This was something that other participants had noted as a desired outcome from the study as they shared that prior to joining the groups, they did not know any other families within the home apart from saying hello to each other as they were signing in for visits. Lastly, whilst he personally did not find the study helpful, Participant Six still felt that the study was “*worthwhile*” as he could see how it had benefitted other members

of the group, and how the resource could potentially be used by other families to help them with their own visits.

7.5 Joint group session

The last activity of the cycle was a joint group session which brought family visitors and staff members together for the first time in the study. In this session we aimed to further refine our co-produced resource and have a discussion with staff on how we imagine it could be used within the care home. There were three main objectives for this session:

- To give the staff members a brief overview of the study activities and what we found
- To get feedback on the draft resource and further refine the final draft
- To discuss how the resource could be used with new families coming into the care home.

7.5.1 Focus Group Methods

This last group session used the same focus group process as previous sessions with the aim of meeting the three key objectives outlined above. This group session was centred on the refinement of our co-developed resource on our approach to family-centred reminiscence. Moreover, the purpose of the group was to bring staff and participants together to have a discussion on how staff could introduce this to families and support them to use it. This provided an opportunity for an open dialogue between staff and families and helped to strengthen our approach, knowing that staff supported the concept of family-centred reminiscence.

7.4.2 Research methods used

There was no variation from the planned methods outlined above. Prior to the group session, all participants were provided with a copy of the draft resource to read over so that we could discuss this during as a group. Whilst Participant Four was unable to make the last group session, he provided his thoughts via a text message and a voicemail message. He felt that the draft practical guide was a “*quality, quality production*”, was “*delighted*” to see the work of the group in print and was sure that it would “*impact and help lots of people*”.

The group session was conducted in September 2024 and was held in the library in the study site as I knew from previous groups that it was a quiet area free from distractions. However, as the staff involved in the group were currently on-duty, I was mindful of the fact that there was the possibility that they would need to leave the group at any time to help with residents

To open the session, I briefly summarised what I aimed to cover during the group, and to remind participants that they were free to withdraw from the group at any time. The session was digitally recorded with full consent using a digital recorded supplemented by field notes. Following the same procedure as previous groups, I had the recording device set up and recording prior to the start of the group, however the informal chat amongst participants was not included in the transcript. As with previous group sessions, a semi-structured guide was prepared to steer conversation, whilst allowing for flexibility for participants to raise additional issues that they wanted to bring to the group (see Appendix 22).

7.5.3 Findings from the joint group session

Following the same transcription and analytical process as outlined in Cycle One, I conducted a reflexive thematic analysis. There were two overarching themes which centred on the

development of our resource. The first theme was the groups initial thoughts of the resource and our approach to reminiscence. The second overarching theme was the refinement of our resource, and this had three sub-themes which focussed on the content, timing, and format of the resource. As with previous groups, the concept of peer support ran through the session, with opportunities for shared learning and mutual respect between participants and staff.

7.5.3.1 Initial Thoughts

The session was opened by having a discussion on the group's initial thoughts on our draft resource, and to get the staff members' thoughts on the study, and our approach to family-centred reminiscence.

7.5.3.1.1 On the resource

Staff Member One, a Senior Carer in the home, started the discussion by saying that when she read the practical guide, it made her think of ways that staff could help families as she felt that *"speaking to people with dementia is something that you pick up skills with over time"* and that staff could share these with families. Additionally, she felt that the resource could help to facilitate conversations as a way for the staff to learn more about residents from their loved ones as she recognises that there is not a *"one size fits all"* approach and that *"not everybody wants to talk about the 1930s"*. Participant Five shared that she appreciated the section towards the end of the booklet, which centred on the key findings from the study as after reading it she realised how much we covered and how far she has come since the start of the study:

"... Now we're at the end of it, we can really see what has happened, and you didn't expect to, so that was good, the key findings."

Whilst this section was relatively brief, it captured the initial thoughts on our practical guide before we discussed this in more detail later in the group. It was encouraging to hear how Staff Member One was already thinking about how care home staff could assist families with the practical aspects of reminiscence, such as dementia friendly communication, by sharing tips with family visitors.

7.5.3.1.2 On the study

The group also shared their thoughts on the study, and our approach to reminiscence. For Staff Member One, a key benefit of a family-centred approach to reminiscence is that it allows families to “*move with the times*” and focus on what their loved one was interested in compared to finding a topic that would work for a full group session. For Participant Five, the study, and reminiscence, was a much-needed source of support and hope:

“The hope that I’ve got now from when I started, you know, has increased, you know, like more confidence about speaking to your, you know, loved one and like trying all different things with them, you know? And if it doesn't work, try again or just try different things and just keep, keep going, basically you know.”

This was great for the staff to see as it showed how beneficial this has been for some families, and the staff themselves noted that they particularly see a difference in Participant Five over the duration of the study. Conversely, Participant Six shared his experience and how he did not find it helpful due to the advanced nature of his sister’s dementia. He explained that he can sometimes “*get something out of her for two minutes then nothing*” which he felt made reminiscence-based activities beyond her abilities. Again, staff appreciated hearing how reminiscence might not work for everybody the same way and during this discussion they shared how his sister engaged with group reminiscence activities, particularly music and Cliff

Richard, highlighting that group reminiscence sessions can be an effective approach for some people with dementia. During the conversation, Staff Member One stated that hearing about the study made her appreciate the emotional complexities of visiting as from the staff perspective *“it’s just a visit, but to [families] it’s emotional”*. This was interesting to hear and could indicate that some staff were not aware of the emotional challenges of visiting, and how this could influence the frequency of visiting for some families.

7.5.3.2 Refining our resource

The second part of the group session focussed on refining our resource and discussing how we thought this could be used within the home. There were three sub-themes during this discussion centred on the content, timing, and format of the resource.

7.5.3.2.1 Content

As with the development of the resource, there were two key aspects of the content of the booklet which were focussed on: practical help, and emotional support.

In terms of practical help, the group believed that sharing examples of how reminiscence could be used during visits was a great way to help other families as it illustrated what worked well and how it could be adapted to meet different abilities. Participant Five believed that a key piece of advice that she wanted to pass on to other families was:

“You know, because it doesn’t always work, and when it doesn’t work, I don’t say anything I just step back and I try it again another day, you know.”

This was great advice to include as our study showed that the same reminiscence activity could elicit different reactions from visit to visit and that families do not need to be discouraged if an activity does not go to plan. Staff Member Two, an Activities Coordinator,

also noted that from their point of view, the more information staff get from the families on their loved one's hobbies and interests, then the more they can incorporate into their activities and keep residents engaged. Whilst this was not necessarily the main aim of the study or the resource, it indicates that the practical guide could also facilitate healthier relationships and information sharing between staff and families. Therefore, we decided to include a table as a communication tool which could be used to record how families had used reminiscence and the reaction that it elicited. It was hoped that this could be used by families and staff members to help them to identify the objects or topics which were effective for each resident. Staff Member Three, also an Activities Coordinator, shared that an effective part of the practical guide was *"reading about the families actually getting that connection"* as it demonstrated the benefits of family-centred reminiscence and could be a great source of encouragement for other families as it illustrates why participants continued using reminiscence during their visits.

Both staff and families also noted the importance of including practical advice for families on the best way to approach family-centred reminiscence. Staff Member One shared that they often see families struggling to communicate with their loved ones. They wanted families to recognise that if their loved ones are not verbally responding, that does not mean that they are not listening or diminishes the importance of maintaining communication:

"So, it's about knowing that you can talk to somebody, and they might never talk back to you."

In line with this, Staff Member One talked about how effective non-verbal communication can be and particularly emphasised the importance of touch as it can be an effective means of connecting with people living with dementia who are non-verbal. However, they noted that

some families have *“different attitudes to public affection”* and might not want to come into the home and give their loved one a cuddle, although she further emphasised that the *“power of touch does help”*. Similarly, Participant Five suggested that including a short definition of dementia and how it can be presented could be beneficial for families as she shared that prior to her mother’s diagnosis she did not know what it meant and struggled to find the best approach to helping her mother. Staff also shared the importance of taking a strengths-based approach to visits, and how they have been surprised that the abilities that residents have retained despite living with dementia, as Participant Six rightly shared that *“they’ve all had lives”* which helps to see beyond the dementia diagnosis.

The group also felt that our resource could be a source of support for new families coming to the home and as Staff Member Two stated it can help families *“know that they’re not alone”*. Participant Five continued this theme and wanted our resource to capture the importance of peer support and looking out for other families. She explained that although each person living with dementia is unique, she wants everyone to be able to look past the diagnosis to see the person so that they can *“all support each other”* within the home and adjusting to their visits. Staff Member Three also shared that from her experience, she feels that there is scope for the resource to be helpful for families before they need a care home admission:

“I know that there are a lot of families out there that haven’t got their loved ones into a home, and I also think that’ll be a fantastic help for them, like reassurance.”

Whilst this was outside of the scope for this study, it was reassuring to hear that staff recognised the benefits of family-centred reminiscence, and how our resource could be used to help and support families caring for a loved one with dementia. Furthermore, Staff Member One shared that for her, it was important to for families to see that activities can take many

forms and that something seemingly small like sharing a biscuit and a cup of tea can facilitate conversations and help to maintain connections with loved ones. This was also transferable to our approach to reminiscence as each participant adapted it to work for their visits, and that it could range from having a more intensive activity such as an Irish themed afternoon tea, to looking at family photos on their phone with their loved one.

7.5.3.2.2 Timing

The next part of the session focused on having a discussion on how the resource could be used within the care home. This included discussing who would be best placed to introduce this resource to families and when would be the opportune time to have this conversation with families. During the initial development of the resource, families felt that this should be introduced as soon as families start visiting. However, the staff took a more pragmatic approach to introducing this to families.

Whilst the staff wanted the resource to be introduced to new families, Staff Member Three shared that there was a worry that they would “*overstep that line*” by introducing the practical guide themselves, or for families to think that they were suggesting that they have not been visiting correctly. Instead, Staff Member One wanted to emphasise that they wanted families to know that they are here to work together with them and that they especially wanted newer families to feel comfortable to come up and “*tell [them] something silly*” such as in-jokes or something light-hearted that gives them a starting point to talk to their loved one with dementia. Staff Member Two also recognised that it must be “*scary*” coming into the care home for the first time to visit a loved one and wanted to work with families to make visits a positive and uplifting experience. In terms of the best time to introduce the resource, staff stated that during the induction meeting was “*too early*” and Participant Three agreed as she

felt that *“you can’t take it all in”* at the start as it can be difficult to adjust to their new role and visiting in the care home. Staff Member One shared that they generally give families three weeks to settle to visiting the home as from her experience as this is typically how long it takes for residents to settle into the home.

The group felt that the permanency meeting could be an opportune time to introduce this to families as this would give their loved one time to settle in the home and time for the families to get used to visiting the home. This meeting marked the end of the settling-in phase and the permanent move into the care home. Staff Member One also felt that the permanency meeting would be ideal as it would be attended by *“practitioners, alongside [managers] and the social worker”* and would be an opportunity to introduce the resource and have a discussion on if this could be something that could help them. Participant Five felt that families would be more likely to give family-centred reminiscence a try if the resource was recommended to them by staff *“instead of just giving them a booklet”*. Building on this, Staff Member Two suggested that it could be beneficial for new families to talk to one of the participants as they have used reminiscence themselves and could share firsthand accounts of how it has helped them with their own visits. This aligned with my approach to the resource as I wanted it to be rooted in the experiences of the participants and used their quotes where possible to demonstrate how they used reminiscence and the impact it had for them and their connection to their loved one.

7.5.3.2.3 Format

The last part of the conversation centred on discussing the format of our resource and ensuring that the group felt that it was readable and easy to understand. This included having a discussion on whether we thought that a printed guide was the best format for our resource

or if the group had any suggestions to enhance the accessibility of this. Furthermore, we wanted to ensure that the language used throughout the resource was easy to understand, by striking the balance between avoiding overly academic language without coming across as patronising. The group were happy with this, with Participant Five feeling that “*we’ve got everything quite good*” and that our practical guide effectively conveyed the benefits of family-centred reminiscence and how this can be practically incorporated into visits. Moreover, our practical guide was an appropriate length as it was not too long yet had enough information to help families get started with reminiscence. Staff Member Three stated that she thought:

“...that was the best thing about it cause it was easy to read; it was easy to get through. When I saw it, I thought it was going to be a lot of reading, but when I got into it, I read the whole thing in one go.”

This indicates that our practical guide is easily accessible, and more importantly, easy for families to understand. This was something that I was mindful of, as with the introductory video, I wanted to explore concepts such as dementia-friendly communication without families feeling like they were previously visiting incorrectly. Additionally, I wanted to base the resource on the experiences of the participants as I felt that would be a more effective approach for families than producing an overly academic publication. However, whilst the group approved of the printed booklet, staff raised that some people do not like reading and that they will read through a booklet and decide to put it “*in the bin*”. Due to time constraints, I was not able to adapt the practical guide for this study, however, a future study could use a QR code to combine a printed booklet approach alongside an introductory video to make the resource as accessible as possible.

7.5.3.2.4 Additional Thoughts

Whilst the main purpose of the group was centred on refining the resource, it provided an opportunity for both participants and staff to share any additional thoughts on the resource and the study. Staff were enthusiastic about introducing the resource to the wider care home as they recognised that a key benefit of reminiscence is that it *“keeps families together”*. This aligned with a relationship-centred care approach to reminiscence that placed the family at the heart of the visit by using reminiscence to have meaningful connections with their loved ones living with dementia.

Additionally, the group had an interesting conversation on how families could support each other within the home as Participant Five felt that an additional benefit of the study was that it helped her to not only understand her mother’s dementia, but also other residents and families coming into the home. Conversely, Participant Six shared that he believed that families *“tend to keep to themselves”* and therefore could not see this peer support forming outside of the study. Interestingly, the staff somewhat disagreed with this as they have seen families interact in activities such as quizzes and felt that it could be beneficial for families to come together to support each other. Following the theme of support, Staff Member One believed that the resource could be a source of support for families who do not want to ask for help or connect with organisations such as Alzheimer Scotland, with Participant Three sharing that some families *“like to be quiet and keep themselves to themselves”*. Therefore, this could be a way for them to get additional support and connect to other families going through similar experiences.

7.6 How this further informed our resource

After the last group session concluded, I took the feedback from the participants and staff onboard and worked to refine our resource to align with what the group wanted to get from it. The main changes were the addition of the 'communication tool' to aid with information sharing on reminiscence, and the dementia definition which was added to the end of the booklet. It was important for me to ensure that the definition was accurate to the reality of dementia whilst keeping the hopeful tone that was prevalent throughout the study. After this was drafted, I reconnected with the UWS Marketing team to produce and print the final draft of the booklet. The final draft of our practical guide on family-centred reminiscence is included in Appendix 23. Once I had the copies of our resource, I arranged an informal group session to mark the end of the study, and to show my thanks to the group for participating. During this group, participants were given their own copy of the resource, and the home were provided with a batch of fifteen copies to distribute to families that they feel could benefit from it.

7.7 Chapter Conclusion

Cycle Three centred on the development and refinement of our family-centred reminiscence resource. We developed an initial draft of a practical guide during a group session to ensure that the content, format, and timing of this was led by participants. A final round of phone interviews was carried out to capture the participants' thoughts on reminiscence during their visits, and their thoughts on the study. It was particularly beneficial to hear from Participant Six as he did not always fully engage with the group sessions, or found reminiscence helpful, and I was keen to hear if anything could have been done differently to better support him. The final group session brought participants and staff together to further refine our resource, and

to hear from the staff on how they think this could be used within the home. This helped to place our resource into the wider context of the care home, and the practicalities involved in sensitively introducing this to new families. Furthermore, it was interesting to hear how the resource could be used to foster more communication between staff and families on the interests of the person living with dementia, to enhance the activities offered to them. It was encouraging to hear from participants how the use of reminiscence had helped them have meaningful connections during their visits, and their enthusiasm in passing this onto other families. This further reinforced the importance of peer support for families and wanting to help other families going through similar experiences. Additionally, this indicated that participants had developed a sense of ownership over the study and actively wanted to continue the use of reminiscence after the study had finished, highlighting that collaborative action research was an effective approach to explore family-centred reminiscence.

Chapter Eight – Discussion

This chapter will discuss the pertinent points raised throughout this thesis, and how it could inform future research and practice. Firstly, it will provide an overview of the strengths and limitations of the study to contextualise my interpretations of the study findings. After this, I reflect on the action research methodology used for this study, with a particular focus on the researcher positionality and how I ensured that I did not conflate my own experience as a carer with the experiences of participants. Additionally, I will briefly discuss the concept of the wounded researcher, and how I managed my own wellbeing whilst researching a topic which was often similar to my own role as a carer. Following this, the key findings from across the three action research cycles are discussed, with reference to new literature, and with consideration to the original contribution to knowledge, and how this addresses the research gaps highlighted in Chapter Two. Lastly, I will explore the contention between reminiscence and ‘shared activities’, along with peer support, in relation to how they were connected to the study findings and consequent implications for practice and further research.

8.1 Merits and Limitations of the study

As mentioned in Chapter One, there are approximately 775 care homes for older people in Scotland, with an estimated 63% residents living with either suspected, or diagnosed dementia (Public Health Scotland, 2024). When compared to these numbers, the number of participants I recruited from the study site could be considered to be too small to properly determine the effectiveness of an intervention such as family-centred reminiscence. However, I would contend that six visiting family members and three staff members was sufficient to meet the research aim. This is also in line with the crux of action research as the findings were intrinsically focussed on the visit experiences of each individual within the same care home,

and generalisable findings was not a primary concern for this study. As outlined in Chapter Four, I was originally aiming to recruit up to three study sites to show the transferability of the results and reminiscence resource. However, due to the recruitment issues I experienced, and the limited time and resources available meant that in discussion with my supervision team, I made the pragmatic decision to conduct the study in one study site. A smaller sample size allowed me to explore the experiences of families in more depth as I had more time to build relationships built on mutual trust and respect with families that resulted in participants feeling comfortable to share in detail their thoughts and experiences in detail with me.

Another limitation of this study could be the differing levels of engagement throughout the group sessions. Whilst the aim was for each participant to have an equal input during the sessions, this was not the reality of the study. Although each participant was treated equally during the study, some participants were more vocal during the sessions and were more enthusiastic about using reminiscence during their visits. For example, Participant Five used reminiscence the most during her visits, and would discuss this over multiple one-to-one phone interviews. Furthermore, Participant Six was often more reserved during the group sessions and he later shared that he felt that he did not have much to contribute to the groups as he did not find reminiscence helpful with his sister. Oftentimes the group discussions would be led by one or two participants and whilst this allowed them to discuss the issues that were pertinent to their experiences, it resulted in one or two voices overpowering the groups. This perhaps could have been addressed by having larger group sessions or a more experienced facilitator as more points of views and experiences may have sparked different conversations and avoided the imbalance in participant input. However, this also could have resulted in dominant voices overpowering a larger group which would still result in less people speaking. Additionally, when staff members joined the last group session, the conversation was often

led by them instead of the family members. This may have been due to a perceived power imbalance with families feeling that they had to defer to staff, particularly when we were discussing how the resource could be used within the care home. However, this had limited impact on the study findings as the study was a collaborative action research study which was focussed on visiting family members, with limited input from staff during the refining stage of the development of the resource.

As a result of the requirements of my ethical approval for this study, participants were recruited through a gatekeeper, who for this study was the deputy manager of the Care Home. Recruiting through a gatekeeper had inherent strengths and challenges which could have impacted this study. One key strength of this approach was that prospective participants were approached by someone they knew and trusted instead of being approached by an external researcher. I believed that this approach would reduce the risk of participants feeling coerced into joining the study. However, during one of the sessions, Participant Six stated that he felt *“lightly strongarmed”* into joining the study by the deputy manager and his daughter, who also worked in the care home, as they believed that this would benefit him. Whilst he appeared to say this half-jokingly, it gave me cause for concern as I did not want anyone to feel that they were forced or coerced into the study. After he mentioned this, I had a short talk with him to ensure that he knew that participation was voluntary and that he was free to withdraw from the study at any point if he felt it was necessary. He reassured me that he was happy to participate and to continue to the end of the study. Although I recognise that the deputy manager and the participant’s daughter had good intentions, it highlights how easy it can be at times for participants to feel somewhat coerced into joining a study and how it was necessary to ensure to the best of my ability that all participation was voluntary and without coercion. This was consistent with the literature on recruiting through gatekeepers. Singh and

Wassenaar (2016) who note that although gatekeepers are an effective way to recruit participants, it can sometimes be difficult for colleagues, clients, or service users to decline research participation if they are approached by someone who they perceive to be in a position of power within their organisation. This could therefore undermine the principle of voluntary informed consent if left unchecked. This also raised the issue that as I recruited through my gatekeeper, I could not control how they portrayed the study to potential participants. I followed the process outlined in Chapter Four section 4.3.2, to work alongside the gatekeeper to develop and guide how participants would be approached and how the study would be described. However, as I was not present during these initial conversations with potential participants, I do not know how closely this process was followed. To mitigate this, I had an introductory phone call with each participant to introduce myself, go into some of the details about the study and what participation would entail. During this call, participants also had the opportunity to ask any initial questions that they may have had regarding the study.

A reliance on participants self-reporting, whether this was during individual interviews or group sessions could be seen as a potential limitation of this study. Whilst self-reporting is a fundamental aspect of understanding the perspectives of those with lived experiences, it relies on participants being able to readily recall information about past events. Therefore, a key weakness of self-reporting can be recall bias as during this study I was asking participants to retrospectively think about their experiences of care home visits and their use of reminiscence. Althubaiti (2016) contend that a shorter recall period is preferable over a longer one, particularly when asking about frequent or events, such as care home visits in the case of this study. I tried to overcome the recall bias by conducting the telephone interviews that centred on their reminiscence activities as close to the visits as possible. The majority of these

were conducted a day or two after the visit to ensure that participants were able to recall what they did, and how they felt during the activities., Participants often sent a short text message outlining how they used reminiscence which were then used as interview prompts to aid with their recall of events.

Another potential limitation of self-reporting is that as I was not conducting observations of visits, I could not validate if participants were telling me the truth of their experiences or telling me what they believed I wanted to hear. I aimed to overcome this using my semi-structured interview guides. The guides included prompts to probe for more information depending on participants responses as Jager *et al.* (2020) state that social desirability bias can be minimised by standardising interview questions and reducing the occurrence of leading questions which could influence participant's answers. However, as this study was interested in how families felt after using reminiscence, and if they felt more connected to their loved one, rather than the minute details of their visits, self-reporting was sufficient. This allowed participants to discuss the impact that reminiscence had on their visit experiences in more depth than if I used an overly standardised approach such as questionnaires.

A final limitation of this study was that it is unclear if participants were solely helped using family-centred reminiscence, or if the peer support and interpersonal communication also played an important role within the study. Although the development of a standardised approach to reminiscence could have offset this to some degree, this would not have aligned with our family-centred approach which centred on participants using aspects of reminiscence to fit with their visits. Conversely, as the subject of peer support was prevalent throughout the study and raised by participants themselves, the impact this has had on their visits cannot be dismissed and is itself a key finding of the study as we explored reminiscence as a group

which intrinsically involved shared learning and peer support. Loughheed *et al.* (2016) contend that a good facilitator can bring groups together through humour and rapport to elicit positive emotions which in turn creates a sense of companionship and group identity. This strongly suggests that interpersonal communication and relationships play an important role within studies of this nature and that the experiences of families visiting care homes cannot be seen in isolation from each other. Crucially, due to the emphasis placed on relationships within care homes through relationship centred care, and communication between visiting families, peer support is not something that is necessarily a weakness and instead should be embraced and encouraged.

8.2 Critical Reflection of Action Research Methodology

Reflexivity and reflection are critical components of an action research study (Koshy, Koshy, and Waterman, 2011; Heikkinen, Huttunen, and Syrjälä, 2012; Townsend, 2013; McNiff, 2017). While the overall study aims and objectives outlined for each cycle were addressed, the action research approach used in this study raises concerns regarding the feasibility of applying the methodology in practice.

Outlined in Chapter Three, Section 3.4, a key component of action research is that it focusses on collaborative problem-solving within each action cycle (McNiff and Whitehead, 2006; Reason and Bradbury, 2008; Kemmis, McTaggart and Nixon, 2014; McNiff, 2017). Participation is seen as a central tenet, whereby the goal is to work together towards practical outcomes while creating new forms of understanding through the collaboration and shared decision making. It stands to reason that if this is not achieved, and decision making primarily rests with individuals instead of the whole group, then the study cannot be truly cooperative or collaborative. Whilst in an ideal action research study, participants would be involved from

the offset and be part of the decision-making process from the design stage, this was not feasible for this study. Due to the requirements for the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee, I had to provide an indication of what the three action cycles would focus on and the associated data collection activities prior to meeting with participants. This resulted in a contention between striving to align closely to my action research methodology, whilst also recognising that due to the realities of PhD research, I had to guide the research along in more of a facilitator role.

Across the three research cycles, issues arose surrounding the shared decision-making process, which was an integral part of action research, whereby the group would struggle in reaching decisions which would potentially delay the study progressing through time delays and uncertainty for the group as a whole. Therefore, at several junctions throughout the study, I had to make decisions to allow the study to continue towards our goals for each cycle. It is possible that this undermined the authenticity of the study as the decision-making process was not collaborative (Reason and Bradbury, 2008). To address this risk of inauthenticity, and to adhere to the spirit of cooperative decision-making, I brought options to the group sessions to either seek their approval or to listen to any alternatives. A key example of this was the telephone interviews throughout Cycle Two. Whilst I ultimately made the decision to incorporate these interviews into the study, I approached the group and asked if they were happy to have these over the phone, or if they would prefer in-person interviews in the care home. Additionally, at the end of each group session I would ask for any feedback to ensure that the group were happy to continue with the sessions or if they wanted to try alternative approaches. This avoided the study stagnating, whilst also ensuring that participants, in the spirit of action research, were engaging in aspects of the collaborative decision-making process. Cycle Three embraced collaborative decision-making more than the previous cycles,

as I wanted our resource to be a product of the group as a whole instead of overly guided by me as an external researcher. To achieve this, we made decisions on the content and format of the resource as a group. I also sought the group's approval on the draft resource that I developed following the group session to agree on content and structure.

Another challenge within this collaborative action research study was managing the varying levels of participation from participants. Ideally, action research should be democratic in nature and strives for equality between researcher and participants (Meyer, 2000). Collaborative action research focuses on bringing together different viewpoints and roles to work together towards a shared goal or purpose (Greenwood and Levin, 2007; Townsend, 2014). However, the reality of applied collaborative action research was that this sense of equality was somewhat difficult to achieve due to the varying levels of participation within the group. Whilst everyone was treated as equals, some participants were more vocal than others and therefore it could be argued that not every participant had an equal say within the group. Although this was a source of some concern, I used the individual interviews (both in-person and over the telephone) to hear some of the quieter voices within the group to ensure that everyone's perspective was included and to counteract the lack of direct participation during some group discussions. Despite the varying levels of direct participation, the group successfully worked collaboratively throughout the study as evidenced by our co-produced practical guide. One of the participants who did not directly participate in some of the group discussions on reminiscence later explained that he felt that he had limited input to offer the group as he did not find reminiscence helpful. Whilst this was unfortunate, it highlighted the success of our collaborative action research group as we included opposing views yet still collaboratively worked together in an authentic action research process. This aligns with the key tenet of collaborative action research of bringing together people with differing

perspectives to work together towards a shared goal (Townsend, 2014). It also highlighted that we had a group built on mutual respect and trust which allowed participants to voice opinions on the study that went against the consensus, knowing that the group was a safe space.

8.2.1 Reflection on my role within the action research study

Action research is an inherently reflective process which requires an openness to question personal beliefs and preconceptions (Townsend, 2013). Therefore, it was prudent that I critically reflect on my role as a researcher throughout the study.

In Chapter Three, section 3.7 I outlined how I envisioned I would manage my role within the action research study, moving from an 'outsider' and external researcher to an 'insider' and trusted member of the group. However, as previously indicated in Chapter Three, it would be remiss of me to overlook my own ongoing experiences of caring for a parent living with dementia, and how this could have potentially influenced my role within the study. Being aware of this potential bias allowed me to take steps to minimise the impact on the study, and to be mindful of my role, particularly during the group sessions.

At no point throughout the study did I conceal or diminish my own experience of caring for a parent with dementia as it was pertinent to the research topic and relevant to the experiences that participants shared with me. By being open with participants from the offset, I was able to build strong, healthy relationships with the action research group, which was built on mutual trust and reciprocity as evidenced by participants sharing their experiences with me and the rest of the group. I also felt that by sharing my own experiences, I was able to make participants feel comfortable discussing their own experiences as we were able to empathise with each other. This helped to create a feeling of equality between me as a researcher and

participants as the group were able to share our similar experiences without fear of judgement. This was particularly beneficial during the exploratory interviews at the start of Cycle One as I was able to approach the interviews almost as a fellow carer which helped with the conversational flow and build rapport with participants which was integral to action research.

By sharing our caring experiences, the group sessions involved a high degree of reciprocal learning whereby we were learning from each other on how to incorporate aspects of reminiscence into care home visits or daily life. This was a characteristic of action research that drew me to the methodology as I wanted to explore reminiscence as a group instead of purely acting as an external researcher coming into the care home and telling families what to do. For me, this also demonstrated to participants that I was ‘practising what I was preaching’ regarding reminiscence which helped to encourage them to endorse our approach as I was able to share how I had used reminiscence myself. I was also mindful at this point not to overshare with families and view myself as an additional participant instead of my role as the researcher and facilitator of the groups. This was a careful balancing act between sharing parts of my own experience to illustrate points, or to inform how I was introducing topics, without leading the conversation too much or influence how families would use reminiscence during their own visits. This was a challenge that I faced throughout the study as whilst my role as a carer assisted with building relationships with participants, I had to ensure that I did not conflate my own experiences with theirs, biasing the study results and undermining the study’s rigour. Participants noted that they appreciated me sharing my own caring experiences as it illustrated how the research was alive and could be applied in practice. For example, during the closing interviews that were explored in Chapter Seven, Section 7.3, Participant Six talked about how I was “*experiencing what [they’re] all experiencing*” and that “*it wasn’t just*

theory based, or book based, you know, you're living it, and I think that's a big, big plus, you know, for [the] study". On reflection, this highlighted how being open about my dual role as both an insider and outsider potentially enhanced the study by encouraging families to endorse our approach to reminiscence by learning from each other by viewing each other within the context of our experiences of caring for relatives living with dementia, instead of purely as participants and researcher.

Embracing my role as a carer informed how I approached certain parts of the study. For example, this was beneficial during Cycle One when I first introduced the concept of dementia friendly communication as I wanted to be tactful to avoid families feeling that they were visiting 'wrong' prior to engaging with the study. To do this, I used examples from my own caring experience to demonstrate my recognition that I knew how easy it can be to overwhelm someone living with dementia with questions unintentionally. I was also able to use my experience as an example of how dementia positive communication could be adopted and the positive impact this can have on interactions. Similarly, my experience somewhat shaped my approach to the Time Machine activity outlined in Chapter Six. Although I had met with an Alzheimer Scotland dementia nurse consultant prior to the session, I was acutely aware of how emotional this activity could have been and wanted to take a sensitive approach. As part of this, I used my parent's dementia as an example for the timeline and how their dementia has caused them to 'go back in time'. I believed that this helped with my approach as it demonstrated to the group that I was going through similar experiences as them and wanted to work together to find ways to support our relatives living with dementia.

Whilst I believe that being open about my role as a carer assisted with aspects of my study particularly with building trusting relationships with participants, it was also something that

needed to be managed, both to avoid bias, but also to protect my own wellbeing. As the research topic was often similar to my caring role at home, I was mindful of taking steps to ensure that I did not become overwhelmed. This recalled the concept of the “*wounded researcher*” or “*wounded healer*”. The term “*wounded healer*” can be used to describe both the positive and negative phenomenon that can occur between an analyst and analysand whereby the wish or drive to help is rooted in the analyst’s own experience of suffering (Hankir and Carrick, 2021; Hadjiosif, 2021). Similarly, a wounded researcher is driven to research a topic by their own lived experiences of the issue. In my case, I was driven by my own experience of being a carer. Romanyshyn (2010) contends that whilst can be a positive phenomenon, caution and safeguards are required to avoid the researcher becoming overwhelmed. The first safeguard that they recommend is to contain research in a “*ritual time and place*” meaning that research work is contained to a particular time or place where possible. However, they state that as there can be no complete separation between a researcher’s life and their work, additional steps are required, primarily the need for a “*community of support*” (Romanyshyn, 2010). For my study, this involved weekly supervision meetings with my lead supervisor, particularly during Cycles One and Two, to ensure that I was not overwhelmed by researching a topic that was closely aligned with my own homelife. This was also a beneficial step in ensuring that I was not conflating my own experiences with my participants’ and that bias was not bleeding into the study.

On reflection, I would determine that embracing my own experiences and acting as both an insider and outsider throughout the study was a strength of my approach. It allowed me to form strong relationships not only with participants but also with staff within the care home through our similar experiences of caring for someone living with dementia. This personal angle also assisted with families sharing their experiences with me as we were going through

similar journeys, albeit at different stages of dementia, and found ways together that reminiscence could be used in a family-centred manner to strengthen connections. Importantly, by following the recommendations by Romanyshyn (2010) I had frequent supervision sessions to manage my positionality within the study and ensure that whilst I was using my insights of being a carer to benefit the study, I was not losing sight of my role as the researcher and allowing my own experience to influence the participants or the study.

8.3 Discussion of key findings

The overarching aim of this study was to generate a collaborative understanding of the benefit and practical application of family-centred reminiscence and to co-create a framework and resource to support family members to use structured reminiscence during visits with their relatives living with dementia in care homes. This aim was met over the three action cycles of this study. A family-centred approach was collaboratively developed and used by six family members, and founded on the experiences of participants, a practical guide was co-produced by the group to share the benefits of our approach.

As previously outlined in Chapter Three, section 3.8, this study was underpinned by relationship-centred care (Woods, Keady, and Seddon, 2008), and the Senses Framework, (Nolan *et al.*, 2006). This theoretical underpinning informed our approach which placed the family and familial relationships at the fore. A key benefit of a family centred approach to reminiscence was that it helped families to maintain or strengthen their familial connections with their loved ones living with dementia. Additionally, reminiscence was a way for Participant Four to connect with his wife when verbal communication was no longer feasible, further demonstrating how this aligned with relationship-centred care and strengthening connections.

Typically, relationship-centred dementia care considers the interpersonal relationships between the person with dementia, staff, and families, this study primarily focused on the relationship between the person with dementia and their family members. However, as participants stated that they were interested in exploring the peer support aspect of the groups, this study also examined how relationships could be formed between relatives to form a peer support network. In their advocacy for a relationship-centred approach to dementia care, Woods, Keady, and Seddon (2008) warned that some families could be profoundly affected by the progression of dementia as they struggle with their loved one changing due to the disease, especially when recognition and communication become impaired. Woods, Keady, and Seddon (2008) therefore stated that continued family involvement without increased support or guidance could be a distressing or upsetting experience. This was addressed by this study as the relationships that formed from the group sessions provided participants with the opportunity to support each other throughout their visit experience.

The Six Senses Framework, with a focus on relating this to dementia and the experiences of family visitors, was also used to underpin this study as aligned with the concept of relationship-centred care based on the importance of interactions among people as the foundation of any therapeutic activity. The Six Senses Framework was comprised of six 'senses': security, continuity, belonging, purpose, fulfilment, and significance (Nolan et al., 2006). Although Nolan et al. (2006) contend that achieving all six senses is a prerequisite for relationship-centred care, for this study, I undertook a novel approach to the framework which focussed on the two 'senses' of Belonging and Continuity with an emphasis on how they related to the relationships between family visitors and their loved one with dementia and maintaining familial relationships. The senses of Belonging and Continuity were selected as they aligned with the goal of this study which was to explore the use of family-centred

reminiscence as a means of sustaining family relationships within care homes. Therefore, achieving a sense of belonging was integral to this approach. Similarly, achieving a sense of continuity was crucial as the study sought to preserve pre-existing relationships by using reminiscence to explore hobbies or interests as a way of remaining connected in the moment during visits.

Whilst reminiscence is usually delivered by trained professionals such as therapists, this action research study sought to determine if families could be empowered to use aspects of reminiscence themselves during their visits with their loved ones living with dementia in a Scottish care home. This study incorporated aspects of carer education relating to reminiscence and dementia friendly communication to allow families to adapt this into their visits, which was also included in our practical guide.

Important learning points about the experiences of visiting family members emerged from the three action cycles, with an unexpected focus on the crucial role that peer support can play in helping families to adjust to their role as a visitor within the care home and in helping them find coping strategies for difficult periods of the visit experience. The key findings that emerged from each of the three action research cycles are discussed in the cyclical fashion that they arose to illustrate the emergent nature of action research.

8.3.1 Cycle One

Cycle One of this study was primarily an exploratory cycle which centred on firstly creating a shared understanding with participants which captured their current experience of visiting their loved one in a care home, and secondly to understand the ways that families might already use reminiscence during their visits. For every participant, this was their first time taking part in research and were enthusiastic about sharing their experiences of visiting their

loved one living with dementia in the care home. This aligned with the key finding from the literature review outlined in Chapter Two, which identified a gap in the contemporary literature regarding care homes as there was a paucity of research on the visit experience for families in the period in between the transition phase and end of life care.

Over the course of the interviews, it became apparent that fundamentally, families viewed their visits as a means of connection. There were three key components to this: connection with their loved one, connection with staff, and connection through a shared activity. These findings demonstrated that sustained and frequent family visits were an integral part of maintaining familial relationships following a move to a care home. As outlined in Chapter Two, frequent family visits are not only a crucial part of maintaining relationships but they also have positive impacts on the well-being of both the resident living with dementia (Helgesen, Larsson, and Athlin, 2013; Cronfalk, Norberg, and Ternstedt, 2018; Hennings and Froggatt, 2019; Pritty, De Boos, and Moghaddam, 2020; Tasseron-Dries, 2021; and Van Corven *et al.*, 2022) and the family visitors (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Johansson *et al.*, 2014; Lee *et al.*, 2022). This finding also relates to relationship-centred care, which aims to preserve familial relationships over the duration of the dementia journey, including within a care home and during the advanced stages of illness (Woods, Keady, and Seddon, 2008). The concept of relationship-centred care was instrumental for this study as not only was it a fundamental aspect of facilitating continued family involvement, but it was also a guiding principle in developing our family-centred approach to reminiscence. This was used to frame the family-centred approach to work together to preserve or even strengthen their familial relationship with their loved one with dementia and to overcome potential communication barriers resulting from advanced stages of dementia.

Another key finding from the initial round of interviews was how some families, particularly Participant Four, relied on non-verbal means of communication to remain connected to their loved ones as the advanced stages of dementia had rendered verbal communication either difficult, or unobtainable. In the case of Participant Four, he centred his visits on getting a smile from his wife as for him, simply seeing her was the part of the visit that he most looked forward to. This echoes the findings from previous studies which showed that towards the advanced stages of dementia, families often relied more on non-verbal communication as a means of remaining connected to their loved ones (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; McCormack, Tillock, and Walmsley, 2017; and Cronfalk, Norberg, and Ternestedt, 2018). McCormack, Tillock, and Walmsley (2017) stated that a foundational aspect of this was for families to be present in the moment and to have an awareness that seemingly small actions, like a smile in the case of Participant Four in this study, can have a wider impact for their loved one in maintaining a sense of Purpose and Belonging, as outlined in Chapter Three, Section 3.8.2. This was an aspect of the study that I wanted to explore throughout Cycle Two, as using a family-centred approach to reminiscence to enhance family relationships through in the moment connections was a novel and original component of this study.

Throughout Cycle One, it was evident that sustained family involvement was a fundamental component of life in the care home and played a crucial role in the provision of care. During the group session, participants discussed how crucial family involvement was for them and their loved one living in the home. Participants Two and Three talked about how their mother was always very family orientated and therefore they always tried to mark family events within the care home to keep their mother involved in family life as much as possible. This recalled the Six Senses Framework (Nolan *et al.*, 2006), particularly the Sense of Belonging, which was outlined in Chapter Three, section 3.8.1.1. The Senses Framework was a fundamental

underpinning not only for this study, but also for relationship-centred care as it was crucial that the person living with dementia still felt included and loved by their family even when they may no longer be able to express themselves verbally or are unable to recognise their loved ones. Sustained family involvement helped families to keep in mind that a care home admission is not the end of their loved one's life story but merely the next chapter and as such the continuation of family relationships should be at the foreground. This is also consonant with the literature (Puurveen, Baumbusch, and Gandhi, 2018) as visiting family and friends play a fundamental role in the care provision for people living with dementia in care homes by providing much needed emotional and spiritual care. Thus, dispelling the notion that families must completely relinquish their caring role once their loved one has moved to a care home and further empathises the importance of continued family involvement in the care home environment. As previously highlighted by Participant One, visiting family members can often notice the early indications of illness or changing health before staff as they have more experience of looking after their loved one to draw upon. Information sharing between staff and families can be a fundamental component of a family's role with the care home. This can allow staff to become more responsive to when the person with dementia was becoming distressed or if families noticed signs of illness such as a chest or urine infection which they were able to alert staff to (Johansson *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, this reinforces the important role that families have within care homes and demonstrates that continued family involvement can bolster the care of their loved one and support staff to fully care for them.

An essential part of Cycle One focussed on understanding the current reality of families who were visiting their loved ones within the care home. This was a much-needed exploratory exercise as the literature review from Chapter Two highlighted that whilst there are countless studies looking at either the transitional period following a care home admission or the end-

of-life stages, there is a dearth of literature looking at the period in between. Thus, Cycle One yielded interesting findings regarding the visit experience and how this would shape the second and third cycles of the study. During the interviews, many participants understandably shared that their visits feel different. Participant One captured the conflicting emotions that families often face whereby they recognise that their loved one requires a level of care that they would not be able to feasibly deliver in the family home, whilst simultaneously feeling grief, and oftentimes guilt, towards their loved one moving into a care home. It has been shown that families can often experience feelings of guilt rooted in the misconception that they have failed in their duty to care for their loved one at home or in the community (Graneheim, Johansson, and Lindgren, 2014; Midtbust *et al.*, 2018; Statz *et al.*, 2021). This further demonstrates the originality of this study, and how it contributed to the body of knowledge on the family experience of visiting care homes.

However, the findings from Cycle One also highlighted that there is not a universal experience for families where every family experiences heightened feelings of guilt or loss. Instead, Participant Two noted that as she now views the care home as her mother's home, she does not feel overly different from before as she, from her perspective, she is visiting her mother at home. Despite this, during her interview, she discussed the impact of visiting during the covid pandemic and the emotional turmoil she experienced as the sole designated visitor for her mother, and that during this period she would often leave her visits in tears. Whilst the covid pandemic had an adverse impact on the mental health of much of the population, arguably families visiting care homes felt this more acutely than most due to the restrictions that were in place (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021). During the visiting restrictions, families were reported as experiencing clinical mental distress, which were heightened for those who visited more than once a week (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et*

al., 2021). This clearly demonstrates the importance of family involvement in care for the emotional and mental wellbeing for families and the adverse impact if this is suddenly removed or severely restricted. The experience of Participant Two also illustrates that this had a long-lasting impact on her as she shared that since the pandemic, she is unable to visit her mother on her own due to the emotional distress that she went through. This builds on the findings from studies that looked at the emotional and mental toll of the visit restrictions from during the pandemic and illustrates that the impact had long lasting reverberations for families that has impacted how they visit their loved ones today (Creative Covid Care, 2021; Prins *et al.*, 2021).

8.3.2 Cycle Two

The key finding from Cycle Two was that families can be empowered to incorporate aspects of reminiscence into their care home visits, which was not only an enjoyable activity, but also one that facilitated meaningful connections with their loved ones. From Cycle Two, there were four main ways that families had used reminiscence: reminiscence based on past hobbies, reminiscence as a communication aid, reminiscence as spiritual care, and music-based reminiscence.

Cycle Two demonstrated that reminiscence based on past hobbies was an effective and enjoyable activity for both the visiting family members and their loved one living with dementia. The clearest example of this was the experiences of Participants Two and Three who successfully used knitting as the basis for several of their reminiscence sessions with their mother. Craft based reminiscence triggers have been shown to aid with recall due as they are tangible and familiar (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014). Moreover, looking and handling objects, such as knitting needles and wool, and replaying associated movements, can help to create a

focus for revisiting the past and eliciting emotional responses, thus supporting reminiscence based on past hobbies (Schweitzer and Bruce, 2008). Towards the end of Cycle Two, Participants Two and Three shared their experience of using knitting during a visit with their mother, and whilst the knitting itself did not go to plan, they were able to have a laugh with their mother at their attempts. As previously illustrated, reminiscence rooted in hobbies of the person living with dementia is an enjoyable and meaningful activity (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014), and thus could help to keep families connected, and create fond memories of time spent together for families. This is consonant with the Six Senses Framework and relationship-centred care which seeks to prevent 'social death' and isolation for people living with advancing dementia by maintaining relationships (Watson, 2016). As 'social death' occurs when an individual is no longer considered a social actor or being actively involved in the lives of other people (Brannelly, 2011; Froggatt, 2001), family-centred reminiscence works to avoid this by maintaining or strengthening familial relationships through enjoyable activities, such as craft-based reminiscence. This further highlights how this study added to the current knowledge base on reminiscence and the family experiences of care home visits, by demonstrating that family-centred reminiscence can help to prevent social isolation through in-the-moment connections between families and their loved one living with dementia.

For some families, reminiscence was an effective communication aid which allowed them to transcend the communication barriers which can often accompany the advanced stages of dementia. This was particularly pertinent for Participant Four who shared that as his wife is non-verbal, he relies on facial responses as a means of communication and adapted his approach to reminiscence to elicit these responses from her. As outlined in Chapter Six, section 6.1, he used cookery books for the basis of a reminiscence activity and went through the process of planning a Christmas meal with his wife. As a discussion was not feasible, he

instead showed her the pictures in the books and he would talk about his memories of them cooking together, a frequent activity, and past Christmas dinners that they shared. Although he got a limited response, he felt that it was a worthwhile session that allowed him to connect to his wife, illustrating how reminiscence could be used as a means of enhancing connections to those living with dementia. Previous studies have highlighted how reminiscence could be used to aid communication, albeit in different settings than this study (Pollanen and Hirsimäki, 2014; Evans, Garabedian, and Bray, 2019). In their craft-based study, Pollanen and Hirsimäki, (2014). also highlighted how their approach aided with communication within a group setting. Their results showed that reminiscence could elicit non-verbal means of communication, such as body language to enhance reciprocal non-verbal communication. Similarly, in a music-based reminiscence study, Evans, Garabedian, and Bray (2019) demonstrated how reminiscence could assist in facilitating non-verbal communication with those living with advanced dementia and their families which helped to keep them feeling connected. Broadly, reminiscence has been a well-known means of aiding with communication, as it *“builds bridges between people”* (Gibson, 2011). Whilst this study did not necessarily uncover novel ways of using reminiscence broadly as a means of communication, it did demonstrate how it could be used by families in their intimate visits with their loved ones as a way of enhancing their visits and facilitating meaningful connections and added to the evidence base on how reminiscence could be used to aid with non-verbal communication.

An unexpected finding from Cycle Two was how families used religious items as effective reminiscence triggers and used reminiscence as a quasi-form of spiritual or religious care which provided comfort for both them and their loved one. This could be seen in the experiences of Participants Two, Three, and Five, who used their respective mothers' catholic faith as the basis for reminiscence activities. Whilst this can seem like a small activity in

isolation, it can have a meaningful and long-lasting impact for visiting families, as Participant Five noted that she feels that there is “*healing*” in these types of activities. The idea of reminiscence as a tool for “*healing*” is an interesting one to consider, as for families, exploring their loved one’s faith through reminiscence may have somewhat of a healing effect regarding their religion and strengthening their connections to one another. Spiritual reminiscence therapy has previously been explored by other authors and has been shown to be a source of comfort and support for those living with dementia. (Bender, Bauckham, and Norris, 1999; Mackinlay and Trevitt, 2010; Wu and Koo, 2016; Syed Elias *et al.*, 2020). Spiritual reminiscence has been shown to support those living with dementia through facilitating connections with meaning which improved their hope, life satisfaction, and spiritual well-being (Mackinlay and Trevitt, 2010; Wu and Koo, 2016). Wu and Koo (2016) note that whilst hope is a much-needed resource throughout the life cycle, it is particularly important for those living with dementia as they cope with the progressive cognitive and physical decline associated with the illness. A more recent study by Syed Elias *et al.* (2020) suggested that there was value in group-based interventions in reducing instances of loneliness and depression but there was inconclusive evidence on the effectiveness of spiritual reminiscence therapy specifically. Bender, Bauckham, and Norris (1999) note that as people age, they are confronted with spirituality more intensely and therefore spiritual reminiscence can support their sense of worth and identity and reaffirm their sense of self in a way. Therefore, the use of spiritual or religious based reminiscence could be a worthwhile endeavour for families as not only as a means of connecting them to their loved ones, but also in providing a sense of comfort or hope for their loved one as their dementia advances.

Music has long been known to be an effective trigger for reminiscence, and the experiences of the participants from this study are no different. During Cycle Two, Participant Two talked

about how music was an effective method of keeping her mother engaged in reminiscence sessions which strongly suggested that music was a powerful trigger as Irish music had strong emotional links to her mother's childhood. Additionally, Participant Two discussed how prior to her mother's dementia diagnosis, they would have nights in her house as a family listening to tapes of old Irish and Scottish music, as her father was a piper. This further adds credence to this use of music for future reminiscence sessions as it was something they used to enjoy together as a family. As highlighted in Chapter Two, Evans, Garabedian, and Bray (2019) examined the impact of a music-based reminiscence programme on people with dementia and their families. In their study, participants were gifted personalised CDs and booklets based on observations from group reminiscence sessions. These materials helped to facilitate connections between family members and fostered discussions on music and past experiences. However, the experience of Participant Six showed that whilst he did not find reminiscence an effective activity, he shared how his sister often spontaneously sang Scottish songs with a group of other residents. This demonstrated that whilst individual family-centred reminiscence may not have been the best approach for her, a music-based group reminiscence approach could be beneficial.

8.3.3 Cycle Three

The third and final cycle of this study focussed on co-creating with family carers a resource to support delivery of family-centred reminiscence informed by the study findings. During Cycle Two, another objective emerged to be explored in Cycle Three which was to assess the participants' experiences of the study, and if they would recommend a family-centred approach to reminiscence to other visiting families. To meet these objectives, a round of closing telephone interviews was conducted which asked families to reflect on their

experience of the study, along with two group sessions which focused on the development of our resource.

The main finding from Cycle Three was that most participants found incorporating aspects of reminiscence into their visits beneficial in enhancing their connections with their loved ones. Reminiscence based interventions have long been proven to be a beneficial non-pharmacological intervention for people living with dementia. As highlighted in Chapter Two, reminiscence has been shown to have several benefits for those living with dementia with previous studies indicating that reminiscence can have a positive impact on cognition, autobiographical memory (Kirk *et al.* 2019) and symptoms of depression (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013; Siverová and Bužgová, 2014; Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2016; Bohlken *et al.*, 2017). Individualised, thematic reminiscence sessions have been shown to have a positive impact on cognition and depressive symptoms for those with mild to moderate dementia (Van Bogaert *et al.*, 2013). Those with moderate dementia were found to have a greater change in their MMSE score, however, the intervention was shown to have a positive impact in the GDS scores for both mild and moderate levels, indicating that reminiscence can be an effective intervention for those living with dementia. Similarly, Siverová and Bužgová (2014) showed that prior to a reminiscence intervention, 70% of participants presented depressive symptoms, however, this declined to 37% afterwards, suggesting that reminiscence can be an effective, nonpharmaceutical intervention. Siverová and Bužgová (2014) contend that, at its core, reminiscence is based on the idea that people long for connection and recognition, particularly those living with dementia who often lose their feelings of self-worth and value through isolation and a lack of meaningful connections. Whilst this thesis did not examine the cognitive impact of a family-centred approach to reminiscence, our findings showed that the use of reminiscence enhanced participants' connections to their loved ones living with

dementia. Furthermore, the findings indicate that incorporating aspects of reminiscence into visits improved participants' views of their visits, and allowed them to see it as an enjoyable activity instead of feeling duty-bound to visit. This highlights the originality of this study as it demonstrated how family-centred reminiscence builds on relationship-centred care by placing familial relationships at the heart of visits, and explored how reminiscence activities could strengthen connections between loved ones.

This could particularly be seen in the experiences of Participant Five who shared that she felt more confident in her abilities to assist her mother during visits.

Although reminiscence has been shown to have benefits for those living with dementia, there is contention surrounding the longevity of the impact. Whilst reminiscence can improve cognition scores immediately after the course of the intervention, these start to wane over time, suggesting that reminiscence only has short-term benefits (Woods *et al.*, 2018). Though this could discourage the use of reminiscence as a standalone intervention, this study demonstrated that families did not view reminiscence as an intervention or a treatment, but instead saw it as a means of achieving in-the-moment connections with their loved one living with dementia. Additionally, whilst the longevity of reminiscence is debated, participants shared how they were encouraged by the positive changes, and despite recognising that their loved ones would not always remember their visits, the reminiscence activities allowed participants to connect to them in the moment. This was a novel aspect of this study as it demonstrated that a family-centred approach reframed reminiscence as an enjoyable activity that families could use during their visits to connect to their loved ones, instead of viewing it as a standalone intervention conducted by trained therapists. Participants endorsed our approach to reminiscence and, every participant noted that they would recommend this to

other families coming to the care home, indicating that they felt that family-centred reminiscence is beneficial for visiting family members of care home residents with dementia as it helped them to maintain their relationships through supporting in-the-moment connections.

8.4 Co-production process

Co-production was a key component throughout this study and was integral to the development of our practical guide on family-centred reminiscence. Messiha *et al.* (2025) contend that there are five dimensions that are related to the co-production process. The first of these was “*multi-stakeholder collaborative action*”. Multi-stakeholder collaborative action referred to the collaborative and participatory process of working in partnership with various stakeholders (Mesiha *et al.*, 2025). This could result in local ownership and commitment to a research project and could ultimately lead to empowerment of participants (Handberg, Mygind, and Johansen, 2019; Hoeg, Christensen, and Grabowski, 2019; Manou, Chinapaw, and Altenburg, 2020). This was consistent with my collaborative action research approach, which sought to bring individuals with different roles and responsibilities together and work towards a shared goal and purpose (Greenwood and Levin, 2007; Townsend, 2014). By engaging in a collaborative process, participants took ownership of our family-centred approach to reminiscence and were empowered to adapt our approach to align with their visits.

The second dimension was the “*process of co-learning towards innovation*” which centred on working towards project outcomes, skills, and empowerment (Manou, Chinapaw, and Altenburg, 2020; Messiha *et al.*, 2025). This process was evident throughout Cycle Two whereby each session was centred on activities which allowed us to explore reminiscence as

a group. Additionally, the reflection at the start of each session incorporated aspects of co-learning as participants were able to learn from each other on how they had used reminiscence during their visits. The idea of co-learning towards innovation was also evident through our co-produced practical guide on family-centred reminiscence as this was a novel and innovative approach which was rooted in the experiences of families. It is also hoped that other families coming into the care home can use our practical guide to learn about family-centred reminiscence and be empowered to incorporate it into their own visits.

The next two dimensions were “*contextual knowledge production*” and “*generating meaning*”. These centred on understanding the context-specific information and insights from participants (Messiha *et al.*, 2025). This recalls Townsend (2014) who stated that as collaborative action research incorporates differing viewpoints, researchers need to understand how the attitudes and beliefs of individuals inform their perspectives. As previously mentioned in Chapter Three, a challenge for collaborative action research is to co-create knowledge and understanding through shared activities that acknowledges and benefits from the varying perspectives of collaborators. Therefore, this was achieved throughout the three action cycles of this study, and the rounds of telephone interviews were used to ensure that some of the quieter voices in the group had opportunities to share their perspective. This continued in our co-produced practical guide as I wanted readers to hear from the participants on their own experiences and perspectives of using reminiscence and how this could be used to help other families.

The last dimension centred on having “*open, trustful, and inclusive dialogue*” throughout the co-production process (Messiha *et al.*, 2025). This is consonant with the literature on action research which states that it is democratic in nature and strives for equality between

researcher and participants (Meyer, 2000). Having an open, trustful and inclusive dialogue with participants was integral for this study, and for action research in general, as I wanted to work alongside participants to determine the benefits of using reminiscence during their visits. Therefore, I wanted participants to be honest about their experiences, as seen in the responses from Participant Six, who was able to share that he did not find it beneficial but still wanted to be part of the process to help other families. As previously mentioned, I was open with participants about my own role as a carer for a parent with dementia, which helped to further remove the traditional barrier between researcher and participant and allowed us to work together towards a shared goal.

Our co-produced practical guide was influenced by “Jenny’s Diary” produced by Watchman, . Tuffrey-Wijne, and Quinn (2015). This was a strong model to emulate as it is a readily available resource which is accessible to both academics and non-academics. The accessibility of our practical guide aligned with the democratic and empowering nature of action research which allowed the guide to be readable by the action research team, and staff from the study site.

8.5 Discussion of main themes raised

From the analysis over the three cycles, two key themes emerged which were prevalent throughout the study. The first of these was the contention between reminiscence and shared activities. This centred on whether families were using pure reminiscence during their visits, or if they were completing an informal shared activity with their loved one. The second theme was the concept of peer support, and how this impacted the study. Peer support was raised throughout the study by participants as this additional source of support was important for families coming into the home.

8.5.1 Contention between reminiscence and shared activities

Throughout the study, it was debated if whether the activities of participants could be considered 'pure' reminiscence or if they were completing an informal shared activity during their visits, and if this distinction mattered for families. Whilst reminiscence is inherently a shared process, I viewed a 'shared activity' as one that did not have an aimed outcome or underpinned by the principles of reminiscence. At its core, reminiscence is based on using tangible prompts or trigger items to stimulate conversation and recall of past experiences in a strengths-based manner by focussing on preserved abilities instead of dwelling on what has been lost (Subramaniam and Woods, 2016; Woods *et al.*, 2018; Ryan *et al.*, 2020). As outlined in Chapter One, Section 1.4. there are two main types of reminiscence: informal and formal, each with their own goal and process for conducting them (Tolson and Mitchell, 2019). Informal reminiscence is typically spontaneous and occurs naturally in conversations and storytelling with others. At the other end of the spectrum, formal reminiscence is intentional planned activities and usually delivered as part of an intervention or therapy. Reminiscence Therapy is a non-pharmacological, psychosocial treatment which supports people living with dementia to discuss events, people, and experiences from the past with the aim to induce memories, promote mental stimulation and to improve well-being (Woods *et al.*, 2018; Redulla, 2020). Like informal reminiscence, Reminiscence Therapy makes use of prompts or trigger items such as videos, pictures, objects, music, or even smells (Redulla, 2020; Syed Elias *et al.*, 2020). Prior to this study, participants would employ the use of informal reminiscence throughout their visits, often without recognising that they were doing it as reminiscing and sharing stories are in integral part of human interaction. This could clearly be seen during the exploratory interviews from Cycle One as participants shared how they used trigger objects such as family photo albums, or albums relating to past hobbies, such as hillwalking in the

case of Participant One and her partner. Thus, illustrating how informal reminiscence has a valuable place in care home visits was a common visit activity.

For this study, I was interested in exploring whether families could be empowered to incorporate short activities based on the principles of formal reminiscence into their visits to enhance their connections with their loved one living with dementia. As part of this, our family centred approach was situated in-between the typical informal and formal approaches to reminiscence as families planned their reminiscence activities beforehand with a desired goal in mind, without taking an overly formal approach, or viewing reminiscence as a prescribed intervention or treatment (Tolson and Mitchell, 2019). Over the course of the study, families developed their own approach to incorporating aspects of reminiscence into their visits. The findings from the Cycle Two exemplify how aspects of formal reminiscence were successfully incorporated by families whereby they planned beforehand the topic and associated trigger objects and used this to frame the reminiscence activity and subsequent discussions. However, during Cycle Two, it was debated whether participants' visit activities were rooted purely in reminiscence or if they were shared activities. That is not to say that shared activities should be dismissed, as leasurable activities are a fundamental part of the socio-emotional support that families offer their loved ones living in care homes (Habjanič and Pajnkihar, 2013; Puurveen, Baumbusch, and Gandhi, 2018).

This debate emerged following the first telephone interview with Participant Four. The question was posed by my supervision team if his activity was using rooted in reminiscence or if it was an activity, whilst meaningful, that did not involve reminiscing. Participant Four was limited on what he could realistically achieve through reminiscence with his wife due to her advanced dementia and enthusiastically described how he elicited positive reactions from her

during the activity. Whilst this was not a conventional use of reminiscence, this study never set out to examine how families could use reminiscence therapy. Instead, I was interested in uncovering how families could develop their own family-centred approach to reminiscence that was strengths-based and could be used during their visits. Therefore, I would argue that this was an example of a novel family-centred approach to reminiscence which enhanced the connection between Participant Four and his wife by eliciting a positive reaction from her. Similarly, the knitting activities that Participants Two and Three used with their mother are another example of a reminiscence-based activity as this was something that was intrinsically linked to their family life. Thus, the act of their mother knitting assisted in facilitating conversations about their childhood and allowed them to have a laugh with their mother and enhance their connection during visits. From these examples, I would argue that family-centred reminiscence activities assist families in facilitating conversations about the past in more depth than shared activities and can be used to strengthen connections between family members. This was a novel approach to reminiscence which proved to be successful in facilitating in-the-moment connections which in turn maintained or even strengthened familial relationships.

8.5.2 Peer Support

Throughout this study, participants raised how important peer support was for them, and this was evident in the way they approached the groups sessions and each other. From the offset, there was a supportive environment within the group, down to seemingly small things like participants getting tea and coffee for each other or offering to drive each other to the train station after the session. While these are small things, this demonstrated to me that participants did not approach the groups purely to help their own situation but also to work to support each other, and by extension other families in the care home. This illustrates how

action research was an effective way of bringing families together for this study and forming a peer support network for families, thus adding to the knowledge base on the importance of involving those with lived experiences in research.

During the exploratory interviews in Cycle One, participants shared that they were enthusiastic about meeting with other family visitors and receiving the peer support that they felt was sorely missing. Participant One noted that she felt that this was a part of the care home culture that did not fully recover post-pandemic as she did not have an opportunity to meet other families coming into the care home outside of exchanging pleasantries whilst they were signing in or out of visits. Previous studies have highlighted that peer support can be a crucial component of the support network available to family caregivers of people living with dementia (Bramboeck *et al.* 2020; Carter, Monaghan, and Santin, 2020; Velloze *et al.*,2022). However, despite the importance of peer support, most studies have only examined this whilst the person living with dementia is still being cared for in the community.

In a review of the current literature surrounding peer support interventions for caregivers of those living with dementia, Carter, Monaghan, and Santin (2020) discussed the merit of such approaches and the important role that they can play in supporting family caregivers. They contend that as the population of those living with dementia continues to increase, national dementia policies should consider the merit of utilising peer support intervention for family caregivers that are timely, responsive, and accurately reflects the needs of carers. Similarly, Velloze *et al.* (2022) explored the interventions that were available to caregivers as a means of reducing loneliness. Peer support was highlighted as being the most frequently used intervention with results suggesting that caregivers who experiences a similar situation can effectively empathise with and support their fellow caregivers throughout their journey as a

carer. Bramboeck *et al.* (2020) stated that caregiver loneliness was heightened during the early stages of the caregiving journey, suggesting that some carers became acclimated to social isolation as they adjusted to their role as a carer. Whilst these studies have examined the role that peer support can play in supporting caregivers of people living in the community, there was significantly less on the importance of peer support within a care home environment.

Harrad-Hyde *et al.* (2024) explored the possibility of formally introducing peer support mentors in care homes with a specific aim of enabling conversations regarding deterioration and end of life care. Their findings suggested that the introduction of peer mentors could be an effective way of empowering families to prepare for discussions on the options available for their relative as their health deteriorates and they reach the threshold for end of life or palliative care. Having lived-experience of supporting a relative in a care home was viewed as being a fundamental component of being a peer mentor (Harrad-Hyde *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, they noted that as peer mentoring can often be time-limited, they suggest that peer mentors could be introduced to families before a care home admission to develop a healthy, trusting relationship prior to having the discussions on expectations and care options as their relative moves towards needing end of life care. Although the focus of this Harrad-Hyde *et al.*'s (2024) study was beyond the purview of my own, it highlighted the importance for families to have someone to talk to who has been through or currently going through a similar situation to their own, as seen in the experiences of Participant Five. This adds credence to the call for more peer support to be offered to visiting families within care homes as it can be a crucial source of support and comfort for those families who are struggling with their visits.

Interestingly, Participant Four seemed to view the group as not only being peers, but instead as “*one big family*”. Whilst this was an endorsement of the supportive nature of our action research group, on reflection it added an additional dimension to his experiences as “family” is not an interchangeable term for peer. Participant Four was a vocal proponent of the importance of peer support from the offset as he had mentioned during his initial interview that the study site was the third care home that his wife had been in, and that he wanted to share what he had learned from his experiences to help support others coming into the care home. The use of “*family*” to describe the group clearly shows the strength of the relationships that were formed between participants. Establishing a form of peer support was something that participants indicated that they wanted to achieve through the study, and “*family*” signifies that this was successfully achieved. However, the use of “*family*” was interesting to consider when looking at how our family-centred reminiscence resource could be used by other families as a recommendation from a “*family*” member would arguably hold more weight than a recommendation from a peer. This could be a topic that would benefit from further research into how this could impact the implementation of our family-centred approach to reminiscence.

Lastly, through the inherent cooperative nature of collaborative action research, it could be argued that our group became a quasi-learning-community or community of practice, whereby participants not only learnt from our group sessions but also from each other. Cao *et al.* (2024) examined the role of learning communities for teacher’s collaborative learning and contended that learning communities should be founded on reciprocal learning as the learning process is inherently a communicative and collaborative activity. They also linked learning communities to the concept of communities of practice. A community of practice is a term used to refer to a group of people who work together to achieve individual and group

goals through a common concern, shared interest, or common difficulties, and gain knowledge and experience through their ongoing contact and work in pursuit of their shared goal (Lave and Wenger, 1991). This aligned with the definition of collaborative action research which focussed on how it seeks to co-produce knowledge in the shared pursuit of social change (Greenwood and Levin, 2007). The idea of the group acting as a community of practice enhances the peer support aspect as the participants continuously learned from each other during the sessions by sharing how they had used reminiscence and the reciprocal sharing of advice. Reflecting on the study, and the importance of peer support for families, it is unclear if the peer support aspect of the study was of equal merit for families as the use of family-centred reminiscence. This could suggest that the effectiveness of our approach could be enhanced by continuing the group sessions with the original participants becoming peer mentors to new families to maintain the community of practice and learning that was established over the duration of the study. Maintaining the community of practice and peer learning beyond the conclusion of this study aligns with a key principle of collaborative action research which was a desire for mutual benefit and a desire to work together to achieve social change (Townsend, 2014). Social change could refer to calling for wider peer support within the care home setting to better support visiting families and assist them to incorporate aspects of reminiscence into their visits. Therefore, this study successfully added to the knowledge base on the need to establish formal peer support for visiting families within care homes by demonstrating that families effectively learned and supported each other to use reminiscence during their visits.

8.6 Chapter conclusion

This chapter provided an overview of the pertinent points raised throughout this thesis. It opened with a summary of the strengths and limitations of the study, which contextualised my interpretations of the findings. I then reflected on the collaborative action research methodology used, with a particular focus on how I managed the researcher positionality and the concept of the wounded researcher. The key findings from the three action research cycles were discussed, with reference to new literature, and with consideration to the original contribution to knowledge, and how this addresses the research gaps highlighted in Chapter Two. Lastly, the two themes of the contention between reminiscence and shared activities, and peer support were explored with relation to how they were connected to the study findings and consequent implications for practice and further research. The last chapter of this thesis will offer a conclusion for the study, and outline recommendations for policy, practice, and future research.

Chapter Nine –Thesis Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter will offer a conclusion for the thesis. Following this, it outlines my recommendations for care home practice, policy, and future research.

9.1 Thesis conclusion

In this study, I contributed to the evidence base on the effectiveness of reminiscence by generating a collaborative understanding of the benefits and practical application of family-centred reminiscence and to co-create a framework and resources to support family members to use aspects of reminiscence during visits with their relatives living with dementia in care homes. This contribution was made using collaborative action research, during which I worked alongside six visiting family members from one Scottish care home.

Cycle One was an exploratory cycle which examined the visiting experiences for participants prior to the study. Within this, two key themes emerged which were the idea of having a connection within visits (a connection with their loved one, connection with staff, and connection through a shared activity), and the visit experience (does it feel different to before, the visit environment, and feelings after a visit). This allowed me to understand how families viewed their visits and the activities that they would typically undertake with their loved one. The last part of the interviews focussed on introducing reminiscence to families. The findings showed that whilst participants had no formal experience of reminiscence, some families had used it informally through activities such as looking at family albums with their loved one living with dementia. The second half of Cycle One involved bringing the group together for the first time, and to explore reminiscence in more detail through an introductory video. Again, the idea of connection was an overarching theme which had two sub-themes: informal reminiscence, and the importance of family involvement. The second theme focussed on

introducing reminiscence and had two sub-themes: countering the idea of “visiting wrong”, and the ways that families think they could use reminiscence in their visits. During this session, the concept of peer support was raised within the context of the group sessions, and how participants thought that this could help support them. Cycle One ended with participants being invited to try a short reminiscence activity during a visit, which lead into Cycle Two which centred on co-developing a family-centred approach to reminiscence which was rooted in reminiscence in action activities and the participants’ experiences of using this during their visits.

Cycle Two was the largest of the three cycles of this study and had two overarching aims. The first was to explore with family visitors, the benefits and practical application of using reminiscence techniques during their care home visits. The second aim was to develop a participatory approach to family-centred reminiscence which the families trialled during their visits. Cycle Two involved three group sessions each with a different aim, which were interspersed with reminiscence in action activities with follow-up phone interviews. Throughout the cycle, families used reminiscence in various ways to determine if this was something that they found beneficial in maintaining or strengthening their connections to their loved ones living with dementia. We used activities such as the time machine analogy to explore reminiscence in more detail and to think about the types of memories that could be effective for sessions. This incorporated the idea of the “reminiscence bump” and how this could be used to inform our approach to reminiscence. We used emotional touchpoints to assess if the use of reminiscence had changed how families felt before, during, and after visits. The key finding from Cycle Two was that families were empowered to incorporate aspects of reminiscence into their care home visits, which was not only an enjoyable activity, but also one that facilitated meaningful connections with their loved ones.

Cycle Three was centred on the development and refinement of our family-centred reminiscence resource. During the first group session we developed an initial draft of a printed booklet, to ensure that the content, format, and when we thought would be the opportune time to give this to other families was led by participants. A closing round of telephone interviews was conducted to capture the participants' thoughts on using reminiscence during their visits, and their thoughts on their experience of participating in the study. This was a particularly fruitful exercise as I was keen to hear about Participant Six's experience as he did not always fully engage with the group sessions, or found reminiscence helpful, and I was keen to hear if anything could have been done differently to better support him or families that were in a similar position. A final group session was held, which brought participants and staff together to further refine our resource, and to hear from the staff on how they think this could be used within the home. This helped to contextualise our research within the culture of the study site, and the practicalities involved in sensitively introducing our research to new families. Additionally, it was interesting to hear how the resource could be used to foster more communication between staff and families regarding the interests of the person living with dementia, to enhance the activities offered to them by staff. It was encouraging to hear from participants how the use of reminiscence had helped them have meaningful connections during their visits, and their enthusiasm in passing this onto other families. This further reinforced the importance of peer support for families and wanting to help other families going through similar experiences to them.

The study has fulfilled the aim, whereby we produced evidence on the benefits and practical application of family-centred reminiscence by visiting family members of people living with dementia in care homes. An unexpected finding from this study was that families wanted more peer support to be available throughout their visiting journey. The peer support that

emerged from the action research group arguably strengthened our approach to reminiscence through reciprocal learning and sharing of advice. Furthermore, this study has demonstrated how families can be empowered to use aspects of reminiscence themselves as a means of enhancing their familial connections to their loved ones living in the care home. The study findings also indicated that participants had developed a sense of ownership over the study and actively wanted to continue the use of reminiscence after the study had finished, highlighting that collaborative action research was an effective approach to explore family-centred reminiscence.

9.2 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, I have outlined recommendations for future research, care home practice, and policy.

9.1.1 Recommendations for care home practice

The recommendations for care home practice are:

- To introduce our family-centred reminiscence resource at an appropriate time, such as during permanency meetings, to families coming into the care home, to aid with their visits
- To support staff to have conversations with families regarding family-centred reminiscence

The recommendations for care home practice were selected as the study findings demonstrated how family-centred reminiscence can be used during care home visits. As highlighted during the group session with participants and staff members, our resource would be beneficial for new families provided it was introduced at an appropriate time and manner.

As outlined in Chapter Seven, section 7.4.3.2, for the study site, the group believed that the best time for this would be during a permanency meeting with the care home manager as this would give families time to adjust and acclimatise to their role as a visitor within the care home. Additionally, the group felt that the care home manager would be best placed to introduce this as during the transitional phase they are the first point of contact for families and would have established a relationship with them. Regarding the second recommendation, the group session with staff members raised an interesting point on how the resource could be used to facilitate conversations on reminiscence between staff and family members. The participating staff members felt that this could be used to tailor reminiscence activities that staff conduct to better meet the needs and interests of residents living with dementia.

9.1.2 Recommendations for policy

The proposed recommendations for policy are:

- To incorporate peer support for families into future Care Inspectorate quality indicator frameworks

As highlighted throughout this study, peer support was seen as essential component of the support network for families, and something that was not always in place. Under the current quality indicator framework used by the Care Inspectorate (Care Inspectorate, 2023), family involvement is only examined within the context of working in partnership with staff, and that their views are meaningfully considered by the care home. This study has demonstrated how instrumental peer support can be for some families who are perhaps struggling with visiting their loved one. This peer support not only offers a sympathetic ear to families, but also facilitates the reciprocal sharing of advice, which was shown by this study to help families feel more confident about care home visits and remain connected to their loved ones.

9.1.3 Recommendations for future research

The proposed recommendations for future research are:

- To conduct a future study with multiple study sites to determine the transferability of our family-centred reminiscence approach.
- To conduct a future study on the application of our practical guide on family-centred reminiscence for families caring for people living with dementia in different contexts such as in the family home, or within a hospital setting.

The recommendations were selected for several different reasons. Firstly, as highlighted in Chapter Eight, a potential weakness of this study was that it was conducted in one study site. Whilst the reasons for this were outlined, a future study could have multiple study sites to determine the transferability of our approach and add more credence to effectiveness of family-centred reminiscence. Furthermore, whilst our study was successful within the care home context, it could also be of benefit to families caring for a loved one with dementia living in the family home, or within hospital visits. This would further support the application of family-centred reminiscence by demonstrating the benefits in different settings.

9.1.4 Recommendations for nursing education

The proposed recommendations for nursing education are:

- To incorporate the practical guide on family centred reminiscence into nursing education to demonstrate the potential benefits for both staff and families.

As highlighted in Chapter Three, Section 3.8.2, there is a common misconception that advancing dementia removes an individual's personhood. However, incorporating novel approaches to reminiscence in nursing education, would work to address the stigma

surrounding advanced dementia and care homes by highlighting the ways that families and staff communicate and connect with people living with dementia through exploration of past hobbies or life events. This may have the additional benefit, of promoting working in care homes by demonstrating how supporting families to connect with their loved ones living with dementia can be a rewarding aspect of the job.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Notes used for ‘cold calls’ with study sites

Notes for study site phone calls

Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice based at the University of West Scotland
Lanarkshire Campus

Wendy Baxter Scholarship

- Works in partnership with Alzheimer Scotland

Why here?

- Great Care Inspectorate report
- Great feedback from families online
- Fits the criteria of caring for PwD with 24h nursing
- Close geographically

Study

- Looking at working with family visitors to explore the idea of family-centred reminiscence during visits and discovering what works well/is helpful
- Aim to create a resource with participants to help other families to use this in their visits
- Potentially the first study to look at family-led reminiscence in care homes

Action Research Study

- Collaborative and participant-led (not a traditional study)
- Emergent – built on the results and outcomes of the cycles

Time

- Roughly 12 months for data collection
- Expect to go into the home once a week or fortnightly
- Care home will help to facilitate the discussions with family carers, rather than being observed or directly involved in the data collection
 - Hopefully in a quiet room in the home, free from distractions

Appendix 2 – Letter for study sites outlining study

Study Title:

A collaborative exploration of family-centred, structured reminiscence administered by visiting family members of care home residents with dementia.

About Me:

My name is Connor McDonald, and I am a PhD student based in the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice at the University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting a research study into the practicalities, challenges and benefits of family-centred reminiscence delivered during visits with care home residents with dementia with the aim to help family visitors to adjust to the visiting role and to have more meaningful visits with their loved ones.

What will the study entail?

I am planning on conducting an action research study with three cycles, working collaboratively with family visitors to develop an intervention based on the principles of reminiscence for use during visits with loved ones. Family involvement will be an integral aspect of this study due to their first-hand experience of visits and the associated challenges. Additionally, involving families will be crucial to determine the feasibility of a family-centred, reminiscence-based intervention for visits.

The first cycle will consist of individual interviews with family visitors to explore their experience and to uncover any difficulties they may have during visits. These interviews will be transcribed, and the analysis will form the basis for a small group session with family visitors to explore these issues in more detail.

The second cycle will consist of group sessions to develop the family-centred reminiscence intervention. During this cycle, it is expected that I will explore with family carers, the principles of reminiscence that they feel could be beneficial for visits.

Following this, family visitors will be invited to trial it during visits with follow-up interviews discussing personalised outcomes to assess the carers' experience of using the intervention.

The third cycle will be more group based and will aim to create a resource that could be used by other family visitors to implement family led reminiscence with their own loved ones. A potential secondary aim could be to equip families with a resource that could be used in conjunction with care home staff to inform them about the prospective benefits of accommodating family-led reminiscence and how they could help to facilitate it.

Time Commitment

The data collection is expected to take approximately 6 months, with the second cycle taking the longest. The first cycle is estimated to take a month with participants being actively involved for approximately an hour and a half over an individual interview (approximately 30 minutes) and a focus group session (approximately one hour).

The second cycle is expected to take around four months to complete. Participants will be invited to participate in a range of short sessions, to a maximum of six hours in total. This will comprise of individual interviews to establish and review their desired personalised outcomes for the intervention and five one-hour group sessions to explore reminiscence, co-create the intervention, and reflect on how it worked during their visits. During this cycle, participants will be invited to trial the intervention during their visits with their loved one.

The third cycle is expected to last around one month with participants actively involved for an estimated two hours to allow for two one-hour group sessions to create a resource that could be shared with families from outside the study to illustrate the benefits of family led reminiscence during visits and tips on how conduct it. This will start off as group sessions but may bring in more creative avenues such as vignettes or short films to make the resource accessible to those outside of an academic setting.

Participants can continue with the study for as long as they are able and interested. There will be a rolling program of a maximum of eight active participants from each study site due to the likelihood of attrition with new family carers being recruited at the end of the first or second cycle when appropriate. If participants join after the study begins, they will be briefed by the researcher about the progress of the study thus far.

Where will the interviews/group sessions be held?

It is expected that data will be collected in person in a quiet room in the care home that is free from distractions for example, in a staff training room. Alternative arrangements could be made if a suitable space is not available on site. Plans will be made to collect data virtually through software such as Microsoft Teams or Zoom if needed.

Will it have an impact on staff?

The study is expected to have a minimal impact on the day-to-day activities for staff as the participants will be family visitors and data will not be collected during visits. Assistance from staff may be needed to set up the room for the interviews and group sessions. Staff involvement may be needed during the second cycle to help family visitors arrange space or time for reminiscence.

Appendix 3 – Letter sent to study sites asking for managerial permission

UWS Lanarkshire Campus
Stephenson Place
Hamilton International Technology Park
South Lanarkshire
G72 0LH
Scotland

Dear XXXXX

XX/XX/XX

Study Title: A collaborative exploration of family-centred reminiscence within visits of care home residents with dementia.

Thank you again for your interest in my PhD study and for making the time to speak to me over the past month. This is an area of research which I am really interested in, and hope will benefit residents, families, and staff. Following on from our recent conversations, I am writing to you to request your permission that XXXXXXXXXX can become a study site in my doctoral research.

It would be most helpful at this stage to receive a formal letter indicating your indicative management permission for the study. I would also like to reassure you that no data collection will commence until I have secured Ethical Approval, but it is helpful to identify my study sites when completing the application for this.

What Does it Mean to be a Study Site?

Becoming a study site would involve you/your team in identifying family carers with a potential interest in participating. I will then provide information about what taking part involves, and those who consent will be invited to progress the study with me. Some family carers may wish to be involved throughout the entire study; others may wish to take part in selected study activities running over approximately 12 months.

The study is expected to have a minimal impact on the day-to-day activities for staff as the participants will be family visitors and data will not be collected during visits. Assistance from staff may be requested to identify suitable dates and quiet spaces for any project activities to be undertaken on site and to facilitate communication with families. In addition, from time to time, it would be helpful to discuss project progress and thoughts on the practicalities of family led reminiscence.

School of Health & Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish Charity Number SC002520

As previously explained the aim of the study is to collaboratively build and test in practice family led reminiscence with care home residents who are living with dementia. The study design I will use is called action research and the research will be undertaken in cycles. The first cycle will explore the current visiting experiences of families, then we will collaboratively explore how families might use the principles of reminiscence during visits. Finally, we will look at the practicalities and merits of the family led reminiscence activities and create an intervention based on the principles of reminiscence with the families.

I would be delighted to arrange a short meeting (via TEAMS) or an in-person meeting to elaborate. If you have any questions in the meantime, please email me at Connor.McDonald@uws.ac.uk or my lead supervisor, Professor Debbie Tolson at Debbie.Tolson@uws.ac.uk.

Kind Regards,

Connor McDonald
PhD Student, Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice
School of Health and Life Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Lanarkshire Campus

CC

Professor Debbie Tolson

School of Health & Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish Charity Number SC002520

Appendix 4 – Letter of managerial permission from Study Site One

07/11/22

Dear Connor

Following our telephone discussions and your letter explaining what is required of a “Study Site”, I write to confirm that gives permission to be involved in your PhD Study.

If you require any further information please do not hesitate to contact myself.

With Regards

Are you a family visitor of someone living with dementia?

**My name is Connor McDonald,
and I am a PhD student at the
University of the West of Scotland
looking at the experiences of
family visitors of people with
dementia**

I'm looking for adults 18 years and older who regularly visit a loved one with dementia living in a care home. This is a research study to explore family-centred, structured reminiscence. We plan to generate a shared understanding of the practicalities, challenges and benefits of family-centred reminiscence delivered by family visitors during visits with care home residents with dementia. This is possibly the first study to explore family-centred reminiscence in care homes.

Participants will be asked to take part in:

- An individual interview with this study researcher
- A series of group discussions with family visitors to develop a new way of using reminiscence in care homes.

School of Health & Life Sciences

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish Charity Number SC002520

Are you eligible?

- If you are a spouse/ partner or adult child of a person with dementia who lives in a care home for longer than three months
- Visit at least twice a month
- 18 years or older

If you are interested, or if you have any questions, please email me at:

Connor.McDonald@uws.ac.uk

Appendix 6 – Participant Information Sheet

Information Sheet for family carers

A collaborative exploration of family-centred, structured reminiscence administered by visiting family members of care home residents with dementia.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part.

Reminiscence is an activity that often involves discussing past events and experiences with the aim to prompt memories, promote mental stimulation and to improve well-being.

What is the aim of this study?

The aim of this study is to generate a collaborative understanding of the practicalities, challenges and benefits of family-centred, structured reminiscence administered by visiting family members of care home residents with dementia.

There are five main objectives of this thesis:

- To create a shared understanding with family visitors of the experience of visiting the care home.
- To understand the ways that family visitors might already use informal reminiscence during visits.
- Explore with family visitors the acceptability, and potential benefits and challenges of using reminiscence approaches during visits.
- Develop ways of working in partnership with families to explore family-centred, structured reminiscence within the care home.
- Work together with family carers to create a resource to support delivery of individualised family-centred structured reminiscence informed by the study findings.

Why have I been asked?

You have been asked to take part in this study because you are a frequent visitor of a spouse/partner, parent, grandparent, or close friend who lives with dementia within a care home.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. Participation is entirely voluntary; however, it would be great to have your participation as it would provide an insight into your individual experience of visiting a loved one and trialling family-led reminiscence during visits which could be beneficial for other families.

What will happen to me if I take part?

It is anticipated that there will be three phases to this study. Each phase will have its own objectives and aim. We hope that you will participate at varying stages across these three phases.

In the first phase we hope that you will attend an individual interview where you will be asked about your experience of visiting the care home and your thoughts on what makes a good visit. After this we hope you will be able to join a group session with other family visitors who have also attended an individual interview to create a shared understanding of the visit experience and to explore the acceptability of family led reminiscence.

As the study progresses, we anticipate that we will generate a shared understanding of the practicalities, challenges and benefits of family led reminiscence delivered during visits with care home residents with dementia. We will work in partnership with families to co-create a resource that can be shared with other family visitors in a care home setting around the use of family led reminiscence. This may include a series of sessions around key areas such as developing and applying family-led reminiscence, personalised outcomes, and reflection on the experience.

Are there any risks involved if I choose to participate?

It is unlikely that there will be any risks associated with your participation in this study. However, as we are discussing a topic that may be of a sensitive nature, it may unintentionally become upsetting at times.

Appropriate support will be provided if this happens, where we will pause what we are doing to ensure you are in a place to continue if you choose to.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The main benefit of participating is that this could be the first study to explore the use of family-centred reminiscence during care home visits which could have some benefit to you as a family carer and for other family visitors of people with dementia living in care homes. Another benefit of participating is being actively involved in a research study and collaboratively supporting the development of a resource.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS Data Protection Officer can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data is your name and your relationship to your loved one living in the care home. However, this will be anonymised in transcripts and documents relating to the study. All transcripts and This will be processed for the purposes outlined in this information sheet. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. We will anonymise the personal data you provide during the transcription process.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The information collected from your participation will be used in two ways:

- PhD thesis submitted for my examination.
- Academic research papers and presentation at academic conferences

All the information collected will be kept confidential and only discussed with the supervision team. Quotes may be used from the discussions in this thesis, academic papers, and presentations but no names will be used. All identifying details, such as your name and the name of the care home, will be kept anonymous and will not be used in any supporting documentation. The data will be stored on a secure OneDrive account and will be password protected and encrypted.

This study has been reviewed by the School of Health and Life Sciences Research Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland

Contact for further information:

If you require any further information, please contact:

Researcher:

Connor McDonald
University of the West of Scotland,
Technology Avenue,
Blantyre,
G72 0LH
UK

E-mail address:
Connor.McDonald@uws.ac.uk

Lead Supervisor:

Professor Debbie Tolson
University of the West of Scotland,
Technology Avenue,
Blantyre,
G72 0LH
UK

E-mail address: Debbie.Tolson@uws.ac.uk

Thank you for taking time to read this

Appendix 7 – Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

A collaborative exploration of family-centred, structured reminiscence administered by visiting family members of care home residents with dementia.

Ethics Approval Number: 16344

Investigator(s):

Connor McDonald

Researcher Email:

Connor.McDonald@uws.ac.uk

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information and understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

Initials

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Date

Signature

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Date

Signature

Appendix 8 – Semi-structured guide for individual interviews

Interview Guide

Introduce myself and the study.

Mention how long it is expected to take - maximum 40 minutes.

Ask what they want to be called.

'Icebreaker'

- How was the journey in etc?
- How's their day been so far.

Do they have any questions for me before we begin?

Topic 1 - Current Visits

I understand that you have a relative who is living in this care home. I would like to know a little more about your relationship before their admission and your experiences of visiting them now.

- Could you begin by explaining your relationship with XX and a little about your relationship before they moved to the care home.
Prompts about relationship – who else is close to XX and do they/you often speak/visit?

I would like to understand what it is like for you/family visiting XX in the care home.

- **Has the move changed your relationship at all?**
- **Do you/family visit regularly – and if so, how often?**
- **Who else visits – and how often?**
- **On a typical visit would you speak to any of the staff before saying hello to XX?**
How do staff get involved if at all in visits?
- **When you visit XXX how is the time you spend together different than when they were at home?**
- **How do you get ready for your visits? What do you look forward to?**
- **Do you ever bring things in with you or maybe plan an activity?**
- **Do you co-ordinate visits with others to spread visits out for example or maybe visit together?** Prompts visit frequency. Time of day. Duration.
- **Tell me about a recent visit-** what did you do for example, where did you meet, how long? Was this a typical visit for you? What did you feel about this visit or think about afterwards?
- **What makes a visit with XX in the care home a good experience for you?**
- **Have you ever had a visit that didn't go so well?**
- **How do you feel after a visit?**

If you were talking with someone, a friend or neighbour who had a relative going into a care home – what would tell them to expect about visiting based on your own experiences? Reminiscence etc

Briefly summarise what we have discussed, ask if there is anything they want to add.

Topic 2 – pre-existing knowledge of reminiscence

For this study, I am trying to find out if family centred reminiscence could be a helpful tool for families to use during their visits.

- **Is this something that you have heard of?**
 - Do they do this here?

Reminiscence is an activity that often involves discussing past events and experiences with the aim to prompt memories, promote mental stimulation and to improve well-being, with a focus on the feelings behind memories rather than the factual details.

There are different ways of approaching reminiscence.

- **Have you had a chance to take part in any sessions?**
 - What did you do?
 - Did you enjoy it?
 - Did your..... take part?
 - How did that go?
- **Do you think your might find it helpful?**

In my study I am wondering if families could draw upon aspects of reminiscence when visiting.

- **What do you think of this idea?**
- Is this something you'd be interested in?
 - Briefly outline next steps
 - Group session based on interviews.
 - Series of group sessions including a guided session on reminiscence.

Is there anything you'd like to add?

Do you have any more questions for me?

Quick debrief:

- Sign post further support
 - Alz. Scot 24hr helpline
 - Liaison nurse(s)
 - Local carer groups

Appendix 9 – Ethics Approval Letter

28/02/2023 (Dr Gordon Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear RESCHHL Connor McDonald,

Your application 19659: A collaborative exploration of family led reminiscence within visits of care home residents with dementia., submission 16344, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Gary Boyd". The signature is written in a cursive style.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 10 – Staff Information Sheet

Staff Information Sheet

A collaborative exploration of family centred reminiscence within visits of care home residents with dementia.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish as it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. If there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information, then please contact me on the contact details provided at the end of the information sheet.

Reminiscence is a therapy often involves discussing past events and experiences with the aim to induce memories, promote mental stimulation and to improve well-being.

What is the aim of this study?

Study aim:

To generate a collaborative understanding of the practicalities, challenges and benefits of family led reminiscence delivered during visits with care home residents with dementia.

There are five main objectives of this thesis:

- To create a shared understanding with family visitors of the experience of visiting the care home
- To understand the ways that family visitors might already use informal reminiscence during visits
- Explore with family visitors the acceptability and potential benefits and challenges of using reminiscence approaches during visits
- Develop ways of working in partnership with families to explore family-led reminiscence within the care home
- Work together with family carers to create a resource to support delivery of family led individualised reminiscence informed by the study findings.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a care home staff member directly involved in the care of a resident living with dementia or dementia-like symptoms.

Do I have to take part?

If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. Participation is entirely voluntary where it is up to you to decide whether to take part. However, it would be great to have your participation as it would provide a staff insight into a resource focussed on family-led reminiscence during visits which could be beneficial for families. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet

to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

In previous parts of the study, I have explored with family visitors the acceptability and potential benefits and challenges of using reminiscence approaches during visits. We have also co-created a resource to support delivery of family led individualised reminiscence informed by the study findings.

As this is a resource that would be distributed by care home staff to other families, it would be beneficial to have a short group session with staff to discuss this as you will have valuable insight into how usable the resource could be for families, or if there is any additional information that you feel should be included.

Are there any risks involved if I choose to participate?

It is unlikely that there will be any risks associated with your participation in this study. However, as we are discussing a topic that may be of a sensitive nature, it may unintentionally become upsetting at times.

Appropriate support will be provided if this happens, where we will pause what we are doing to ensure you are in a place to continue if you choose to.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The main benefit of participating is that this could be the first study to explore the use of family led reminiscence during care home visits which could have some benefit to you as a staff member and for other family visitors of people with dementia living in care homes. Another benefit of participating is being actively involved in a research study and collaboratively supporting the development of a resource.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be [the provision of your consent.] You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. We will anonymise the personal data you provide during the transcription process.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The information collected from your participation will be used in two ways:

- PhD thesis
- Academic research papers and conferences

All the information collected will be kept confidential and only discussed with the supervision team. Quotes may be used from the discussions in this thesis, academic papers and presentations but no names will be used. All identifying details, such as your name and the name of the care home, will be kept anonymous and will not be used in any supporting documentation. The data will be stored on a secure OneDrive account and will be password protected and encrypted.

This study has been reviewed by the School of Health and Life Sciences Research Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland

Contact for further information

If you require any further information, please contact:

Researcher:

Connor McDonald

University of the West of Scotland,

Technology Avenue,

Blantyre,

G72 0LH

UK

E-mail address:

Connor.McDonald@uws.ac.uk

Lead Supervisor:

Professor Debbie Tolson

University of the West of Scotland,

Technology Avenue,

Blantyre,

G72 0LH

UK

E-mail address: Debbie.Tolson@uws.ac.uk

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix 11 – Ethics Amendment Approval Letter

04/03/2024 (Dr Gordie Mackay, ethics)

Dear RESCHHL Connor McDonald,

Your application 19659: A collaborative exploration of family led reminiscence within visits of care home residents with dementia., submission reference 17426, has been approved, with conditions, by the Health and Life Sciences SAIEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Details of the Amendment(s):	Please make sure that you have permissions from the study sites in place to approach additional participants before additional recruitment begins.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 12 – Worked example of reflexive thematic analysis

P5: I was just wondering because when you're supposed to answer for them and you know so we've got to know what we're doing wrong, you know, because you're not thinking about what you're doing right, you know, I find that hard.

I: I know from my Dad, it's something that I can struggle with cause you want to try and fill the gaps for them when you ask a question. I think if you do it once or twice its not the end of the world but you don't want to begin just quizzing them.

P5: And if you've done something to upset them then just stop, you know, or whatever?

I: Yeah, if it doesn't work or if it starts upsetting them then just move on because it's not worth causing you distress and upsetting-

P5: So that was just my thoughts if someone is like kinda, you know, not wanting to respond to you, you know. So that was just my question. So, I find that hard when you've got a difficult person with dementia, you know, so you know, it's just something to ask about that don't know how everybody else copes cause I'm finding it hard, you know.

P2: What we find with mum is, she changes every time you visit really. Sometimes you can have a brilliant visit and she's upbeat and happy another time she'll sit and ask where she is and that she wants to go home and see on those days, you can go home crying because you think that she's going back the way to what she was like when she first came in here.

P3: She hasn't said that she wants to go home for a long time, for about a year at least. I was visiting with my other sister on Tuesday and she said that the whole way through the visit for an hour or more. It was like she'd just moved to the home. It was really strange.

P4: [Wife] doesn't communicate

P2: Oh not at all [Participant 4]?

P3: Does she look at you?

P4: Oh aye, or you might get a smile, that kind of thing. Her sister is up from England at the moment, she's upstairs so that's nice. But no, there's no verbal communication.

P3: How long has she been like that?

P4: Oh, must be 3 or 4 years.

[crosstalk]

P5: I get some days now as well when my mum doesn't say anything, and you know, she's sleeping a lot so it's difficult.

P2: [Participant 5], are you the only sister that comes?

P5: Yeah

P3: Are you an only child?

P5: No I've got two brothers

Connor McDonald
October 18, 2024 at 2:09 PM

Principles of rem.

Connor McDonald
October 18, 2024 at 2:13 PM

Struggles with visits

Connor McDonald
October 18, 2024 at 2:14 PM

Changing visits

Connor McDonald
October 18, 2024 at 2:15 PM

Communication issues?

Connor McDonald
October 18, 2024 at 2:15 PM

Communication issues

Appendix 13 – Slides used for Reminiscence video

Introduction to Reminiscence

1

Why Reminiscence ?

Research shows that reminiscence activities help care home residents in several ways:

- An enjoyable activity
- Alleviates boredom and loneliness
- Focuses on personal abilities, recallable memories
- Improves communication and connection
- Helps to reduce dementia related stress

Utilising the positive benefits requires 'reminiscence know how'.

2

Principles

- Person centred
- Make sure hearing aids and glasses if worn are used or nearby
- Topic choice (one theme) - relevant, sensitive
- Being attentive to the person
- Be assets based (what someone can do – not attempting things they cannot do)
- Focus on memory sharing, not factual accuracy
- Dementia positive communication

3

Dementia Positive Communication

- Make eye contact, introduce yourself (smile – say hello in your usual way)
- Wait to receive permission (positive gesture or spoken response)
- Use dominant eye (right, if right handed)
- Allow time to process what you are saying (pause and check to 7)
- Think care partnership (do with, not do to)

4

What can go wrong with reminiscence?

The person does not show interest - don't force it

Answering for them

...of course you remember that, it was ...

5

Family Centre Reminiscence- what is the best way to do this?
That is what you are helping us to understand.

6

What we need to do next

Try a small reminiscence activity during your next visit and bring in an object from the house that holds meaning to both you and your relative with dementia.

- What made you choose this object?
- How did you use it during your visit?
- What happened?

7

Appendix 14 – Guide for Cycle One group session

Session 1 – 40-60 minutes (Group activity)

- Ice breaker task? – 5 to 10 minutes?
- Establish ground rules – 10 minutes?

- **Group discussion on ‘topics’ from interviews – 10 minutes?**
 - **Ethical issues**
 - **Topic of connection**
 - **I.e. differing experiences.**
 - **Whilst no-one had previous experience of Reminiscence, they all use it informally during their visits**

- **Show video to start conversations about how we could begin to explore reminiscence – 15-20 minutes?**
 - **What are their thoughts on this?**
 - **How could they carry out the task?**
 - **Do they have an object in mind?**
 - **What do they think they’ll get out of this?**
 - **How will they report back?**

- **Point for evaluation/reflection**
 - **How could they carry out the short rem. task**
 - **How will they report back**
 - **Ask them what they think worked for the group?**
 - **What could be done differently next time?**

- **Plan next steps i.e. communication strategy etc – 10 minutes?**

3 main objectives

- Go over topics from interviews
- Begin conversations on reminiscence
- Plan next steps

Appendix 15 – Reminiscence telephone interview guide

Guide for Reminiscence Telephone Interviews

1. How did you choose an object or topic?
(This could be something that frames the whole session, for example their wedding day)

2. How and when did you start reminiscence?
(How did it come about? Where were you in the care home? Was it planned?)

3. What happened?
(Can you describe what you did? Did your plan change?)

4. How did you close the session?
(Did you plan how to finish the session? Were they engaged throughout the session? Was it cut short?)

Appendix 16 – Guide for first group session of Cycle Two

Plan for time machine group session– Approx. 40-45 minutes.

- Icebreaker – 5 minutes
 - o General chat to settle in
 - o Introduce new participant(s)
 - o Update regarding Participant 1
- Recap of what we covered last time – 15 minutes
 - o Established group expectations
 - o Topic of connection
 - o Started discussion on reminiscence and how this could be used to maintain connections
 - o Mention the video
 - Did you find this informative
 - What stood out for you from the video?
 - On reflection, did we overlook anything from the video
 - Some of you mentioned that you wanted a handout, do you still want this?
- Feedback and reflection on short reminiscence task – 15 minutes
 - o Since we last met as a group, it would be helpful if you can share what reminiscence activities you have been able to do
 - How did you find using this during your visit?
 - What went well/didn't go well
 - Is there anything you would do differently next time
 - [Opportunity to share tips with others]
- Activity on "reminiscence bump" – 15 minutes
 - o I wanted to do a short activity with you called a "Time Machine"
 - o What's their earliest memory
 - o Use "timeline" to illustrate this
 - First job
 - Married
 - First child
 - o Discuss what the reminiscence bump is:
 - Dementia affects short term memory
 - Memories from adolescence – mid/late 20s tend to be "stronger" and easier to access even with moderate dementia
 - Focus on preserved abilities/memories
 - How could this inform our approach
 - Next task: It would be great if over the next month have at least 2 attempts a reminiscence activity
 - I.e. Life events, hobbies, holidays etc
 - Did you get a different reaction from before?
 - It would be great to hear from them
 - Did the phone call work for them? Do they want me to contact them initially about this?
- Ask them what they think worked for the group?
- What could be done differently next time?

3 main objectives

- Recap 1st group session
- Reflect on reminiscence task
- Discuss "reminiscence bump" and how this could inform our approach

Appendix 17 – List of words used for emotional touchpoints

Before visits

- Apprehensive
- Looking forward to it
- Feeling Down
- Duty-bound
- Excited
- Relaxed
- Reluctant

During Visits

- Feeling Lost
- Happy
- **Hard**
- **Enjoyment**
- Feel at home
- Frustrated
- Difficult
- Contentment
- **Emotional**
- Not coping
- Unsure
- Joyful
- Having fun
- Feeling Connected
- Relaxed
- Fortunate
- Sad
- Feeling Loved
- Feeling useful
- Pleased
- Appreciative
- Lonely

After Visits

- Satisfied
- Pleased
- Disappointed
- Relieved
- Upset
- Uplifted
- Heartbroken
- Feeling Down
- Melancholy
- Worried
- Grateful
- Sense of Accomplishment

Emotions gathered from transcripts

Emotions gathered from literature

Emotions removed prior to activity

Appendix 18 – Guide for second group session of Cycle Two

Plan for first Emotional Touchpoints session – Approx. 50 minutes.

- Icebreaker – **5 minutes**
 - o General chat to settle in
 - o Introduce new participant(s)

- Recap of what we covered last time – **10 minutes**
 - o Time Machine Task
 - o Reminiscence Bump

- Feedback and reflection on short reminiscence task
 - o Since we last met as a group, it would be helpful if you can share what reminiscence activities you have been able to do
 - How did you find using this during your visit?
 - What went well/didn't go well
 - Is there anything you would do differently next time
 - [Opportunity to share tips with others]

- Activity on Emotional Touchpoints – **40 mins**
 - o I wanted to do a short activity with you on the emotions that you experience before, during, and after a visit
 - o Lay out the emotions and 1st touchpoint (Before a visit)
 - Spend 1 minute looking at the emotions (timed)
 - Is there any that we could remove
 - Any that you want to add?
 - Spend 1 minute looking at the emotions (timed)
 - What emotion jumps out at you or covers how you normally feel before a visit
 - Spend up to 2 minutes each discussing why they picked this
 - Get a photo of each card selected under the touchpoint
 - Make a note of who selected what.
 - Repeat this for the 2nd and 3rd touchpoints.
 - We'll repeat this at the next group to see if reminiscence has changed anything

 - Ask them what they think worked for the group?
 - What could be done differently next time?

3 main objectives

- Recap 2nd group session
- Reflect on reminiscence task
- Emotional touchpoints task

Appendix 19 – Guide for third group session of Cycle Two

Plan for Second Emotional Touchpoints Session – Approx. 50 minutes.

- Icebreaker – **5 minutes**
 - o General chat to settle in
 - o Introduce new participant(s)

- Recap of what we covered last time – **10 minutes**
 - o Emotional Touchpoints task based on how you felt about visits before trying reminiscence

- Feedback and reflection on short reminiscence task
 - o Since we last met as a group, it would be helpful if you can share what reminiscence activities you have been able to do
 - How did you find using this during your visit?
 - What went well/didn't go well
 - Is there anything you would do differently next time
 - [Opportunity to share tips with others]

- Activity on Emotional Touchpoints – **40 mins**
 - o I wanted to do a short activity with you on the emotions that you experience before, during, and after a visit
 - o Lay out the emotions and 1st touchpoint (Before a visit)
 - Spend 1 minute looking at the emotions (timed)
 - Is there any that we could remove
 - Any that you want to add?
 - Spend 1 minute looking at the emotions (timed)
 - What emotion jumps out at you or covers how you normally feel before a visit
 - Spend up to 2 minutes each discussing why they picked this
 - Get a photo of each card selected under the touchpoint
 - Make a note of who selected what.

- Repeat this for the 2nd and 3rd touchpoints.

- Ask them what they think worked for the group?
- What could be done differently next time?

3 main objectives

- Recap 3rd group session
- Reflect on reminiscence task
- Emotional touchpoints task

Appendix 20 – Guide for first group session of Cycle Three

Plan for group on resource development – Approx. 50 minutes.

- Icebreaker – **5 minutes**
 - o General chat to settle in

 - Recap of what we covered last time – **10 minutes**
 - o Emotional Touchpoints task based on how you felt about visits after trying reminiscence

 - Feedback and reflection on short reminiscence task
 - o Since we last met as a group, it would be helpful if you can share what reminiscence activities you have been able to do
 - How did you find using this during your visit?
 - What went well/didn't go well
 - Is there anything you would do differently next time
 - [Opportunity to share tips with others]

 - Discussion on resource development – **40 minutes**
 - o Format
 - Video? Printed Handout? Both?
 - Perhaps show video again?
 - o Content
 - Tips and best practice
 - What families need to know
 - Why do it?
 - o Timing
 - When would be the best time for families to receive this?
 - How would be best placed to give it to families?
 - Management? Someone else?

 - Ask them what they think worked for the group?
 - What could be done differently next time?
- 3 main objectives
- Recap 4th group session
 - Reflect on reminiscence task
 - Discussion on resource development

Appendix 21 – Closing interviews semi-structured guide

Closing interview guide

I was wondering if you would be able to reflect on your experience of the study and of using reminiscence.

- What do you think worked well?
 - o Do you think anything should've been done differently?
- Did anything surprise you?
- Was there anything else that you think we should've covered in the groups?
 - o Did you find anything difficult?
- Do you think you'll continue using reminiscence?
 - o Would you recommend using reminiscence to others?
- Do you think this could help other families?

Appendix 22 – Guide for joint group session

Plan for joint group session– Approx. 50 minutes.

- Brief recap of study – **10 minutes**
 - o Time Machine task/ reminiscence bump, Emotional touchpoints, reminiscence phone interviews
- Icebreaker – **5 minutes**
 - o Introductions
 - o Share with the person next to you one thing that you liked about the booklet
- Discussion on resource– **40 minutes**
 - o Content
 - Initial thoughts (ask families, then staff)
 - Does it convey the message that rem. is helpful and how it can be used by families
 - Could this encourage families to use reminiscence
 - What are your thoughts on the information in the booklet
 - Would this be enough for other families to start reminiscence
 - Does this reflect the work that we've done?
 - Discussion on "communication tool" (blank table with columns for topic, object, notes etc)
 - Could this be helpful for families to use?
 - Is there anything we could add to make it easier for families to get started?
 - Should pictures of objects that you've used be included?
 - Should we include an amended version of the video as a QR code?
 - o How could this be used in care homes?
 - Timing
 - When would be the best time for families to receive this?
 - How would be best placed to give it to families?
 - Management? Someone else?
 - Should we include a leaflet at the start outlining why the home took part in the study and why families should try it?
 - o Format
 - Initial thoughts
 - Does the current format work?
 - Can this be improved?

3 main objectives

- Recap study
- Initial thoughts on resource and how can it be improved
- How can it be used by other families

The research which has informed the development of this guide was funded through the Wendy Baxter Doctoral Scholarship at the University of the West of Scotland between 2021 and 2024 Connor McDonald, the Wendy Baxter Scholar completed a collaborative action research project with families who were visiting relatives living with dementia in Care Homes.

The information contained in this guide sets out the key findings from the research and tips for others. Illustrative quotes and images from research interviews and participatory workshops and tips about what worked well and not so well are included. The intention being to offer an informative and practical resource for others to use to have positive visiting experiences and special moments of connection.

You will find more information about the research and what it takes to complete a PhD (Doctoral Study) towards the end of this booklet. ©

Contents

What is Reminiscence?	4
Why should you use reminiscence?	5
How to do Reminiscence	5
Dementia Positive Communication	6
What we did and what we found	7
Understanding visiting experiences	7
Getting to grips with reminiscence	7
What difference did using reminiscence approaches during visits make?	7
Sharing what worked well	10
Examples of reminiscence in action	11
Essential tips for reminiscence	14
Communication tool	15
About the Research	17
Key Findings	18

At the start of the study we looked at existing evidence to help us understand what reminiscence is, why it is considered helpful and what is considered good practice. We also familiarised ourselves with advice on communicating with people with dementia.

Below is a summary of the information that helped us to get started on our collaborative project.

What is Reminiscence?

Humans are natural story tellers and love to reminisce. It is something we all do informally and spontaneously and something we can do purposefully with more structure. In dementia care both forms of reminiscence are popular and considered helpful. Care home staff often use reminiscence techniques to stimulate care home residents and provide an enjoyable activity.

For this study, we defined reminiscence as an activity that often involves discussing past events and experiences with the aim to prompt memories, promote mental stimulation and to improve well-being, with a focus on the feelings behind memories rather than the factual details.

This study used a "family-centred" approach to reminiscence, meaning that we viewed reminiscence as a way to maintain the family relationship after a move to a care home with the hope that this could be a tool to keep families connected to their loved ones for as long as possible.

*Reminiscence
builds bridges
between people*

Gibson, F. (2011). *Reminiscence and Life Story Work: A Practical Guide* London Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

Why should you use reminiscence?

Research shows that reminiscence activities help care home residents in several ways:

- An enjoyable activity
- Alleviates boredom and loneliness
- Focusses on preserved abilities, retrievable memories
- Improves communication and connection
- Helps to reduce dementia related stress

Additionally, families involved in the study have noted that they have benefited from reminiscence as well and that it has changed how they view their visits.

After using reminiscence over several months two families stated that it gave them "hope for the future" and that "It was heart lifting".

How to do Reminiscence

- Reminiscence works best if it is Person-centred. This means the person with dementia is at the heart of any activities.
- Ensure hearing aids and glasses if worn are used or are nearby.
- Ensure that reminiscence tasks are centred on one topic or theme that is sensitive and relevant to your relative living with dementia. For example, a session could focus on their wedding day, or a pastime that they used to enjoy like knitting.
- Being attentive to the person. Reminiscence can be effective if used for short periods of time ranging from 5-20 minutes. This is to reduce the risk of the person with dementia becoming over-tired.
- Take a strengths-based approach, focussing on what your relative can still do and set realistic activities or goals.
- Focus on memory sharing, not factual accuracy. Reminiscence works best when it is focussed on the feelings behind memories and being connected, instead of focussing on getting the details of memories correct.
- Use dementia positive communication.

Dementia Positive Communication

Whilst care home visits can take a number of different forms, reminiscence works best with a slower approach to communication.

- Make eye contact, smile, introduce yourself as you usually would.
- Wait to receive permission before starting reminiscence. This could be through a spoken response or a positive gesture
- Use their dominant side (right - if right-handed)
- Allow time to process what you are saying. Pause and count to 7 in your head before asking another question.
- Think of care partnership. You're doing a reminiscence activity with your loved one, you're not doing it to them.

What to avoid

Whilst reminiscence can be a positive visit activity, it does not always go according to plan.

- It is important that if the person does not show interest, don't force it. Leave it for a short while and come back to it later in the visit, or for another visit.
- Although it can be difficult, avoid answering for them ("...of course you remember Dad, it was..."). Reminiscence is not a quiz or a memory test, it's ok if they don't remember some details.
- It is also important to be mindful and avoid topics that you think could cause your loved one distress, we want this to be an enjoyable activity for everyone.

What we did and what we found

The research activities were planned to help understand what it is like to visit a relative with dementia in a care home. Then to explore the potential for using reminiscence approaches during a visit. After learning about reminiscence, families were invited to try short reminiscence tasks during their visits. Based on their experiences, we were able to learn together and develop greater confidence. It was important to know the difference that this made to the visiting experience and the various research methods used and the key findings are summarised below.

Understanding visiting experiences

We explored with family carers their experience of care home visits. This was done through individual interviews with families and a follow-up group session. Over these activities we discussed their current visit experience and if they had any prior experience of reminiscence.

What they told us was that as much as they wanted to see their loved one, some visits go well, and others don't. When visits don't go well it is upsetting not knowing what to do or say. One of the hardest things is a feeling of not connecting with the person you know so well.

Getting to grips with reminiscence

Over a series of group sessions, we introduced reminiscence and discussed as a group how this could be used during visits with relatives with dementia.

We created an informative video describing reminiscence and how it can be used with care homes residents and people living with dementia. We talked about how family carers could use reminiscence and the importance of thinking about the topic and of using a familiar object (e.g. a photograph or meaningful object such as a favourite apron) to trigger connection. Each family carer then agreed to have a go at trying to identify a topic or object to bring in to initiate a reminiscence experience during a future visit.

Some people found it easy to identify the topic or find an object to bring along, others took more time. It took a few attempts to feel confidence using reminiscence ideas during visits. Sometimes reminiscence worked really well and occasionally there seemed to be little interest. However, more often than not just leaving the reminiscence object close by or trying again next time they visited yielded a good response. In other words, going with the flow and not forcing things was a good tip.

What difference did using reminiscence approaches during visits make?

To understand the difference we used a research technique called emotional touch point interviews. This involved asking family carers about their emotions during visits before they tried reminiscence and asking them again after they had used reminiscence. The before and after emotional touchpoints show a positive shift in the emotional experience of visiting.

As a group, we used emotional touchpoint interviews as a way of determining the impact that reminiscence had on their visits. This involved asking families to select emotions that captured how they felt at various stages of the visit (before, during, and after a visit) before they tried reminiscence during their visits.

Before Trying Reminiscence:

Before a visit

Upset

Looking forward to it

Accepting whatever happens

Feeling down

During a visit

Being Positive

Sad

Joyful

Feel at home

Happy

Feeling loved

Feeling connected

After a visit

Grateful

Uplifted

Mixed Feelings

Worried

This was repeated after families had a chance to use reminiscence during their visits:
 This activity demonstrated that although reminiscence did not always go to plan,
 families still left their visits feeling "uplifted" and "grateful".
 After trying Reminiscence:

Before a visit

<i>Relaxed</i>	<i>Looking forward to it</i>
<i>Accepting whatever happens</i>	<i>Excited</i>
<i>Duty Bound</i>	

During a visit

<i>Being Positive</i>	<i>Fortunate</i>	<i>Joyful</i>
<i>Feel at home</i>	<i>Happy</i>	<i>Feeling loved</i>
<i>Relaxed</i>	<i>Feeling connected</i>	<i>Pleased</i>

After a visit

<i>Grateful</i>	<i>Uplifted</i>
<i>Mixed Feelings</i>	<i>Worried</i>
<i>Pleased</i>	<i>Satisfied</i>

This activity demonstrated that although reminiscence did not always go to plan,
 families still left their visits feeling "uplifted" and "grateful".

Sharing what worked well

Throughout the group sessions, families shared stories about how they used reminiscence during their visits, and what worked well or didn't work well for them. This allowed families to help each other give each other tips that they found helpful.

We also had a short phone interview with each family. During the phone interviews families were asked to reflect on how they found using reminiscence during their visits and if they would recommend it to other families. Every family carer said that they thought that reminiscence could be a helpful tool for families which could keep them connected to their relative with dementia.

Following on from this, we had a group session to discuss how we could design a resource that included these tips and could be used by other families during their visits with relatives. This involved discussing the format of the resource, and the key tips which families would need to know before trying reminiscence themselves.

Examples of reminiscence in action

Reminiscence can be used in a number of different ways from something like bringing in family pictures, or basing sessions around hobbies that the person with dementia used to enjoy. Over the course of the study, families used reminiscence in various ways that met the abilities and interests of their loved one.

Hobbies

One family brought their mum in some knitting to do as it was something she used to and enjoyed making jumpers for the family.

"The knitting because she was a great knitter. She always done a lot of it. And so we gave her the, the wee bit that was already started with a few rows and we gave her it and went 'oh that's good, mum. You like knitting don't you' and things like that."

When asked why they selected knitting as an activity they replied:

"Yeah, it just came into my head because she always knitted and thought it's a shame she's been up in this place almost four years and she's never knitted. So, we thought why don't we try it?."

Despite having not knitted for several years, their mum only dropped one stitch which was encouraging for her family to see.

"Yeah. It was lovely to see her knitting again, definitely yeah."

Similarly, another family brought in old cookbooks as just before Christmas, him and his wife used to go through them and plan their Christmas Dinner together.

"Ehm, the reason I chose it was, eh, it was over a Christmas dinner because [wife] and I used to kind of sit down and decide what we were going to have for Christmas, you know starters, main courses, that kind of stuff, so that's what I did. I took some cookery books into the place and did that with her. It's unfortunate to say but there's very little response from [wife]... I mean, I don't have any discussions really with [wife], it's all facial stuff that I get from her...We always had our own favourites, I talked about that. "Remember when we did such and such" you know."

Despite his wife having limited verbal communication, he still thoroughly enjoyed the activity and spending time with his wife.

"Oh aye. I've got so many fond memories, as I say, with cooking with, you know, with [wife] and certainly discussing what we were going to have in the Christmas period, a lot of fun out of that. We'd go through books, look at new recipes or try old ones, you know. It's just unfortunate that we can't have the Christmas dinner that we planned. [laughs]"

This is another great example of how reminiscence can be used in different ways that can be enjoyable for everyone and focusses on the abilities of the person living with dementia.

Family Life

Discussing past events and family life can also be an effective avenue to explore through reminiscence.

One family brought in an Irish newspaper and used that with their mum to talk about growing up in Ireland and her childhood.

"So anyway, we showed my mum this the Irish paper and she was kind of looking at it and on one of the pages was an Irish farmer, you know with his sheep behind him. So, we start to talk and I went "Mum, do remember Grandad", her dad, "remember Grandad had sheep" ... So we had a great talk about that and then some of it was in Gaelic and my mum was reading it in ...it was really lovely and we read that paper from top to bottom, every bit we could you know what I mean. So, that was a wee thing that we would never have thought about, do you know what I mean."

As the family only brought in a small object, a newspaper, they were able to have a natural start to their reminiscence that allowed their mum to decide to look at with them.

"I just brought the paper out really, because we weren't even thinking of that for reminiscence. It was just the way it happened, [My sister] happened to say "look what I found at the back of the chapel, somebody must've left it". [My Sister] just brought it out and brought it in and thought we could go through it with mum."

Another popular and effective tool for reminiscence can be looking through family pictures together. One family used their mobile phone to show their mum old photos as it was easier for her to see them compared to paper copies.

“So like when me and my Dad visited together a few times as well, which was good. She saw the two of us, and I had said to her, I’ll show you some pictures on the phone because I thought maybe that might be better, you know, looking at a picture...So, I showed her my 21st Birthday with her and my Dad and I said ‘do you remember that’ and she said ‘yeah’. I couldn’t believe it”.

For this family, this was a big achievement as previously, her mum did not recognise pictures of herself or family members.

Whilst reminiscence does not work for everyone for every visit, these few examples show how it could be adapted to fit into your visits and can be used with a variety of different objects and topics.

Essential tips for reminiscence

- Decide beforehand what is going to be the topic (This could be something like a family holiday, or their wedding day).
- Choose an artifact or object that fits the topic (This could be a family photo, or an object from the family home).
- Think about how they would describe the object and use similar words (for example, use any pet names or nicknames for people in pictures).
- If you find something that works well, try using it again. You don't need to do something different each time.
- Don't go in with too many high expectations – go with the flow and take your lead from them.
- Don't force it. If it doesn't work, come back to it later in the visit, or try again another day.
- If it doesn't work, come back to it.

About the Research

What is dementia?

Dementia is an umbrella term for over 100 different types of illnesses and disease symptoms and is not a part of the natural ageing process (Alzheimer Scotland, n.d.). Symptoms of dementia can include memory loss and a deterioration in thinking and behaviour, which can impact the ability to perform day-to-day tasks (Alzheimer Scotland, n.d.; WHO, 2018).

Whilst the symptoms of dementia can be similar, how these are experienced, and impact everyday life can vary greatly (Innes, Calvert, and Bowker, 2021)

However, it is important to keep in mind that a dementia diagnosis is not the end of their life story but merely the next chapter and as such the continuation of family relationships should be at the foreground and that it is possible to maintain hobbies and interests throughout the dementia journey.

What it takes to complete a PhD

A PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) is awarded for an in-depth study that helps us discover something new or understand something in a new way. In other words, the research makes an original contribution to Knowledge. The student plans and completes the research with support of academic supervisors. The research is reported in a large scientific report known as a thesis, which is examined by topic experts. It can take anything from 3- 6 years to complete. On graduation the successful candidate is awarded a PhD and the title Dr.

About this study

This study used a design called collaborative action research. Action research focusses on solving a practical problem, building understanding through a series of research activities. The relationship between the people who take part in the study and the researcher is a collaborative partnership. Together they aimed to understand the usefulness of reminiscence during visits with residents with dementia, and how to provide family led reminiscence.

To do this used several different research methods including individual interviews, group interviews and co-design workshops. Data was analysed by the researcher and sense checked with the group. Findings from each activity helping to inform the next step in the action research study. Over the course of three years they addressed five research objectives:

- To create a shared understanding with family visitors of the experience of visiting the care home
- To understand the ways that family visitors might already use informal reminiscence during visits
- Explore with family visitors the acceptability and potential benefits and challenges of using reminiscence techniques during visits
- Develop a participatory approach to family-centred reminiscence within the care home
- Co-create with family carers a resource to support delivery of family led individualised reminiscence informed by the study findings.

Key Findings

Four Individual interviews showed that:

- Prior to the study, families had no formal experience of reminiscence; however, they all used it informally in differing ways during their visits such as looking at family photos.
- Remaining connected to their loved one was a key point for families and every participant wanted to remain connected and maintain their relationship for as long as possible.
- Families were interested in using the group sessions to build a peer support network with the other participants

The group sessions showed that:

- Prior to the study some families struggled with visiting but have now said that they "have more hope" about visiting and some have started visiting more frequently.
- Most participants had a positive experience of using reminiscence during their visits and for some, this has improved their connection with their loved one.
- Some participants encouraged their family members to use reminiscence during their visits and for some, this allowed them to strengthen their connection and have more joint visits together using reminiscence.

Detail of the study design, methods used, theoretical and ethical considerations are reported in the thesis and publications. If you are interested in reading more, you will be able to find links on the [**Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice Website**](#).

Thank you to the family visitors involved in the Wendy Baxter Action Research Group, the Baxter family for funding the research, and to my supervisors: Professor Debbie Tolson, Dr Bryan Mitchell and Dr Anne Marie Craig.

This study was funded through the Wendy Baxter Scholarship. The focus of the scholarship was to collaboratively develop an approach to optimise family care home visiting experiences with their relatives living with advanced dementia with a particular focus to develop opportunities for family involvement in creative individualised activities. It is well known that caring for a relative with dementia is both a rewarding and emotionally challenging experience. As dementia progresses it is common that family carers experience psychological and emotional strains including anxiety, depression and increased feelings of guilt and loss, which are often exacerbated by their loved one moving to a care home.

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